

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

edited by

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Foreword

LoGov aims to form a global research and training network and to provide **solutions for local governments** in order to address the **changing urban-rural interplay** and to manage its impacts. As a consortium composed of 10 European and 8 non-European partners, we seek to achieve the following specific objectives:

- to identify, evaluate, compare and share practices in five major local government areas: local responsibilities and public services, local financial arrangements, structure of local government, intergovernmental relations of local governments and people's participation in local decision-making;
- to encourage the effective application of these practices by local governments;
- to strengthen international and intersectoral collaborative research on local government;
- to enhance the skills and career perspectives of the staff exchanged between the project partners.

LoGov's methodological approach relies on a comprehensive comparative analysis that draws on findings from **15 countries** or wider regions on six continents, the extensive **involvement of local policy-makers** through local government associations and a multi- and interdisciplinary approach that is facilitated by the Consortium's expertise in four disciplines: public law, political science, public administration and economics.

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The LoGov consortium is pleased to present this document which summarises the output of the research conducted regarding the identification, evaluation, and comparison of practices in the local government area of intergovernmental relations of local governments.

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1. Summary of the Evaluation of Practices on Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

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1.1 The Impact of the Architecture of Intergovernmental Relations

The impact of the architecture of intergovernmental relations may be vertical and horizontal, as well as formalized and informal, on the representation of the interests of ULGs and RLGs. Intergovernmental relations take vertical or horizontal forms. The vertical dimension includes relations between the different levels of government, therefore from national to subnational and vice versa. From the perspective of vertical intergovernmental relations, LGs advance their interests in a formal and institutionalized format directly or through national, regional, or specialized local government associations or vertical intergovernmental consultation bodies (see the Thematic Introductions to IGR in Italy; Germany; Spain; Austria, Switzerland; Croatia, Albania, Moldova, South Africa, Ethiopia, Argentina; “The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy’s Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations” [Italy]; “The Coordinating Role of the Associations of Local Entities in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP)” [Spain]; “The Association of Bernese Municipalities: Representing Municipalities in the Cantonal Decision-Making” [Switzerland]; Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland - The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government” [Poland]; “Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations in Ethiopia” [Ethiopia].

The horizontal dimension includes forms of cooperation across LGs to achieve a common purpose, usually taking the form of inter-municipal cooperation, including regional conferences, joint utility companies, joint budgetary users or joint municipal departments or recently developed project agglomerations (“The Regional Conference of Municipalities, a Regional Cooperation Mechanism in Different Urban-Rural Settings” [Switzerland]; “INKOBA – Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria” [Austria]; “Institutionalization of Intergovernmental Relations in Croatia” [Croatia]). At the same time, inter-municipal cooperation is also related to the structure of local government of local government because it is especially for small RLGs often an alternative to amalgamation.

The need for a vertical and horizontal dimension of IGR becomes particularly visible as regards specific services or policy issues, affecting single or a multitude of local governments. In a context of growing complexity or of addressing complex issues a well-coordinated approach across and within levels of government is required (“Intergovernmental Cooperation between Cantonal and Municipal Authorities: The Issue of Primary Education in the Canton of Berne” [Switzerland]; “Management by Objectives in the Field of Compulsory Schooling” [Austria]; “Migration Management as an Intergovernmental Cooperation Instrument in Rural Areas”

[Italy]; “Migration and Integration” [Germany]; “Digitalization of the Administration in Bavaria” [Germany].

1.2 Local Government Associations

The local government associations (LGAs) with nation-wide or, if existing, region-wide membership are at the core of intergovernmental relations. The practices show that when it comes to intergovernmental relations with the national and regional governments, LGAs play a fundamental and irreplaceable role in representing the interests and where possible the consensual – if not unified – voice of member LGs. In most countries LGAs have a longstanding tradition of participating in multilevel governance and they have national coverage and strong political leverage, promoting the interest of (all) local governments, urban and rural, vis-à-vis the higher levels of government. As the main representative organization of local authorities, LGAs are institutionally anchored in the system of the multilateral cooperation mechanisms (See in particular the Thematic Introductions to IGR in Italy, Germany, Austria, Spain, Switzerland, Croatia, Ethiopia; The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy’s Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations” [Italy]; “The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations” [Italy]; “The Coordinating Role of the Associations of Local Entities in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP)” [Spain]; “The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations” [Poland]; “Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations in Ethiopia” [Ethiopia]).

LGAs also play a fundamental role in representing the interests of local governments vis-à-vis other actors such as parliament, the judiciary, the business sector and also at international level, where they act as facilitators of international cooperation. “Institutionalization of Intergovernmental Relations in Croatia” [Croatia]; “INKOBA – Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria” [Austria].

The practices show the importance that LGAs shall be very well structured in terms of internal thematic organization, through permanent commissions or professional forums composed of municipal employees (mostly civil servants and only sometimes external professionals), covering from a functional perspective the responsibilities of local governments. This would allow LGAs to draw and build from the collective knowledge and expertise of their members and be more effective in their advocacy efforts towards higher levels of governments.

1.3 The Mechanisms of Supervision from Higher Levels of Government

The mechanisms of supervision from higher levels of government continue to be strong and intertwined with mechanisms of cooperation across levels of government. LGs and their representative LGAs are given the opportunity to be heard in consultation and coordination bodies, such as intergovernmental councils, committees, conferences etc. However, their opinions are not binding, and the representatives of higher levels of government have far more

power in setting the agenda and therefore steering the action of such bodies. This seems the case in both advanced and developing countries (The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy's Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations" [Italy]; "The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations" [Italy]; "The Coordinating Role of the Associations of Local Entities in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP)" [Spain]; "Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination – Albania's Central/Local Government Consultative Council" [Albania]; "Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland - The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government"). The policy response to these intertwined tendencies has been either the improvement of the internal representation and composition of decision-making bodies of the LGAs and/or the proliferation of special interest bodies and associations that represent in a specialized manner the special interest of smaller and more rural LGs.

While in most cases, LGAs liaise with national/regional governments or with consultative bodies involving governmental/regional representatives, the practice from Croatia also highlights, the importance of Parliament in the institutionalized intergovernmental relations, in particular when it comes to balancing of the urban-rural interplay. Croatia's Parliamentary Board for Local Government includes members of Parliament as well as representatives of all three types of local governments. It is deemed that such high-level institutional intergovernmental relations mechanisms are critical to achieve consensus on broadly accepted norms and standards, while at the same time, they guarantee that different LGs, irrespective of their political affiliation or political and economic power are heard prior to legislative changes.

1.4 The Heterogeneity of Local Interests

The heterogeneity of local interests based on territorial, socioeconomic conditions and political environment impact the representation of the interests of ULGs and RLGs in IGR and the functioning of the LGAs. As a rule, the composition, functioning and organization of the national associations reflects the heterogeneity of local interests based on territorial, socioeconomic conditions and political landscape. From this perspective, the composition and organization of the decision-making bodies of the LGAs, is very important as they determine the strategic direction of the association. The representation of all types of LGA member LGs within such decision-making bodies is critical, to ensure a balanced orientation in terms of advocacy or specific position ("The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy's Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations" [Italy]).

In some cases, there seems to be a certain imbalance of representation in favor of larger ULGs, which are more active and/or have more political power within the LGAs and/or towards the higher levels of government and therefore are in a more favorable position within IGR. Larger ULGs can directly negotiate with higher levels of government. Their smaller and more rural peers cannot and are often even the object of such negotiations. Additionally, the proximity of larger ULGs to the higher levels of government and national politics, also puts them in a closer position in the policy preparation, consultation and implementation at this level (see the

Thematic introduction of Italy, Germany, Croatia, Albania, Argentina, South Africa; “Representing Toronto’s Distinct Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government” [Canada]; “Creation of a Further Third-Tier Administrative Unit – Munich as an Independent District” [Germany]; “The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations” [Italy]; “Co-operative Approaches to Fiscal and Financial Management across the three Spheres of Government through Bulk Resources for Municipal Services”; [South Africa] “Intergovernmental Relations in Integrated Development Planning” [South Africa]).

A great degree of heterogeneity within national LGAs, however, may limit their advocacy efforts on specific issues and create dissent between members. In Switzerland, the Bernese Association of Municipalities focus on common interests of municipalities – instead of feeling squeezed between conflicting positions – has helped the association to raise a strong voice of all municipalities on issues of municipal concern. Their deliberate policy of balancing interests, integrating all relevant political parties, conveying clear messages but investing in confidential relations with the powerful cantonal counterparts, has made the association a very influential player (“The Association of Bernese Municipalities: Representing Municipalities in the Cantonal Decision-Making” [Switzerland]). However, in specific circumstances the diverging priorities of member LGs may lead also to extreme outcomes and implications for the LGAs themselves (“Representing Toronto’s Distinct Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government” [Canada]).

Informal intergovernmental relations, and in particular political actors operating simultaneously at the different levels can additionally provide other channels of communication and cooperation between the three levels of government, through direct party-level affiliation. From this perspective, the formalization and institutionalization of IGR is very important to ensure an open, inclusive, transparent and non-partisan intergovernmental dialogue to balance the interests of urban and rural communities or lagging and developed areas.

Political alignment or opposition between local governments and the national and provincial counterparts plays a fundamental role and the activism of local government within specific national or regional policies is essential to strengthen citizen mobilization (“The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy’s Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations” [Italy]); “The Coordinating Role of the Associations of Local Entities in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces” [Spain]; “When Governors Resist in their Territories: Intergovernmental Conflicts Related to Federal Labor Legislation” [Argentina]; “Multilevel Government Cooperation for Open Pit Mining Projects” [Argentina]). Similarly, the dynamics of national politics may also be reflected in the composition and decision making of the LGAs. In Albania for example the tense political environment has also led to the division of LGAs across political lines, which has been detrimental for the representation of local government interests (“Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination – Albania’s Central/Local Government Consultative Council” [Albania]).

The response to the tendency of larger ULGs that may have a higher weight on intergovernmental relations has been the creation of special interest bodies, special interest associations or consultation bodies etc., that are specialized to represent in IGR the interests of smaller or more rural LGs and can have a stronger position and impact on specific major

policy issues, than their national level counterparts. In Italy for example the Council of Local Authorities, is an important consultative body between the regions and local authorities.

The Basque Council for Local Public Policies is also a collegial advisory body that brings together representatives from different levels of government to promote institutional cooperation and guarantee the recognition of municipal interests in the processes of design, preparation, execution, and evaluation of public policies. However, very frequently, their actual political influence remains limited by their only consultative function (“The Basque Council for Local Public Policies” [Spain]; “The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations” [Italy]).

While additional consultation of LGs with other levels of government via different platforms and LGAs, helps improving intergovernmental dialogue, it may also lead to fragmentation and even slow decision-making processes if more bodies need to reach an agreement on specific policies.

The case of the Ethiopian Association of Cities highlights the fundamental importance of financial sustainability and independence of the Local Government Associations as a key requirement for the effectiveness and credibility of the association and their advocacy efforts (“Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations in Ethiopia” [Ethiopia]).

1.5 Complex Issues Require Coordinated Multilevel Approaches to Service Delivery

The practices from Italy and Germany show the key role and increased need for horizontal and vertical coordination when it comes to tackling very specific issues such as migration, integration, depopulation, digitalization, to avoid the ‘natural’ imbalance in this regard between urban and rural local governments (“Migration Management as an Intergovernmental Cooperation Instrument in Rural Areas [Italy]”; “Migration and Integration” [Germany]; “Digitalization of the Administration in Bavaria) Germany]; “Regional Plans to Prevent Depopulation of Rural Areas” [Spain]).

The practices from Switzerland and Austria focusing on the delivery of primary education and compulsory schooling show that, in particular in major social sector responsibilities such as education, service delivery is shared between levels of government, requiring the development and maintenance of complex systems of vertical and horizontal cooperation to integrate in a balanced manner the needs and priorities of both urban and rural LGs and communities. Among key success factors, the Swiss practice highlights the regular exchange of information between levels of government so that each of them is informed about challenges, priorities, opportunities and planned actions (“Intergovernmental Cooperation between Cantonal and Municipal Authorities: The Issue of Primary Education in the Canton of Berne” [Switzerland]). The practice from Austria, shows how important the reconciliation of interests between rural and urban areas is to set up a successful coordination and cooperation mechanism (“Management by Objectives in the Field of Compulsory Schooling” [Austria]).

Another practice from Austria concerns the formation of a municipal association to jointly develop and promote business locations, thereby bridging the gap between smaller and larger,

rural and urban municipalities. When it comes to such horizontal cooperation, the mutual interest and political will and commitment are key success factors. At the same time, backing from higher levels of government is equally important to push forward such complex initiatives ("INKOBA – Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria" [Austria]).

1.6 Experiences and Lessons Learned from the Practices of Formalized Intergovernmental Cooperation (e.g. Intergovernmental Conferences)

Besides LGAs, other important mechanisms for intergovernmental cooperation between different levels of government include conferences, committees, commissions, councils, forums or other types of formal consultation bodies that bring together representatives of different levels of government, on a regular basis or ad hoc basis to discuss relevant policies, as well as challenges affecting local governments. In Italy for example, there are the Conference of the State, Cities and Local Autonomies, the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces, and the Unified Conference. In addition, at regional level, there are also Council of Local Authorities. In Poland there is the Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government. In Albania, just few years ago, it was established the Central/Local Government Consultative Council, as formal two-level executive mechanism of policy consultation and coordination. A few years earlier, the Basque Country established the Basque Council for Local Public Policies as a permanent institution entrusted with the task of ensuring that institutional cooperation between local, regional and national levels of governments is effective. Other examples from Spain include the National Commission of Local Administration, and the Committee for Local Issues, both of which constitute the formal mechanisms for the intergovernmental relationships between the different tiers of government ("The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy's Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations" [Italy]; "The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations" [Poland]; "The Basque Council for Local Public Policies" [Spain]; "Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination – Albania's Central/Local Government Consultative Council" [Albania]); Thematic Introduction to South Africa.).

The composition, functions and rules for the adoption of resolutions of these types of bodies are rather similar across countries. In most cases they bring together key actors of the multilevel governance system, and have an advisory role, and therefore non-binding opinions for the higher levels of government. The operations of such bodies are intrinsically linked to the operations of the LGAs which in almost all cases are direct members of such bodies.

These types of bodies, in some cases have formal requirements to ensure a balanced representation of all types of LGs, including, an urban-rural dimension. This is also very important to guarantee that smaller or rural LGs are given an opportunity to directly contribute to national/regional level policymaking and make their voices heard. The establishment of these mechanisms plays a fundamental role to reinforce the relations between the national

government and local authorities and giving the latter a voice regarding policies that concern them.

Without doubt, the structure and organization of these consultative bodies play a fundamental role in their ultimate ability to ensure intergovernmental consensus on major policies and issues. Often these bodies are overwhelmed with the discussion of technical issues, which are of key importance of course, but take out the opportunity to focus on fundamental challenges, that would require more time.

On the other hand, it is also important to consider that the success of the consultation bodies, also depends on how early LGs are invited to participate in the policymaking process, via the LGAs. If LGs and their LGAs are invited to participate in the early stages of the design of the policies, then also 'consultation' on 'technical issues' is swifter, and room is created to discuss major policies also.

Equally important is that the consultation bodies do not 'mimic' or 'replicate' the professional forums of the LGAs, which have the key role to discuss on the details and technical aspects of the major policies.

The practices also highlight that the key function of these mechanisms is consultative. From this perspective, while LGs and LGAs formally collaborate and sit together to discuss policy issues, their opinions may not be taken into consideration. Another problematic aspect related to the intergovernmental consultation bodies, is the fact that in some cases the mechanisms to ensure a follow up of the decisions or agreements within such bodies, are weak or non-existent ("Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination – Albania's Central/Local Government Consultative Council" [Albania]). The COVID-19 pandemic has played a fundamental role to strengthen the cooperation, coordination and consultation between the levels of government in the phase of policy design, consultation and implementation ("The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy's Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations" [Italy]).

The practices show also the duality between formal and informal consultation mechanisms – where in parallel to the institutional ones such as the intergovernmental conferences, committees and councils, there are also informal consultation mechanisms, including political access, which puts challenges on the ability of such systems to speak with one common voice representing all LGs. From this perspective, the composition of these bodies and internal democracy in decision-making play a fundamental role in the effectiveness of their advocacy efforts.

The success of these intergovernmental consultation bodies is intrinsically linked to the people and the personalities participating in the process. Their proactive approach and early-stage involvement of the local government representatives determine which problems will be raised and promoted in front of the national government representatives. Another important factor in the success of the consultation bodies is the balanced political and territorial representation of local governments in the commission. "The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations" [Poland].

1.7 Cross-cutting and Transversal Topics

The multidisciplinary nature of WP4 is very visible. Intergovernmental relations influence how functions are performed, financed, organized and even consulted with citizens. At the same time local government functions, finance systems, territorial organization and citizen engagement influence how intergovernmental relations are taking place. On this note, intergovernmental relations are per se a cross-cutting topic which is relevant for all the LoGov work packages.

- With regard to WP 1 (Local responsibilities and public services) practices under WP 4 have shown that both horizontal and vertical, formal and informal intergovernmental relations are fundamental in the delivery of local government responsibilities by bringing together all actors responsible for the design and implementation of policies and planning and delivery of services. Very often local governments of different size and structure partner with each other in service delivery, and they regularly coordinate with higher levels of government to address challenges.
- Regarding WP 2 (Financial arrangements) intergovernmental relations were identified particularly in the areas of budgeting and financial planning, negotiations of financing instruments, including local taxes and equalization transfers.
- Regarding WP 3 (Structure of local government), intergovernmental relations play a fundamental role in shaping inter-municipal cooperation and partnership for service delivery, across and within levels of government, but at the same time the practices show how such intergovernmental relations have helped to overcome or address potential conflicting/diverging interests of different local governments.
- Regarding WP 5 (People's participation in local decision making), the practices show how citizens and stakeholders' engagement in the policy development process influences the interests and motivation of policymakers and thereby the vertical and horizontal, formal and informal intergovernmental relations, and ultimately the outcomes of specific policies.

1.8 Conclusion

Based on the results so far, the next phase of the LoGov project, aimed at comparing local government practices, should focus on the following key topics and questions:

- How local government associations with a broad membership base, represent effectively the potentially different interests of both urban and rural local governments?
- How can the political and economic power of larger urban municipalities be balanced in terms of their impact on intergovernmental relations?
- How can the interests of smaller and more rural local governments be more proactively advocated at the regional and national scene and more effectively integrated in intergovernmental relations?
- How can mechanisms of cooperation prevail over supervision in intergovernmental relations with higher levels of government?
- How can the existing mechanisms for intergovernmental dialogue and consultations be strengthened and made more effective?

- How can the internal functioning and decision-making bodies of the local government associations be strengthened to ensure more effective advocacy and lobbying?
- How can local governments and their associations be more adequately integrated in the process of planning, consulting, and implementing the post COVID-19 recovery efforts, building on the subsidiarity principle?

2. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Italy

2.1 The System of Local Government in Italy

Greta Klotz and Karl Kössler, *Eurac Research*

Types of Local Governments

In Italy, there are three main types of local governments which are recognized under Article 114 of the Constitution as making up, together with the 20 regions¹ and the State, the Italian Republic. These are the municipalities (*comuni*), 14 metropolitan cities (*città metropolitane*) and 83 provinces (*province*). The basic units of local government throughout the country are the 7,914 municipalities (*comuni*). However, in order to facilitate the social and economic integration of urban agglomerations, there are the metropolitan cities (*città metropolitane*). While their establishment had been discussed time and again at least since the 1950s, fierce resistance, especially from the regions, had made their actual creation impossible. Only the constitutional reform of 2001 introduced the metropolitan cities into the Constitution. Then it took over a decade to clarify how they would actually operate and to overcome resistance from other government levels. The Ordinary Law no 56/2014 ('Delrio Law') finally established the metropolitan cities.² The third type of local governments that is recognized under Article 114 as a constituent unit of the Italian Republic are the provinces. They are umbrella entities between the regions and municipalities. Similar to second-tier local governments in other countries the main function of the provinces is the coordination of policies and public services.

Apart from these three main types enshrined in the Constitution, the Legislative Decree no 267/2000 mentioned some more types of local governments. The unions of municipalities (*unioni di comuni*) are composed of two or more municipalities and are an institutional form of cooperation in order to jointly exercise certain functions.³ A similar rationale is behind specific local government entities for particular geographical areas, namely the mountain communities (*comunità montane*) and the island communities (*comunità isolane*).

Legal Status of Local Governments

¹ There are 15 regions with ordinary statute and five regions with special statute, recognized under Article 116 of the Constitution, namely Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-South Tyrol, Aosta Valley and Friuli-Venezia Giulia.

² Giovanni Boggero, 'The Establishment of Metropolitan Cities in Italy: An Advance or a Setback for Italian Regionalism?' (2016) 8 *Perspectives on Federalism* E-1, E-5.

³ Italian Constitutional Court, Judgment no 50/2015.

According to the above-mentioned Article 114 of the Constitution, '[t]he Republic is composed of the Municipalities, the Provinces, the metropolitan cities, the Regions and the State. Municipalities, provinces, metropolitan cities and regions are autonomous entities having their own statutes, powers and functions in accordance with the principles laid down in the Constitution'. Even if this provision seems to suggest that the constituent parts of the Italian Republic are on an equal footing, the Constitutional Court soon emphasized the special role of the state vis-à-vis the other government levels.⁴ While Article 114 ensures that the three main types of local government enjoy autonomy within constitutional principles, it does not go any further in regulating them.

Article 117(2)(p), however, determines that national government shall establish the rules regarding the 'electoral legislation, governing bodies and fundamental functions of the municipalities, provinces and metropolitan cities'. The relevant law consolidating pre-existing rules is the above-mentioned Legislative Decree no 267/2000. The regional legislator can only become active in a complementary manner on the basis of the residuary power under Article 117(6). This is true, however, only for the 15 regions with ordinary statute (hereinafter, ordinary regions). The five regions with special statute (hereinafter special regions) are allowed to regulate their local governments in their autonomy statutes (e.g. Article 4(3) and Article 61-65 of the Statute of Trentino-South Tyrol) and, more in details, through ordinary regional legislation.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

There are certain types of local government with special status that take into account different realities in urban and rural areas, like the above-mentioned metropolitan cities, unions of municipalities, mountain communities and island communities. Certain variations follow from Italy's system of asymmetrical regionalism, more concretely, from the different regulatory regimes concerning ordinary regions and each of the five special regions.

Nonetheless, the local government system is quite symmetrical. This is because the system is rooted in ideas of municipal organization from the French Revolution and Napoleonic times. These ideas were supported by the House of Savoy and after their founding of the Kingdom of Italy in 1861 extended to the whole country by enacting the laws of administrative unification in 1865. This explains adherence, in principle, to the French model of uniform municipalities, which are supposed to carry out the same functions irrespective of territorial size, demography, economic power, as well as urban or rural character.

Political and Social Context in Italy

The political situation at the national government level and, to a lesser extent, in the regions has in recent years witnessed profound changes of the party system. At the national level, a coalition government formed by the Five Star Movement and the League came to power in

⁴ Italian Constitutional Court, Judgment no 274/2003.

2018 and was replaced by a coalition between the Five Star Movement and the Social Democratic Party (PD) in 2019. As for the regions, candidates from the League over the last decade have been elected Presidents in Veneto, Lombardy and Friuli-Venezia Giulia, while Brothers of Italy, another right-wing party, took power in the Abruzzo region in 2019. At the local level, there is a similar tendency. When about half of Italy's municipalities were called to vote in 2019, the center-right block led by the League won, from among those with over 15,000 inhabitants, in 75 municipalities (up from 36).

A good indicator for the social and demographic context of local governments is the OECD definition of functional urban areas as composed of a densely inhabited city and a surrounding area (commuting zone) whose labor market is highly integrated with the city. Following this definition, only 30 per cent of Italy's population live in metropolitan areas (more than 500,000 inhabitants), 20 per cent in small- and medium-sized urban agglomerations (50,000 to 500,000 inhabitants), compared to an OECD average of 49 per cent and 18 per cent, respectively.

As for the structure of municipalities, only 144 of them have more than 50,000 inhabitants, while 70 per cent have less than 5,000 inhabitants and are thus, according to the Italian classification, 'small municipalities'. The average population size is 7,653. But this, of course, says little in view of an extremely wide spectrum ranging from Rome's almost 2.9 million inhabitants to 33 in the municipality of Morterone in the Region of Lombardy.

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2.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Italy: An Introduction

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When it comes to intergovernmental relations with the national government, local government associations are the main actors. The National Association of Italian Municipalities (*Associazione dei Comuni Italiani – ANCI*) has a long-established tradition, as it was founded in 1901 as a non-profit organization active throughout the national territory. It is not recognized by the Italian Constitution, but as the main representative organization of local authorities, it is institutionally anchored in the system of the multilateral cooperation mechanisms with the national government. Not all Italian municipalities are members of the ANCI. As of July 2019, it had 7,041 members from among 7,914 Italian municipalities and represents approx. 90 per cent of the Italian population.⁵ The main goal of ANCI is to represent the interests of municipalities and metropolitan cities vis-à-vis the national and regional governments. It is also a facilitator of international cooperation and even a shareholder of some companies for service provision.

ANCI's assembly, bringing together all members, meets once a year, but the organization has 17 permanent commissions on different policy fields, ranging from local finances and social welfare to immigration and integration policies. Furthermore, ANCI comprises within its structure several special interest bodies. Among others, there is a National Council of Small Municipalities (*Consulta Nazionale dei Piccoli Comuni*). This institution represents all ANCI municipalities with a population of less than 5,000 inhabitants and has the aim to secure and promote the coordination of initiatives, which support small municipalities and to promote initiatives with regard to inter-municipal cooperation. Apart from this council, there is within ANCI also a Coordination Body of Metropolitan Cities' (*Coordinamento delle Città Metropolitane*). Similar to the aim of the above-mentioned council, the task of this coordination body is to support specific initiatives with regard to the metropolitan realities. The mayors of the 14 metropolitan cities as well as the coordinator of the Council of Small Municipalities, also the coordinators of regional councils of small municipalities, are members of the important National Council (*Consiglio nazionale*) of ANCI. This body is important because it determines above all the strategic direction of the association. As in addition to the mayors of the metropolitan cities those of all regional and provincial capitals participate as well, there seems to be a certain imbalance of representation in favor of urban areas.

ANCI is complemented by the National Association of the Italian Provinces (*Unione delle Province d'Italia – UPI*) as well as the National Union of Mountain Towns and Communities (*Unione Nazionale Comuni, Comunità ed Enti Montani – UNCEM*).

In terms of local government councils at the regional level, it should be pointed out that ANCI has branches in all of the 20 Italian regions. In the Autonomous Provinces of Bolzano and Trento, the ANCI is represented by particular provincial associations of local authorities, i.e.

⁵ National Institute of Statistics, 'Codici statistici delle unità amministrative territoriali, novità per l'anno 2019' (*Istat*, 30 June 2019) <<https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/6789>>.

the *Consorzio dei Comuni della Provincia di Bolzano-Südtiroler Gemeindenverband* and the *Consorzio dei Comuni della Provincia di Trento*.

Apart from the regional branches of ANCI, an important body of intergovernmental relations between the regions and local entities was established by the constitutional reform in 2001. According to Article 123 of the Italian Constitution, regions with ordinary statute have to foresee and regulate in their statute a so-called Council of Local Authorities (*Consiglio delle Autonomie Locali* – CAL), an organ ensuring consultation between regions and local authorities. All 20 regions have established this institution. Although the five regions with special statute (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-South Tyrol and Val d'Aosta) enjoy autonomous competences regarding the organization and functioning of local authorities and are, following the Constitutional Court decision no 370/2006, not obliged to establish this institution, all of them have also set up such an advisory body. The main task of a CAL is consultation and sometimes their advice during the legislative process is compulsory. The councils of local authorities of some regions established in 2012 a Permanent Coordination Body of CALs in order to promote inter-regional collaboration between these institutions, as well as to exchange experiences and best practices among each other. According to a recent study, the CALs in the regions with ordinary statute have so far only played a marginal role of influence in regional decision-making, with the lacking implementation of the principle of subsidiarity being a main reason.⁶

As for mechanisms of supervision, it is important to note that the constitutional reform in 2001 cancelled Article 130 of the Constitution, which had foreseen, according to the principle of hierarchy between levels of government, a regional preventive control of acts of local authorities. Before this change the regions had tightly controlled the provinces and municipalities and had been controlled, in turn, by the national government. However, there is still a system of internal administrative monitoring, auditing and the extraordinary substitution power under Article 120 of the Constitution.

According to this provision, '[t]he Government can act for bodies of the regions, metropolitan cities, provinces and municipalities if the latter fail to comply with international rules and treaties or EU legislation, or in the case of grave danger for public safety and security, or whenever such action is necessary to preserve legal or economic unity and in particular to guarantee the basic level of benefits relating to civil and social entitlements, regardless of the geographic borders of local authorities. The law shall lay down the procedures to ensure that subsidiary powers are exercised in compliance with the principles of subsidiarity and loyal co-operation'. This power of the national government to intervene is only for the exceptional circumstances explicitly mentioned in the cited provision and measures must observe the principle of proportionality. Only those measures may be taken that are necessary to achieve, to the benefit of citizens, a swift return to normality and legality. Financial supervision is exercised by the Court of Auditors and its regional branches. Law no 131/2003 strengthened control powers of these courts. But this supervision does not concern the political assessment of measures taken by local governments. It controls the compliance of local government

⁶ Elena di Carpegna Brivio, 'Il CAL tra sogno e realtà. Problemi attuali delle istituzioni di raccordo nel sistema regionale delle fonti' (2018) 5 *Federalismi.it* <<http://www.consigliautonomieitali.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/Inserire.pdf>>.

actions with budget legislation and other rules and policies from the regional, national and EU levels, especially regarding financial mismanagement and balanced budget requirements.

The most important mechanisms for intergovernmental cooperation between the national government, regions and local authorities are the following two conferences: the Conference of the State, Cities and Local Autonomies (hereinafter CSCLA) and the Unified Conference, which brings together the CSCLA with the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces. The latter conference therefore comprises three levels of government (national, subnational and local). The CSCLA was introduced with the Decree of the President of the Council of Ministers on 2 July 1996 and was reformed by the Legislative Decree no 281/1997. The same legislative decree also created the Unified Conference.

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2.3 The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy's Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations

Greta Klotz, *Eurac Research*

Relevance of the Practice

In Italy there are two important formal mechanisms to facilitate intergovernmental relations and to include the local level of government in the political decision-making process: the Conference of the State, Cities and Local Autonomies (hereinafter CSCLA) and the Unified Conference, which brings together the CSCLA with the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces. The latter conference therefore comprises three levels of government (national-subnational and local). The CSCLA was introduced with the decree of the President of the Council of Ministers on 2 July 1996 and was reformed by the Legislative Decree no 281/1997. The same legislative decree also created the Unified Conference.

The two conferences are the only formal institutions where political representatives of the local authorities meet regularly with members of the national and subnational governments to discuss relevant policies, as well as challenges of the local institutions. They are thus of utmost importance.

Description of the Practice

The members of the CSCLA is composed of representatives of the national government as well as representatives of the local authorities. The chair of the conference is held by the Italian Prime Minister or, through delegation, the Interior Minister or the Minister for Regional Affairs. In addition, the following members of the national government participate in the Conference: the Ministers of Finance, Economy, Infrastructure and Health. For the local authorities, the members are: The President of the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI), the President of the Union of Italian Provinces (UPI), 14 mayors appointed by ANCI and 6 presidents of Italian provinces appointed by UPI. The institution tries to strike a balance between urban and rural areas with the provision that five out of the 14 mayors have to represent metropolitan cities. The same persons also form part of the Unified Conference, together with the members of the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces (Prime Minister, Minister of Regional Affairs, all presidents of the Italian Regions and the two presidents of the Autonomous Provinces Trento and Bolzano).

The CSCLA meets normally at least once a month (according to law it has to meet at least every three months). In addition, the Prime Minister, the President of the ANCI and the President of the UPI have the right to ask for a meeting whenever they deem it necessary. On the contrary,

only the Prime Minister has the right to convoke the Unified Conference. The tasks of the CSCLA are about consultation, information and exchange:

- coordination of relations between the state and local authorities;
- study, information and discussion on issues related to policies that may affect the functions of provinces, municipalities and metropolitan cities;
- discussion and examination of problems with regard to the organization of local authorities, including aspects of financial and budgetary policies as well as legislative initiatives and acts of the national government;
- discussion and examination of problems relating to the management and delivery of public services and any other problem that is submitted to the opinion of the Conference itself by the President or at the request of the local authorities;
- encouraging information and initiatives to improve the efficiency of local public services.

In contrast to the CSCLA the Unified Conference brings together three levels of government. According to the Legislative Decree no 281/1997, there is the obligation to consult the conference with regard to draft laws, legislative decrees or acts, which are of common interest for regions and local authorities. Specifically, the Unified Conference expresses opinions (*pareri*), among others, on:

- the draft stability pact that aims to ensure sound public finances;
- the draft finance law and related draft laws;
- the economic and financial planning document.

The function of the conference is purely consultative, as its opinions are not binding. Furthermore, according to Article 9 of the above-mentioned legislative decree, the Prime Minister can put on the agenda each other topic that he/she regards as being of interest for the regions, provinces, municipalities, as well as mountain towns and communities. This can also occur, however, upon request from ANCI, UPI or the National Union of Mountain Towns and Communities (UNCCEM). The UNCCEM was founded in 1952 as a non-profit association, which represents all Italian mountain towns and municipalities, which cover 54 per cent of Italy's territory and are home to around 10 million inhabitants. According to law, the President of UNCCEM should also be a member of the CSCLA. In practice, this function is left to the representation of ANCI, with whom UNCCEM is working closely and on the basis of a written agreement. However, the President of UNCCEM is present at the meetings of the Unified Conference.

Beyond its consultative function, the Conference promotes and confirms, for instance, intergovernmental agreements (*intese*) between the government entities represented there. However, if there is no agreement within 30 days, the Council of Ministers can take a unilateral decision (with justification).

It is interesting how the Unified Conference works in practice. It does not take decisions in common but separately in two groups of entities. The group of regions which are members of the Conference of the State, Regions and Autonomous Provinces and the group of representatives of the local authorities who are members of the CSCLA have to give consent in two separate blocks. Usually, the consent is given in unanimity by the members of these two

groups. If there is no unanimity, the consent is given by the majority of the representatives of each of the groups. Therefore, there is a differentiation in the decision-making process between regional and local authorities but not, among the latter, between authorities from urban areas (e.g. metropolitan cities) and rural areas (e.g. mountain towns and communities).

Assessment of the Practice

The rationale behind the establishment of these two conferences is very important, as they are about reinforcing the relations between the national government and local authorities and giving the latter a voice regarding policies that concern them. Thus, it strengthened the position of the local level of government in the multilevel system and gave it the possibility to discuss these policies and their repercussions in a formal framework. However, it must be borne in mind that there in Italy two dimensions of political access and representation, i.e. the formal channels such as the conference system and the direct, (party-)political informal channels.⁷ The system of intergovernmental relations is therefore not as coherent as a purely formal perspective might suggest.⁸

In spite of their potential crucial role, the conferences are often criticized as being limited to discussing relatively minor technical issues instead of big policy issues and as being imbalanced in terms of decision-making power. It is indeed true, especially, that the role of the local authorities is, in comparison to the national government, quite a limited one. This is underlined by the fact that the Prime Minister chairs both conferences and sets the agenda. Furthermore, the agreements and opinions of the conferences are not binding. Therefore, although there is the formal collaboration between government levels, these opinions are in fact often ignored by the national government. There are of course some decisions which require not only consultation with local authorities but also their agreement, even if constitutional jurisprudence has defined this requirement on a case-by-case basis in very different ways. Arguably even more problematic is the fact that there is no mechanism for verifying compliance with what was agreed upon, especially when it comes to implementation.⁹ In fact, as some scholars have pointed out, it was only the Covid-19 pandemic which eventually seems to have prompted the national government to take the conference system more seriously.¹⁰ Before that, the latter had after some debates in the end often relied on 'hard' instrument such as financial tools and pressure.

From the perspective of the local authorities, a further challenge is within the conference system to speak with one common voice. This is so because experiences especially with metropolitan cities suggest that there is an intense struggle for representation and that

⁷ Statement by Silvia Bolgherini, Senior Researcher, Institute for Comparative Federalism, Eurac Research, Bolzano/Bozen (LoGov Country Workshop, Structure of Local Government, 23 October 2020).

⁸ Statement by Andrea Lippi, Associate Professor, Department of Political Science, University of Florence (LoGov Country Workshop, Structure of Local Government, 23 October 2020).

⁹ Interview with Claudia Tubertini, Associate Professor, Department of Legal Studies, University of Bologna (14 May 2021).

¹⁰ Statement by Andrea Lippi, Associate Professor, Department of Political Science, University of Florence (LoGov Country Workshop, Structure of Local Government, 23 October 2020).

medium- and large-sized local governments typically prevail.¹¹ For this reason, the broad spectrum of different views on specific policies by local governments from urban and rural territories might be not visible. Metropolitan cities have a strong position as they represent 5 out of 14 mayors, even if about 90 per cent of Italian municipalities have less than 3,000 inhabitants. As for the above-mentioned two channels, the political and institutional one, local governments other than metropolitan cities are therefore disadvantaged concerning the institutional channel. As a result, they focus on political contacts with other government levels, through ANCI or outside of it. Due to Italy's historical legacy of localism, it is not that municipalities are not heard at all, quite often mayors even in appear public and media debates concerning national issues. What is missing is stronger integration through the institutional channel.¹²

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<<http://www.conferenzastatocitta.it/it/>>

¹¹ Statement by Silvia Bolgherini, Senior Researcher, Institute for Comparative Federalism, Eurac Research, Bolzano/Bozen (LoGov Country Workshop, Structure of Local Government, 23 October 2020).

¹² Interview with Andrea Lippi, Professor, Department of Political and Social Sciences, University of Florence (10 June 2021).

2.4 The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations

Greta Klotz, *Eurac Research*

Relevance of the Practice

With the Italian constitutional reform of 2001 (Article 123 of the Italian Constitution), it was introduced that each Italian region shall regulate in its statute the activity of a Council of Local Authorities (*Consiglio delle Autonomie Locali* – CAL) as a consultative body between the regions and local authorities. Although the five special regions (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-South Tyrol and Val d'Aosta) enjoy autonomous competences in the organization and functioning of local authorities and they are, following the decision by the Constitutional Court no 370/2006, not obliged to establish this institution, all of them have set up such an advisory body.

On this legal basis, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/South Tyrol established in 2003 the Council of Municipalities (hereinafter the Council) which was then reformed in 2010. The Council is based at the South Tyrolean Parliament and issues 'advisory opinions' (*Gutachten/pareri*) on all draft laws and resolutions of the provincial parliament and government concerning the local level: 'The Council is required to express an opinion on draft legislative acts, state ordinances and general administrative acts, where these concern matters in which the relevant functions are wholly or partly assigned or allocated to municipalities, local taxes or local finances'.¹³

The Council has a crucial role for representing the positions and assessments of local authorities in the decision-making process at subnational level and it has to speak with one voice.

Description of the Practice

In the respective Law no 4 of 4 February 2010, the Council is defined as 'advisory board' and as 'body of cooperation' between the Autonomous Province and the municipalities.

The Council consists of 17 members (16 ordinary members and the President) which are at the same time also the members of the executive board of the local government association of South Tyrol (*Südtiroler Gemeindeverband/Consorzio dei Comuni*). The Council brings together political representatives of different municipalities and guarantees also a balance between big and small municipalities and different territories of the Province. Only current or former mayors as well as members of the local executives can be elected as members of the Council. This applies also for the President of the Council. The vast majority of the 17 members is

¹³ Article 6, Provincial Law no 4/2010

elected by the plenary assembly of all South Tyrolean mayors and only some of them, for instance the members representing the City of Bolzano, are nominated. For a territorial balance, each of the seven *Bezirksgemeinschaften/comunità comprensoriali* (intermediate territorial bodies between the municipalities and Autonomous Province) is entitled to have one member in the Council. The City of Bolzano as capital city of the province has the right to nominate three members. In addition, the municipalities with more than 20,000 inhabitants and the group of municipalities with up to 1,200 inhabitants each send one member.

If population size of more than 10,000 inhabitants is taken as indicator (because only such municipalities can apply for recognition as town), then urban-rural representation is quite balanced. Six out of 17 members are currently from such municipalities. Formally, local authorities from urban areas seem to be overrepresented compared to those from rural areas. The City of Bolzano nominates three members and municipalities with a population of over 20,000 a fourth one, while those with less than 1,200 inhabitants are only represented by one representative. However, most of the Council members elected irrespective of whether they come from an urban or rural municipality (e.g. those from each *Bezirksgemeinschaft/comunità comprensoriale*) are in practice from smaller rural local governments. The latter dominate these elections for demographic reasons. Only seven out of 116 municipalities in South Tyrol have more than 10,000 inhabitants, even though they constitute 43,6 per cent of the total population in the province.

Apart from guaranteeing a balance between big and small municipalities, the composition of the Council has also to respect a balance of the three linguistic groups in South Tyrol: one member has to be from the Ladin language group and four members from the Italian language group. Furthermore, in relation to the number of female mayors and executive members also the representation of women has to be guaranteed in the Council. The election of the members is announced by the President of the South Tyrolean Parliament, who also appoints the members by decree. The Secretary General of the Council is also the Managing Director of the provincial local government association.

As for its tasks and functions, the Council gives its opinion on all drafts of laws and resolutions which concern the local level, although these are not binding opinions. It must provide an opinion within 30 days of being requested by the South Tyrolean Parliament or the provincial government. If the political representatives do not comply with the opinion, the parliament or the government must provide a written justification. Apart from the fact that its opinions may be overruled, it has no right to initiate the process of giving opinions. As the Council may only act upon request, the definition of what constitutes a 'local' issue and thus triggers the consultation mechanisms is a prerogative of the provincial parliament and government. The Council issues positive, negative or conditionally positive opinions. The latter are opinions that contain comments or proposed changes. In 2018, a total of 84 opinions on draft laws or government resolutions were issued. Almost half (45 out of 84) were positive without conditions, 24 were positive with conditions or comments, four were negative. Apart from this most important function, the Council has the following rights:

- it has legislative initiative with regard to provincial laws concerning local issues;
- the President of the Council can request hearings by the legislative commissions of the provincial parliament;

- it can, with the approval of two thirds of its members, initiate a referendum to abolish a provincial law, except in areas relating to local taxes, finance or the provincial budget.

Assessment of the Practice

The establishment of the Council as institutionalized advisory body can be seen as a huge valorization of the local level of government, as the involvement of the municipalities in the legislative process contributes to the enhancement of local autonomy. Nevertheless, the Council's actual political influence remains limited by its only consultative function. Through the personal union between the Council members and its Secretary with the executive board and the Managing Director of the provincial local government association, both bodies form a unity which further reinforces their central role in vertical relations with the province and horizontally between the municipalities themselves. The provincial local government association would like to enhance the functions of the Council: They propose that a deviation of the Council's opinions should require approval by a qualified majority. Furthermore, they request the presence of the Council President also at the legislative committee discussions which follow the hearing involving the President before this committee.

Recently, however, the Council has been involved in the implementation of the new Law no 18/2017 on the organization of the municipalities including the forms of inter-municipal cooperation.¹⁴ It is actively involved and all decisions have to be taken in agreement. In this regard, however, it is stipulated that if there is no agreement between the Council and the provincial government within 60 days, the latter can continue with the implementation. This underlines that the role of the municipalities has been enhanced but they are not (yet) equal partners. It is difficult to assess the effectiveness in comparison with the Councils of Local Authorities (CAL) in other regions. In general, the latter are not seen as having had a major added value.¹⁵ The degree of their involvement depends very much on the regional government in office, but according to many studies they are not the places where real consultation takes place. For this purpose, informal political channels are normally preferred.

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¹⁴ For more detail on this law and on inter-municipal cooperation in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/South Tyrol, see report section 4.5. on Inter-municipal Cooperation Based on a Model Agreement: A Top-down Approach in South Tyrol.

¹⁵ Interview with Claudia Tubertini, Associate Professor, Department of Legal Studies, University of Bologna (14 May 2021).

Peterlini E, 'Der Rat der Gemeinden. Von schwammigen beratenden Funktionen zum politischen Gewicht in der Landespolitik' in Elisabeth Alber, Alice Engl and Günther Pallaver (eds), *Politika 2016. Südtiroler Jahrbuch für Politik* (politika and Raetia 2016)

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2.5 Migration Management as an Intergovernmental Cooperation Instrument in Rural Areas

Caterina Salvo, *Eurac Research*

Relevance of the Practice

Italy, due to its geographical position at the center of the Mediterranean Sea, occupies a strategic location regarding the migratory routes towards Europe. The 2014 so-called ‘refugee crisis’ marked a crucial turning point in the Italian immigration policy regime. Italy was on the front line in hosting the newcomers and, as the first state of arrival accordingly to the Dublin Convention and its modifications, it was responsible for examining the majority of the international protection requests, a condition that placed the reception and legal system in a difficult situation. The number of asylum applications jumped from 25,207 in 2013 to 83,970 in 2015.¹⁶ The number of requests rose to reach its peak in 2017 with 130,119 applications made.¹⁷ Therefore, migration became an issue of key relevance for all Italian government levels. Migration policies concerning control and management of entries into Italian territory is within the competence of the national government, while asylum seekers’ reception and integration are issues of complex multi-level governance dynamics.

The present practice concerns the role of local governments within this multi-level governance, which in Italy is both vertical and horizontal. Vertical governance, characterized by center-periphery relations, aims at guaranteeing a coordination mechanism between the various levels of government. Horizontal governance, based on the collaboration between public actors and private-sector players, seeks to create an integrated system of services. The overall objective is to design a territorially decentralized reception and integration system (*accoglienza diffusa*) to avoid substantial concentrations of migrants in a few larger urban centers. Empirical evidence has shown that the local level is pivotal in determining not only the implementation but also the formulation and decision-making phases of immigration policies.¹⁸ This is particularly relevant in Italy considering the morphology of its territory:

¹⁶ Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration, ‘Quaderno statistico per gli anni 1990 – 2020’ (Ministry of the Interior, undated)

http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/quaderno_statistico_per_gli_anni_1990_2020.pdf> accessed 9 July 2021.

¹⁷ The number of applications is calculated on the basis of the so-called C3 module of international protection deposited at the local police headquarter (*Questura*). Therefore, the number of arrivals exceed the number of applications: as for 2017, the number of undocumented migrants arrived was 181,436. See Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration, ‘Quaderno statistico per gli anni 1990 – 2020’; Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration, ‘Cruscotto statistico giornaliero’ (Ministry of the Interior, undated)

http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/cruscotto_statistico_giornaliero_31-12-2017.pdf> accessed 9 July 2021.

¹⁸ To expand on that point and on the so-called ‘local turn’ in migration and integration policies, see, for instance Peter Scholten and Rinus Penninx, ‘The Multilevel Governance of Immigration and Integration’ in Blanca Garcés-

among a total number of 7,954 municipalities 69.85 per cent (5,545) have less than 5,000 inhabitants,¹⁹ and almost all of them are located in inland areas.²⁰ The Italian multi-level and decentralized migration governance system therefore has significant implications for urban-rural relations.

Description of the Practice

The Italian migrant reception and integration system is organized in such a way that rescue, aid and assistance take place in the so-called ‘hotspot areas’,²¹ namely national governmental centers located at the main places of arrival. Those applying for asylum in Italy enter the first phase which takes place in government collective centers called Primary Reception Centers (*Centri di Prima Accoglienza* – CPA). The stay inside the CPA centers corresponds to the time necessary for the asylum application procedure to begin.

The second phase consists of the Reception and Integration System (*Sistema Accoglienza e Integrazione* – SAI). The program, introduced in 2020 with the Decree Law no 130/2020, substitutes the Protection System for Persons with International Protection and Unaccompanied Foreign Minors (SIPROIMI) established in 2018 following the so-called Security Decree (Decree Law no 113/2018 also known as Salvini Decree), which in turn replaced the Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SPRAR) in force from 2002 to 2018. The SAI re-established the principles that had inspired the SPRAR: a coordinated and territorially decentralized system of reception and integration and specific measures to promote integration. The SAI can be accessed by both applicants for and beneficiaries of international protection even though organized on two levels of services. The first level is dedicated to applicants for international protection; the second to those who already have been granted international protection entailing additional services focused on fostering integration.

In the absence of sufficient places within the programs of the two above-mentioned phases of reception and integration (CPA and SAI), the system authorizes the possibility for the prefectures to establish so-called Extraordinary Reception Centers (*Centri Accoglienza Straordinaria* – CAS). CAS are managed directly by the prefecture, the operational arm of the Ministry of the Interior at the local level, and entrusted to private entities. Despite the fact that this is an extraordinary system, CAS centers have become by far the majority of reception

Mascarenas and Rinus Penninx (eds), *Integration Process and Policies in Europe. Contexts, Levels and Actors* (IMISCOE Research Series 2006); Francesca Campomori and Tiziana Caponio, ‘Immigrant Integration Policymaking in Italy: Regional Policies in a Multi-Level Governance Perspective’ (2017) 83 *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 303.

¹⁹ Data from the National Institute for Statistics ISTAT, ‘Annuario Statistico Italiano 2019’ (ISTAT 2019) 3-30 <<https://www.istat.it/it/files/2019/12/Asi-2019.pdf>> accessed 9 July 2021.

²⁰ Inland areas are also called ‘inner areas’ following the definition made by the National Strategy on Inner Areas – SNAI. For more information on the topic, see the respective website of the Agency for Territorial Cohesion, <<https://www.agenziacoesione.gov.it/strategia-nazionale-aree-interne/?lang=en>>. To the scope of the present research, they can be compared to rural areas, even if the majority of them is located in mountain regions.

²¹ By the end of 2015, the operative hotspots were 6: 4 in Sicily (Porto Empedocle, Pozzallo, Trapani, Lampedusa) and 2 in Puglia (Augusta and Taranto).

facilities over the years.²² As of January 2021, among the total of 80,097²³ migrants welcomed only 30,049²⁴ have been hosted inside SAI facilities with the remaining being received inside CAS centers (around 62,5 per cent).

One main difference between the two levels of the Italian reception system concerns their management. CPA and CAS centers are administered centrally by the Ministry of the Interior and peripherally by the local prefecture following national government instructions with a top-down approach. As for CAS in particular, while until 2018 the legislation provided (albeit rarely applied) for the involvement of local authorities in the identification of extraordinary centers, this involvement was completely set aside with the security decrees²⁵ which entailed a centralization and securitization of migration policies.

SAI facilities are initiated by municipalities responding to a ministerial call for project funding following a bottom-up logic. The SAI network is coordinated by the Central Service (*Servizio Centrale*) based in Rome, whose administration is assigned by the Ministry of Interior to the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI) with the operational support of the Cittalia Foundation. Cittalia is the ANCI foundation dedicated to promoting and disseminating the culture of welcome, integration and citizenship, contributing to strengthening the role of cities in implementing social inclusion and integration policies.²⁶

The municipalities that choose to join the SAI network, as it was also in the previous systems SIPROIMI and SPRAR, outsource the implementation of the project to one or more managing bodies (usually private-sector organizations) and sometimes also involve second-tier local governments. The fact that in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/South Tyrol the seven

²² As of 31 December 2019, there were 5,469 CAS centers located all over the country. See Openpolis, 'I comuni dove vengono offerti più posti nei centri di accoglienza' (*Openpolis*, 9 April 2021) <<https://www.openpolis.it/i-comuni-dove-vengono-offerti-piu-posti-nei-centri-di-accoglienza/>> accessed 2 August 2021.

²³ Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration, 'Cruscotto statistico giornaliero al 31 dicembre 2021' (Ministry of the Interior 2021) <http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/cruscotto_statistico_giornaliero_31-01-2021.pdf> accessed 9 July 2021.

²⁴ The present number encompasses ordinary beneficiaries, unaccompanied foreign minors and asylum seekers with special needs (mental or physical disorder). 'I numeri della rete SAI. Progetti Territoriali gennaio 2021' (*Sistema Accoglienza Integrazione*, January 2021) <<https://www.retesai.it/i-numeri-dello-sprar/>> accessed 9 July 2021.

²⁵ Openpolis & Actionaid, 'Centri d'Italia, una mappa dell'accoglienza' (*Openpolis*, 16 March 2021), <<https://www.openpolis.it/esercizi/limportanza-di-un-monitoraggio-dettagliato/>> accessed 9 July 2021. In this regard, it is interesting to note that in October 2016 the Minister of the Interior, following the pressure made by the Italian Association of Municipalities (ANCI), issued a directive concerning the so-called 'safeguard clause' (*clausola di salvaguardia*). Such a clause exempted the municipalities already involved in a SPRAR project (or having formally expressed the intention to do so) from having a CAS center opened on their territory. 'Piano di Ripartizione e Clausola di Salvaguardia' (*Sistema Accoglienza Integrazione*, undated) <<https://www.retesai.it/piano-di-ripartizione-e-clausola-di-salvaguardia/>> accessed 9 July 2021.

²⁶ Founded in 2008, the Cittalia Foundation has dealt with environment, institutions and innovation and then focused on welfare and social inclusion; study and research activities, as well as the development of new projects which are devoted to asylum, human rights, immigration, citizenship, social inclusion, social and socio-health policies. For more information, see the Cittalia website, <<https://www.cittalia.it/utility/la-fondazione/chi-siamo/>> accessed 9 July 2021.

Bezirksgemeinschaften/comunità comprensoriali, intermediate territorial bodies between the municipalities and autonomous province, were involved in the SPRAR is a case in point.

The emergency nature of the CAS allows, on the one hand, greater flexibility in terms of organization, and, on the other hand, less administrative transparency compared to the SAI model.²⁷ Such features combined with, on the one hand, the voluntary nature of signing up to SAI projects and, on the other, the possibility for the local prefecture to force the opening of CAS centers, have contributed to a climate of tension between the different levels of government regarding migration and integration management.

The complexity of multi-level migration governance is exacerbated by the above-mentioned multitude of small inland municipalities. These are small in demographic terms but often cover large territories so that access to public services is limited or even problematic. The trend of the depopulation of these areas is complemented by the rationale behind the territorially decentralized reception and integration system to incentivize the settlement of migrants in rural municipalities and not only in cities.²⁸

Even though the majority of asylum seekers are hosted in large urban areas, a distinction between the two levels of receptions in relation to their territorial distribution is worth to be explored.

Considering the CAS/CPA system, 75,43 per cent²⁹ of the total available places³⁰ are located in the so-called 'pole', 'inter-municipal pole' and 'belt', namely those municipalities having inside their territory or the neighboring one all essential services³¹. Interestingly, only around 24 per cent of the total CAS/CPA places are located in 'intermediate' and 'peripheral' or 'ultra-peripheral' areas. The center-north has the highest number of facilities, with Emilia Romagna

²⁷ In this regard, two recent contributions made by Openpolis are particularly relevant. They offer a comprehensive and updated overview of the CPA/CAS facilities by municipalities. It is the first time that data concerning location, number of centers and migrants hosted in governmental centers at the national level is made publicly available. See Openpolis & Actionaid, 'Centri d'Italia, una mappa dell'accoglienza' (Openpolis, 16 March 2021), <<https://www.openpolis.it/esercizi/limportanza-di-un-monitoraggio-dettagliato/>> accessed 9 July 2021; Openpolis, 'I comuni dove vengono offerti più posti nei centri di accoglienza' (Openpolis, 9 April 2021) <<https://www.openpolis.it/i-comuni-dove-vengono-offerti-piu-posti-nei-centri-di-accoglienza/>> accessed 2 August 2021.

²⁸ See, as an example, Martin Hedelund, Doris A Carson, Marco Eimermann and Linda Lundmark, 'Repopulating and Revitalising Rural Sweden? Re-examining Immigration as a Solution to Rural Decline' (2017) 183 The Geographical Journal 400; Manfred Perlik and Andrea Membretti, 'Migration by Necessity and by Force to Mountain Areas: An Opportunity for Social Innovation' (2018) 38 Mountain Research and Development 250. The recent EU-Horizon 2020 MATILDE three-year project focus specifically on the impact of migration on the local development of rural and mountain regions. For more information, see <<https://matilde-migration.eu/>> accessed 9 July 2021.

²⁹ The following data are referred to 2019. See Openpolis & Actionaid, 'Centri d'Italia, una mappa'.

³⁰ 'Available places' means the full capacity of each center, regardless of whether or not the places are occupied.

³¹ The categorization of municipalities in classes (pole, inter-municipal pole, belt, intermediate, peripheral and ultra-peripheral) is the one proposed by the National Strategy on Inner Areas (SNAI). Such classification introduced an interesting novelty feature compared to previous ones because it considers as main feature the accessibility to so-called citizenship rights: primary education, emergency health care services and mobility infrastructures, in particular high-speed railways. The last three classes (intermediate, peripheral and ultra-peripheral) are generally referred to as inner areas.

and Toscana leading the way with in each case 55 per cent respectively of their total municipalities hosting a CAS.³²

Looking at the SAI network, the picture is reversed. Official data concerning the SAI territorial distribution are not yet available. However, looking at the distribution in 2017 of the SPRAR facilities which preceded and formed the basis of the SAI system,³³ 20 per cent of southern municipalities, individually or in association, hosted a project as opposed to 9 per cent of those in the north. In fact, with the exception of Trentino-Alto Adige where 39 per cent of the all municipalities were involved in a SPRAR project, the top regions in the ranking are located in the south: Puglia (38 per cent), Calabria (30 per cent), Sicilia (26 per cent) and Molise (21 per cent). The last positions, on the contrary, were occupied by Lombardy (6 per cent), Piedmont (5 per cent), Veneto (5 per cent), Abruzzo (5 per cent), Friuli Venezia Giulia (4 per cent) and Valle d'Aosta (1 per cent).³⁴ Applying the criterion of inner areas, it appears that almost one out of two municipalities belonging to the SPRAR is located in such an area (323 out of 659).³⁵

Assessment of the Practice

The data clearly shows that, on the one hand, the concentration of the CAS system is in the north, mainly in pole and belt municipalities, and, on the other hand, a greater territorial decentralization of the SPRAR model is witnessed in southern regions, concentrated in inner villages. Looking at this evidence from an urban-rural divide perspective, such an uneven territorial distribution is striking. The reasons that have led to this imbalance between first and second phases of reception and integration are to be found at the local and regional levels. The establishment of inter-municipal cooperation regarding reception and integration is complicated by the voluntary nature of signing up to SAI projects. The limited extent of such cooperation is a general problem but more evident in the north than in the south. Moreover, southern municipalities often cooperate inside the SAI framework to convey public funds and resources into their territory where employment and investment rates are generally low. The consequence is that, overall, poorer municipalities welcome relatively more beneficiaries with fewer services, while richer municipalities host fewer migrants but with higher standards.

What is important to emphasize in relation to the urban-rural divide concerns above all the provision of public services: in the inland areas the access to basic services such as compulsory education, health care and railroad infrastructure, is denied or extremely limited. The

³² Data are referred to 2017. See Luca Pacini, Nicolò Marchesini, Monia Giovannetti, 'L'accoglienza di richiedenti asilo e rifugiati nelle aree interne: una strategia per il rilancio del territorio' (*Percorsi di secondo welfare*, 25 February 2019) <<https://www.secondowelfare.it/immigrazione-e-accoglienza/accoglienza-nelle-aree-interne-una-strategia-per-il-rilancio-del-territorio.html>> accessed 9 July 2021.

³³ The SIPROIMI system was established in 2018, following the so-called Security Decree (Decree Law no 113/2018) and was replaced by the SAI in 2020. Being short-lived it did not change the overall territorial distribution of the precedent SPRAR system.

³⁴ Claudio Buongiorno Sottoriva and Francesco Longo, 'Accoglienza: quando la realtà smentisce le narrazioni' (*lavoce.info*, 16 October 2020), <<https://www.lavoce.info/archives/69965/accoglienza-quando-la-realta-smentisce-le-narrazioni/>> accessed 9 July 2021.

³⁵ Data are referred to 2017. See Pacini and others, 'L'accoglienza di richiedenti asilo e rifugiati nelle aree interne'.

challenge to guarantee services to asylum seekers in such places offered occasions to rethink the meaning of inter-municipal cooperation beyond migration management, as SAI resources could be directed towards actions to the benefit of the whole community. An example is ‘Small Welcoming Municipalities’ (*Piccoli Comuni del Welcome*), an initiative promoted by the Caritas of Benevento with the support of the Sale della Terra Consortium, born from the union of four cooperatives active in the fight against poverty. In the four years of activity, the network has brought together 34 small municipalities in southern and central Italy. The main objective of the network is to foster reciprocity between those who welcome and those who arrive. The intention is to create a new model of welfare capable of empowering the small municipalities to cope with the challenges they are facing. The welcoming of newcomers is seen as a strategy not only to tackle depopulation, rural demographic ageing and environmental degradation but also to rethink the development strategies at the local level. The network supports the strengthening of the SAI System, assistance to fragile fringes of the population, a focus on social agricultural activities and artisanship, overcoming the digital divide, the transition to clean energy and implementation of community-based cooperatives.³⁶

In conclusion, the new system of multi-level governance concerning reception and integration which is in place since 2020 has countered the centralization attempts made in 2018 in several respects and gives rise to an increasing role of local governments. First, it involves single municipalities adhering to the SAI, places the local government association ANCI at the heart of the SAI network and in some cases even features the participation of second-tier municipalities. Secondly, it harks back to the principles and objectives of the pre-2018 SPRAR system and seeks to achieve steering effects in terms of a territorially decentralized reception and integration so as to avoid the ‘natural’ imbalance in this regard between urban and rural local governments. The varied extent to which such decentralization of centers hosting newcomers actually occurs across Italy’s regions is striking. What is common, however, to local governments in all regions are the need – in spite of certain obstacles – to reap maximum benefits from inter-municipal cooperation and to see reception and integration services for migrants as specific group as a platform to rethink local development and public service provision to each local community as a whole.

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3. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Germany

3.1 The System of Local Government in Germany

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Types of Local Governments

In Germany, government at the local level is administered through municipalities (*Gemeinden*) as well as second-tier local governments such as counties (*Kreise*). Larger municipalities with more than 100,000 citizens are often assigned the status of independent city or county-free city (*kreisfreie Stadt*); in addition to their municipality responsibilities, these cities also carry out (second-tier) county responsibilities. In some of the German *Länder*, there are even third-tier local governments, for example districts (*Bezirke*) in Bavaria.³⁷ There are no areas that fall directly under federal or *Länder* rule, as the system of local government extends to the entire territory of the country. However, as jurisdiction over the organizational powers of local authorities lies with each of the 16 *Länder*, 'local government' may come in different shapes. This is particularly true for its internal organization, but may equally be said of its precise powers and responsibilities. Nevertheless, there are several common features of local government.

The German concept of local self-government, as enshrined in Article 28(2) of the Basic Law, implies that local government entities have a general competence (*Allzuständigkeit*) to carry out all responsibilities that are relevant to the local community. Since this general competence is comprehensive, there is, as a result, no such thing as single purpose local governments in Germany. This means that local governments in Germany may, for instance, run public libraries, museums, theaters, opera houses or concert halls, that they can provide airport facilities, energy/water supply, waste/sewage disposal, run hospitals, kindergarten facilities or homes for the elderly. Of course, these vast competences do not go unchecked; local authorities may engage in such activities only within their financial capacity and, in all their activities, local authorities have to abide by the laws and limitations of federal and *Länder* legislation. Nevertheless, contrary to the Anglo-Saxon concept of 'ultra-vires'³⁸, local authorities do not act illegally if they take measures in areas that do not fall within responsibilities explicitly transferred to them by federal or state legislation. In view of their

³⁷ For these and the following considerations see Martin Burgi, 'Federal Republic of Germany' in Nico Steytler (ed), *Local Government and Metropolitan Regions in Federal Systems* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2009) 140-142.

³⁸ See Veith Mehde, 'Steering, Supporting, Enabling: The Role of Law in Local Government Reforms' (2006) 28 *Law & Policy* 164, 165.

general competence, they just need not to be empowered specifically to take action at the local level.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right of local governments to self-government (i.e. to carry out all responsibilities falling within their 'general competence') is constitutionally enshrined at the federal level in Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL).³⁹ This provision reads as follows: 'Within the limits prescribed by law, municipalities shall be guaranteed the right to regulate all local affairs in their own responsibility. Within the limits of their responsibilities as defined by law, associations of municipalities shall equally have the right of self-government according to the laws. The guarantee of self-government shall include the basis of financial autonomy; it shall comprise the right of municipalities to a source of tax revenues that corresponds with the economic ability of the tax debtors (e.g. business tax – *Gewerbesteuer*), and the right to fix the rates at which these sources shall be taxed.' Provisions similar to Article 28(2) BL are also contained in the constitutions of the 16 *Länder* which thus reinforce the constitutional recognition of local authorities and their right to self-government. The constitutional recognition of local government is generally the same for all municipalities, regardless of size or socio-economic importance.

In contrast, the constitutional standing of counties and districts is weaker. Compared to the comprehensive self-government of their constituent municipalities, these second- and third-tier local government entities may not carry out all responsibilities of local importance but are granted the right to self-government only 'within the limits of their responsibilities as defined by law' (Article 28(2) BL).

It is important to stress that Article 28(2) BL as well as the corresponding constitutional provisions at *Länder* level do not grant local autonomy as an absolute right. Local autonomy is only guaranteed in principle, while its precise scope is subject to legislation. Thus, it is the law-makers at federal and *Länder* level that define the precise extent and limitations of local self-government. In practice, the sheer volume of (sometimes very detailed) federal and *Länder* statutes has considerably limited local autonomy. However, as local autonomy is constitutionally guaranteed in principle, local governments are protected by virtue of Article 28(2) BL against excessive and immoderate restrictions of local autonomy and preserves a 'core sphere' (*Kernbereich*) of responsibilities that must remain with municipalities (i.e. finances, local planning, personnel matters, organizational autonomy and the freedom to engage in joint administration with neighboring communities). In addition to that, Article 28(2) BL protects local authorities, to some extent, against the revocation of responsibilities (*Aufgabenentzug*) e.g. by reallocating them at a higher (more centralized) administrative level (*Hochzonung*). As a result, only *very substantial* gains in cost-efficiency, for instance, may justify that responsibilities are taken away from local governments.

³⁹ See Burgi, *Federal Republic of Germany*, above, 143-146.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As pointed out, the legal status is primarily the same for all municipalities regardless of their size and socio-economic importance, although larger municipalities (and especially independent cities) have, with no doubt, more political bearing. As a general principle, the German system follows a symmetrical approach towards the legal status of local governments. However, this symmetry of responsibilities *de jure* can be modified in various ways which may result, *de facto*, in an asymmetrical allocation of responsibilities.

Local authorities may, for example, agree among themselves to join forces and create joint administrative units to carry out specific responsibilities in forms of what is called inter-municipal cooperation (*interkommunale Zusammenarbeit*). For instance, they may, with regard to capacity and cost-effectiveness, share their resources and establish a joint inter-municipal corporation (*Zweckverband*) which is assigned to take care of sewage and/or waste disposal. Such cooperation is particularly common between smaller municipalities but are equally practiced within larger conurbations and between counties and independent cities.

Because of their size, independent cities are capable of carrying out both municipal and county responsibilities through their city administration as a single unit. In rural areas, by contrast, county responsibilities are carried out by counties along with their constituent (smaller) municipalities. The precise division of duties between counties and their municipalities is laid down in *Länder* statutes and may therefore vary. As a general rule, the allocation of responsibilities depends on the capacities of the individual local unit. This means that for reasons of administrative efficiency, counties will regularly assume the execution of duties that cannot be effectively handled by their constituent municipalities. For instance, hospitals will usually be run at county (or even district) level while minor administrative duties such as citizen registration may remain with the constituent municipalities.

Political and Social Context in Germany

Despite the recent turbulences in the course of the financial and migration crises, the political system established under the Basic Law has proven to be relatively stable. In the overall perspective, two parties, the Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU) and the Social Democrats (SPD) still each win between 20 to 40 per cent of total votes while four smaller parties, the Liberal Free Democrats (FDP), the Greens (*Bündnis 90/Die Grünen*), the Left Party (*Die Linke*) and the Alternative for Germany (AfD), attract between 5 and 20 per cent of all voters. In the East German 'new' *Länder*, *Die Linke* and AfD are usually stronger in elections than in West Germany. On the *Länder* level and on the local level, the landscape of political parties is more diverse. In addition to the aforementioned parties, there are several parties which are particularly active in certain regions and municipalities, taking account of political issues with specific relevance for the respective region or municipality. In Bavaria, for example, the Independent Voters (Freie Wähler) are usually quite strong in the elections – they won 11,6 per cent of the votes during the 2018 elections for the Bavarian *Landtag* and are hence currently part of the Bavarian government, and they are represented in numerous municipal councils.

The spatial distribution of the population still reflects, to a certain extent, the decentralized structure of the Federal Republic of Germany. 27 per cent of the population (i.e. around 22 million people) live in smaller municipalities with 5,000 – 20,000 inhabitants. Another 27 per cent live in medium sized cities (*Mittelstädte*) with 20,000 – 100,000 inhabitants. 31 per cent of the German population live in major cities (*Großstädte*) with more than 100,000 inhabitants. The largest cities with more than 1,000,000 inhabitants each are Berlin (3,700,000), Hamburg (1,890,000), Munich (1,470,000) and Cologne (1,080,000). Of course, many smaller municipalities and medium sized cities are part of a metropolitan area (*Ballungsraum*). Together with Böblingen (50,000), Waiblingen (55,000), Sindelfingen (64,000), Tübingen (89,000), Ludwigsburg (93,000) and Esslingen (93,000), for instance, Reutlingen (115,000), Heilbronn (123,000) and Stuttgart (634,000) as well as all surrounding municipalities form the Stuttgart metropolitan area (total population: 5,300,000). In this perspective, around 77 per cent of the German population nowadays live in metropolitan regions.

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3.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Germany: An Introduction

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System of Local Tasks and State Supervision

The structural distinction between the two poles of self-government tasks (tasks of a local government's own sphere of influence; *Selbstverwaltungsaufgaben*) and state tasks (tasks in the assigned sphere of influence or external tasks; *staatliche Auftragsangelegenheiten*) is elementary for the understanding of intergovernmental relations of local government in Germany. Due to the existence of different task categories⁴⁰ in horizontal and vertical respects, voluntary or compulsory, but also thematically and structurally, as well as the fragmentation of Länder law, it is not easy to filter out a general system of intergovernmental relations. In the course of development, a distinction has been made in Germany between Länder with a dualistic task model (e.g. Bavaria) and Länder with a monistic (uniform) task model (e.g. Brandenburg).⁴¹ In the relationship between the county and the respective Land, the tasks are carried out in the same structures as in the relationship between the municipality and the Land, i.e. separately depending on whether the dualistic or the monistic system is the basis. As a result, the same types of tasks are to be distinguished at the county level as at the municipal level. The debate on the various task categories and the resulting legal consequences must take place according to the affiliation to one of the two models. In Ländern with the dualistic system, local governments can be assigned state tasks as external tasks, which are generally outside the scope of Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL). Their imposition is an intervention that needs to be justified and often leads to intergovernmental disputes, particularly because of the financial implications of resolving them. That is why local governments are increasingly defending themselves against the excessive burden of tasks (*Aufgabenüberbürdung*). This applies mostly to RLGs which are already struggling with their financial capacity and don't get enough support from the higher local levels.

Intergovernmental relations are also relevant when a municipality wants to defend itself against a measure of state supervision. In the event of a dispute, it is usually a question of the competence of the state authority and the scope of its supervisory powers.⁴² The result depends – as already mentioned above – on whether the municipality is involved in the execution of a self-government task or a state task. State supervision can be divided into two dimensions: on the one hand, it serves the municipalities as a defensive right, while at the same time it can also be used as a controlling tool. It is governed by the Länder constitutions

⁴⁰ Around the two poles there are further categories such as 'compulsory task according to instructions' (*Pflichtaufgabe nach Weisung*), 'compulsory task without instructions' (*Pflichtaufgabe ohne Weisung*), 'lending of organs' (*Organleihe*), 'actions being taken as lower state administrative authorities' (*Tätigwerden als untere staatliche Verwaltungsbehörde*), etc. In all cases there is an interlocking with the state administrative organization through the so-called state supervision of the local governments.

⁴¹ A further detailed explanation of the two systems can be found at Martin Burgi, *Kommunalrecht* (6th edn, CH Beck 2019) para 8.

⁴² For legal protection in the relationship between the state and the municipality, see Burgi, *Kommunalrecht*, above, para 9.

and, depending on its scope, is intended to ensure legality (legal supervision; Rechtsaufsicht) or coordination within the state as a whole (subject-specific supervision; Fachaufsicht). Legal supervision aims to ensure compliance with formal and substantive European law, federal and Länder law. It is open to the execution of voluntary and compulsory tasks without instructions. In the case of state tasks or compulsory tasks in accordance with instructions, the standard of expediency is added to the standard of legality. In principle, authority to issue directives (Weisungsbefugnisse) only exists for the last-mentioned tasks. The instruments are to be differentiated according to preventive or repressive supervision. The following supervisory instruments are provided for in all Länder: right to information (Informationsrecht), right of objection or cancellation (Beanstandungs- bzw. Aufhebungsrecht), right to order or instruction (Anordnungs- bzw. Anweisungsrecht) and substitute performance (Ersatzvornahme). The selection within the supervisory instruments should be based on the prohibition of excessive use, i.e. graduated according to the intensity of the intervention. State supervision gains the greatest relevance in the course of monitoring the budgetary system of the municipalities. The respective Municipal Code contains the principle of balanced budgets. If this rule is violated by the municipality, the state supervisory authority is obliged to ensure that the municipality restores the budget balance. In the relationship between the county and the respective Land, the tasks are carried out in the same structures as in the relationship between the municipality and the Land, i.e. separately according to whether the dualistic or monastic system is the basis. As with the municipalities, but to a much greater extent, there is also an interlocking with the administrative organization of the Land at the lower level. The scope of tasks of the counties is, of course, to be delimited not only with respect to the Land but also with respect to the municipalities belonging to the county. There are no significant differences between urban and rural areas with regard to intergovernmental relations, only with regard to which authority is specifically responsible for supervision.

The legal protection against a supervisory action is available to a local government and takes place before the Administrative Court (Verwaltungsgericht). Its decision depends on whether it is involved in the handling of a self-government task or a state task. In most cases, it is a question of the delimitation of the competence of a state authority and the scope of its supervisory powers. As mentioned earlier, the right of local self-government in Article 28(2) BL gives local governments a strong position to defend themselves.

Local Authority Associations

Not municipalities, but representatives of municipal interests organized under private law are the Local Authority Associations (*Kommunale Spitzenverbände*), which are very powerful in political life: The German Association of Cities and Municipalities (*Deutscher Städte- und Gemeindebund*), in which mainly small and medium-sized municipalities and cities (approx. 13,000) are grouped together, the German Association of Cities (*Deutscher Städtetag*), an association of larger towns and cities (approx. 3,600), and the German Association of Counties (*Deutscher Landkreistag*; approx. 295), each with state associations. They are voluntary associations on a private law basis so they don't underlie state supervision. These umbrella organizations represent the interests of the counties, cities and municipalities vis-à-vis other political actors and exert a decisive influence on the *Länder* and federal governments. An

indication of the increased importance of European law in this area as well is the existence of the so-called European Office of German Local Self-Government in Brussels.

The coordination of their work lies within the Federal Association of Local Authority Associations (founded on 19 May 1953). The Local Authority Associations are organized at both federal and state level while they are financed primarily by membership fees or by levies and are thus independent and autonomous in relation to state directives. This enables them to represent the interests of their members decisively. Despite numerous advances, the Local Authority Associations have so far not succeeded in establishing a qualified right to be heard or even a right of legislative co-determination by supplementing Article 28 of the Basic Law. However, individual *Länder* (such as Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hesse, Saxony, Thuringia and Brandenburg) guarantee constitutionally that they can participate in legislative procedures. Other external functions include an advisory and consultation function for planning projects and decisions of the federal government and the *Länder* relevant to local authorities, and the representation of the interests of the members of the associations vis-à-vis the federal government and the *Länder*. Another major field of activity of the Local Authority Associations is their internal functions, e.g. the organization of the exchange of experience and opinion-forming process between the members, as well as their technical and legal advice.

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3.3 Migration and Integration

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Relevance of the Practice

The integration of refugees has in the recent years become an urgent task in Germany due to the immigration of over 1 million people since the late summer of 2015. Due to the character of the integration task as primarily person – and location-related, the focus of the task completion – at least after recognition as an asylum seeker – lies with the local governments.⁴³ This is where the urgently needed integration of the various tasks (education and training, social affairs, employment promotion, housing provision but also social participation) can most likely succeed (or fail). In the emerging ‘integration administrative law’ the local governments play a central role. At its core is the question of which level in the federal state can most effectively solve which task in the area of asylum and integration administration (first reception/asylum application processing/integration). An answer to this is always found in the tension between fundamental considerations with regard to the distribution of competences in the federal state and the existing administrative structures. The fact that only from January 2015 to June 2018 a total of 876,000 persons received a positive BAMF (Federal Office for Migration and Refugees) decision (in addition to persons whose deportations are suspended) demonstrates the need for action. This is also why the integration of new immigrants is the more protracted and fundamental task that requires more attention. Particularly with regard to various factors (security, peace and quiet, cleanliness, support from volunteers, mobility, job opportunities, housing) there are major differences between but also pros and cons of integration in the urban and the rural area.⁴⁴ Overall, it should be a high priority to create the same organizational conditions both for urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs). If this is not so easy to accomplish for RLGs (with regard to their financial situation) on their own, intergovernmental relations can (or should) often give them a better starting position.

Description of the Practice

The BAMF is a central higher federal authority (*Bundesoberbehörde*) and was founded to ensure uniform application of the law, i.e. equal treatment of all asylum seekers. The task

⁴³ On the fact that the accommodation of asylum seekers is not a local task, see BVerwG NVwZ 1990, 1173; NVwZ 1994, 694.

⁴⁴ An interesting insight into the perspective of refugees with regard to integration in rural areas (in Bavaria) with practical comments can be found here: ‘Sicht der Geflüchteten auf ländliche Räume’ in Peter Mehl (ed), *Aufnahme und Integration von Geflüchteten in ländliche Räume: Spezifika und (Forschungs-)Herausforderungen* (Thünen Institut 2017) <https://www.thuenen.de/media/ti-themenfelder/Laendliche_Lebensverhaeltnisse/Thuenen-Arbeitsgruppe_Integration_von_Fluechtlingen_/Integration_als_Forschungs-Herausforderung/5_TR53_Teil_II.pdf>.

portfolio can be fundamentally divided into the two pillars ‘migration’ and ‘integration’. The migration-related tasks result mainly from the implementation of the asylum procedure (acceptance of applications, examination in the Dublin procedure, personal interview, decision on the application). In the field of integration, the BAMF has constantly expanded its range of tasks since the Immigration Act (*Zuwanderungsgesetz*) came into force in 2005. This includes in particular the nationwide responsibility for the two central language courses and the integration courses. The increasing expansion of competences is leading to concerns on the part of local governments that the BAMF could develop in the direction of a ‘Federal Integration Agency’ (*Bundesintegrationsagentur*). A coordination of language courses at local level can be seen as a better way of linking integration courses with measures for labor market integration that are also at local level. At federal level can also be found the Central Register of Foreigners (*Ausländerzentralregister*) which is a database where personal data records of foreigners are stored. Data are stored on foreigners in Germany who have or have had a residence permit, as well as on those who have applied for asylum, had applied for asylum or are recognized asylum seekers. The register is maintained by the BAMF. The Central Register of Foreigners is one of the most comprehensive automated registers of public administration in Germany. 6,500 partner authorities have access to this large database, including all immigration authorities, the BAMF, the federal government Commissioner for Migration, Refugees and Integration and the German police and customs services. The majority of the integration-related administrative tasks lie with the local governments as ‘Immigration Authority’ (*Ausländerbehörde*). Local integration includes all measures for the integration of refugees who either have a ‘good prospect of staying’ or are already recognized by the BAMF with regard to one of the forms of protection. Immigration Authorities are the municipalities themselves in urban regions and the counties with their county offices (*Landratsämter*) in rural areas.

Asylum procedures need to be completed as quickly as possible in order to obtain early clarity on the residence status of protection seekers. Anchor centers (AnKER) are certain reception centers for asylum seekers in Germany. The designation stands for ‘Centre for Arrival, Decision, Return’. Refugees are to be accommodated in an anchor center until they are distributed in communities or deported to their country of origin. In an anchor center, various authorities should work together, such as a youth welfare office or the BAMF. In principle, there is an ‘obligation to stay’. People with positive prospects of an asylum status are to be quickly distributed among the municipalities, the rest remaining in the anchor center until deportation or voluntary return. The responsibilities of establishing and operating the anchor centers lie in the administrative competence of the *Länder*.

In recent years, integration policy in the *Länder* has been significantly upgraded. In the meantime, one ministry in each *Land* is in charge of integration, and the *Länder* have created the office of a Commissioner for Foreigners and Integration almost nationwide. In addition, a large number of the *Länder* have so-called state advisory councils, which advise governments on integration policy issues. In addition, four *Länder* have enacted their own integration laws. An essential task of the *Länder* is the promotion of municipal integration tasks. Looking at the support measures of the *Länder* in detail, it becomes clear that the variety of support measures is hardly manageable and that the associated problem is that there is hardly any transparency about these various support options (‘support jungle’). There is a clear need for action with

regard to the design of funding measures at *Länder* and federal level. The aim should be to dovetail and focus measures and to evaluate their effectiveness, as well as to enable a better overview (e.g. through a comprehensive funding portal). Many local governments have already had positive experiences with an integrated administrative unit for migration and integration. In essence, it is a question of bringing together the three areas of migration, integration and service and accommodation in one organizational unit. Integration is a ‘cross-cutting task’, which leads to the visibility of many different fields of law and to the competence of different administrative bodies and authorities. It is precisely for this reason that coordination between the federal government, the *Länder* and the local governments is indispensable (as a tri-level mechanism). Integration is primarily a personal task. Both with regard to the (individual) person to be integrated and with regard to the integration environment, i.e. the persons or the collective into which the integration takes place. Within the *Länder*, it is the municipalities to which all the integration tasks of the Immigration Authority are assigned, but above all the tasks of child day care, school sponsorship, social assistance or basic security (there and in vocational training projects in cooperation with the Federal Employment Agency), child and youth welfare, urban planning and housing, as well as cultural work and adult education center sponsorship.

Assessment of the Practice

The opinions, in which area – urban or rural – refugees are better integrated, divide. On the one hand, the urban areas offer more jobs and, in general, a better variety of activities. On the other hand, there are better housing options in the rural area (housing bottlenecks in large cities) and a more communal atmosphere than the anonymity-driven metropolitan areas. The manageable size of rural local governments (RLGs) and the proximity and intensity of living together can also have a positive effect on integration, in that old-established residents and immigrants meet and cooperate with each other in everyday life much more frequently than is the case in urban local governments (ULGs). In local kindergartens and schools, there is a good mix of children from the different groups of origin. In small RLGs, civil society actors and institutions - volunteers, associations, churches and other religious communities - play a key role in the integration of immigrants. Here too, geographical proximity creates far more opportunities for cooperation than in sprawling structures of a large ULG.

In summary, it is a fact that integration takes place on site. Therefore, the role of the local governments as central actors in the integration process and as bearers of important integration offers must be further strengthened, but also be adapted to local (urban or rural) needs. The BAMF must be limited to its existing competencies and must not develop into a ‘Federal Integration Agency’ because that would not have a positive impact on the efficiency of implementation. This is particularly true with regard to the integration courses. In order to enable such courses to start quickly and to coordinate them with other integration programs, the local governments must be given the opportunity to assign participants to a suitable course

instead of the BAMF.⁴⁵ The integration administration represents a local task in the main focus. Another note can be added with regard to report section 6 of this report and the participation of citizens: In all *Länder*, even if only partially on an explicit legal basis, there are advisory committees or advisory boards in which foreigners living in the community can bundle and articulate their concerns. These foreigners' advisory councils (*Ausländerbeiräte*) or, more recently, some 'integration councils' (*Integrationsräte*) are elected by the foreigners living in the community.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Bogumil J and others, *Bessere Verwaltung in der Migrations- und Integrationspolitik – Handlungsempfehlungen für Verwaltungen und Gesetzgebung im föderalen System* (Nomos 2018)

Bogumil J, Hafner J and Kastilan A, *Städte und Gemeinden in der Flüchtlingspolitik. Welche Probleme gibt es – und wie kann man sie lösen?* (Stiftung Mercator 2017)

Burgi M, 'Das werdende Integrationsverwaltungsrecht und die Rolle der Kommunen' (2016) 131 DVBl 1015

⁴⁵ Detailed recommendations for future action at Jörg Bogumil and others, *Bessere Verwaltung in der Migrations- und Integrationspolitik – Handlungsempfehlungen für Verwaltungen und Gesetzgebung im föderalen System* (Nomos 2018) 289ff.

3.4 Creation of a Further Third-Tier Administrative Unit – Munich as an Independent District

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Relevance of the Practice

In some of the German *Länder*, there are even third-tier (first-tier: municipality, second-tier: counties) local governments, e.g. districts (*Bezirke*). This is for example the case in Bavaria.⁴⁶ These units vary depending on in which *Land* and thus under which laws they have been created and they have only few things in common. They 'are created as public corporations formed by their member cities to fulfil local public tasks; (...) and they are nowadays mostly charged with responsibilities of a social and cultural nature, such as youth and disabled welfare or museum maintenance'.⁴⁷ Hereinafter the focus lies within the Bavarian districts.

These districts are an amalgamation of several counties and independent municipalities (*kreisfreie Städte*) and thus self-governing bodies. The District Code (*Bezirksordnung für den Freistaat Bayern*) regulates further details. They assume special tasks on the part of the local level, which the individual administrative units could independently or on their own not perform. These tasks extend beyond the competence and capacity of the independent towns and administrative districts. Therefore, the district provides comprehensive and joint task management for rural local government (RLG) and urban local government (ULG) and thus improves the cooperation between the different entities. The tasks include in particular the creation of social, economic and cultural institutions (e.g. the districts are responsible for psychiatric and neurological hospitals, special clinics, specialist and special schools and open-air museums). They are also supra-local providers of social assistance. There is a district council, which organically steers the district and is elected by the people.

Districts (*Bezirke*) are not to be confused with administrative districts (*Regierungsbezirke*) – although both are geographically identical and constitutionally linked. The Bavarian State Government, responsible for the entire *Freistaat* of Bavaria, sets up a government in the seven sub-areas (i.e., administrative district) in order to be able to better implement policies of the *Land* (state central authorities).

Description of the Practice

⁴⁶ Further examples of this third-tier structure in Germany: Rhineland-Palatinate (*Bezirksverband Pfalz*) or the 'Region Stuttgart' in Baden-Württemberg, in a broader sense (*Höherer Kommunalverband*, i.e., higher level associations of municipalities) also in Lower Saxony and in North Rhine-Westphalia as well as in Hesse and Saxony.

⁴⁷ Martin Burgi, 'Federal Republic of Germany' in Nico Steytler (ed), *Local Government and Metropolitan Regions in Federal Systems* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2009) 140-142.

There are currently seven districts and seven administrative districts in Bavaria. On the part of the Bavarian State Government, there are efforts to create another, eighth administrative district: Munich. Firstly, many jobs can be transferred from the Munich conurbation to rural areas (the cost of living there is much lower for civil servants and the rapidly growing city is relieved in terms of housing demand and infrastructure).⁴⁸ Secondly, it could lead to improved cooperation between the *Land* government and urban local government (ULG). Thirdly, the metropolitan character is to be strengthened so that competencies are enhanced and Munich is upgraded.⁴⁹ With this structural policy of reconstitution and relocation of authorities, the Bavarian Government is trying to counteract unequal developments in the federal state. In this way, urban regions could be relieved and rural ones promoted.

The creation of a new administrative district would probably also have to lead to the establishment of a new district according to Article 10 of the Bavarian Constitution. Especially here, factual and legal questions arise: Should the district comprise the City of Munich or the County of Munich (*Landkreis München*) or even further counties? Here, special attention has to be paid to how the relationship between the ULGs of the City of Munich or rural local governments (RLGs) of the counties and a possibly separate new District of Munich should function. It arises the question whether a close collaboration of municipalities (different local governments (LGs)) in a metropolitan region is aspired or a very strong ULG.

The advantage of considering only the City of Munich to form the new district would be that the corresponding administrative structures already exist – the city council could, theoretically, also take over the tasks of the district council. Thus, no new administrative structures would have to be created. This is however not mandated, so there is also the possibility that a parallel structure could be established, although this would duplicate administrative units and institutions. The City of Munich currently pays EUR 500 million as a district levy – it is not yet certain how financing issues will then be resolved.⁵⁰

Legal issues⁵¹ that can be assessed very differently may emerge due to the Bavarian Constitution: Firstly, the question arises, if the Bavarian Constitution (BC) would have to be amended. Because of Article 185 BC, that says the administrative districts have the same division as before 1933, it is disputed, whether Munich can be a separate administrative district or will have to stay part of Upper Bavaria. Such constitutional change in the *Freistaat* would only work through a referendum of all citizens, second sentence of Article 75(2) BC. Secondly, according to the third sentence of Article 8(2) District Code, the citizens of Munich may also have to be asked whether they would like to change their district affiliation. Thirdly, there is

⁴⁸ Wolfgang Wittl, 'Söder will München zum achten Regierungsbezirk in Bayern machen' (*Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 15 January 2020) <<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/bayern/bayern-behoerdersverlagerung-soeder-regierungsbezirke-1.4757610>> accessed 5 March 2020.

⁴⁹ *ibid.*

⁵⁰ Kassian Stroh, 'Was an Söders Reformidee schwierig ist' (*Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 23 January 2020) <<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/bayern/bayern-muenchen-regierungsbezirk-probleme-1.4767073>> accessed 5 March 2020.

⁵¹ See also Martin Burgi in 'Viele Fragezeichen zur Trennung von München und Oberbayern' (*BR24*, 16 January 2020) <https://www.br.de/nachrichten/bayern/viele-fragezeichen-zur-trennung-von-muenchen-und-oberbayern,RnIDXRp?UTM_Name=Web-Share&UTM_Source=E-Mail&UTM_Medium=Link> accessed 15 April 2020.

the question of whether the city council can simply become a district council as well; otherwise a separate district council would have to exist alongside the city council.

Assessment of the Practice

The main criticism of these projects is that they would not improve the current problems with which the City of Munich as an ULG is struggling. The order of competences remains unchanged and the reasons why traffic, mobility and housing are among the greatest challenges of ULGs, and the reasons why projects take a long time and cost issues are difficult, would remain the same. Especially when concentrating the district on the city area, an exclusion of the neighboring municipalities may occur – even though city and neighboring municipalities share the same problems in infrastructural and housing topics. Thus, a high political interest is, to strengthen the cooperation between ULGs and neighboring RLGs in financial regards of these projects, which will not be improved by creating the district of the City of Munich. Political reservations against such institutions originate from those institutions that may lose influence – it is a classic form of ‘interorganizational jealousies’.⁵² A further problem is that ‘the concern has been raised that the establishment of such “mixed administration” leads to problems of legitimacy, transparency, and above all, accountability. Another point made is the danger of weakening the power of the local authorities, as well as local civil-society projects. However, the competences of these regional entities are still few, and their legal status remains mostly unclear. Legally, as well as politically, large cities and counties, therefore, continue to play the predominant role within those regional areas’.⁵³

Other regions of Germany have made very different and individual decisions in similar cases, and thus put new concepts to the test. It lays within the competence of the Länder, hence, quite diverse and heterogeneous forms occur. In Rhineland-Palatinate, the regional administrations (*Regierungspräsidien*) have been reformed ‘where new service centres organised according to functions have replaced the traditional administration organised on a territorial basis. Similar structural changes can be observed in Saxony-Anhalt (...)’.⁵⁴ However, specific metropolitan policy reforms have also taken place. For example in Baden-Württemberg, the state capital Stuttgart and neighboring counties have merged to the so called ‘Region Stuttgart’, obviously without relinquishment of sovereignty. The Landtag of Baden-Württemberg passed the legislation for this merging in 1994. It is an association with a wide catalogue of tasks and has therefore an own local parliament.⁵⁵ This parliament aims to increasing decision-making between the City of Stuttgart and the neighboring counties.⁵⁶

⁵² Burgi, ‘Federal Republic of Germany’ 140-142.

⁵³ *ibid.*

⁵⁴ Arthur Benz and Anna Meineck, ‘Sub-National Government and Regional Governance in Germany’ in Vincent Hoffmann-Martinot and Hellmut Wollmann (eds), *State and Local Government Reforms in France and Germany* (Springer VS 2006) 65.

⁵⁵ *ibid.* 69.

⁵⁶ See more, ‘179 Kommunen, ein starker Standort’ (Region Stuttgart) <<https://www.region-stuttgart.de/die-region-stuttgart.html>> accessed 28 February 2020.

Another comparable example is the Region Hanover.⁵⁷ The regions of Stuttgart and Hanover have in common, that ‘new administrative entities have been established to cope more effectively with specific problems arising from the relationship between large cities and their surrounding areas’.⁵⁸ A third example is the Regionalverband Ruhr,⁵⁹ which is the largest conurbation of Germany including Duisburg, Essen, Bochum, and Dortmund. It is part of the even greater metropolitan Rhine-Ruhr region (additionally including Dusseldorf, Cologne, and Bonn).⁶⁰

All these new concepts could ‘represent an “institutional nucleus” for an unconventional model of regional administration for a metropolitan region. (...) [And thus] represent a model of how to create a strong shared public governmental institution and might give impetus to the further creation of such shared public service agencies with possibly broader competences’.⁶¹ *The political decision if Munich will be an independent district and how is still pending. By choosing the city region as a district region, local intergovernmental relations to neighboring municipalities are being ignored. The comparisons made here suggest that the concepts of ‘Regions’ seem more sustainable at least for the cooperation of ULG and RLG.*

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Benz A and Meineck A, ‘Sub-National Government and Regional Governance in Germany’ in Vincent Hoffmann-Martinot and Hellmut Wollmann (eds), *State and Local Government Reforms in France and Germany* (Springer VS 2006)

Burgi M, ‘Federal Republic of Germany’ in Nico Steytler (ed), *Local Government and Metropolitan Regions in Federal Systems* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2009)

Stroh K, ‘Was an Söders Reformidee schwierig ist’ (*Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 23 January 2020) <<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/bayern/bayern-muenchen-regierungsbezirk-probleme-1.4767073>>

Wittl W, ‘Söder will München zum achten Regierungsbezirk in Bayern machen’ (*Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 15 January 2020) <<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/bayern/bayern-behoerdderlagerung-soeder-regierungsbezirke-1.4757610>>

⁵⁷ See more, ‘Die Region Hannover stellt sich vor’ (*HANNOVER.DE*) <<https://www.hannover.de/Leben-in-der-Region-Hannover/Verwaltungen-Kommunen/Die-Verwaltung-der-Region-Hannover/Stellt-sich-vor>> accessed 28 February 2020.

⁵⁸ Burgi, ‘Federal Republic of Germany’, above, 140-142.

⁵⁹ See more, ‘Verbandsleitung und Organisation’ (Regionalverband Ruhr) <<https://www.rvr.ruhr/politik-regionalverband/ueber-uns/start-organisation/>> accessed 28 February 2020.

⁶⁰ Burgi, ‘Federal Republic of Germany’, above, 160, endnote 18.

⁶¹ *ibid* 140-142.

3.5 Digitalization of the Administration in Bavaria

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Relevance of the Practice

Digitalization is the aim of many current projects, both in the private and the public sector. This has been further intensified by the enactment of a federal law (OZG)⁶² that obliges all governmental agencies to offer their services online until end of 2022.⁶³ While the law on *Länder* level (the Law on E-Government in Bavaria)⁶⁴ does not contain a similar obligation,⁶⁵ the local governments (LGs) are also bound by the OZG. To support this mandatory digitalization on the municipal level, the *Land* government engages in several projects and initiatives to nudge and support LGs in their digitalization efforts. Hence, the field of digitalization is a very current example for intergovernmental cooperation, while many projects are of course still in their early stages. As the digitalization of public administration requires a sufficient network infrastructure, the obligation to digitalize described below may have beneficial side effects for rural areas that so far lack sufficient infrastructure and a stable network connection. Digitalization can also enable municipalities to respond to problematic realities which is the focus of one of the projects described in this entry.

Description of the Practice

Digitalization of course presupposes the existence of (broadband) infrastructure. While this aspect is described in the first entry to report section 2 on local responsibilities, this entry will focus on the implementation of digital tools/technology in the municipal sector and how this is an example for intergovernmental cooperation. The intergovernmental cooperation in the

⁶² *Onlinezugangsgesetz* (OZG) enacted (jointly with other laws) on 14 August 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3122).

⁶³ Sec 1(1) OZG. The implementation of this obligation takes place in close cooperation between the federal and the *Länder* governments, as the law requires the creation of a joint online portal (*Portalverbund*) in Sec 1(2). The federal and the *Länder* governments established an organisation to oversee this cooperation, the federal IT-cooperation (FITKO), for further information see 'Das Onlinezugangsgesetz (OZG)' (FITKO) <<https://www.fitko.de/Start#StartFIM>> accessed 25 June 2020. A detailed overview on the cooperative projects is given here: 'Digitalisierungsprogramme' (*Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community*) <<https://www.onlinezugangsgesetz.de/Webs/OZG/DE/umsetzung/digitalisierungsprogramme/digitalisierungsprogramme-node.html>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁶⁴ *Gesetz über die elektronische Verwaltung in Bayern* [Law on the Electronic Administration in Bavaria] (*Bayerisches E-Government-Gesetz – BayEGovG*), enacted 22 December 2015. Most other states as well as the federal legislature have enacted similar laws, see, for a list of the state laws from mid-2019, 'Sachstand – E-Government in Deutschland Aktueller Stand auf Bundes- und Landesebene' (File no WD 3 - 3000 - 134/19, Research Services of the German Bundestag 2019) 9f (hereinafter: WD Report) <<https://www.bundestag.de/resource/blob/655082/32a17c3834d5c5c5d6f5a7232f0491c0/WD-3-134-19-pdf-data.pdf>>.

⁶⁵ It obliges LGs to offer citizens a way to communicate with them electronically (Art 3), but only encourages the actual provision of electronic/online services (Art 4).

field of digitalization of municipal services follows a common approach regarding the division of competences, with the *Land* government providing financial and technical support while the LGs are tasked with the implementation itself.

The Bavarian Government is implementing several means to incentivize LGs to engage in digitalization. One project is a website named 'BayernPortal' that provides information to citizens and also LGs on (digital) governmental services.⁶⁶ Furthermore, the state set up a system enabling each Bavarian citizen to create its own account to access governmental services online, the so-called 'BayernID'. This system is supposed to be taken up by all LGs that implement digital provision of services.⁶⁷ Another aspect is the inter-governmental financing of digitalization. Here, two state-administered funding programs are worth mentioning.

The first one is named Digital Town Hall (*Digitales Rathaus*) and is focused on subsidizing the digital transformation of LGs' administration. It grants funding (from *Länder* level) to specific LGs upon application in accordance with a Bavarian funding directive enacted in 2019.⁶⁸ The directive pursues a holistic approach, as only concepts containing more than 20 online services in total are eligible for financing.⁶⁹ This shows that the directive wants an overarching digitalization instead of only special sectors of governmental services. However, the directive only applies to totally new online services and explicitly excludes the modernization/updating of preexisting services.⁷⁰ This is meant to increase the number of digital services offered by municipalities and to implement the requirements of the federal law (OZG) mentioned above.⁷¹ A broadening of existing services could however be eligible for funding.⁷² While urban local governments (ULGs) are not in general excluded from financing under the initiative, financing has so far been granted mostly to rural local governments (RLGs) (from North Bavaria, as the funding allocation for South Bavarian LGs has not yet been announced).⁷³ This might be explained by the fact that most ULGs already have digital systems in place, which makes them ineligible for funding.

The second project is called Digital Village Bavaria (*Digitales Dorf Bayern*)⁷⁴ and picks specific pilot projects in RLGs that are meant to deal with upcoming challenges by employing the benefits of digitalization. In a first step, several regions (comprising several municipal LGs⁷⁵)

⁶⁶ Accessible via the website <<http://www.freistaat.bayern/>>, also available in English (accessed 25 June 2020).

⁶⁷ See, e.g., Sec 4(1)(1) of the funding directive for the project Digital town hall (see infra for further detail) that makes funding conditional upon the compatibility of digital projects with the BayernID-system.

⁶⁸ *Richtlinie zur Förderung der Bereitstellung von Online-Diensten im kommunalen Bereich* [Regulation on the Promotion of the Provision of Online-Services in the Municipal Field] (*Förderrichtlinie digitales Rathaus – FöRdR*), BayMbl. 2019 no 290, 7 August 2019.

⁶⁹ Sec 4(1)(4).

⁷⁰ Secs 2; 4(1)(4); 4(2).

⁷¹ Sec 1.

⁷² Sec 4(1)(4).

⁷³ See for a list of the beneficiaries: 'Füracker und Gerlach: E-Government im Kommunalbereich ausbauen' (*Digitales Rathaus Bayern*) <<https://www.digitales-rathaus.bayern/aktuelles/news/artikel9.html>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁷⁴ See <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/>>. A similar project called digital villages (*Digitale Dörfer*) was set up in Rhineland Palatine and now caters to RLGs all over Germany. For further information and a list of the participating LGs see <<https://www.digitale-doerfer.de/>> both accessed 25 June 2020.

⁷⁵ The smallest region selected is made up of two municipalities, the biggest of 16.

where selected in a state-wide competition, the selection being based on concepts that were submitted by regions. The regional LGs were asked to identify challenges they are facing due to demographic change (e.g. public transport services becoming unprofitable, lack of qualified workforce, discontinuation of healthcare services, etc.⁷⁶) and to come up with digital concepts that are meant to help them tackle these challenges. Currently, there are five so-called pilot regions working in the project framework, each of them lying in a peripheral area of Bavaria.⁷⁷ These regions receive (mostly financial) support in the development and implementation of their concept. Furthermore, each region will be marketed as an innovative region by the project and on its website.⁷⁸

Assessment of the Practice

While the Bavarian initiatives and accompanying statements by politicians and LGs show that the *Länder* government is focused on achieving e-government, there are some points that warrant attention. Most of the current programs focus mainly on RLGs. While ULGs might have more budgetary leeway to fund digitalization efforts by themselves, this could also be an indicator for a lagging implementation in RLGs (in comparison with ULGs). Especially the Digital Town Hall program is tailored towards these issues, as it only covers first-time digitalization. In this regard, the efforts seem to be driven mainly by the requirements of the federal legislation described above. Another factor for primarily funding RLGs is the need to tackle demographic changes, as a well-implemented digitalization could make rural areas more attractive for companies and/or younger inhabitants.⁷⁹ This is explicitly addressed within the Digital Village project.

One could argue that these considerations exclude 'experienced' ULGs that would be able to test innovative projects more efficiently. While this does indeed not seem to be the main priority of the existing funding programs examined in this entry, it also becomes clear that the different circumstances in ULGs and RLGs render a 'one fits all'-approach not feasible. To the contrary, funding programs that are able to take into account the individual circumstances will produce more fitting results. Changing circumstances in different regions as well as the rapid technological development in the field of digitalization also show that a continuous evaluation and adaption of existing programs is necessary.

Looking at the programs from the perspective of inter-governmental cooperation, the biggest disadvantage lies in the lack of a deeper cooperation between the different layers of government. Instead of setting up one or several centralized project(s) to engage in the

⁷⁶ For a list of identified challenges, see 'Herausforderungen' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/dd-herausforderungen/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁷⁷ See for a list of regions and the respective projects pursued: 'Übersicht der Pilotregionen' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/die-modelldoerfer/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁷⁸ The benefits enjoyed by the pilot regions are listed here: 'Leistungsumfang' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/dd-herausforderungen/leistungsumfang/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁷⁹ This idea is also ushered by the following report on a digital village in Rhineland-Palatine: 'Leben auf dem Land. Ein Dorf wird digital' (*Die Bundesregierung*, 9 August 2019) <<https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/themen/digitalisierung/digitales-dorf-1604066>> accessed 25 June 2020.

(technical) development itself, it seems that the government (through centralized projects) merely funds initiatives on the LG level. While this enables the LGs to actually tailor the specific projects to their needs, it might lead to plenty of parallel research and development on similar projects. A centralized agency⁸⁰ that engages in development itself or provides general tools/services for LGs could be more efficient and should be broadened in scope beyond the 'framework software' described above. The lack of central development is also one of the aspects criticized by governmental authorities when surveyed on the implementation of e-government.⁸¹ At the same time, it should not be overlooked that the Bavarian digital villages project is supposed to develop and test programs that could be feasible for other LGs too, using the pilot regions as a kind of testing labs.⁸² Additionally, the federal and the *Länder* governments created the federal information management system (FIM)⁸³ to establish a platform where developed digital solutions can be made accessible to other governments/agencies.

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⁸⁰ Such as the Government Technology Agency in Singapore, for further information see <<https://www.tech.gov.sg/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

⁸¹ WD Report 14.97% of the agencies obliged to implement e-government services stated they are facing challenges in their implementation. Besides the lack of centrally developed IT solutions, the other substantial difficulties in the implementation referred to by governmental agencies/bodies are: lack of funding; data protection rules; lack of acceptance by users and lack of relevant competences within the agencies.

⁸² A similar project (*Smarte Landregionen*) focusing on rural regions is also pursued by the federal government. The application phase for regions began in December 2019. For further information see 'Smarte Landregionen' (BMEI.de) https://www.bmel.de/DE/Laendliche-Raeume/Digitales/SmarteLandregionen/texte/MuD_Smarte_LandRegionen.html accessed 25 June 2020.

⁸³ Further explanation on this process is provided on <<https://fimportal.de/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

4. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Spain

4.1 The System of Local Government in Spain

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Types of Local Government

The Spanish Constitution assigns public authority to four levels of government: the central state, autonomous communities, provinces and municipalities. Spain consists of 17 autonomous communities, two autonomous cities (Ceuta and Melilla), and two types of local bodies: 50 provinces and 8,131 municipalities.

The Constitution includes two principles regarding local government: the right to 'local autonomy' from all public authorities including the state legislature, and legislative powers over local government given to the central state and autonomous communities. The constitutional recognition of a right to local autonomy (Article 137 of the Constitution [CE]) implies that the municipalities and provinces are not merely internal divisions of the autonomous communities, but part of the state as a whole. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the guarantee of local autonomy 'does not ensure specific contents or spheres of authority established and fixed once and for all, but rather the preservation of an institution in terms that are recognizable for the image that society has of such institution in each time and place' (Ruling of the Constitutional Court [STC] 32/1981). Local autonomy is contrary to any hierarchical position of the local governments under the state or the autonomous communities.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The legal system of local government falls under the concurrent jurisdiction of the state and the autonomous communities. The state has the power to establish the 'basis of the legal system of the public administrations'. On the other hand, the statutes of autonomy confer to the autonomous communities complementary powers over local government. In interpreting the Constitution together with the statutes of autonomy, the Constitutional Court has concluded that the Spanish local system has a 'two-fold nature'. The state is responsible for the 'fundamental' regulations while the autonomous communities are responsible for the 'non-fundamental' or so-called 'development' regulations (STC 214/1989, FJ 4). When regulating the local government system, both state and autonomous communities' laws must respect local autonomy, as directly guaranteed by Article 137 of the Constitution. But the Constitution does not specify what this local autonomy shall consist of, since it limits itself to a vague connection between local autonomy and 'matters of local interest', without specifying

what these are. Consequently, both state and autonomous communities' laws have a wide margin for regulating the functions and organization of local governments.

The current fundamental regulations of the state on local government are primarily found in two Acts repeatedly amended: Law of the Basis of the Local System (LBRL) of 1985, and a Royal Legislative Decree of 2004, which approves the Restated Text of the Local Tax Authorities Act (LHL). This far, the state has interpreted its own 'fundamental' powers broadly, limiting the legislative and executive powers of the autonomous communities. The amendment of several statutes of autonomy since 2006 has not changed this situation.

Generally speaking, Spain's current local government system includes very limited state and autonomous community supervision or control on municipal and provincial activity. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the local autonomy guaranteed by Article 137 excludes these governmental controls to a great extent (STC 4/1981). In the absence of such controls, only courts are ordinarily responsible for oversight of the administrative activity of local councils. The LBRL replaces state and regional controls on local governments with a complex system of intergovernmental relations based on the idea of full respect for the powers of local institutions and the principle of cooperation. Basically, the LBRL establishes legal instruments to prevent conflicts between state and autonomous communities on one hand, and local authorities on the other while obliging local governments to share information with other government levels. To prevent or resolve conflicts of authority, the law promotes the 'free cooperation' of public administrations, either in the form of agreements or by participation in collaborative bodies, and by encouraging local level administrations to participate in the decision-making processes.

On this legal basis, the Spanish local government system has overall functioned satisfactorily since 1985. Local government is thoroughly democratized and has been receptive to new forms of participatory democracy. The elimination of controls from the upper-level territories has resulted in significant improvements to local public services, despite some cases of corruption in urban planning.

(A)Symmetry of the Local Government System

The Spanish local government system is very uniform and symmetrical due to the approaches of both the central state and most autonomous communities: the central state has established a common two-tier system with few variations for all Spain; and the autonomous communities have introduced very few particularities for the local government of their territory.

First, the state maintains a structure of local government that, to a large extent, was defined in 1833. That is, each village, town or city is a municipality. And the whole territory of Spain is divided into 50 provinces which currently (not originally) act as the second level of local government. Every municipality is integrated in a province.

Second, regional particularities within the 17 autonomous communities are scarce. It has been said before that each autonomous community has legislative power to develop the state basic legislation on local government. But since the state basic legislation is in fact very intense and extensive, and imposes a local government scheme made up of municipalities and provinces,

the possibilities of innovation for any autonomous community are quite limited. Particular institutions have appeared especially in Catalonia and Aragon, which add a third level of government: the townships (*comarcas*). Also, in the areas of some large cities such as Barcelona, Madrid, Vigo or Valencia there are some metropolitan government structures, normally focused on the management of very specific municipal services. The metropolitan area of Madrid does not have its own government structure because that space is occupied by the regional government (the Autonomous Community of Madrid).

Political and Social Context in Spain

Local politics is largely symmetrical to national and regional ones. National or regional parties also act at the local level. And this limits the effective autonomy of local politicians, even though they are elected locally. Currently, after the municipal elections of May 2019, most municipalities have leftist governments, although many of them are minoritarian. Some very important cities, such as Madrid, Malaga or Zaragoza, have conservative municipal governments.

Provincial governments are indirectly elected, by the councilors of the municipalities in each province. In that indirect election the political parties have great power. In this way, provincial governments normally reproduce municipal political majorities.

Beyond the local level, the general political situation shows common features to many other European countries: strong polarization of politics and absence of clear majorities. This has led to the current – and for the first time since 1978 – coalition government, between the traditional center-left Social Democratic Party (PSOE) and a new radical left-wing party (Unidas Podemos).

The general social and political situation is marked by two circumstances. A national economy that, although formally recovered from the great crisis of 2008, still shows very high unemployment rates (around 15 per cent of the active population), and where income inequalities dramatically increase. The second major social and political concern is the territorial integrity of Spain. Since approximately 2010 a very strong independence movement has emerged in Catalonia, which is one of the richest regions in Spain. This secessionist movement has the support of approximately 50 per cent of the population of the region.

More than 80 per cent of the 8,131 Spanish municipalities are very small having less than 5,000 inhabitants. Given the technical and economic incapacity of these municipalities, in many tasks they are replaced by the 50 provinces, which show a remarkable financial capacity. In some autonomous communities such as Catalonia or Aragon there are, in addition to the provinces, other intermediate supra-municipal local entities.

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4.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Spain: An Introduction

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General Framework of Intergovernmental Relations

Despite the fact that in the Spanish political system municipalities precede the creation of other territorial entities (i.e. autonomous communities), their sphere of competences is decided by the laws of the state and, to a lesser extent of the autonomous communities. The Spanish Constitution (Article 137) establishes the principle of local autonomy although with no further specification or delimitation of competences.

This top-down configuration of the local autonomy affects not only the competences of municipalities but also the intergovernmental relationships, both horizontal cooperation among municipalities and vertical coordination and cooperation between municipalities and other territorial entities (provinces, autonomous communities and the state).

The horizontal cooperation between municipalities is frequently channeled by the creation of single-purpose entities (i.e. the so-called *mancomunidades* or commonwealths) to provide public services, most frequently those related to environmental and social policies (e.g. waste management, social assistance). The Law of the Basis of the Local System (LBRL) of 1985 establishes formal requirements in the process of constitution of *mancomunidades*, leaving municipalities to define the scope and internal organization (Article 44 LBRL).

As for the vertical intergovernmental relationships, the LBRL refers to the principle of 'institutional loyalty' by which each level of government (state, regional and local) is supposed to cooperate with the others and not interfere in the legitimate exercise of other levels' competences. Therefore, vertical cooperation is understood as administrative assistance without compromising each level of government's competence. The cooperation between levels of government is made on a voluntary basis. In addition, upper levels of government (the state and the regions) may coordinate the action of municipalities to guarantee coherence and according to the subsidiarity principle (Article 58 and 59 LBRL).

Control and Supervision of the Local Government

Generally speaking, the Spanish current local government system includes very limited supervision or control on municipal and provincial activity by the state and the autonomous communities. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the local autonomy principle under the Spanish Constitution (Article 137) excludes governmental controls to a great extent. The LBRL replaces state and regional controls on local governments with a complex system of

intergovernmental relations based on the idea of full respect for the powers of local jurisdictions and the principle of cooperation. Basically, the LBRL establishes legal instruments to prevent conflicts between state and autonomous communities on one hand, and local authorities on the other, while obliging local governments to share information with supra-local authorities. To prevent or resolve conflicts of authority, the law promotes the 'free cooperation' of public administrations, either in the form of agreements or by participation in collaborative bodies, and by encouraging local level administrations to participate in the decision-making processes.

The most important control on the local governments is performed by the judicial branch (i.e. administrative courts). The inter-administrative litigation regarding local issues is abundant. All municipalities and provinces must communicate the decisions and by-laws adopted to the autonomous communities and the state. In case of infringement, both the autonomous communities and the state may require local governments to accommodate local decisions to the laws, or alternatively and directly bring the case before the administrative courts. The judicial proceedings deal with the legal correctness of local authorities' decisions and not with the political opportunity or necessity of adopting specific measures at the local level.

Despite the fact that local government action is controlled through the judicial branch of the government, there are also some cases of administrative supervision by regional or state authorities, as directly foreseen by sector-specific laws. This is the case of land use and urban planning policy where the approval of municipal land use plans requires the regional government's approval. This type of supervision is usually channeled through cooperative administrative procedures.

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4.3 The Coordinating Role of Local Government Associations in Intergovernmental Relations: The Case of FEMP

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Relevance of the Practice

Most municipal and provincial governments are integrated into associations, either in the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP), or in other regional associations. These associations, especially the FEMP, represent and defend local interests before the state and the autonomous communities, either through intergovernmental bodies, or by informal means.

The formal mechanisms for the intergovernmental relationships between the different tiers of government operate in two strands: between the state and the local governments and between the latter and the regional governments. State-local cooperation is channeled through two different committees: a permanent body, the National Commission of Local Administration (*Comisión Nacional de la Administración Local, CNAL*), and the Committee for Local Issues (*Conferencia Sectorial para Asuntos Locales, CSAL*).

The CNAL serves as a consultative organ whose decisions are not binding. CNAL's competences include, firstly, the preparation of reports in the case of draft laws and administrative provisions of state competence in matters affecting local government, secondly, the identification of criteria for local government's borrowing operations, and thirdly, the submission of proposals from local entities to the state in local administration.

In addition, the Committee for Local Issues (*Conferencia Sectorial para Asuntos Locales, CSAL*) was formally created in 2005 as a coordination platform gathering the three levels of government (state, regional and local jurisdictions). Up to date, the CSAL does not meet on a regular basis. Unlike other committees, the CSAL has not yet approved its own statute establishing its composition, functions and rules for the adoption of resolutions. These circumstances determine a limited operability of the CSAL and reinforce the division of intergovernmental relations into two main axes: state-local and regional-local. Regardless of the formal mechanisms, political actors (e.g. political parties, associations and interest groups) operating simultaneously at the different levels can additionally provide other channels of communication and cooperation between the three levels of government.

At the regional level, autonomous communities have passed legislation on local government that regulate intergovernmental relationships between local and regional authorities in a divergent way. In some cases, autonomous communities replicate the creation of a permanent body of consultation composed by representatives of local entities and the regional government (e.g. Castilla-La Mancha, Castilla-León, País Vasco, Andalucía, among others). Other autonomous communities (e.g. Aragón, Madrid, Murcia) reduce intergovernmental

relationships to the interadministrative cooperation required for the exercise of each administration's competences. In the latter case, there is no permanent body gathering regional and local governments but different forms of cooperation (e.g. exchange of information, development of policy programs, creation of ad hoc commissions, among others).

In both cases (i.e. state and regional cooperative platforms), the representatives of the local entities are usually elected by the largest association of local governments at the national and regional levels respectively. This system of representation fueled the role of local entities associations as promoters or mediators of local interests. Regional and nation-wide associations of local entities are supposed to deploy different strategies to aggregate local interests and to access the intergovernmental platforms.

The process of aggregation of interests is especially troublesome in the case of the largest association of local entities, the FEMP. The heterogeneity of local interests based on territorial and socioeconomic conditions and the multiplication of intergovernmental platforms at the regional level may consolidate the heterogeneity of local interests.

One of the main areas where there is a need for integration of local interests concerns the division between urban and rural municipalities. The rural-urban divide is caused by the existence of phenomena mainly associated with the rural world, such as depopulation and ageing, or policies associated with this area, such as agricultural policy or the management of rural development funds. Aware of these differences, associations of local entities have also been developed, at national and regional levels, which try to coordinate the specific interests of rural municipalities (this is the case of the Spanish Association against Depopulation or the Spanish Network for Rural Development). These associations sometimes respond to partnerships between public entities and private interest groups of rural origin. This composition increases their lobbying capacity, although they do not have direct access to the intergovernmental platforms of coordination. The participation of these associations occurs through the regional and national associations of municipalities and provinces, as is the case of the FEMP. Integration within the latter is therefore an essential issue for the functioning of the organization of municipalities and provinces.

The consolidation of differences between territories challenges the role of the FEMP in achieving a unique voice representing local interests. The FEMP usually promotes the inclusion in the political agenda of certain programs to guarantee its leadership in the coordination of local interests. With regard to the rural-urban divide, the FEMP has taken advantage of its organizational resources and privileged access to intergovernmental platforms to play a leading role in representing specific interests in the rural world. This has been the case, for example, with the creation of the Commission on Depopulation of the FEMP in 2016. This commission is aiming to promote the adoption of a National Strategy against Depopulation. The result of this initiative was the creation in 2018 of a working group between the FEMP and the CNAL to address the demographic challenge affecting rural areas.

Description of the Practice

The access of local entities to either the regional or the state level of government largely depends on FEMP's capacity to coordinate heterogeneous interests at the local level. The capacity to integrate members' interests is achieved through organizational mechanisms (e.g. representation in the permanent bodies of the FEMP, creation of study commissions or working groups), the exchange of information and the promotion of good practices or the provision of technical assistance by the FEMP to its members. The aggregation of preferences in one voice is key in intergovernmental platforms such as the CNAL or the regional institutions alike where decisions, although of non-binding nature, are adopted by a simple majority of their members.

At the national level, the CNAL consists of 5 representatives of the state administration, related to the areas of finance, public works, interior and security issues, social policy and industry and energy, along with 13 representatives of the local entities. The local representatives are designated by the largest association of local entities nation-wide. The FEMP is the largest national association of local entities, encompassing up to a 90 per cent of all local governments (i.e. 7,410 local entities). CNAL internal organization consists of the plenary, two subcommittees (cooperation and financial issues), and working groups related to salient issues at stake. Decisions are adopted by simple majority with the casting vote of the presidency. The presidency is occupied by a representative of the central administration. In addition, the secretariat is allocated in the representatives of the central administration.

The CNAL is responsible for two main functions. First, CNAL issues non-binding reports on laws and regulations affecting local government. More in concrete the CNAL adopts a position on three main areas: (i) law proposals and administrative decisions to be adopted by the state in matters affecting local government, (ii) criteria for authorizing public debt operations of local entities, (iii) dissolution of the governing bodies of local entities due to exceptional circumstances (Article 61 of the Law of the Basis of the Local System LBRL). Second, the CNAL makes proposals to the central government in matters of local administration (i.e. delegation of competences to local entities, distribution of subsidies, credits and transfers from the state to the local administration, local finance and general state budget). The CNAL requires reports to other administrative organs in fulfilment of its functions.

There are also regional associations of local entities in every autonomous community. Although the statutes of the regional associations converge in the defense of the local autonomy there are differences in certain aspects such as the relationship with the FEMP or the scope of their activities. In some cases, the membership in a regional association does not imply to become a member of FEMP. In addition, some regional associations identify the regional government as the primary interlocutor whereas in other cases the area of influence of the association is defined nation-wide. These differences across regional associations may consolidate different political agendas based on territorial concerns. This fragmentation is fostered by the intergovernmental platforms at work in every region.

In this fragmented scenario, the FEMP develops different strategies to aggregate local interests. At first sight, the large composition of the FEMP does not help to achieve that objective. The Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces is constituted by the municipalities, islands, provinces and other local bodies that voluntarily decide to join it for the promotion and defense of their interests. The FEMP does not replace the competence of their members, and in some cases, there may be conflicting interests such as in the case of

municipalities and provinces in the allocation of competences or the distribution of economic resources.

The definition of the political agenda is a crucial stage in the influence of the FEMP for two reasons. Firstly, the agenda setting allows for the identification of common concerns among local authorities, while avoiding conflicting issues. Secondly, the agenda setting reinforces the role of the promoter and the need to coordinate efforts to achieve the final goal.

The process of shaping the public agenda on local issues is not straight forward. The FEMP presents mechanisms *ad intra* and *ad extra* to facilitate this objective. As for the *ad intra* mechanism, the internal organization of the FEMP is oriented to counteract the fragmentation and heterogeneity derived from territorial representation. The internal structure of the FEMP depends largely on party affiliation. In this respect, party affiliation determines the formation and functioning of several of the FEMP's main organs. This is the case of the Territorial Council in charge of implementing the agreements of the plenary. The Territorial Council is made up of (i) the presidency and the rest of the members of the governing board, (ii) sixty-one members elected by the plenary from among the full members of the FEMP and according to party affiliation. The members of the Territorial Council elected by the plenary who for any reason no longer belong to the political group for which they were elected shall automatically cease and be replaced by another representative that belong to the same political group. Likewise, the members of the governing board form groups in line with their partisan affiliation. In general terms, the organization of the FEMP gives priority to partisan dynamics over territorial criteria in the configuration of their organs. However, partisan dynamics can give way to a prevalent territorial pattern depending on the issues to be addressed. To this regard, the unequal distribution of demographic trends such as ageing or depopulation affecting mainly rural areas or economic circumstances can rebalance the weight of partisan and territorial factors in FEMP decision-making.

The FEMP also seeks to encapsulate the representation of local interests by creating sectoral commissions and promoting networks of local entities facing common challenges. The commissions and working groups make it possible to coordinate local interests in a wide range of areas that even exceed the current competences of local authorities (e.g. development cooperation, employment and economic development, public employment, public health, international relations, among others) or that represent pressing issues such as the depopulation process or the digital agenda. This broad scope of the FEMP's work allows it to increase its influence in promoting local interests on issues that are discussed at the national level.

With regard to *ad extra* mechanisms, the FEMP maintains collaborative relationships with regional associations of local entities through different protocols that specify the scope of the collaboration and the instruments to do so. In addition, the FEMP has signed collaboration agreements with other institutions, public institutions and private entities relevant to the management of local affairs (for example, the General Council of Notaries, the National Institute of Statistics, the National Tax Agency, the society for the management of assets derived from bank restructuring operations, different ministries of the executive branch, among others). The broad representation of the FEMP is an incentive for third parties to reach collaboration agreements.

Other mechanisms for aggregating interests are related to the generation of knowledge. In this regard, the FEMP provides training and updated information or technical knowledge on complex local administration issues (finance, human resources management, among others). In addition, the FEMP disseminates examples of good practice by local governments.

Assessment of the Practice

The contribution of the FEMP to intergovernmental relations between the local, regional and state levels is its capacity to aggregate local interests that do not always coincide. The strengthening of a logic of representation more linked to party affiliation than to territorial representation, together with the creation of the public agenda through training, technical assistance or the dissemination of good practices, has allowed the FEMP to reinforce its role as a promoter of local interests both in formal (CNAL) and informal relations between the different levels of government.

However, the aggregation of local interests also takes place in other regional associations of local entities that also perform their functions in a diverse institutional framework created by regional laws on local governments. Hence, the scenario of intergovernmental relations is characterized by the fragmentation produced by the regional platforms of intergovernmental coordination and the regional associations of local entities.

The representation of local interests through the FEMP is a controversial issue. First, the aggregation of local interests by a nation-wide association limits the scope of the agenda to issues that do not generate debate internally or that are sponsored by the most influential entities or regional associations. In addition, consensus on proposals is achieved at the cost of not defining measures to be implemented. In this sense, the programmatic action plans adopted by the FEMP are aimed more at setting priorities and objectives than at specifying the means to achieve them. The political stance of the FEMP tends to seek coordination and co-responsibility between administrations, avoiding issues that can lead to greater dissent, such as the financing of the execution of programs, the competencies and responsibilities to be assumed by each level of government, or the stages and timetables for policy action implementation. Second, the partisan logic of aggregation of local interests may prevent territorially defined issues from entering the public agenda on local government. In this sense, local interests and concerns are not distributed homogeneously throughout the different local entities (depopulation, aging, among others). The relevance of territorially defined issues makes regional associations and regional intergovernmental coordination platforms more suitable settings for addressing the demands of local governments. Thirdly, the FEMP does not eliminate the competences of their members, nor of the regional associations. In this scenario, the FEMP has signed up agreements with regional associations of local entities that do not respond to a single model. Therefore, the role of the FEMP as the sole interpreter of the local interest cannot be taken for granted.

From the interviews with representatives of the regional associations of municipalities, it is revealed that the FEMP's capacity to coordinate local interests is based on its role as the main interlocutor with the central government. The FEMP's involvement with the central government is channeled through various means such as the formal recognition of FEMP's representatives in consultative bodies of the central government, or the agreements with different bodies of the central government that also serve for the allocation of funds. The FEMP also operates as a platform for organizing local interests at the international arena and, mainly, at the European level. However, in some cases, the greater size and experience of the regional associations in managing international programs gives them a greater capacity to defend their interests independently at the international level.

The rural and urban dimension of local entities yields to the leading role of the territorial dimension in the definition of local interests. In other words, the coordination of local interests seems to follow territorial patterns related to the particular institutional aspects at play in each of the regions. For example, the fact that in some regions there are provinces affects the management of the funds available to local entities. Additionally, many of the policy initiatives with an impact at the local level (e.g. depopulation, circular economy or digitization) are part of plans and programs at the regional level which fosters the capacity of regional government in the integration of local interests.

Thus, a certain specialization of the tasks of the FEMP and the regional associations of municipalities can be observed. The latter build an agenda that is mainly regional in nature due to the main functions they perform. In this sense, the regional associations concentrate their influence capacity on participating in the legislative process at the regional level by informing legislative proposals in order to protect local autonomy. One consequence of this role is that the agenda of the regional associations of municipalities is largely determined by the government program of the regional government.

This scenario generates a positive assessment of the FEMP in terms of counterbalancing the relevance of the regional level and proving a common ground for local entities representation at the national and international levels.

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4.4 Regional Plans to Prevent Depopulation of Rural Areas

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Relevance of the Practice

The Spanish population has increased by about 36 per cent since 1975, from 34.2 million to 46.9 million⁸⁴. However, this demographic trend is coupled with a process of imbalance in the distribution of the population with a concentration of residents in large cities and the depopulation of rural areas. These trends are at work both at national and regional levels. As for the former, the population of the capital City of Madrid has grown by 73 per cent in the referred period whereas 44 per cent of the municipalities in the Region of Madrid have less than 2,500 inhabitants. These demographic trends represent a challenge to all levels of government. Up to 63.1 per cent of municipalities and 13 provinces have lost inhabitants between 2000 and 2018.

In addition, the demographic trends also affect the balance between urban and rural local governments since the provision of public services is affected by both an excess and a lack of demand. One of the main drivers of depopulation in rural areas is internal migration. The internal migratory flows reinforce the imbalance in the distribution of population and therefore the attracting force of large urban centers along with shrinking rural areas. The imbalance also increases deficiencies in the provision of goods and services, especially those of a collective nature. Consequently, depopulation is not a problem solely addressed by rural local government but also for urban local governments that may be the destination of migratory flows.

Up to date not all the Spanish autonomous communities have developed specific plans to tackle depopulation. In 2001, the Autonomous Community of Aragon approved the Comprehensive Plan on Demographic and Population Policy. The Autonomous Community of Castilla y León, the most affected region by depopulation, agreed on a policy document Regional Strategy to Fight against Depopulation in 2005. Afterward, the policy document turned into the Agenda for the Population of Castilla y León 2010-2020⁸⁵ with a further specification of objectives and measures to be implemented. The regional Government in the Community of Madrid has sponsored a Strategy to revitalize rural municipalities in the Community of Madrid since 2018.⁸⁶ Recently, the Autonomous Community of La Rioja

⁸⁴ Data in this section is obtained from the Spanish Statistical Office.

⁸⁵ Available at <<https://www.icyl.es/web/es/agendapoblacion/agenda-para-poblacion/agenda-poblacion-2010-2020.html>>.

⁸⁶ Available at <<https://www.comunidad.madrid/etiquetas/estrategia-revitalizacion-municipios-rurales>>.

elaborated on a Regional strategy to face the demographic challenge and depopulation in February 2020.⁸⁷

Description of the Practice

The regional plans on depopulation contain a set of priority actions to reverse the depopulation process in rural areas. The regional plans largely coincide in identifying the following areas of policy action: (i) education and training, (ii) infrastructure, (iii) information and communication technologies in rural areas, (iv) public housing, (v) transport, (vi) gender equality, (vii) regional incentives for the development of economic activities and entrepreneurship, (viii) environmental protection and use of natural resources, (ix) policies for the elderly, (x) culture and tourism, (xi) social participation. In general terms, the regional plans and strategies are subject to be reviewed in order to expand both their territorial coverage and the measures to be implemented. Therefore, the regional plans present an evolving dynamic fueled by particular initiatives not necessarily related to all rural areas but focused on the specific context of certain municipalities.

The regional plans commonly point to reduce the migratory flows from the rural to the urban centers if not to revert the flows. However, there are differences in terms of the scope of the strategies. In some cases, the regional plans especially focus on rural areas whereas others explore a broader set of measures targeting the regional territory as a whole. As for the latter, the regional plan of La Rioja is mainly designed at the regional level. This circumstance implies that most of their content is not territorially delimited (e.g. training programs and professional activities - self-employment and solidarity-based economic activities such as the implementation of ethical banking and finance; theatre and journalism workshops, grants for immigrants, integration-). Yet, part of the activities in the regional program aimed at the development of projects that foster the relationship between urban local governments (URLs) and rural local governments (RLGs) (e.g. the project 'Semillalab' consists of a ICT environment to connect people, institutions and undertakings). Regarding RLG centered programs, the Strategy to revitalize rural municipalities in the Community of Madrid targets the 78 RLGs with less than 2,500 inhabitants. In this context, the measures adopted address specific problems of RLGs such as the low participation of women in the economic or the limited access to ICT.

From an institutional perspective, the design of these regional plans follows a top-down approach with limited involvement of local governments in the initial stages. To a large extent, this top-down approach is influenced by the need to endorse regional development plans that are eligible for support from the European Commission's European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development. This scenario creates an incentive for centralizing the decision-making process at the regional level. Nevertheless, the participation of local governments normally occurs at a later stage in the implementation of the plans. In this regard, regional plans usually foresee the establishment of working groups that are set to follow up on the plans' actions. In some cases, the working groups are configured as a consultative body with rules of internal governance.

⁸⁷ Available at <<https://www.larioja.org/agenda-poblacion/es>>.

The regulations of these working groups require a composition with a certain percentage of members representing local governments of rural areas.

In addition, the regional plans promote signing cooperation agreements between the municipalities targeted by the plans and the regional government in order to adapt the plans' objectives to municipalities' needs and preferences.

Assessment of the Practice

Depopulation is a widespread trend, but its causes and consequences may be determined by the most immediate context of the municipality. These circumstances make it difficult to adopt a general plan to tackle depopulation uniformly. On the other hand, depopulation produces effects not only on rural areas but also on urban municipalities as a consequence of migratory flows. Therefore, the regional plans face a complex scenario where a general approach towards depopulation in terms of the public policies and the territory covered has to be combined with tailor-made measures for certain rural areas.

This combination of flexible general goals and in-depth understanding of the specific characteristics of each rural area requires to anticipate the incorporation of the different types of local governments (urban and rural) to early stages in the elaboration of the regional plans on depopulation.

One of the problems presented by the late incorporation of the municipalities through monitoring groups or collaboration agreements with the regional administration is the overlapping of initiatives to face the same problems from different levels of government not necessarily coordinated, and with the participation of different stakeholders. Thus, the development of regional plans incorporates, for example, universities and associations of municipalities, and the initiatives to tackle depopulation at a local level integrate active members of the community and businesses. The assessment of regional plans will, therefore, depend on their capacity to integrate and coordinate stakeholders and initiatives that follow one another simultaneously.

In addition, the plans still have a limited scope in terms of promoting the leadership of local governments themselves and the coordination with other stakeholders in order to boost the economic and social development of the most depopulated areas. Local governments are mainly dependent on regional, state, and European initiatives in this regard. This is the case of the promotion of female employment in agriculture in RLGs. Despite of the nation-wide legal framework for promoting female management of farms (Law no 35/2011 on Shared Ownership of Farms) the results in terms of initiatives are quite diverse, ranging from 0 initiatives (provinces of Madrid, Barcelona, among others) up to almost 300 in the Autonomous Community of Castilla y León (298 as for October 2020). This lack of convergence points to other factors at play such as the economic resources and grants placed by the regional governments to implement the legal framework.

Finally, regional plans to prevent depopulation of rural areas present a limited effort in the inclusion of assessment and monitoring tools or concerning the exchange of practices between

regions. Ultimately, the comparison between the different initiatives would allow for identifying best practices.

The workshops and interviews conducted allow us to identify two dimensions in the development of regional plans to address depopulation that affect the local level of government. First, one dimension concerns whether the initiative is led by regional governments or sponsored by local entities. A second dimension of variability is whether the measures are contained in multi-year policy plans or are translated into regulatory provisions.

With respect to the first of the above dimensions, the interviews conducted point to a greater frequency of regional initiative in the development of these plans. This predominance is due to several factors, including the greater capacity of regional governments to attract public funds linked to depopulation plans.

The interviews also show that the phenomenon of depopulation is not necessarily linked to rurality. In this sense, some income guarantee programs, or aspects such as the proximity of rural entities to urban areas, have served to settle the population and avoid depopulation processes. In other cases, depopulation phenomena are localized in certain areas characterized by a productive system dependent on the primary sector or are not perceived as a generalizable phenomenon in the region's municipalities. In this sense, the main need to identify and locate where the depopulation phenomena occur in a concrete manner is observed in the plans. These circumstances make it difficult to draw up general plans on depopulation, consolidate the formation of specific local interests, question the generality of the relationship between rurality and depopulation and force the search for ad hoc solutions.

Regarding the second dimension that characterizes regional plans on depopulation, there are examples of autonomous communities, such as Castilla la Mancha, have passed legislative measures on depopulation instead of programmatic plans without binding force (i.e. Law no 2/2021, of May 7, on Economic, Social and Fiscal Measures against Depopulation and for the Development of the Rural Environment in Castilla-La Mancha). In this case, the municipalities are classified into different zones according to demographic, economic activity, land use and accessibility criteria in relation to the rural environment. The application of planning and programming measures for the territorial development of the rural environment is based on the characteristics of each of the zones thus defined. This model of depopulation plan with a legislative basis is presented as necessary in order to remove from the political debate the development of a policy that requires a sustained action in the medium or long term.

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4.5 The Basque Council for Local Public Policies

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Relevance of the Practice

In the Spanish legal system, the autonomous communities are entitled to develop further the legal system of local government while respecting municipal autonomy (Article 140 of the Spanish Constitution), the fundamental regulations of the state in local government and liability of the public administration (Article 149(1)(18) of the Spanish Constitution).

In the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country, the participation of local governments in decision-making processes is mainly articulated through collegial advisory bodies. These are made up of representatives from different levels of government. Article 7 of the Act 40/2015 on the Legal Regime of the Public Sector establishes that the so-called advisory administration may be articulated through specific bodies with organic and functional autonomy. The characteristic element of this collegial advisory administration is precisely its hierarchical independence in order to guarantee the fulfilment of its functions. In addition to collegiate advisory bodies, this legal framework makes it possible to create collegial bodies that can perform various functions (decision, proposal, advice, monitoring, or control). These collegial bodies share with the consultative bodies the hierarchical independence unless otherwise is provided for by their constitutional rule.

Recently, the Act 2/2016 on Local Institutions in the Basque Country established the Basque Council for Local Public Policies (BCLPP) as a permanent institution entrusted with the task of ensuring that institutional cooperation between local, regional and state levels of governments is effective, and guaranteed the recognition of municipal interests in the processes of design, preparation, execution, and evaluation of public policies. Hence, BCLPP plays an important role in planning and evaluating public policies. The BCLPP aims to promote cooperation or, where appropriate, coordination, for the integrated management of public policies by the different levels of government. Furthermore, the council is in charge of requiring the competent autonomous body (Basque Government Council) to file an appeal of alleged unconstitutionality when it identifies a breach of local autonomy.

One of the first actions taken by the BCLPP has been the elaboration of an Action Plan to evaluate collegial advisory bodies. The implementation of this Plan is instrumental for the development of the functions of the BCLPP since this entity is intended to replace a set of collegial bodies for the coordination in the provision of local services. The Action Plan is therefore a diagnostic exercise of how the bodies aimed at coordination for the provision of public services have functioned. The result of this Plan is that the BCLPP is able to achieve a more efficient and effective coordination for the delivery of public services at the local level.

Description of the Practice

The BCLPP consists of eighteen members: six members representing the regional government, two members from each of the three provincial councils (*diputaciones forales*), and six members corresponding to the municipalities. As for the latter, at least one-third of the municipal representatives are elected from municipalities with a population of fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. At present, the representatives of the municipalities cover from municipalities with 78 inhabitants (Orexa) or 1,614 inhabitants (Asparrena) to cities with more than 300,000 inhabitants (Bilbao). Consequently, the balance between rural and urban municipalities is obtained through composition to a large extent. To this regard, the representation of urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs) is channeled through the Association of Basque Municipalities (EUDEL) preserving the presence of municipalities from different sizes, so with at least one-third of the municipal representatives elected from municipalities with a population of less than 5,000 inhabitants.

The main functions of the BCLPP are the promotion of intergovernmental relations and the channeling of proposals to promote regulations on those matters related to the competences of the municipalities and within the scope of the Autonomous Community of Basque Country. The BCLPP's main organ, the board, adopts its decisions by plurality, and it is assisted by a Secretariat linked to the regional government. Despite of the fact that the BCLPP operates in complete organic and functional autonomy, the BCLPP is attached to a department of the Basque Government, although only for budgetary purposes.

The BCLPP is a relatively new institution that has to operate in an institutional context densely populated by different types of collegial bodies. In other words, the BCLPP competes with other bodies for the promotion of inter-administrative cooperation between local, provincial, and regional governments. In this scenario, the BCLPP aims at reorganizing the fragmented collegial advisory bodies landscape. In doing so, the BCLPP replaces those collegial bodies in their role of cooperation and coordination mechanisms for the integrated management of public policies by the different levels of government.

In general terms, collegial bodies are the most common form of collaboration between different public administrations. These collegial bodies are present in almost all areas of activity and may include representatives of civil society. Despite their role, there is a lack of knowledge about how these collegial bodies perform their function and how local interests are represented and integrated into public policies. Moreover, there are no evaluation criteria or indicators of efficiency and effectiveness that would allow these collegial bodies to be held accountable. To fill this gap, the CBPPL has promoted the development and implementation of the Action Plan for the Evaluation of Interorganizational Collegial Bodies (APEICB) as part of the Strategic Plan for Governance and Public Innovation 2020.

The APEICB aims to (i) analyze the functioning of collegial cooperation bodies (i.e. regulations, structure and composition, meetings, plans and actions implemented), (ii) evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the collegial advisory bodies in the Basque institutional systems, (iii) assess the impact that collegial bodies have on the definition, monitoring and evaluation of sectoral public policies, (iv) propose measures to rationalize and improve the work of collegial bodies, (v) identify the existing collegial bodies whose functions can be assumed by

the BCLPP and the possible creation of Sectorial Commissions within it (Article 86(3) Act 2/2016). Therefore, the APRIAB's objective is to transform knowledge into institutional change.

In order to meet these objectives, the APEICB was structured in four main stages: (i) identification and elaboration of an inventory of inter-administrative collegial bodies, (ii) evaluation of the functioning of the organs, (iii) elaboration of an executive program of proposals, (iv) implementation of the executive program. Up to date, the APEICB has reached the third stage. The APEICB has allowed to mapping the landscape of inter-administrative collegial bodies. A total of 350 collegiate bodies have been established since the 1970s. The pace of creation has not been uniform, with the creation of bodies being concentrated in periods (V, VIII, and X legislative terms) – see the figure below.

Figure 1: Evolution of inter-administrative collegial bodies.⁸⁸

Up to 74 of the 350 collegial bodies have been inactive for the past 4 years (i.e. no meetings or actions reported). Moreover, 174 of the 250 bodies did not have approved internal governance rules. The collegial bodies respond to a plurality of subjects, of which health (16 per cent), education (13 per cent), economy and finance (7 per cent), environment, and Basque language (5 per cent) are prevalent. The bulk of these bodies (119) are of an inter-institutional nature as other public administrations participate (provincial councils, municipalities, universities, among others). Regarding their function, most of them are of an advisory nature (60 per cent), mainly executive (10 per cent), and more participative than other functions (14 per cent). Local governments participate in 34 per cent of these collegial bodies, and 38 per cent along with the provincial councils. Up to 38 per cent of the collegial bodies issue binding reports.

The above-mentioned results empowered the BCLPP to make proposals for institutional changes in the collegial bodies in order to promote efficiency, transparency and coordination of the different levels of government (e.g. suppression of duplicate or inefficient collegiate bodies, reallocation of functions in the BCLPP). In this regard, the APEICB presents several features to facilitate institutional change. First, the APEICB evaluates a broad range of administrative bodies regardless of their formal denomination (inter-administrative organs,

⁸⁸ Source: APEICB.

committees, consultative bodies, among others). This broad definition allows BCLPP to gain full knowledge of the landscape of collegial bodies and therefore to legitimate their proposals for institutional change. Second, the APEICB elaborates on a methodological scheme to evaluate the collegial bodies systematically. In this regard, the APEICB is made of information about the legal framework, functions, organization, resources and methods, activity, impact on the design of public policies, gender equality dimension regarding the collegial bodies. Third, the APEICB was considered a collaborative instrument in itself since all the information gathered was shared through a SharePoint collaborative space located at the BCLPP. Finally, the APEICB foresees accountability mechanisms such as the requirement for collegial bodies to submit information to the BCLPP regularly to update the information of the database of collegial bodies.

To sum up, The BCLPP represents a balance in the influence and greater coordination between the ULGs and RLGs due to the characteristics of the composition of the BCLPP and the type of public management it carries out, which is based on the generation of knowledge and the accountability of the other collegiate bodies. Therefore, the APEICB is an example of instrument of political influence by the BCLPP through the management of knowledge.

Assessment of the Practice

The APEICB can be initially evaluated in terms of its ultimate goal, which is to make the BCLPP the institutional space for the design of local public policies. From this perspective, and although the APEICB is currently in the implementation phase of institutional change proposals, its capacity as an engine for institutional change can be foreseen. This capacity is based on two main elements. On the one hand, the generation of knowledge about the functioning of the collegial coordination bodies. On the other, the establishment of a system of accountability, since these collegial bodies are required to report on a series of activity indicators that will serve to propose new organizational changes in order to better achieve coordination of local public policies.

From this perspective, the APEICB may enhance the role of urban and rural municipalities in decision-making through monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. In the case of rural municipalities, rural local governments are granted with at least one-third of the representatives of the BCLPP. Secondly, the very configuration of the BCLPP as a center for promoting knowledge on public administration at the local level represents an opportunity for local governments to have a say in decision-making due to their access to information.

Notwithstanding the above, the level of compliance with the APEICB in terms of accountability and the extent to which the weaknesses observed can be addressed by the BCLPP remain open questions. The resources of the BCLPP are not significant due to its novelty, so its capacity to assume responsibility for the coordination of local public policies remains to be confirmed.

The results of the BCLPP are limited so far due to the profound transformation of the organizational structure involved and the recent implementation of its main mechanism, the APEICB. Its necessity, however, stems from the limitations of the other mechanisms for local entities involvement in upper levels of government. Specifically, local entities participation in

the legislative process at the regional level is mainly channeled through regional associations of local entities. The latter associations verify that legislative initiatives respect local autonomy and the competences of local governments.

However, this participation does not necessarily imply that local entities may define the main issues on the political agenda. The determination of the issues to be discussed is still monopolized by the regional governments. Therefore, the BCLPP, through mechanisms such as the APEICB, tend to anticipate the participation of local government in the legislative process and therefore increase its political leverage.

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5. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Switzerland

5.1 The System of Local Government in Switzerland

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Types of Local Governments

The Swiss model of federalism, based on the principle of subsidiarity, is structured in three layers of political representation, i.e. the Confederation (national government), the cantons and the municipalities. The Constitution of the Swiss Confederation, however, focuses on two layers only, the national and cantonal. In its Article 1 it not only lists the official 26 cantons but also gives them constitutive effect. In Article 3 it sets the rules for the power-sharing arrangements between the Confederation and the cantons: ‘The Cantons are sovereign except to the extent that their sovereignty is limited by the Federal Constitution. They exercise all rights that are not vested in the Confederation.’ However, one must bear in mind that the term ‘competent’ would be more appropriate than ‘sovereign’ to describe the power vested in the cantons. In fact, the cantons have competence on all the tasks and duties that do not fall on the Confederation. But they nevertheless remain subdued to the Confederation, as the majority of the other cantons can impose their will on a canton via a revision of the Swiss Constitution. Indeed, according to the Article 48(a) of the Swiss Constitution, at the request of interested cantons, the Confederation may declare intercantonal agreements to be generally binding or require cantons to participate in intercantonal agreements in the following fields:

- the execution of criminal penalties and measures;
- school education in the matters specified in Article 62(4);
- cantonal institutions of higher education;
- cultural institutions of supra-regional importance; e. waste management;
- waste water treatment;
- urban transport;
- advanced medical science and specialist clinics;
- institutions for the rehabilitation and care of invalids.

The Federal Constitution does not attribute any competence to regulate local government to the national government. The municipalities are therefore created by and subjected to cantonal regulation. Thus, each canton defines the status and the competences of its municipalities in its cantonal constitution and legislation. We therefore differentiate 26 systems of municipalities corresponding to each of the 26 Swiss cantons. Still, one can identify five main types of municipalities:

- the classical political municipalities which are called *commune* in French, *comune* in Italian and *Gemeinde, Ortsgemeinde* or *Einwohnergemeinde* in German depending on the cantons. They are the basic general-purpose type of municipality;
- the so-called *bourgeoise* municipalities that have survived from the Middle Age in some cantons. When in 1798 the Helvetic Republic is proclaimed; the cantons are put on an equal footing and the inhabitants of the Swiss territory receive the Swiss citizenship. The original bourgeois do not agree to share the communal properties (lands, forests, etc.) with the new *bourgeoise*. Thus, the *bourgeoise* municipalities keep the control over the communal properties and the political municipalities guarantee the political rights to the new *bourgeoise*. As of today, in the cantons where such *bourgeoise* municipalities remain, they are mainly land owners and service providers (for example retirement houses, subsidized apartments, young offenders' facilities, etc.);
- the ecclesiastical community is the territorial division that is attached to a church and that is often called parish (*paroisse* in French). They are a single-purpose body;
- the so-called scholar commune *commune scolaire* is also a single-purpose body that deals with the school system on a certain territory within the limits assigned by the canton and that does not automatically match with the political municipality. For example, the school program remains a cantonal competence but the decision to build the school or to organize the carriage of school pupils is, to a large extent, delegated to the scholar municipalities;⁸⁹
- other types of municipalities that exist in some cantons.

Finally, one must add that the majority of the Swiss cantons have put in place an intermediary political level between the cantons and the municipalities called the district (*district* in French, *Bezirk, Verwaltungsregion, Verwaltungskreis, Wahlkreis, Amtei* or *Amt* in German, *distretto* in Italian). Out of the 26 cantons, only six do not have such a subdivision. These districts are very different from each other but they usually correspond to a group of municipalities. Again, the cantons hold the primary competence regarding their internal organization and scope.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The constitution framework that prevailed until 1999 did not mention municipalities, unless incidentally. Only the adoption of a new constitution that year ensured that local autonomy was granted constitutional protection.⁹⁰ Article 50 reads as follows: (i) 'The autonomy of the communes is guaranteed in accordance with cantonal law.'; (ii) 'The Confederation shall take account in its activities of the possible consequences for the communes.'; (iii) 'In doing so, it shall take account of the special position of the cities and urban areas as well as the mountain regions.'

The effect of the new provision is limited. The extent of local autonomy remains in the hands of the cantons ('in accordance with cantonal law') and each of them thus continues to autonomously define its internal governance system. Only as far as cantonal law provides for

⁸⁹ Nicolas Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland: Organisation and Competences* (forthcoming).

⁹⁰ Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland*, above.

municipal autonomy, it is guaranteed by the Federal Constitution. Consequently, municipal autonomy is justiciable and the Federal Supreme Court hears disputes concerning violations of it (Article 189(1)(e)). When it does so, it refers to the cantonal constitution and the cantonal legislative framework to determine the scope of local autonomy and decide whether the canton has impinged on it or not.

If the Article 50(2) of the Constitution constrains the Confederation, while fulfilling its tasks (e.g. military, national highways), to be considerate of municipalities, it does not confer additional jurisdiction on the Confederation. Essentially, this constitutional provision aims at fostering vertical cooperation between the three institutional levels of the Swiss federal structure but without bypassing the intermediary level, the cantons. The article refers specifically to the urban-rural divide and explicitly compels the national government to take account of the special priorities and needs of cities and urban areas on the one hand and mountain regions on the other hand. Among the concrete initiatives, the Tripartite Conference can be mentioned. It will be discussed at length further in the Country Report.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As mentioned above, there are 26 systems of local government corresponding to the 26 Swiss cantons. Thus, there are considerable differences regarding the rules that apply to urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs), etc. For example, the Canton of Zürich has granted a special status to the cities of Zürich and Winterthur. Most cantons, however, are based on a symmetric system and allocate the same tasks and responsibilities to all municipalities, irrespective of their size.

Despite of the wide variety of cantonal local government arrangements, some common features can be identified. Schmitt demonstrates that all municipalities are run by an executive council of five to ten members who are elected by the citizens and who are compelled to take decisions on a collegial basis.⁹¹ While they traditionally are not paid for their work, the elected members of municipalities' councils in the ULGs tend to be professionals.

As regards legislative power, small municipalities (not to say RLGs) have citizens' assemblies that meet regularly to pass new laws and/or to elect the executive council members and other authorities. On the contrary, some cantons have compelled larger municipalities (ULGs) to create a parliament, i.e. an elected legislative body *representing* the citizens. As Schmitt notes, the Canton of Fribourg has adopted the Law on the Municipalities (*Loi sur les communes* in French) that requires eight specific municipalities to set up such a parliament while municipalities with over 600 inhabitants are only invited to do so.⁹² Smaller municipalities can keep their citizens' assemblies.

Finally, Schmitt puts a light on an interesting paradox: while municipalities still enjoy a large set of competencies and have the right to collect taxes (and set the tax rates), judicial power is not granted to the municipalities. In fact, the lowest judicial level is, in some cantons, the

⁹¹ Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland*, above.

⁹² *ibid.*

district's judge. Once again, one must look carefully at all the 26 cantonal organizations in order to grasp the subtleties of the local government systems that make Swiss federalism so complex.⁹³

Political and Social Context in Switzerland

If the prominent role and the many responsibilities conferred to the municipalities have long been praised and recognized as a key factor for the success of the Swiss political model, one must note that they tend to lose their luster. In fact, the degree of autonomy enjoyed by the municipalities decreases due to the increasing requirements (land use planning, environmental protection, social aid, waste management, etc.) from the Confederation, the cantons and, to some extent, the people themselves. The democratic pressure (complexity of the legal frameworks, over technical policy fields, procedural overload, etc.) on the municipalities is difficult to manage, especially for non-professional elected representatives and somehow encourages the centralization of the decision-making power and the pooling of local tasks and duties at a superior level.

In the last 30 years, Switzerland has thus witnessed a strong acceleration of the number of amalgamations of its municipalities. From more than 3,200 municipalities in 1999, the number has dropped to approximately 2,200 municipalities in 2018. While the rural municipalities tend to merge, it can be observed that urban municipalities tend instead to agglomerate⁹⁴ via different types of inter-municipal agreements. In any case, cantons and municipalities follow their own path with little interference from the national government. Today, approximately two thirds of the Swiss population is concentrated in the cities' centers⁹⁵ or agglomerations.

According to 2017 data, the 2,212 Swiss municipalities are relatively small, with 1,060 inhabitants on average, but very different in size. The smallest is Corippo with 12 permanent inhabitants and, like many others, spreads on less than 1 km². The largest in terms of territory is Scuol with 438.62 km² and the most populated is Zurich with 400,000 inhabitants. Many municipalities being unable to cope with the organizational requirements of today's life (school facilities, firefighter's service, water sanitation, etc.) and finding it difficult to recruit personnel, a strong process of merging local authorities has begun some sixty years ago and has accelerated in the last thirty years.

The four main coalition parties, namely the FDP. The Liberals, the Christian Democratic People's Party, the Social Democratic Party and the Swiss People's Party are all represented at the Federal level and in almost all the 26 cantons. Interestingly, in the urban cities, the

⁹³ *ibid.*

⁹⁴ According to the Federal Office of Statistics, the agglomeration can be defined as follows: An agglomeration is a group of municipalities with a total of more than 20,000 inhabitants (incl. overnight stays in converted hotels). It consists of a dense center and usually a crown. The delimitation of the crown is based on the intensity of the commuter flows.

⁹⁵ According to the Federal Office of Statistics, the city-center can be defined as follows: The municipality which, among the central municipalities of an agglomeration, has the highest number of HENs (= sum of inhabitants, work places and overnight stays in converted hotels) is considered as a city-center. In some cases, it is possible for an agglomeration to have several central cities.

traditional political parties are well organized and represented while in the smaller rural municipalities, political parties are less active. The peculiarity of small municipalities where every citizen knows each other means that people vote first for a specific candidate rather than for the parties.

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5.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Switzerland: An Introduction

Erika Schläppi and Kelly Bishop, *Ximpulse GmbH*

It is not possible to make generalized statements on the relations between canton and municipalities for all of Switzerland. In the Swiss federal system, the cantons (and not the Confederation) determine the status and role of municipalities. Each canton has its own way to organize relations with municipalities, allocate competences and organize municipal finances. Thus, intergovernmental relations differ largely among the cantons. Because of historic and cultural reasons, the cantons of the French speaking part have a more centralistic approach, while municipalities in the eastern and central part of Switzerland show a more decentralized structure when it comes to the allocation of tasks. Our examples mainly refer to the Canton of Berne and its relation to the Bernese municipalities. The canton is perceived as a bridge builder between the German and the French speaking cantons and their traditions. Regarding municipal autonomy it might be considered as a kind of Swiss average. The Canton of Berne is one of the biggest cantons in terms of territory as well as the number of residents (around 1 Mio, 16.3 per cent foreign passport holders according to the census of 2018). The City of Berne is the capital of the canton as well as of the Swiss Confederation. Socially and politically, the canton is quite heterogeneous: relatively big urban and peri-urban areas are coupled with reasonably big rural and mountainous areas that are thinly populated. Around 10 per cent of the residents are mainly speaking French, the big majority are German speakers. All these elements make the Canton of Berne an interesting object of observation.

In Switzerland there is hardly any public task that is exclusively performed by municipalities, without any central steering or co-financing, and the distribution of responsibilities is constantly evolving. In all important policy areas there is a sharing of competence that requires a cooperative set-up between cantons and municipalities at various levels. As a rule, the canton focuses on the adoption of the legal framework, establishes a control system and exercises oversight. With the increasing mobility and the evolving complexity of public tasks it is not surprising that generally, the central competences are increasing and the scope of action of municipalities tend to be decreasing. The principle of subsidiarity (Article 5(a) of the Federal Constitution) is providing (federal) orientation for the allocation of competences, stating that tasks should be performed as close to the population as possible. Thus, the primary schools, social welfare, local spatial planning, public security, local transport, water supply and waste management are most often in the competence of municipalities – but there are still many federal and cantonal rules and standards that are to be considered by municipalities.

Financial equalization is an important pillar of the Swiss political system, allowing for financial collaboration and cooperation among cantons and municipalities. At the level of the Confederation it focuses on the equalization of resources as well as the equalization of financial burdens between cantons. The same idea of equalization is also applied at cantonal level, between municipalities. Regarding the allocated tasks, the cantonal regulations hardly make any difference between municipalities that, in terms of inhabitants, tend to be bigger in urban areas and smaller in rural areas. The cantonal specifications and standards are the same, the cantonal controlling and oversight does not differentiate between urban or rural, big or small

municipalities. However, the Canton of Berne is contributing to the financing of municipal tasks in many respects. The cantonal share is calculated according to the constitutional principle of 'financial equivalence': The canton pays what it is commissioning. For example, the canton has adopted a relatively dense regulation concerning the salaries of primary teachers, the curricula and the required lessons for primary schools – thus, the canton pays 70 per cent of the salary expenses for primary school teachers. The rest of the salary expenses are financed by the municipalities, through their own tax income.

Today, municipalities with low financial capacities would not be able to finance their tasks by their own tax income. Thus, a horizontal equalization scheme has been developed. This scheme is mainly alimented by payments of well-off municipalities but the canton is also contributing funds. The payment scheme for equalization of resources is meant to allow for an adequate (but not full) equalization of standards among municipalities, independent of their financial capacities. In addition, the equalization of burdens aspires to balance specific burdens on the municipalities that are caused by social demography, geographical challenges (for example, the cost of an extensive water supply or road system in a thinly populated rural area), or specific tasks of urban centres (*Zentrumslasten*). The equalization payments are calculated based on a cantonal law and decided upon by the cantonal government, taking into account a very differentiated set of parameters that is adjusted regularly. The equalization system in the canton of Berne has grown over the years into a complex body of horizontal and vertical, direct and indirect, general and sectorial mechanisms. The impact of the equalization scheme on the canton and (urban and rural) municipalities is regularly evaluated and assessed in the light of the context dynamics, and adjustments are frequently thematized and discussed in the political debate..

Every Swiss municipality is participating in intermunicipal cooperation in multiple ways and forms and obtains services from third parties. From the political point of view as well as from the accountability perspective, there is hardly any difference whether the (public) task is performed by the municipality itself, in cooperation with other municipalities or by third parties. In the Canton of Berne, in average, around half of the municipal budgets are spent by own activities, around a third of the budgets go to legally autonomous bodies owned by the municipalities (such as associations of municipalities, or shareholder companies owned by municipalities), and one sixth of the budget is spent for buying services from third parties. Smaller and even medium size municipalities have difficulties to perform their tasks according to the required quality standards and the cooperation with other municipalities or the private sector allows them to improve their professional performance. However, in many cases, cooperation is not cheap – it will not lead to lower costs as it is often hoped for.

Intermunicipal cooperation is mainly organized in two legal forms: the association of municipalities and the assignment of one municipality to perform tasks of others. The association of municipalities is a legally autonomous municipal body that is foreseen by the cantonal municipal law. Individual municipalities commission this body to fulfill a certain task. The association is organized in a legislative and an executive body and acts according to a set of rules that must be adopted by the participating municipalities. Essential changes to the delegated tasks or the funding parameters cannot be adopted by the majority within the association against the will of participating municipalities. This form of cooperation has proved itself many times. However, the challenge is that the steering of the associations is often

mediated through individual representatives in their decision-making bodies, there is often a certain self-reinforcing momentum, and municipal authorities have difficulties to have their voices as owners heard. The second legal form is the contracting of one municipality to fulfill tasks on behalf of other municipalities. The advantages of the association (for example, the participation of the delegating municipalities in decision-making processes) can also be reflected in the contract. The advantage of this form is that the fulfillment of the task is embedded in an existing municipal set-up and can profit from existing professional structures and administrative services. While these forms of intermunicipal cooperation are ruled by public law, municipal tasks are often also delegated to companies that are formally under private law, for example joint-stock companies or cooperatives that run a regional sports facility on behalf of various municipalities. Here again, the steering and the ensuring of accountability can be challenging. Increasingly, the participating municipalities do no longer engage in the steering boards of such companies but are agreeing among themselves on an owner strategy that they then commission to the private company for execution.

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5.3 The Association of Bernese Municipalities: Representing Municipalities in the Cantonal Decision-Making

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Relevance of the Practice

The question whether and how the interests of municipalities are taken into account in political decision-making processes of the cantonal as well as at the Confederation level is of high relevance, for urban as well as rural municipalities. The cantonal level is key for defining the scope of action of the municipalities in Switzerland, the intergovernmental relations, the structures, tasks, standards for municipal services, the funding systems and equalization schemes. Thus, for municipalities, influencing the decision-making in the cantonal parliaments and governments, raising their voice in administrative processes as well as in the broader public is very important. The Association of Bernese Municipalities is an example of making urban and rural municipalities join forces to defend the municipalities' common interests in relation to the cantonal authorities that are regulating and overseeing municipal activities.

Description of the Practice

The Association of Bernese Municipalities has been representing the interests of Bernese municipalities for almost 70 years. 98 per cent of the municipalities are members of the association which is fully funded by membership fees. It is important to mention that the association is regulated by private law and has no official public status per se. The association's aims are to represent the interests of Bernese municipalities vis-à-vis the Canton of Berne. It strives for keeping municipal autonomy and is committed to an adequate distribution of tasks between the canton and the municipalities as well as to adequate funding systems. It also provides support services on behalf of its members.

At the annual meetings of the Association's general assembly a board is elected that is carefully balanced in terms of political parties, regional representation, gender, urban and rural areas, and the two official languages of the canton. The board and the director take decisions based on principles that should ensure the legitimacy, credibility and capacity of the association to speak on behalf of Bernese municipalities. Among these principles, political neutrality is important. To ensure such neutrality, the Association's board incorporates representatives of all parties but avoids being instrumentalized by political parties. It does not take any position in regional politics and is not engaged in political debates around specific tasks. It refrains from taking position in conflicts among municipalities, emphasizing that the political authorities (the cantonal parliament and the government) are better legitimized to take decisions and action on diverging interests. Instead of taking positions the association aspires to constructively balance different interests (between rich and poor, urban and rural, big and small

municipalities, German speakers and French speakers), build on always existing common interests and denominators and find acceptable solutions for all municipalities. According to its principles the association engages for more scope of action of municipalities – and for less operational involvement and influence of cantonal authorities that blur accountability lines and demotivate local authorities. The association gets orientation and guidance from the constitutional principles that enshrines subsidiarity, fiscal equivalence, accountability and financial equalization and admits that a financial balance has to be established also between the canton and the municipalities.

Following these principles, the association engages in many activities related to political decision-making in the Canton of Berne. It seeks to convey clear messages and address conflictual issues while investing in partnership relations and confidence with cantonal authorities. It closely cooperates with the cantonal supervisory bodies to establish models of municipal laws and regulations that take the cantonal legal framework fully into account. It takes position on cantonal draft laws and regulations and policies that involve municipal interests, be it in formalized consultation procedures (that are very common in Switzerland) or in more informal settings. For example, in 2019, the association has taken part in about 40 consultation processes regarding draft of laws and policies in a variety of domains, from local security issues to childcare, from land zoning to biodiversity. The fact that the board members are active local politicians but also part of the cantonal political scene and often members of the cantonal parliament, makes the association even more effective in influencing cantonal politics.

Providing useful services to members helps the association anchoring itself in the municipal scene, keeping touch with municipal practice, and being ahead of problems. The association regularly organizes public information meetings and hearings, to inform municipalities about important reforms and plans and building opinions. It regularly makes surveys to find out about the positions of municipalities. Legal advice and support services are provided to members. Together with other associations and educational facilities, the association is engaged in professional education and training of municipal staff and capacity building of local politicians. It particularly invests in supporting the municipalities in their role as a public employer.

Assessment of the Practice

The Association of Bernese Municipalities is considered to be a successful lobbying organization representing municipal interests in the cantonal political debate. Its deliberate policy of balancing interests, integrating all relevant political parties, conveying clear messages but investing in confidential relations with the powerful cantonal counterparts, has made the association a very influential player. This is also because of the high representation of mayors in the association as well as in the cantonal parliament – an important leverage for the association.

The focus on common interests of municipalities – instead of feeling squeezed between conflicting positions – has helped the association to raise a strong voice of all municipalities on issues of municipal concern. In this logic, the association must refrain from taking position either for urban or rural interests that might seriously hamper its credibility as a representative

of Bernese municipalities at large. The converse example can be seen at national (Swiss) level: Two associations are representing municipal interests, on the one hand the Swiss Cities' Association representing urban interests, on the other hand the Swiss Association of Municipalities, representing small and medium municipalities from peri-urban and rural areas. The two associations have different political orientations – the Swiss Cities' Association tends to have a more left-wing and green orientation, while the Swiss Association of Municipalities tends to be more conservative. Thus, on many political topics at Swiss level, the municipal voice is divided, and the two associations are openly fighting each other wherever urban or rural interests are at stake.

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5.4 Intergovernmental Cooperation between Cantonal and Municipal Authorities: The Issue of Primary Education in the Canton of Berne

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Relevance of the Practice

The allocation of powers, tasks and responsibilities for services and corresponding funding systems are key features of effective local governance. In practice, competences and tasks can rarely be allocated exclusively to one level of government in a way that the responsible authorities can decide on the tasks without any involvement of the other levels. The legal frameworks, tasks and competences are closely interwoven. While the de-bundling of tasks makes politically sense particularly for ensuring clear accountability lines, the idea of a clear-cut separation of powers and tasks between cantonal and municipal authorities must remain an illusion. In the reality of the Canton of Berne, shared responsibilities between the cantonal and municipal authorities are rather the rule than the exception, and this implies complex systems of vertical cooperation. The case of primary education (as an issue of competence that is shared between all levels of Swiss governance) illustrates this need for vertical and horizontal cooperation. This practice example shows how this is organized in the Canton of Berne and its rural and urban municipalities.

Description of the Practice

The allocation of powers and tasks between cantons and the Confederation follows Article 3 of the Federal Constitution: The cantons have original or residual powers, and the Confederation has only powers that are explicitly attributed to it by the Constitution (Article 42). General principles for the allocation of tasks are enshrined in Article 43 of the Federal Constitution: The Confederation only undertakes tasks that the cantons are unable to perform or which require uniform regulation by the Confederation (principle of subsidiarity). The collective body that bears the costs of a public service may decide on the nature of that service. This principle, called 'financial equivalence', is particularly important in the Swiss federal system where the three State levels (including municipalities) have their own taxing powers and are, in principle, responsible for covering the costs of the services within their competence with their own means. Universally provided services must be made available to every person in a comparable manner. Finally, State tasks must be fulfilled economically and in accordance with demand (efficiency and responsiveness). Although the Cantonal Constitution of Berne does not mention these principles enshrined in the Federal Constitution, they are also guiding the allocation of tasks between the canton and the Bernese municipalities and the management of municipal services. Explicitly, the Cantonal Constitution only mentions that the municipalities are fulfilling the tasks that are attributed to them by the canton and the

Confederation (Article 112), and that the cantonal law grants the municipalities as much freedom of action as possible (Article 109(2)).

While vocational education and higher education are shared responsibilities between the cantons and the Confederation, primary school education is a cantonal competence, however with federal standards to be respected (Article 62 of the Federal Constitution). The cantons must ensure the provision of an adequate basic education that is available to all children. Basic education is mandatory and is managed or supervised by the state. Primary education at state schools is free of charge. Where harmonization of school education (on specific topics) is not achieved by means of coordination among cantons, the Confederation shall issue regulations to achieve such harmonization.

Within this federal framework, in the Canton of Berne, primary schools are a shared responsibility of the canton and the municipalities. The Primary School Act refers to the obligatory schooling of children from 5 to 16 years of age. It provides a complex intergovernmental set-up of responsibilities between cantonal and municipal authorities, with no formal differentiation between urban and rural areas. The main features are set out as follows.

The cantonal authorities define contents, objectives and general conditions for primary schools and ensure a comparable offer for all municipalities (Article 50). They set the principles and standards of primary education (objectives, duration, curriculum, rights of students and parents, forms of education, teaching material, etc.).

The municipalities are 'in charge' of the primary schools. Several municipalities can join forces in a municipal association to provide school services jointly, or municipalities contract another municipality to deliver school services for them. They are to ensure that every child can attend primary school (Article 5). The municipalities are responsible for concretizing the contents and objectives of the primary public school, implementing the services, evaluating the results and reporting to the canton (Articles 50-51).

Municipalities are responsible for the construction, maintenance and operational management of school facilities and their equipment, according to cantonal regulations (Article 48). Municipalities decide on the creation and abolition of school classes and the introduction of facultative classes, with the approval of the cantonal authorities who can provide general regulations on these issues (Article 47).

At municipal level, the schools are organizational units within the municipal administration. They are usually overseen by a school board and managed by a school directorate (Article 23) responsible for pedagogic guidance and administrative management. School boards are responsible for ensuring school attendance of all children, anchoring the school in the municipality, providing strategic guidance and fulfilling other tasks, particularly in the context of teachers' employment (Article 35).

The canton is responsible for quality assurance and gives quality feedback to the municipalities. Regional school inspectors are responsible for advice to municipal authorities as well as cantonal oversight (Article 52). The cantonal authorities have a duty to communicate with and inform municipalities and public schools about trends and developments in school organization as well as cantonal support offers (Article 54).

The teachers' personnel costs are jointly financed in the ratio of 70 per cent (canton) to 30 per cent (municipalities) (Article 24 Law on the Equalization of Finances and Burdens FILAG, regulating vertical and horizontal equalization). Infrastructure and operating costs are borne by each municipality. It is estimated that the total costs of the primary school are funded in a ratio of approximately 50 per cent (canton) to 50 per cent (municipalities), in urban as well as rural areas. However, geographical and socio-demographic factors tend to make burdens higher for rural and smaller municipalities, since the rate of children per resident is higher in rural areas, and class sizes tend to be smaller, resulting in higher numbers of teachers per students. In addition, it is more difficult for small rural schools and their teachers to respond to the increasing technical standards (for example, on digitalization). On the other hand, urban schools are facing other challenges and costs, mainly due to the higher diversity of population which may result in a need for specific measures, e.g. for the speakers of foreign languages.

Financial equalization alleviates the financial impact on financially weak municipalities. The direct financial equalization system provides support to weak (rural) municipalities with low financial capacities and relatively high burdens, while the support is funded by financially strong municipalities, mostly urban or peri-urban. In addition, according to Article 24a of the cantonal Law on Equalization of Finances and Burdens, the canton provides additional support for municipalities that are facing specific costs for their primary schools. This additional contribution is depending on various factors such as the linguistic situation of the municipality, the topography, the settlement structures and the student/resident ratio.

Horizontal cooperation on primary schools is often practiced by rural municipalities with a low number of residents, challenged by the high-quality standards for schools and low municipal resources. In many cases, bigger municipalities that are considered to be regional centers offer school services also for surrounding municipalities, particularly for upper school grades. Inter-municipal cooperation takes place in the form of (legally independent) associations of municipalities for providing school services jointly, or municipalities are simply contracted to provide services on behalf of other municipalities. In urban settings, municipalities are big and strong enough to organize their primary schools effectively and cost-efficiently, without any need for horizontal cooperation.

To manage complex interactions around joint responsibilities in a constantly evolving context, vertical cooperation between cantonal authorities and municipalities are needed at various levels. The Covid-19 crisis has particularly shown that vertical cooperation processes are important to ensure that municipal interests are taken into account in assessing upcoming needs, formulating policies, arranging and re-arranging funding systems, developing practical guidance for schools and teachers, evaluating results as well as addressing related challenges. Extensive consultation practices of cantonal authorities, at political, financial as well as technical level, allow for taking into account various stakeholders' views – among them the municipalities and their association – in all stages of processes, from the beginning to the end, when the cantonal authorities envisage the revision of laws and regulations, develop practical guidance or change the financial scheme. For example, the digitalization of public education is a topic that obviously involves the competences of cantonal and municipal authorities. Representatives of the municipalities and the Association of Bernese Municipalities are participating in the working groups and commissions dealing with the issue, from the beginning to the end of the informal and formal processes for developing strategies and guidance. Other

examples include the debate around new teaching material for learning French – an issue intensively debated in and between the canton and the municipalities. Or in the extraordinary situation of Covid-19, the guidance for enhanced sanitary protection in public schools has been developed and communicated jointly.

Assessment of the Practice

The allocation of tasks and their funding as well as the ways of intergovernmental cooperation are a constant topical of political debate, the allocation of municipal competences is very dynamic and never finished. The complex set-up of responsibilities, tasks, funding structures, advice and oversight works well in the field of primary education, if and when the main communication and cooperation challenges are well addressed. The cantonal strategies and policies can be responsive to the realities on the ground if and as far as authorities know about the operational challenges that municipalities and schools are facing in urban, peri-urban and rural settings. A constant exchange of information, formal as well as informal communication processes vertically and horizontally (between municipalities) are needed.

The funding system works well overall but its aspiration to balance burdens and financial capacities of municipalities and respond to the principle of financial equivalence is ambitious and needs constant attention. If tasks are re-defined or re-distributed, or if demographic realities (including urban-rural trends related to specific burdens and financial capacities of municipalities) are changing, the funding system must be re-adapted. The general funding system of primary schooling does not differentiate between urban and rural municipalities. Both rural and urban municipalities are facing challenges that can heavily impact on the costs. While rural municipalities have a lower number of students as well as higher costs for quality services in less densely populated spaces, urban municipalities tend to have a more diverse population and may be required to offer additional support for students. The complex financial equalization system is addressing the specific burdens in various ways. Nevertheless, many small, rural and financially weak municipalities have engaged in cooperation schemes with other municipalities with a view to respond to the general quality standards for primary schools in a cost-efficient way.

The roles of cantonal and municipal stakeholders and the respective accountability lines must be understood by everyone. The distinction between steering and implementing, advising and supervising is not always clear-cut and needs constant communication and often, even re-negotiation. The scope and limits of cantonal oversight on municipal implementation is particularly challenging. For example, the cantonal authorities and the school inspectors tend, with their responsibility to regulate, advise and supervise, to get closely involved in operational and implementing responsibilities. This can blur accountability lines, since, within their legally enshrined tasks, the municipal authorities are accountable towards the municipal structures and not towards the cantonal department of Education and Culture.

A variety of spaces and processes exist for municipalities and the Association of Bernese Municipalities to contribute constructively to political, financial and technical decision-making

on primary education at cantonal level. However, such constructive participation depends on the human resources and technical knowhow that can be made available at the level of the association – also balancing the variety of views among municipalities, urban and rural, small and big.

The possibilities to require a popular vote (referendum) for new or revised laws helps to build political pressure, also on behalf of municipal interests. Nevertheless, successful lobbying requires a lot of human resources and an extensive political network that can be activated by the municipalities. The fact that many members of the cantonal parliament are (or: were) municipal counsellors or mayors and know the municipal challenges from their own experience, helps lobbying cantonal decision-making to a large extent.

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5.5 The Regional Conference of Municipalities, a Regional Cooperation Mechanism in Different Urban-Rural Settings

Erika Schläppi and Kelly Bishop, *Ximpulse GmbH*

Relevance of the Practice

In the Canton of Berne municipalities of a certain geographical area have the possibility to establish a regional cooperation mechanism (RCM), the ‘Regional Conference’, with the purpose of delivering more effectively on tasks that are transferred to them by the municipalities or by the canton. This entry shows the practice of two regional conferences, one representing a more urban and the other a more rural setting. The practice explains a mechanism of municipal cooperation. It also relates to the institutionalizing of intergovernmental relations between the local and the cantonal level and decision-making among municipalities, in a specific kind of association.

Description of the Practice

The historical delimitations of municipalities often do not correspond to the dynamics of functional spaces that are emerging due to increased mobility or changing economic patterns. The need for regional cooperation among municipalities that are sharing common interests and challenges has been recognized for some decades, particularly in the area of zoning and traffic management. In the form of a voluntary association, municipalities united for making regional arrangements and cooperating on zoning issues. To promote more binding forms of cooperation, the cantonal authorities created a regional structure for municipalities willing to engage in regional cooperation, the regional conferences of municipalities. Their geographical perimeter is decided upon by the cantonal government, after consultation of the municipalities. The legal aim of the conferences is to efficiently fulfil tasks of the implied municipalities.⁹⁶ The conferences are separate legal entities that can take autonomous decisions within their competences and have the power to take binding decisions. They are established through a decision by the municipalities within the given perimeter with a majority vote (both the population and the municipal authorities of the concerned municipalities need to vote in favor).

The cantonal law includes a list of mandatory tasks that the regional conferences are responsible for – if and when such a conference is established. In accordance with special legislation, they are responsible for regional structure, overall transport and settlement planning and their mutual coordination, regional cultural promotion and regional tasks in the

⁹⁶ Art 137 of the cantonal Law on Municipalities.

area of regional policy. The municipalities can assign the conference with additional tasks within the scope of municipal duties.

The cantonal Law on Municipalities and the related regulations also frame the organizational structure and decision-making processes but give some leeway for individual approaches of the regional conferences. The main decision-making body is the regional assembly consisting of the mayors of the concerned municipalities. The mayors have weighed voting powers which gives bigger municipalities a greater say. There are possibilities to ask for a referendum on some selected decisions of the regional assembly, and to take an initiative to submit an issue to the assembly. The Executive Board and the Head Office are the executing organs of the conference, which is funded by contributions of both participating municipalities (according to the number of inhabitants) and the canton (based on an ordinance or specific contracts). The regional conference has no direct tax income.

The Canton of Berne is geographically, socio-economically and demographically not homogenous. In terms of urban and rural settings, it consists mainly of three types of areas: a relatively big urban/peri-urban area around the major cities of the canton⁹⁷, a large area of agricultural farmland and a mountain area. This entry looks at two regional conferences that have been established over ten years ago. While both conferences include urban as well as rural municipalities, it can be said that Bern-Mittelland is characterized by a more urban or peri-urban setting, while Oberland-Ost is characterized by a small agglomeration as a regional center and two smaller regional centers (Meiringen and Brienz) surrounded by rural communities. The Regional Conference of Oberland-Ost belongs to the mountainous rural area that is mainly living from extensive farming and tourism and consists of 28 municipalities. The size of the conference's perimeter takes up 21 per cent of the (land) area, 5 per cent of the population and 4 per cent of the workplaces of the Canton of Berne. In contrast, the Regional Conference of Bern-Mittelland refers to a more urban/sub-urban area around the capital of Switzerland and the canton, the City of Berne, and consists of 77 municipalities. 40 per cent of the population of the canton live in this area and 50 per cent of the workplaces are provided here. The main economic activities are within the service delivery, industrial and the public administration sector.

The topics and areas of competences of the two regional conferences and the way they are dealing with the issues, are similar. The Regional Assembly of Bern-Mittelland has formed commissions for each mandatory sector of competence and sub-commissions are dealing with specific topics such as economy and regional politics. The Regional Conference of Oberland-Ost has formed commissions in the following areas: Public transport, landscape, traffic and spatial planning and ADT (quarry, landfill and transportation), and energy. The area of regional development and the culture divisions are directly under the management of the executive board.

⁹⁷ Classified by the Federal Office of Statistics as areas of urban character ('Räumliche Typologien' (*Federal Statistical Office*, undated)

<<https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/querschnittsthemen/raeumliche-analysen/raeumliche-gliederungen/raeumliche-typologien.html>> accessed 27 July 2020, according to criteria such as population density, size and reachability as well as socio-economic criteria.

In the framework of the cantonal regulations, both regional conferences have issued their own regulation on organizational procedures but in terms of content they are largely the same. Both have detailed rules on the composition of the executive board (*Geschäftsleitung*). The regulation for Bern-Mittelland foresees that the composition of the executive board should be balanced taking into account the size of the municipality, its geographical location, the political party and gender of the person to be elected (Article 23). Furthermore, the regulation also mentions that the rural area of the (mainly urban and peri-urban) region must be represented in the executive board. The more rural counterpart for Oberland-Ost does foresee a balanced representation of the various municipalities and lists how many representative members per sub-region (group of municipalities) should be part of the executive board (Article 22). It, however, does not include a reference to political party or gender as seen in the one for Bern-Mittelland.

Both regional conferences have a thematic focus on urban/rural regional planning with different challenges at stake. On the one hand, Oberland-Ost has an agglomeration area around Interlaken, one of the few agglomerations in the mountain region. The agglomeration Interlaken consists of several municipalities and faces particular challenges due to being an alpine city and tourist destination. In Bern-Mittelland there is also a focus on the agglomeration and rural area surrounding the bigger cities.

Another important focus for both regional conferences lays on regional development. Swiss and cantonal regional policies provide targeted support for rural and agglomeration areas, focusing on strengthening the competitiveness of the regions and increasing their value. Both conferences support the design of projects and their funding requests to the canton and submit own projects for funding. A regional development strategy has been established in Oberland-Ost, and the regional conference has the task of a coordinator between the different actors of the region implementing the strategy, in addition to its mandatory tasks. Regional development contributions have been channeled through the regional conferences mainly in the area of tourism, renewable energies and innovative offers in social or cultural areas, but less for industrial projects.

Assessment of the Practice

Looking at this practice, we can see that, first, for small (rural) municipalities, inter-municipal cooperation – with neighbors or at the regional level – can be a way to ensure an adequate level of services and quality and can be an alternative to mergers. According to their purpose, the regional conferences are adequate structures to help municipalities fulfil duties where regional coordination is needed to take regional dimensions into account. They can focus on specific issues that are deemed particularly important for the whole region. However, it seems that in both regional conferences, a regional identity is still to be developed.

Second, the regional conferences also serve to some extent to coordinate the interests and common concerns of municipalities of a certain region and defend these interests in cantonal politics and for accessing cantonal and federal regional development funds. Rural areas and small municipalities in peripheral regions might face particular challenges in communicating with the cantonal authorities, which can be overcome by joining forces in the regional

conferences. Generally, the regional conferences provide a platform for regional exchange and decision-making and thus serve as a bridge among the municipalities of the regional conference, the canton, public administration and private companies. In contrast, urban municipalities often have direct connections to authorities and private companies and may be less interested in the regional coordination.

Third, the two regional conferences that we looked at have different demographics, geographical settings, and socio-economic conditions. They have both urban, peri-urban and rural areas whose differing interests and concerns have to be balanced by the regional conferences internally, in their strategic focus and in their decision-making processes. Both regions are well aware of and address the diversity within the region. Both regions include spaces that are more marginalized than others and in need of additional economic and political support and promotion.

Fourth, in the regional conference model, regional interests are expressed and framed mainly by the municipal mayors of the regions. Space for public participation is clearly narrower than in municipal decision-making, although the impact of regional planning and zoning on municipal life might be relatively high.

Fifth, while letting municipalities decide whether they want to establish a regional conference or not, the cantonal law provides a clear guidance on the structure, mandatory competences and decision-making processes of these regional conferences. This leaves space for increased cooperation among municipalities. However, the incentives for municipalities to cooperate in the form of regional conferences does not seem to be big enough for all, since only three regional conferences out of six regional perimeters have materialized in the last 10 years (two rejections by referendum and one region still without a referendum process).

Sixth, although smaller municipalities may profit from the services offered by the regional conferences, the mode of weighed voting can make them hesitant to join the regional conference. They may fear to be overruled by bigger municipalities and their interests. On the other hand, urban centers may not always have a keen interest in regional cooperation and joining forces with weaker partners, as they may be strong enough to defend their position directly.

Seventh, it has been questioned whether the perimeters of the regional conferences are appropriate for its various topics. The 70 municipalities forming the regional conference Bern-Mittelland have commonalities and differences – depending on the topic at stake. What might be an appropriate perimeter for cooperation on traffic planning, might not be adequate for regional development.

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6. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Austria

6.1 The System of Local Government in Austria

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Types of Local Governments

The Austrian Constitution defines Austria as a federal state formed by nine *Länder*. These are further divided into districts (*Bezirke*), administrative units executing tasks for both the *Länder* and the national government, where no statutory city exists. There are, however, 15 statutory cities (*Statutarstädte*) with a special statute, combining the authority and responsibilities of a municipality and a district. Municipalities (*Gemeinden*) are granted the right to self-government as independent administrative bodies in their sphere of competence by Article 116 of the Austrian Constitution. In sum, the three relevant levels of government are the central government, *Länder* and municipal level with some exceptions such as statutory cities which are assigned responsibilities from district level as well as the Capital City of Vienna, which is a municipality and a *Land* at the same time.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The Austrian Constitution of 1920 entrenches and protects municipalities not only as local administrative units but also as institutions of self-government (Article 116(1)). However, Articles 115–20 of the Constitution also extensively predetermine the organization of municipalities, their powers and intergovernmental relations. This tight national constitutional regime reduces the complementary power of the *Länder* under Article 115(2) of the Constitution to autonomously regulate local government through their own laws (*Gemeindeordnungen*) which results in a tendency towards uniformity.

As for their responsibilities, municipalities may only act lawfully on the basis of competences that are expressly conferred upon them and circumscribed by either national or *Land* legislation. However, this legislation *must* make them responsible for ‘all matters that exclusively or preponderantly concern the local community’ and are ‘suited to performance by the community within its local boundaries’ (Article 118(2) of the Austrian Constitution). Whether national and *Land* legislators observe this rule is checked by the Constitutional Court.

The own autonomous competences of municipalities on this basis, which exist in addition to the competences delegated from the national or *Land* government, include, in particular, the following areas: traffic and transport; gas, water and electricity supply; waste collection; sewage disposal; kindergarten, parts of education; elderly care; cemeteries; and cultural and sport facilities are all within the competences of municipal administration. For providing these

public services, municipalities manage their own budget independently and can own assets of all kind and operate economic enterprises. A major share of municipal budgets comes from intragovernmental transfers, which is a complex system of re-distribution of revenues across all levels of government.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The distribution of powers is uniform for all municipalities and therefore fails to take into account differences between bigger urban and smaller rural local governments. The Austrian Constitution adheres to the ‘principle of the abstract uniform municipality’, as enshrined already in 1920. This means that, with the exceptions of the above-mentioned statutory cities and the capital Vienna,⁹⁸ all municipalities enjoy, also regarding their competences, equal legal status irrespective of variations in territorial size, population or economic and administrative capacities.

Performing the same tasks as big municipalities can be challenging for Austria’s smaller municipalities. The latter are the majority, as 55 per cent of 2,096 municipalities (in 2018) have less than 2,000 inhabitants and 88 per cent have less than 5,000 residents. Thus, Article 116(a) of the Austrian Constitution lays down the possibility for inter-municipal cooperation in the form of local authority associations (*Gemeindeverband*) to manage certain areas of responsibility such as water supply or waste management (single-purpose associations). Since 2011, the founding of multi-purpose associations (*Mehrzweckverband*) between municipalities is possible in order to go beyond coordination and centralize public service provision such as regional planning, economic development or welfare services. Even though it is legally possible, such multi-purpose associations are not very common.

Another form of cooperation is the possibility of municipalities merging into an institutionalized regional authority, the ‘territorial municipality’ (*Gebietsgemeinde*), as foreseen by Article 120 of the Constitution. The territorial municipality offers the possibility of bundling and/or controlling as many tasks as possible on a regional level, while at the same time maintaining decentralized provision of services by the individual local communities. The preservation of the local identity is guaranteed by own local mayors and municipal councils. However, this form of territorial merger (as opposed to amalgamations) is considered ‘dead law’, as it has never been put into practice.⁹⁹

Political and Social Context in Austria

⁹⁸ Vienna has different competences because it is at the same time a municipality and one of the nine *Länder* (Arts 108-112 of the Constitution).

⁹⁹ Thomas Prorok and others, ‘Struktur, Steuerung und Finanzierung von kommunalen Aufgaben in Stadtregionen’ (KDZ 2013) <<https://www.kdz.eu/de/content/struktur-steuerung-und-finanzierung-von-kommunalen-aufgaben-stadtregionen>> accessed 31 January 2020.

The two major parties, the conservative Austrian People's Party and the Social Democratic Party of Austria have historically shared the parliamentary majority, with the right-wing Austrian Freedom Party ranging on third place with a significant share of votes since the 1990s. Other smaller parties are the Green Party and the liberal NEOS party. All mentioned parties are currently represented in different levels of government with different majorities. On the local level, apart from local independent candidate lists, the majority of municipalities are still split between the People's Party and the Social Democrats. This is also reflected in the organization of municipal associations, one being the Austrian Association of Municipalities (*Gemeindebund*), which is typically associated with the conservative party and smaller rural municipalities, and the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns (*Städtebund*), being organizationally closer to the Social Democrats and representative of larger cities.¹⁰⁰ However, this differentiation should be seen in a more historical context, as many municipalities and cities are members of both associations.

As of 2018, 52 per cent of Austria's population lived in municipalities with less than 10,000 inhabitants and 48 per cent in only 86 larger towns and cities, with Vienna alone having 21 per cent of the Austrian population.

As in many countries, urban and rural areas in Austria face different social problems and demographic challenges. Regarding poverty and social exclusion, for example, residents of Austria's urban areas are more at risk than their rural counterparts because of more single parents' households and more households with no or little income.¹⁰¹ On the other hand, rural areas are confronted with out-migration especially of young people, women and highly educated people to cities. This has significant long-term effects on economic development, as well as the provision of health care and elderly care services.¹⁰²

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¹⁰⁰ The representation through either one of these associations is constitutionally regulated in Art 115(3) of the Constitution.

¹⁰¹ Österreichischer Städtebund, 'Österreichs Städte in Zahlen' (2017) 42.

¹⁰² Bundesministerium für Land- und Forstwirtschaft, Nachhaltigkeit und Wasserwirtschaft, 'Masterplan ländlicher Raum' (BMLFUW 2017).

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6.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Austria: An Introduction

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The responsibility of providing public services in most areas, such as education, health, elderly care or transport, is shared among all three levels of government. The intertwinement of public service provision and financial flows, however, is often considered complex. For a long time, a more transparent distribution of competences between all levels of government as well as organizational and financial disentanglement of public service provision is being discussed. Nevertheless, these reforms are only being implemented reluctantly, due to given constitutional federal structures.^{103 104}

Coordination Between the National Government and the *Länder*

When jointly providing public services the need for coordination and coherent actions between levels of government is considerable. Traditionally, the allocation of responsibilities is specified in agreements under private law or in the framework of simple legal regulations. To meet centralistic requirements and decentral preferences, the Constitution (Article 15(a))¹⁰⁵ provides the possibility for the national government and the *Länder* governments to enter into agreements on specified policy fields, for example in health policy¹⁰⁶ or elementary education.¹⁰⁷

Coordination Between all Three Levels of Government

Another example is the Pact on the Fiscal Equalization,¹⁰⁸ which is agreed upon between national government, *Länder* and municipalities for a time period of four to six years. In this pact the financial flows between the levels of government are settled. This affects among other tasks the rights of taxation, the distribution of revenues from the shared federal taxes and who

¹⁰³ An OECD study categorizes Austria as a state with centralized fiscal structures, which ‘tends to combine low autonomy and responsibility with a high level of co-determination and strong fiscal rules and frameworks’ for subnational governments. See Hansjörg Blöchliger and Jaroslaw Kantorowicz, ‘Fiscal Constitutions: An Empirical Assessment’ (2015) 1248 OECD Economics Department Working Papers <<https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrjctrxp8ren>> 5.

¹⁰⁴ See Helfried Bauer and Peter Biwald, ‘Governance im österreichischen Bundesstaat voranbringen’ in Helfried Bauer, Peter Biwald and Karoline Mitterer (eds), *Governance-Perspektiven in Österreichs Föderalismus. Herausforderungen und Optionen* (NWV 2019); Erich Thöni and Helfried Bauer, ‘Föderalismusreformen oder Gamsbartföderalismus in Österreich?’ in Peter Biwald and others (eds) *Nachhaltig wirken. Impulse für den öffentlichen Sektor* (NWV 2019).

¹⁰⁵ Art 15(a) agreements are guaranteed by the Constitution and were made possible in 2004 through a constitutional reform.

¹⁰⁶ Federal Ministry of Finance, ‘Zielsteuerung Gesundheit’ <<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/budget/finanzbeziehungen-laender-gemeinden/paktum-finanzausgleich-ab-2017.html>> accessed 21 February 2020.

¹⁰⁷ Agreement on Elementary Education for the Years 2018/19 to 2021/22, BGBl. I no 103/2018.

¹⁰⁸ Federal Ministry of Finance, ‘Paktum zum Finanzausgleich 2017’ <<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/budget/finanzbeziehungen-laender-gemeinden/paktum-finanzausgleich-ab-2017.html>> accessed 21 February 2020.

bears specific costs. The Pact on the Fiscal Equalization has proven to be a central element for securing the financial autonomy of all government levels, due to the fact that all stakeholders have to agree to the pact. In this process the local level also has a strong role and is represented by the two local government associations (LGAs), the Austrian Association of Municipalities (*Österreichischer Gemeindebund*) for smaller rural municipalities, and the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns (*Österreichischer Städtebund*), for middle-sized to larger cities. Ideally both associations have a joint position during the negotiations with the national and *Länder*-level. However, there are topics where a balance of interests for all sizes of municipalities is not sufficiently met, which weakens the negotiation position of the local level as a whole in this process.

Coordination Between *Länder* and Municipalities

Diverse intergovernmental relationships exist between the *Länder* and their respective municipalities. These include *Länder*-specific regulations for providing and financing public services, complex financial transfers, deployment of human resources for different services and organizational regulations. Regulation for cooperation strategies and instruments between the two levels are not common. The 2018 Regional Development Act of the *Land* of Styria¹⁰⁹ is however a recent attempt for a strategic orientation regarding regional development between the *Land*, the Styrian regions and their municipalities. Furthermore, the act stipulates tasks, instruments as well as joint distribution of resources for the development of regions.¹¹⁰ Other examples relate to reforms enforcing more cooperation on subnational level through outsourcing of organizational units as independent legal entities, regional funds, or the establishment of funds for joint service provision and financing like hospital districts in some *Länder* or the social fund in the *Land* of Vorarlberg.¹¹¹

The potential trade-off between cooperation and supervision is especially relevant for municipalities and their respective *Länder*, as the *Länder* governments are responsible for municipal supervision regarding local finances. Recent developments show that the *Länder* do not predominantly exercise control through this role, but strongly see themselves in a consulting position as well. *Länder* can also influence investments and infrastructure projects of the local level, as they manage cost contributions, financial transfers and grants for such ventures. This poses a discrepancy to the constitutional right to self-government of the municipalities, which is partly limited through the previously stated operational and financial intertwinement with the *Länder*. Therefore, there are calls for reducing these interdependencies.

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¹⁰⁹ Styrian Spatial and Regional Development Act (Steiermärkisches Landes- und Regionalentwicklungsgesetz), LGBl. no 117/2017.

¹¹⁰ Bauer and Biwald, 'Governance im österreichischen Bundesstaat voranbringen', above.

¹¹¹ *ibid.*

Bauer H and Biwald P, 'Governance im österreichischen Bundesstaat voranbringen' in Helfried Bauer, Peter Biwald and Karoline Mitterer (eds), *Governance-Perspektiven in Österreichs Föderalismus. Herausforderungen und Optionen* (NWV 2019)

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6.3 Management by Objectives in the Field of Compulsory Schooling

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Relevance of the Practice

A complex environment and increasing demands by the population increase the need for a well-coordinated service provision between all levels of government. In Austria the area of compulsory schooling is traditionally jointly provided by the national, *Länder* and local level. This area in particular shows complex operational and financial interdependencies. In the context of governance, there is a general lack of planning and coordination mechanisms as well as cross-level educational development goals and strategies.

Improved coordination and governance are essential for providing high-quality and inclusive educational services. Not only is vertical coordination necessary, but also a horizontal one between municipalities, as there are significant differences in the challenges in compulsory schooling that rural local governments (RLGs) and urban local governments (ULGs) face. Rural areas with population loss are struggling to maintain basic educational services while urban spaces must cope with additional strains to the educational system due to a high share of children from a migrant background and/or from families facing difficult social circumstances. The current resource allocation within the school locations is not modified to the different needs. Thus, improving governance by taking into consideration the urban-rural interplay is of great importance.¹¹²

Description of the Practice

There is a diversity of tasks in the area of compulsory schooling that need to be fulfilled by all levels of government.¹¹³ The competencies listed here only refer to general compulsory schooling. In Austria, at the age of 10, there is also the possibility to change to an academic secondary school (*Allgemein bildende höhere Schule*), which is the sole competence of the national government. About two thirds of the school children aged 10 and over attend the general compulsory schools that are of shared competencies.

The following list gives an overview of actors and their roles:

- legislative power generally lies with the national government. However, the *Länder* can enact their own laws on implementation, which results in differences in the organizational structures of schools between the *Länder*;

¹¹² Karoline Mitterer, Nikola Hochholdinger and Marion Seisenbacher, 'Leistungs- und wirkungsbezogene Pflichtschulfinanzierung' (KDZ 2019).

¹¹³ Karoline Mitterer and Marion Seisenbacher, 'Fact Sheets - Pflichtschule und Tagesbetreuung' (KDZ 2019); Mitterer, Hochholdinger and Seisenbacher, 'Leistungs- und wirkungsbezogene Pflichtschulfinanzierung'.

- the newly established Education Directorates (*Bildungsdirektionen*) present a joint agency of the national and *Länder* governments. They are responsible for governing, administrating and supervising schools;
- the teaching and administrative staff as well as support staff are provided and managed by the *Länder*, but largely paid by the national government via financial transfers to the *Länder*;
- staff for facility management and maintenance for schools is provided and managed by municipalities. The local level is also responsible for transport services and school physicians;
- supervised leisure activities within school hours, extracurricular activities and holiday care are to be provided and organized by the local level;

Overall, there are complex interdependencies between all actors in task fulfillment and financing, which hampers the effective governance of the educational sector. Reducing the complexity through government reforms have not led to significant improvements. The 2017 Education Reform Act has taken steps towards more clarity in this interdependent structure, such as concentrating tasks and responsibilities in newly created Education Directorates as well as the establishment of Education Regions. Both instruments have the potential to improve multi-level governance.

Education Directorates

With the 2017 Education Reform Act the Education Directorates were created as joint authorities for the overall schooling sector, where administrative tasks of the national government (responsible for federal schools) and the *Länder* (responsible for general compulsory schooling) were merged. Up until the reform, two separate administrative entities co-existed. The tasks of these new joint authorities are to execute school legislation (such as supervision and quality control), combined human resource management for teachers employed by both levels of government, to strategically plan school locations and organization, as well as managing school psychology services.¹¹⁴ Another important aspect is the coordination with municipalities, who are responsible for maintenance of the school infrastructure and facilities.

Since the Education Directorates are still in the implementation process, it is not yet possible to assess if new types of cooperation have actually occurred.

Education Regions

The Education Regions¹¹⁵ are a regional coordination platform and managing unit for cooperation between actors of the educational system. Austria currently has 31 Education Regions with the key element being the respective regional educational development plan. The overall goal is to supply educational and day-care services as well as to expand all-day school forms, all of which are adequate, coordinated and based on the regional needs. Some examples are:

- development of educational quality across different school locations;

¹¹⁴ Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research BMBWF, 'Steuerung des Schulsystems in Österreich' (white book, BMBWF 2019).

¹¹⁵ *ibid.*

- cooperation between all schools or school clusters in a region in order to identify and use structural, organizational and pedagogical synergies;
- evidence-based analysis and design for smoother transitions to higher school levels or different types of schools;
- cooperation between schools and the regional environment (educational and counseling institutions, private sector, labor market services, health and social services, associations, child and youth welfare as well as civil society initiatives) - so far, this was primarily organized by municipal governments and / or social welfare organizations;
- training support and professionalization of schools and teachers.

As the implementation of these coordination strategies are still in an early stage, an assessment of the effects cannot yet be made.

Different Conditions in Urban and Rural Areas

The requirements in urban and rural areas are different and also affect the range of services provided. The average school size (number of classes per school) increases with the size and centrality of the municipality. This means there are smaller schools in RLGs and larger schools in ULGs. While there are four classes in an average elementary school in rural areas, there are twice as many in urban areas. The class size (students per class) is smaller in rural areas than in urban areas. Taking primary schools as an example, this means that the average class size in urban areas is larger by two students than in rural areas. This is also due to the fact there are many micro schools in RLGs with even smaller classes, which lower the average. In contrast, ULGs have a higher capacity utilization.¹¹⁶

Immigration mainly takes place in urban regions. Especially in cities with more than 20,000 inhabitants, there is a high proportion of pupils with non-German colloquial language. Here the proportion is 4 to 5 times higher than in the municipalities up to 5,000 inhabitants. This indicator indirectly shows a greatly increased risk of early school leaving for young people in cities if there is no appropriate language support or integrative and accompanying measures.¹¹⁷

Assessment of the Practice

A key success factor for the educational system is an improved multi-level governance approach. Currently there are no appropriate mechanisms for all levels of government to better coordinate their contributions and responsibilities. An interesting proposition of the new national government is planned for elementary education (children until age 6). An advisory committee is to be installed in order to determine a common framework, for example in quality standards, trainings and transition to higher school levels. Next to representatives of all levels of government, NGOs and education experts are to be included in such a committee.¹¹⁸ For compulsory schooling on the other hand, there is no such solution planned

¹¹⁶ Mitterer, Hochholdinger and Seisenbacher, 'Leistungs- und wirkungsbezogene Pflichtschulfinanzierung', above.

¹¹⁷ Bifie, 'Nationaler Bildungsbericht 2018' (Bifie and BMBWF 2018).

¹¹⁸ 'Aus Verantwortung für Österreich. Regierungsprogramm 2020–2024' (Bundeskanzleramt Österreich 2020).

yet. Rather, the last educational reform in 2017 showed that the involvement of the local level was insufficient. It is still open to what extent the above-mentioned Educational Regions will lead to an improvement in multi-level governance.

A further success factor would be cross-level management by objectives. This means that the national government, *Länder* and municipalities collectively agree on outcome-orientated goals and define the appropriate measures in line with the competences of each governmental level. Currently this coordination mechanism is not in place and would be necessary to avoid competing measures and financial dependencies.¹¹⁹

There is an ongoing discussion in the framework of fiscal equalization for many years regarding the funding for public responsibilities such as the area of compulsory schooling. This is to ensure that municipalities in rural and urban areas facing different challenges (school and class sizes, number of pupils with migration background) are guaranteed the appropriate means to provide high-quality educational services. In the last fiscal equalization negotiations in 2017, a pilot project for the compulsory school sector was agreed upon. Ultimately, however, this failed due to the unsuccessful reconciliation of interests between the actors, especially between rural and urban areas.¹²⁰

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¹¹⁹ Mitterer, Hochholdinger and Seisenbacher, 'Leistungs- und wirkungsbezogene Pflichtschulfinanzierung', above.

¹²⁰ Karoline Mitterer, 'Aufgabenorientierter Finanzausgleich aus der Governance-Perspektive' in Helfried Bauer, Peter Biwald and Karoline Mitterer (eds), *Governance-Perspektiven in Österreichs Föderalismus. Herausforderungen und Optionen* (NWV 2019) 110.

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6.4 INKOBA: Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria

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Relevance of the Practice

For many individual local governments (LGs) increasing the attractiveness of local building land to companies constitutes a significant challenge. Particularly small LGs often struggle to make large sites available for companies, i.e. to provide the necessary infrastructure and also efficient marketing due to their limited financial resources.

For this reason, the *Land* Upper Austria has launched the INKOBA Initiative in 2001 to economically stimulate the locations in particularly peripheral regions of Upper Austria. Several municipalities join to form a *Gemeindeverband* (municipal association) to develop and promote business locations as partners. This form of cooperation contributes to bridging the gap between smaller and larger, rural and urban municipalities: It reduces the competitive pressure in the provision of business locations between LGs and enables especially financially weaker LGs to benefit from the combination of efforts with other LGs in the region. Due to the crucial role of the *Land* in actively promoting INKOBAS, the INKOBA model of the *Land* Upper Austria, organized in *Gemeindeverbänden*, cannot only be considered a good-practice example for inter-municipal cooperation in the securing of business locations but also for successful intergovernmental relations between the regional and local level, since the initiative is supported by clear provisions of the *Land*, such as the demand for increased cooperation and inter-governmental dialogue, as well as a comprehensive system of incentives both financially and non-financially. The latter through permanent support by the Upper Austrian business agency. Due to this practice's financial scheme (sharing of municipal tax between the LGs involved in the INKOBA) and the model of cooperation between the LGs in a *Gemeindeverband*, the practice is related to report section 3 on local finances as well as section 4 on local government structure.

Description of the Practice

Business Upper Austria (formerly *Technologie- und Marketinggesellschaft* – TMG), the business agency of the *Land* of Upper Austria, has been promoting inter-municipal cooperation since the mid-1990s. INKOBA (*Interkommunale Betriebsansiedelung*) was established with the main goal of attracting companies to the region and thus creating jobs. An INKOBA-*Gemeindeverband* is formed by several municipalities (according to the *OÖ Gemeindeverbandgesetz*, Upper Austria's Municipal Associations Act). One municipality then prepares a building site for its use by one or more companies as business locations. Both, the

cost for the preparation and provision of adequate infrastructure as well as the taxes earned from the companies' activities (municipal tax) are shared between the involved municipalities.

Thereby, the optimal framework conditions for the companies as well as the cooperation among the municipalities are ensured in order to increasingly strengthen the business location through joint efforts. Since 2001, 30 such corporations were established through INKOBA, 28 of which are currently active and 2 are in development. 69 per cent of all local governments in Upper Austria participate in this initiative. Although the INKOBA initiative does not explicitly exclude large Upper Austrian cities INKOBAs comprises in general smaller and medium-sized municipalities in less developed regions. However, for urban agglomerations there are other initiatives of the *Land* that target these areas such as the 'Power Region Initiative' or the 'City Region Initiative'.

Business Upper Austria is an outsourced *GmbH* (Ltd.) of the *Land Oberösterreich* (Upper Austria). As majority owner,¹²¹ the Land controls the company both at the level of the company bodies and at the process level. In addition, and in order to be able to ensure the range of services in the long term, Business Upper Austria is granted an annual subsidy by the Land Upper Austria to cover the annual deficit. Business Upper Austria accompanies the INKOBAs in the development process and provide further assistance and advice. The INKOBAs themselves are legal entities, mostly established according to the *Oberösterreichisches Gemeindeverbandgesetz* (Upper Austrian Municipal Associations Act) as so-called *Gemeindeverbände* (municipal associations).¹²² Although they operate outside of the control of the municipal council, as public bodies they are subject to more transparency and oversight as well as to a higher degree of liability/bindingness regarding its decisions. Thus, it can be considered a more democratic model than e.g. a *GmbH* (Ltd.) or *Verein* (association) and may better reflect processes of intergovernmental dialogue between the local level and the *Länder*. Because the INKOBA initiative is managed by Business Upper Austria, INKOBAs also have the support of the *Land Oberösterreich*.

This is the central advantage of INKOBA compared to other business locations. Due to the joint funding as well as the support of the *Land*, the sites are in optimal condition when a company inquires. The INKOBA initiative is characterized by an efficient combination of bottom-up and top-down processes, as the *Land Oberösterreich* actively incentivizes with subsidies for setting up inter-municipal cooperation and supports the cooperation, mainly through its business agency Business Upper Austria as mentioned above.

There are no noticeable differences between INKOBAS which include more urban local governments (ULGs) or rural local governments (RLGs), because the entire region benefits from these projects. In addition to the direct effects of the additional tax revenue (municipal

¹²¹ OÖ Landesholding GmbH (65%), Kammer für Arbeiter und Angestellte für Oberösterreich (15%), Wirtschaftskammer Oberösterreich (15%), Vereinigung der Österreichischen Industrie Landesgruppe Oberösterreich (5%).

¹²² There are also inter-communal business locations in other *Länder* which, due to the different legal provisions across the *Länder* regarding the establishment of a *Gemeindeverband* between LGs, were founded as a *Verein* (association) or *GmbH* (Ltd., e.g. in Carinthia). Realising and managing investments inter-municipally is less complex and bureaucratic in a *Verein* or *GmbH*. Therefore, such inter-municipal cooperation models in Austria are commonly used for cross-border cooperation between LGs of different *Länder*.

tax, property tax, etc.) for the municipalities, the business locations can also be expected to cause positive agglomeration effects such as influx and increased purchasing power for the entire region. However, in addition to the higher income (e.g. municipal tax, income shares, etc.), rising expenses in infrastructure costs can also be expected. INKOBAs between urban and rural LGs may offer an additional advantage for all involved LGs: Larger municipalities and medium sized cities often lack available building land within their territory, but on the other hand may bring increased know-how and marketing expertise into the cooperation, also due to more personal resources and capacities.

The district Rohrbach in *Oberösterreich* is a very good example for successful regional management. The *Donau-Ameisberg* INKOBA business park was founded in 2003 and is developing into a real model for success. Renowned as well as newly founded companies have settled and, so far, created 150 jobs, both strengthening the region's economy and preventing emigration.

In the future, more cross-border *Gemeindeverbände* for INKOBA projects are to be established. The INKOBA *Inneres Salzkammergut*, joining together 7 LGs from Upper Austria and 2 LGs from Salzburg, serves as role model for further cross-border INKOBAS.

In conclusion, INKOBA projects benefit both rural and urban LGs and cushions the urban-rural divide. The financial risk is divided and through the distribution of municipal tax revenues, the competition between local governments in the provision of high-quality business locations is reduced to the benefit of all while, on the other hand, the negotiating position of the LGs towards economic actors is strengthened. Through cooperation and joint efforts, INKOBAs contribute to a win-win situation for all involved local governments.

Assessment of the Practice

Inter-municipal cooperation in the area of business settlements enables the equal distribution of the benefits and burdens between the municipalities, which subsequently profit from increased attractiveness and competitiveness in relation to other regions. INKOBA is a good example for successful and practice-oriented inter-governmental dialogue, in which both the local governments as well as the *Land* play central roles and are in steady exchange, supported by the Business Upper Austria agency as intermediary.

However, there are several factors which influence the success or failure of INKOBAs and equally affect rural and urban municipalities. Establishing an INKOBA cooperation in a *Gemeindeverband* holds the advantage of a higher degree of liability but also entails a more difficult and time-consuming set-up process, which requires, among others, a resolution of the involved municipal councils. The intermediary role and support of the *Land* and the Business Upper Austria agency in the process are therefore pivotal. The *Land* provides subsidies for the establishment of inter-municipal cooperation and supervises the INKOBA associations. The supervision of the associations is incumbent upon the provisions of Article 22 of the Upper Austria Municipal Association Act (*Oberösterreichisches Gemeindeverbändegesetz*).¹²³ For the

¹²³ LGBl. no 51/1988 (GP XXIII RV 102 AB 186/1988 LT 25).

management of assets and budget management of the association, Article 20 of the Upper Austria Municipal Association Act applies. The Business Upper Austria's support for INKOBAS on the other hand, includes setting up both the association structure and management structure, providing relevant technical know-how for chairmen and managing directors, providing up-to date information on legal issues, infrastructure facilities and financing, drawing up contracts to secure land, establishing and maintaining contact with *Länder* institutions, in particular with political advisers and specialist departments.

The lack of full legal obligation in connection with remaining competitive pressure or developmental gaps between municipalities of an INKOBAs has also led to some issues in the past. It has occurred, for example, that despite their membership in an INKOBAs, an involved LG independently developed and sold their own building land, directly competing with the jointly defined building site.

The potentials of the Upper Austrian INKOBAs cooperation model can be summarized as follows:

- opportunities for growth through increased economic strength in the region;
- creation of additional jobs (direct/indirect);
- positive effects on the choice of residence in the region – especially for the LGs surrounding the company locations;
- shared financing of joint activities may reduce the individual costs for every LG involved, while shared revenues benefit all LGs involved;
- development of attractive business locations and coordinated regional support policies;
- professional location marketing;
- bundling of competences and relieving the pressure on the individual LGs.

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6.5 Austrian Conference of Spatial Planning: ÖROK

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Relevance of the Practice

In Austria, the *Länder* (subnational level), are responsible for the legislation within the field of spatial planning. Nevertheless, the planning system in Austria is rather complex and strongly differentiated.¹²⁴ As a cross-sectional policy many different authorities on all government levels – national, regional and local – are dealing with planning tasks. Local governments in Austria are playing a crucial role in spatial planning since they are responsible for the local development planning within their own competences. Other tasks are shared competencies between two or more governmental levels. Consequently, there is an urgent and huge need for intergovernmental communication, coordination and cooperation. As there is no framework legislation on the federal level, the organization of the Austrian Conference of Spatial Planning (ÖROK), which was founded and established in 1971 by the federal government, the *Länder* and the municipalities, serves as the central intergovernmental communication and coordination platform in the area of spatial planning. Both local government associations – the Association of Cities and Towns and the Austrian Association of Municipalities – are equal and full members of the political decision-making body of the ÖROK. The ÖROK is connecting all three governance levels including the heads of the social and economic partners with a consulting vote. Hence, the conference is an instrument of cooperation and partnership across sectors and levels of government.

Furthermore, the ÖROK is focusing in its recent activities on many specific problems connected with the urban-rural disparities and interplay. First, the project ‘Strengthening Regional Governance’¹²⁵ was built on the results of the ÖREK¹²⁶-partnership published as ÖROK-recommendations¹²⁷ and aimed at making further preparatory steps towards cooperative governance of functional regions and to foster urban-rural linkages. Second, the development of Austria’s urban regions is another long-term core subject of the ÖROK which was also driven by an ÖREK-partnership called ‘Cooperation Platform Urban Regions’ resulting in the roadmap for implementing the ‘Austrian **Agenda Urban Regions**’¹²⁸ and the recommendation

¹²⁴ Markus Gruber, Arthur Kanonier, Simon Pohn-Weidinger and Arthur Schindelegger, ‘Raumordnung in Österreich und Bezüge zur Raumentwicklung und Regionalpolitik’ (publication series no 202, ÖROK 2018) 10.

¹²⁵ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, ‘Die regionale Handlungsebene stärken – Status, Impulse und Perspektiven’ (publication series no 208, ÖROK 2020).

¹²⁶ ÖREK, Austrian Spatial Development Concept.

¹²⁷ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, ‘ÖREK-Partnerschaft Regionale Handlungsebene stärken – Fachliche Empfehlungen und Materialienband’ (publication series no 194, ÖROK 2015).

¹²⁸ Österreichisches Raumentwicklungskonzept ÖREK, ‘Roadmap zur Umsetzung der “Agenda Stadtregionen in Österreich”’ (ÖREK 2017)

<https://www.stadtregionen.at/uploads/files/RoadmapAgendaStadtregionen_FINAL.pdf> accessed 2 August 2019.

‘For an Austrian Policy for Urban Regions’.¹²⁹ In addition, the *Österreichische Stadtregionstag* was initiated and established as permanent exchange platform since 2013 hosted by the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns. And third, because of its thematic focus on ‘Strategies for regions with population decline’. All these activities support both urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs) to cope with spatial challenges jointly and bundle municipal resources in functional areas. The practice is related to report section 2 on local responsibilities, section 3 on local finances and section 4 on local government structure as only coordinated spatial planning between all levels of government ensures sustainable regional and local development and thus contributes to good service delivery, solid public finances and effective administrative and territorial reforms.

Description of the Practice

According to the main purpose – the multi-level and cross-sectoral coordination in the area of spatial planning and regional policy – the work of the ÖROK is threefold:¹³⁰

- spatial planning and development;
- regional policy;
- national contact point for EU-structural funds programs.

One of the core tasks of the ÖROK in the field of spatial planning and development is the elaboration of a common overall and nationwide strategy based on a consensual agreement of all partners: The current Austrian Spatial Development Concept (ÖREK)¹³¹ was published in 2011 and covers a planning period of ten years being a long lasting integrative, multi-level and cross-sectoral process where all partners work together in different thematic working groups. The ÖREK- Partnerships were established in order to implement the guidelines of the ÖREK. Although the Austrian Spatial Development Concept is not legally binding, it serves as the key guiding principle for all planning authorities in Austria. The elaboration of the ÖREK builds upon an intensive dialogue involving all members of the ÖROK and many other actors relevant for the spatial development and is accompanied by research work. For example, in the framework of the ÖREK 2030¹³² process experts, planners and decision-makers discussed in the setting of conferences the future spatial development in Austria as well as the challenges and possible solutions at local, regional and federal level. In addition, the process was accompanied by a think tank made up of international and national experts from a wide variety of space-relevant specialist areas. A special feature of the ÖREK 2030 was the participation of so-called ‘Young Experts’. Analyses and study elaboration are other important tasks of the ÖROK. With the ÖROK Publication Series, the ÖROK Recommendations and the ÖROK Atlas as part of the Regional Monitoring System, the organization of the ÖROK provides important planning

¹²⁹ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, ‘ÖROK-Empfehlung Nr. 55 Für eine Stadtregionpolitik in Österreich’ (ÖROK 2017).

¹³⁰ See ‘Aufgaben und Produkte’ (ÖROK, 2021) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/oerok/aufgaben-und-produkte>>.

¹³¹ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, ‘Österreichisches Raumentwicklungskonzept (ÖREK) 2011’ (ÖROK 2011) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/raum/oesterreichisches-raumentwicklungskonzept/oerek-2011>>.

¹³² Österreichisches Raumentwicklungskonzept 2030, <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/oerek-2030>>.

materials for Austria's spatial development policy such as for example the ÖROK Forecasts. Furthermore, the Austrian Spatial Planning Report¹³³ is published by the ÖROK in regular three-year intervals. Additionally, and with regard to the implementation of the EU structural funds in Austria, the ÖROK supports the strategical EU-programming process on national level ('Partnership Agreement Strat.at 2020') and hosts the Austrian management authority for the Investment for Growth and Jobs/ERDF program 2014-2020.¹³⁴ Within the framework of European Territorial Cooperation, the ÖROK is serving as National Contact Point for promoting the respective EU-programs and provides support both for potential applicants and grantees.

As a multi-level organization, the ÖROK integrates representatives of all of its partners within its permanent bodies.¹³⁵ On the political level, the ÖROK is comprised of the Austrian Chancellor, the federal ministers, the provincial governors (*Landeshauptleute*), the presidents of the Association of Cities and Towns and the Austrian Association of Municipalities, the social and economic partners.¹³⁶ On the administrative level there is the Commission of Deputies¹³⁷ which is functioning as a preparatory organ for the political conference. The Standing Sub-Committee is responsible for the ÖREK, the ÖROK studies and publications and the ÖROK-Atlas. Furthermore, the Sub-Committee Regional Economy is acting as a coordination platform for all issues concerning the regional policy of the EU and its implementation in Austria. And finally, there is a national committee for the transnational and interregional cooperation and network programs.

Assessment of the Practice

In Austria there is a long tradition of balancing out different interests within an intensive multi-lateral dialogue and partnership agreements (e.g. social partnership). Although the recommendations of the ÖROK are not legally binding, the work and activities of this multi-level organization have a crucial impact on the relationships and planning praxis of all authorities by improving the intergovernmental dialogue and providing various planning tools and materials. During the last decades the ÖROK has set up an effective and efficient communication and cooperation system¹³⁸ where all partners – the UGLs as well as the RGLs

¹³³ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, '15. Raumordnungsbericht Analysen und Berichte zur räumlichen Entwicklung Österreichs 2015-2017' (publication series no 204, ÖROK 2018).

¹³⁴ See Johannes Roßbacher and Markus Seidl, 'Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning' (ÖROK undated) <https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder/1.OEROK/OEROK_Folder_EN.pdf>.

¹³⁵ Gruber and others, 'Raumordnung in Österreich und Bezüge zur Raumentwicklung und Regionalpolitik', above, 66.

¹³⁶ The social partnership in Austria comprises four associations at the federal level: on the employers' side the Austrian Chamber of Commerce (WKÖ) and the Austrian Chamber of Agriculture (LKÖ), on the employee side the Federal Chamber of Labor (BAK) and the Austrian Trade Union Confederation (ÖGB). The social partnership has an advisory function. See 'Sozialpartner. Was ist das?' (*Die Sozialpartnerschaft Österreich*, 2015) <https://www.sozialpartner.at/?page_id=127>.

¹³⁷ The Commission of Deputies is consisting of the section leaders, the directors of the provincial government offices, the secretary generals including different committees and working groups.

¹³⁸ Gruber and others, 'Raumordnung in Österreich und Bezüge zur Raumentwicklung und Regionalpolitik', above, 12.

– are treated equally. With several formal bodies¹³⁹ and many other soft (informal) formats the ÖROK has initiated a lot of different processes and developed some good working mechanisms of cooperation, strengthening the intergovernmental relations and giving all municipalities a voice at the national level concerning the spatial development. The ÖROK has succeeded in overcoming administrative borders especially between the Austrian *Länder* and between urban and sub-urban regions. It is acting as a permanent interface picking up new topics both bottom-up and top-down and addressing especially the problems connected with the urban-rural disparities and the regional interplay. Therefore, the ÖROK is strengthening the local level by supporting the needs of the urban and rural municipalities not only within its intergovernmental dialogue and by involving them into the elaboration and implementation of the overall Austrian planning strategy. The information and communication forums offered by the ÖROK and in particular the ÖREK-partnerships are very much appreciated and highly valued by all parties for the creation of a common understanding and of concrete implementations.¹⁴⁰ This can also be seen as the resulting products of the ÖROK – the monitoring system as well as their publications and planning materials – are often used as a crucial background information for political decisions (e.g. population prognosis).

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¹³⁹ e.g. Commission of Deputies, ÖREK Partnerships, working groups, etc.

¹⁴⁰ Gruber and others, ‘Raumordnung in Österreich und Bezüge zur Raumentwicklung und Regionalpolitik’, above, 45.

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7. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland

7.1 The System of Local Government in Poland

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Types of Local Governments

Poland is a unitary state without any autonomous entities. As a consequence, a uniform system of territorial self-government exists throughout Poland. The traditions of territorial self-government date back to 1918 when, after 123 years of political oblivion, the Polish state was established. After World War II, Poland was an undemocratic and centralized state which led to, among other things, the liquidation of territorial self-government. The reconstruction of territorial self-government began in Poland with the political transformation after 1989. The first stage was the restoration of territorial self-government in communes (*gmina*) in 1990, then in 1999 the self-government in counties (*powiat*) and in voivodeships (*województwo*) was introduced.

The current Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997 introduces two types of territorial self-government, namely *local* self-government and *regional* self-government (Article 164). Currently in Poland (since 1999), territorial self-government is three-tier and it is structured as follows:

- self-government in communes as the basic level of local self-government;
- self-government in counties the second level of local self-government;
- self-government in voivodeships as regional self-government.

In addition, large municipalities (over 100,000 residents) may be granted the status and tasks of a counties (city with *powiat* rights/cities with *powiat* status).

Therefore, there are four levels of political representation in Poland: the state and three levels of territorial self-government.

At present (2020), there are 2,477 communes (*gmina*), including 1,555 rural *gminas*, 621 urban-rural *gminas* and 302 urban *gminas*. The population of *gminas* ranges from 1.7 million (the Capital City of Warsaw) to 1,300, and the average population of a Polish *gmina* amounts to 15,000. It means that in the comparison to other European countries, Poland's *gminas* are relatively large. If we take into account only urban *gminas*, the average population is 61,000, whereas in rural *gminas* the average population amounts to approximately 7,000. At the beginning of the political transformation in Poland in 1990, there were 2,383 *gminas*. It means that modifications introduced in the division into *gminas* have been rather minor.

Figure 1: Spatial delimitation of *gminas* in Poland¹⁴¹

The second tier of the local government, i.e. the level of counties (*powiat*), was established in Poland in 1999. At present, there are 314 *powiats* and 66 cities with *powiat* status. The population of *powiats* range from 21,500 to 373,500. The average population of a Polish *powiat* amounts to 82,000, whereas cities with *powiat* status have on average 191,000 inhabitants. When the territorial reform was being prepared in 1999, it was the establishment of *powiats* (as intermediate units between *gmina* and voivodeship) which gave rise to the greatest controversies. Dissenting voices against the introduction of an additional level of territorial structure (and, in consequence, a local government unit) were not rare. Even now the issue of *powiats* is under public debate, mainly due to the problem of the financing of *powiat* local government as well as functional weakness of smaller *powiats* (Polish *powiats* are small units in comparison to their counterparts in other European countries). The formation of seven new *powiats* in 2002 was the last major modification in the map of *powiats*.

The third level of territorial structure applies to voivodeships (*województwo*). The voivodeships correspond to the NUTS-2 regions (according to the European Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics),¹⁴² which are the basis for regional operational programs co-financed by

¹⁴¹ 'Types of *gminas* and urban and rural areas' (*Statistics Poland*, 2020) <<https://stat.gov.pl/en/regional-statistics/classification-of-territorial-units/administrative-division-of-poland/types-of-gminas-and-urban-and-rural-areas/>> accessed 2 November 2019.

¹⁴² Eurostat, 'Background' <<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>> accessed 2 November 2019.

the European Union. The year 1999 marked a crucial point in shaping the territory and political system of voivodeships. After lengthy preparations accompanied by political disputes, it was decided to form 16 voivodeships. It meant a departure from territorial fragmentation on a regional level (in the years 1975-1999 there were as many as 49 voivodeships in Poland). As a result of an enlarged territory, voivodeships as regions gained the right to self-government—thus, another stage of decentralization of Poland was reached. So far, the number of voivodeships has not been changed.¹⁴³

Legal Status of Local Governments

The inclusion of the principle of subsidiarity¹⁴⁴ in the preamble to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997 and the principle of decentralization¹⁴⁵ in the first chapter of the Constitution is of key importance for the legal status of self-government in Poland. Article 16 provides legal guarantees for local authorities: '(i) The inhabitants of the units of basic territorial division shall form a self-governing community in accordance with law. (ii) Local government shall participate in the exercise of public power. The substantial part of public duties which local government is empowered to discharge by statute shall be done in its own name and under its own responsibility.'

A comprehensive regulation concerning territorial self-government is contained in Chapter VII ('Local government') of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997.

Territorial self-government is based on democratic legitimacy. At each level, residents elect a representative body (the number of councilors currently ranges from 15 to 51, with the exception of Warsaw with 60 councilors). In addition, the head of the executive body (mayor) has been elected directly by the residents at the *gmina* level since 2002. Moreover, the Constitution of Poland guarantees residents of *gminas*, *powiats* and voivodeships the right to directly settle matters through the institution of a local referendum. A referendum on self-taxation of residents for public purposes is a special type of the local referendum. However, such a referendum can only be held at the *gmina* level.

Local government shall perform public tasks not reserved by the Constitution or statutes to the organs of other public authorities (Article 163 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997). *Gmina* self-government, which has been granted the presumption of competence in matters of territorial self-government, is of fundamental importance. Article 164 establishes the following: '(i) The commune (*gmina*) shall be the basic unit of local government. (ii) Other units of regional and/or local government shall be specified by statute. (iii) The commune shall perform all tasks of local government not reserved to other units of local government.'

¹⁴³ Mirska Andželika, 'State policy on the formation and modernisation of Polish territorial structure' in Europäisches Zentrum für Föderalismus-Forschung Tübingen EZFF (ed), *Jahrbuch des Föderalismus 2018: Föderalismus, Subsidiarität und Regionen in Europa* (Nomos 2018).

¹⁴⁴ 'Hereby establish this Constitution of the Republic of Poland as the basic law for the State, based on respect for freedom and justice, cooperation between the public powers, social dialogue as well as on the principle of subsidiarity in the strengthening the powers of citizens and their communities'.

¹⁴⁵ Article 15: 'The territorial system of the Republic of Poland shall ensure the decentralization of public power'.

Territorial self-government units are subject to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and the Acts of the Polish State. Three system acts are of fundamental importance:

- the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government,
- the Act of 5 June 1998 on *Powiat* Self-Government,
- the Act of 5 June 1998 on Voivodeship Self-Government.

The only criterion of supervision over the activity of self-government is the criterion of legality, supervision is exercised by government administration authorities (the Prime Minister, voivodes¹⁴⁶ and regarding financial matters - regional audit chambers). However, any disputes between the government administration and territorial self-government shall be settled by an administrative court. There are no authoritative interrelations between the tiers of territorial self-government – only voluntary cooperation is possible.

The Constitution divides public tasks performed by self-government into own tasks (financed from the budget of a self-government unit) and commissioned tasks (financed from the state budget).

Gmina self-government performs a wide range of public tasks which include, among others, issues related to local technical infrastructure, social infrastructure, education, health and order protection and safety. In accordance with the principle of subsidiarity, the *powiat* self-government 'assists' *gmina* in performing local tasks that exceed the capacity of a *gmina* ('supra-communal' local tasks). While the self-government of *gmina* and *powiat* implements a number of public services for local communities on an ongoing basis, the main role of voivodeship self-government is to facilitate economic development of regions. Among other things, the task of the voivodeship self-government is to manage EU structural funds.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

There are three types of *gminas*:

- urban *gminas* (their boundaries correspond with the boundaries of the city forming the municipality);
- urban-rural *gminas*, which include both cities within administrative boundaries and areas outside city boundaries;
- rural *gminas* without cities within their territory.

Cities in Poland are towns and cities with city rights (granted by the central government). However, it is a formal classification based solely on an administrative criterion. The Act on *Gmina* Self-Government does not differentiate the tasks of according to this classification – all *gminas* have the same scope of activity. The exceptions are large urban *gminas* which also have the status of *powiat* (city with *powiat* rights). They carry out the tasks of both *gmina* and *powiat*. Currently, there are 66 of them and the general criterion for their establishment is a

¹⁴⁶ The voivodes (16) shall be the representative of the Council of Ministers in voivodeships. They are appointed by the Prime Minister. *Voivodeships* are the highest-level administrative subdivision of Poland.

population over 100,000. However, some local government politicians claim that this threshold should be reduced to 50,000¹⁴⁷.

On the other hand, the need is recognized to merge the cities with the *powiat* rights and *powiats* whose authorities are seated in the said cities due to significant disproportions in the institutional potential of *powiats*. Government analyses indicated a significantly higher potential of cities with *powiat* rights and a particularly low potential of *powiats* without large urban centers. The data show that *powiats* without large cities have significantly scarcer resources allocated to the fulfilment of public tasks of *powiats*¹⁴⁸.

Public tasks may be performed by individual self-government units independently or by way of cooperation with other self-government units (inter-municipal cooperatives). Self-governments of a given level may cooperate with each other (cooperation between *gminas*, between *powiats*, between voivodeships). Moreover, cooperation between the levels is also possible: since 2016, unions of *powiats* and *gminas* may be established. The form of the *powiat-gmina* union is intended for the implementation of tasks that exceed the competence of one tier of self-government. The aim was to enhance the independence and operational flexibility of territorial self-government units. It can also be interpreted as an attempt to address the problems occurring mainly in metropolitan areas.

The legal form of the union of *gminas* (union of *powiats*, union of *gmina* and *powiat*) requires the establishment of a new legal person to perform part of the tasks of the self-government. Unions of *gminas* are a very popular form of performing self-government tasks (currently there are 313 of them in Poland and they include from 2 to 49 *gminas*). There are 7 *powiat* unions and 8 *powiat-gmina* unions. Their tasks involve mainly the organization of common local public transport. The same applies to education as only a uniform system of education from primary schools (which is the responsibility of *gminas*) to secondary schools (which are subject to *powiats*) can resolve demographic problems or fulfil the expectations of the local labor market.

The performed public tasks may also be modified through 'delegating' public tasks by a territorial self-government unit to another territorial self-government unit. This is done by way of a voluntary agreement.

'Commissioning' tasks to the self-government by the government administration is a different matter – if they are commissioned by virtue of the law, they are imposed on the self-government 'from the top' (together, of course, with financial resources from the Polish state budget). Polish self-governments indicate that those funds are often insufficient.

¹⁴⁷ 'Interpelacja nr 5867 do Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji' (*Sejm Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*) <<http://orka2.sejm.gov.pl/IZ5.nsf/main/2AE373E5>> accessed 1 July 2019.

¹⁴⁸ 'Zasadniczy, trójstopniowy podział terytorialny państwa' (*Ministerstwo Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji*, 31 May 2001) <<https://archiwum.mswia.gov.pl/pl/aktualnosci/1644,dok.html>> accessed 1 July 2019.

Political and Social Context in Poland

Compared to other countries, the national political parties are in Poland not very strongly represented at the local government level.¹⁴⁹ To gain a stronger voice, self-governments attempted to create a nationwide political movement of mayors of large cities. For example, in 2011 Union of Mayors – Citizens to the Senate¹⁵⁰ (*Unia Prezydentów – Obywatele do Senatu*) was established and it put forward its candidates in the elections to the upper house of the Polish Parliament – Senate (majority voting system applies). The Local Government Movement ‘Non-Partisans’ (*Ruch Samorządowy ‘Bezpartyjni’*) was also established, consisting of mayors and councilors. The purpose of the movement is to be an alternative to political parties in local government elections (primarily at the level of the voivodeship self-government).

However, if we analyze the results of local government elections, the influence of national political parties clearly diminishes, the lower the level of government. Starting from the highest level, i.e. the 16 voivodeship self-governments, it is basically political parties that dominate the elections to the voivodeship assemblies. In the local government elections of 2018, candidates of national parties received a total of 89.4 per cent of votes. The Local Government Movement ‘Non-Partisans’ gained 5.28 per cent of the country's vote. Regional groupings received marginal support, except for three voivodeships. In the Opolskie Voivodeship, ‘The German Minority Electoral Committee’ traditionally receives strong support (in 2018 – 14.64 per cent). In two other voivodships, regional movements concentrated around local politicians obtained: 8.29 per cent of votes (the Lower Silesian Voivodeship: Electoral Committee of Voters ‘*With Dutkiewicz for Lower Silesia*’¹⁵¹) and 5.26 per cent of votes (the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship: Electoral Committee of Voters ‘*Wenta*’¹⁵²s *Świętokrzyskie Project*’).

At the *powiat* level, the presence of parties in the elections is weaker, in the 2018 elections the national parties won about 62 per cent of votes. At the level of *gminas*, the parties have obviously the smallest influence – local election initiatives prevail. In *gminas* with up to 20,000 inhabitants (single-mandate constituencies) national parties won about 27 per cent of votes. In *gminas* with over 20 000 inhabitants the figure was approx. 50 per cent.¹⁵³ In rural *gminas*, traditionally, the peasants’ party – the Polish People’s Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*) – has played an important role. In the last elections, the importance of the Law and Justice Party

¹⁴⁹ Bukowski Michał, Jarosław Flis, Agnieszka Hess and Agnieszka Szymańska, *Rządzący i opozycja, partie sejmowe i lokalne w małopolskich wyborach samorządowych 2014* (Attyka 2016) 24.

¹⁵⁰ The Senate is the upper house of the Polish Parliament, the lower house is the Sejm. The Senate and the Sejm exercises legislative power in Poland. The Members of both houses are elected by direct election. The Senate consists of 100 senators, the Senate - 460 deputies.

¹⁵¹ Rafał Dudkiewicz was from 2002 to 2018 the Mayor of Wrocław, the capital city of the Lower Silesian Voivodeship.

¹⁵² Bogdan Wenta having run from his own committee and was *elected* as Mayor of Kielce, the capital of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship. For years related with handball, first as a player of the Polish national team and Germany. 2004 - 2012 was the coach of the Polish national handball team. One of the best handball player in history of Polish handball.

¹⁵³ National Electoral Commission, ‘The Results of Local Elections 2018’ (*Local Government Elections 2018*, 30 June 2018) <<https://wybory2018.pkw.gov.pl/pl/dane-w-arkuszach>> accessed 14 December 2019.

(*Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*) has increased, reflecting the situation at the national government level.

The number and share of rural population in the total population of the country is declining. At the end of 2017, the rural population accounted for 39.9 per cent (in 1950 over 63 per cent)¹⁵⁴. The *gminas'* population forecasts of the Polish Central Statistical Office (GUS) for 2017-2030 indicate, above all, a strong development of major urban agglomerations with adjacent areas. They will continue to attract people from more peripheral areas. At the same time, a continuation of the suburbanization process should be expected, which will lead to a significant increase in population in the *gminas* adjacent to big cities.¹⁵⁵ These changes are caused by lower prices of flats or house building costs and reflect the growing economic status which enables inhabitants to move to an area more beneficial in terms of being a 'greener environment'.¹⁵⁶ In 2018, 55 cities with *powiat* rights (there are 66 cities of this type in total) recorded a decrease in population compared to the previous year. These included cities that aspire to play the role of a metropolis (Poznań, Łódź, Bydgoszcz). Warsaw, the capital city of Poland recorded an increase. The number of *gminas* with less than 5,000 inhabitants is steadily growing. There are already approx. 800 of them.

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¹⁵⁴ Stańczak Joanna and Znajewska Agnieszka, 'Population in Poland: Size and Structure by Territorial Division as of June 30, 2017' (Central Statistical Office, 2017)
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¹⁵⁵ 'Prognoza ludności gmin na lata 2017-2030' (*Statistics Poland*, 31 August 2017) <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/prognoza-ludnosci/prognoza-ludnosci-gmin-na-lata-2017-2030-opracowanie-eksperymentalne,10,1.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

¹⁵⁶ Małgorzata Waligórska, Zofia Kostrzewa, Maciej Potyra and Longina Rutkowska, 'Population Projection 2014-2050' (Central Statistical Office 2014) <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/prognoza-ludnosci/prognoza-ludnosci-na-lata-2014-2050-opracowana-2014-r-,1,5.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

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7.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction

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The model of a unitary state, adopted by Poland, assumes that the legislature is undivided – it is wielded only by the Polish Parliament (two chambers: Sejm and Senate). The principle of administrative decentralization means a division of the executive. It is wielded by the authorities of the Polish state (the President of the Republic of Poland and the government - The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Poland with the central government that is centralized and subject to the governance of the government). The local government has functioned within the executive since 1990. It has fulfilled a part of the tasks of the executive, but it is not subject hierarchically to the government. The local government (in Poland: territorial self-government) is independent in its activities undertaken for the good of its members (residents). However, its activities cannot violate the law (the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, acts, regulation, the EU law). Legal supervision is a mechanism which is triggered when the law is violated by local government (there is no difference with regard to urban and rural municipalities). Supervision is exercised only by the authorities of the Polish state. The local government may challenge that supervision through a complaint lodged to an administrative court. Ultimately, therefore, the court settles the dispute between the state and local government (Article 166 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997: ‘The administrative courts shall settle jurisdictional disputes between units of local government and units of government administration’).

However, there are no governance dependencies or supervision relations between three levels of territorial self-government (*gminy, powiats, voivodeship*). Therefore, the relations between local governments are always voluntary and mutually agreed (only exceptions include situation relating to public security as well as unusual and emergency situations – which are precisely determined in the act).

The state-local government relations are manifold. On the one hand, the local government is subject to the state's regulations and supervision. The scope of tasks and financial resources are regulated by the act – the local government must submit to them. On the other hand, the Preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland includes the principle of cooperation between the public authorities, therefore, between the government and local government as well – for the common good. The principle of cooperation between the authorities, referred to in the Preamble, corresponds with the multi-level governance structure, well established in the modern science of public governance.

In the democratic state there are various mechanisms in place to enable the participation in the law-making process. With regard to the local government, the Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government (*Komisja Wspólna Rządu i Samorządu Terytorialnego*) has functioned in Poland since 1993. It is ‘the forum for the elaboration of a joint position of the central government and local government’. The local governments are formed by the representatives of all-Poland organizations of local government units, both representing the interests of urban and rural municipalities, including metropolises.

The Polish law guarantees the *gminas*, *powiats* and voivodeship the right to establish associations. Their objective should be to support the idea of local government and to defend their common interests. These associations can be established by the units of one local government level, but they can also include the units of different levels. The Association of Polish Local Governments (*gminas*, *powiats*, voivodeships) is such an association established in 2017. The association refers to the Christian values what is novel among the all-Poland associations which do not declare a worldview orientation in their statutes.

The primary role is played by 6 all-Poland local government organizations: the Union of Polish Metropolises (*Unia Metropolii Polskich*); the Union of Small Polish Towns (*Unia Miasteczek Polskich*); the Association of Polish Cities (*Związek Miast Polskich*); the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland (*Związek Gmin Wiejskich Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*); the Association of Polish Powiats (*Związek Powiatów Polskich*); the Association of Voivodeships of the Republic of Poland (*Związek Województw Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*).

There is a range of examples of associations of a regional or even local nature (e.g. the Association of Communes and Powiats of Małopolska (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin i Powiatów Małopolski*), the Association of Communes and Powiats of Central Pomerania (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin i Powiatów Pomorza Środkowego*). There are also associations which determined their scope of interest, e.g.: the Masovian Association of Communes for the Development of Information Society (*Mazowieckie Stowarzyszenie Gmin na Rzecz Rozwoju Społeczeństwa Informacyjnego*), the Association of Health Resort Communes of the Republic of Poland (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin Uzdrowiskowych RP*).

All associations are subject to the registration in the court (the entry to the National Court Register) and legal supervision by the state.

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7.3 Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government

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Relevance of the Practice

The Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self Government is an instrument for cooperation of two separate kinds of public authorities within the framework of the executive. The Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self Government was established by the Polish Government in 1993, inter alia, as a result of the ratification of the European Charter of Local Self-Government by Poland. The Charter refers, inter alia, to the local government's guarantees of the right to influence the government's policy in the matters relating to the local government. Since 1993 to 2005 the legal status of the commission was regulated by three subsequent government's regulations. Now, the Act of 6 May 2005 on the Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self Government and on representatives of the Republic of Poland in the European Union Committee of the Regions is in force. The statutory form of the regulation obviously means the improvement and stabilization of the commission's position in the institutional system of Poland.

The commission is an instrument for dialogue between the central government and the representatives of the bottom-up organized local government environment as well as an expression of cohabitation between the government expressing the state's interests and local government – politically diversified, expressing the regional and local interests.

Description of the Practice

The commission includes 12 representatives of the central government and local government. The central government is represented by the minister in charge of general government and 11 members appointed by the Prime Minister. The local government is represented by two representatives of each of six all-Poland local government organizations determined in the government's regulation of 2008. These are the Union of Polish Metropolises (established in 1990); the Union of Small Polish Towns (established in 2008); the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland (established in 1993); the Association of Polish Cities (established in 1991); the Association of Polish *Powiaty* (established in 1999); the Association of Voivodeships the Republic of Poland (established in 2002). They have a legal form of an association or a foundation. These organizations aspire also to represent their interests at a transnational level. It should be underlined that the establishment of these organizations was a bottom-up process and independent of central authority (during works on the Act on the Local Government in 1990 it was intended to appoint the obligatory local government representation, i.e. 'the National Association of Municipalities'. It did not happen as a result of

an objection of the 'Solidarity' environment and members of local government). The local and regional self-government organizations are an expression of bottom-up initiatives and not an obligation imposed by an act.

Both the composition and the internal organization of the commission indicate that the separate interests of urban and rural communes are taken into consideration. The Team for Rural Areas, Villages and Agriculture and the Team for Functional Metropolitan and Urban Areas are among 12 problem teams established in the commission. The teams' works are additionally supported by experts.

The commission's task is to consider 'problems related to the function of territorial self-government and the state's policy towards the self-government as well as the matters related to the self-government being within the scope of the activities of the European Union and international organizations to which the Republic of Poland belongs (Article 2 of the Act of the Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self Government).

Assessment of the Practice

The Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self-Government is a permanent element of the institutional system of Poland. It has the right, guaranteed by law, to participate in consultations of acts concerning the local government matters. The commission also prepares scientific expert's opinions and is an important forum for discussion on the local government's rights. The meetings of working commissions are held regularly. The primary role is played by the representatives of given local government organizations which separately represent the interests of local governments of cities of the metropolis, cities, urban areas, *powiats*, voivodeships. Their activity and involvement determine which problems will be raised in the discussion with the government. The Union of Polish Metropolises is particularly active; it brings together 12 large cities the presidents of which aspire to conduct the independent policy in opposition to the current government. The Association of Rural Municipalities plays also a very important role. Some antagonism between the concepts of regional policy in Poland can be observed on this plane (the concept of polarizing diffusion development supports the network of metropolises versus the concept of sustainable development supporting the rural areas).

Following the timetable for the works of the commission and its problem teams it can be concluded that the commission is very active.¹⁵⁷ A detailed analysis of the meetings' subjects and interviews with the commission's members would allow for the assessment as far as the commission is able to fulfil its mission and a forum to agree positions between the government and local government as well as between the urban areas and rural areas.

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7.4 County-Commune Unions as a New Form of Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Beskidian County and Commune Union

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Relevance of the Practice

Local government units may cooperate with each other in the public tasks realization. The right to voluntary cooperation is guaranteed by the Polish Constitution (Article 172) and the European Charter of Local Self-Government (Article 10). Three legal forms may be adopted in cooperation: (i) unions (ii) agreements (iii) associations.

- The union of local government units implies that local governments implement a new separate legal unit with legal personality to delegate their task(s) to the unit for performance. Thus, the tasks delegated to the union, throughout its existence, cease to be the tasks of local government units forming the union.
- The agreement of local government units implies that no new legal entity is created, merely one local government unit delegates its tasks to another one.
- The associations – their objective is different. The point is not about the local governments tasks performing but rather about ‘supporting and promoting the idea of local government and common interests of local government units’¹⁵⁸. Regarding associations, a new legal entity is referred to, similar to a union, adopting its statute and operating through its legal organs (authorities).

Ever since the commune (*gmina*) government was reinstated in 1990, unions, agreements and associations have been able to be established by communes among themselves (intermunicipal cooperation). Also counties (*powiats*) could cooperate with each other in these three legal forms since their establishment in 1999.

Intergovernmental cooperation (between communes and counties) was possible in the form of agreements and associations. Unions could merely be established at one level, either solely between communes (*gminas*) or between counties (*powiats*).

Revolutionary change occurred in 2016. It is henceforth possible to create intergovernmental unions, namely between counties (*powiats*) and communes (*gminas*). The establishment of more sustainable and transparent form of local tasks performing was the main purpose. The union may serve primarily the joint performance of tasks concerning public local transport, education or road management.

The decision about the union establishment is made by the representative authority of local government units (the commune council and the county council). Furthermore, the statute is also adopted by local government units. The union operates through its own authorities,

¹⁵⁸ Art 84(1) of the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government.

including the union's assembly (as a regulatory and controlling authority) and the union board (as the executive authority). All unions must be listed in the central 'union register' kept by the minister responsible for public administration¹⁵⁹ (currently: Ministry of the Interior and Administration of Poland).¹⁶⁰

Currently (February 2021), 13 county and commune unions (*związek powiatowo-gminny*) are registered. The organization of local public transport is the most common objective of union establishment (9 unions). Moreover, other tasks include tourism promotion and development, and environmental protection. The number of local government units establishing a county and commune union varies from 2 to 15.

Description of the Practice

The example of intergovernmental union is the Beskidian¹⁶¹ County and Commune Union (*Beskidzki Związek Powiatowo-Gminny*) established in 2017. The union was established to perform tasks concerning the local public transport sector. The union consists of 10 local governments units from two levels, including the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) and 9 communes (*gminas*) located in the county territory.¹⁶²

The Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) is the example of the 'bagel-county'.¹⁶³ Accordingly, its territory consists of communes surrounding a separate city with county (*powiat*) rights (Bielsko-Biała). The population of the city with county (*powiats*) rights Bielsko-Biała is 170,303. The Bielski County population is 159,241.

¹⁵⁹ Karolina Ohtarzewska, 'Zarejestruj, zmień statut lub wyrejestruj związek międzygminny, związek powiatów, związek powiatowo-gminny' (*Ministry of the Interior and Administration*, 2 July 2019) <<https://www.gov.pl/web/mswia/zarejestruj-zmien-statut-lub-wyrejestruj-zwiazek-miedzygminny-zwiazek-powiatow-zwiazek-powiatowo-gminny>> accessed 15 January 2021.

¹⁶⁰ See the website of the Ministry of the Interior and Administration, <<https://www.gov.pl/web/mswia-en>>.

¹⁶¹ Beskids is the name of the geographical region of southern Poland, the mountain ranges in the Carpathians, where the local government units of the union are located.

¹⁶² 'BZPG – Informacje ogólne' (*Beskidzki Związek Powiatowo Gminny*) <<https://www.bzpg.pl/index.php/o-bzpg/>> accessed 15 January 2021.

¹⁶³ For more information on 'bagel' – territorial units in Poland, see report section 4.1. on the Structure of Local Government in Poland.

Figure 16: The border of the 'bagel'-county (Powiat Bielski)¹⁶⁴

The city with county (*powiat*) rights (Bielsko Biała) is not included in the Beskidian County and Commune Union. However, there are apparent functional links between the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) and the City of Bielsko-Biała. An essential place is occupied by the city, constituting the center of work, education, health protection and culture for the inhabitants of the neighboring communes (*gminy*) belonging to the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*). Additionally, links are strengthened by the fact that the City of Bielsko-Biała is the seat of the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) authorities. The City of Bielsko Biała provides and finances own public transport within its territory so the city has shown no interest in participating in the Beskidian County and Communes Union.

One commune of the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) has not been included in the Beskidian County and Commune Union. It is an urban-rural commune with the City of Czechowice-Dziedzice inhabited by 35,631 people. The city provides own-account public transport.

Figure 17: The area of the Beskidian County and Commune Union¹⁶⁵

¹⁶⁴ Own elaboration, with the map taken from D T G

<[https://pl.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plik:Powiat_bielski_\(%C5%9B%C4%85ski\) - Mapa.png](https://pl.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plik:Powiat_bielski_(%C5%9B%C4%85ski)_-_Mapa.png)>.

¹⁶⁵ Own elaboration, with the map taken from Starostwo Powiatowe <<http://www.gminy.pl/powiaty/271.html>>.

No	Commune name	Commune type	Population	Area	Population density (inhabitants/sq. km)
1	Bestwina	Rural	11,441	37.92 km ²	301.7
2	Buczkowice	Rural	11,126	19.33 km ²	571.7
3	Jasienica	Rural	23,471	91.714 km ²	256.0
4	Jaworze	Rural	7299	21.13 km ²	342.4
5	Kozy	Rural	13,024	26.9 km ²	484.2
6	Porąbka	Rural	15,420	64.59 km ²	239.3
7	Wilkowice	rural	13,327	33.9 km ²	87.4
8	Wilamowice	urban-rural	17,017	56.72 km ²	296.8
9	Szczyrk	urban (city)	5734	39.07 km ²	146.76

Table 1: Communes included in the Beskidian County and Commune Union

No	County name	Population	Area	Population density (inhabitants/sq. km)
1	Bielski County (<i>Powiat Bielski</i>): 10 communes (<i>gminas</i>)	165,960	458.64 km ²	361.9

Table 2: The county included in the Beskidian County and Commune Union

The Beskidian County and Commune Union operates on the basis of its statute, adopted by the local government units forming the union. Tasks, authorities, assets and sources of financing are regulated by the statute concerning the union.¹⁶⁶

The union performing its tasks operates through the following bodies:

- the Assembly;
- the Management Board;
- the Audit Committee.

The assembly consists of two representatives from each local government units forming the union. Additionally, a member and a chairman of the assembly is the head of the Department of Communication and Transport in the County Office (*Starostwo Powiatowe*) with the total number of 23 members.

The Management Board of the union (an executive body) consists of 11 members comprising of an executive authority (mayor) from each commune. The representative of the Bielski

¹⁶⁶ Statute of the Beskidian County and Commune Union - consolidated text of 30 October 2018, <<https://bzpg.bip.gov.pl/statut-zwiazku/tekst-jednolity/statut-beskidzkiego-zwiazku-powiatowo-gminnego.html>> accessed 15 January 2021.

County (*Powiat Bielski*) is the County Governor (*starosta*) as the executive body chairman in the county (*powiat*). The director of the union's office is also a member of the management board.

Primarily, the union meets the requirements related to the rural communes. The new legal form assures communes equal participation, interest representation and transparency in the task performance of providing public transport to inhabitants. Before the union establishment, the aforementioned task was performed by the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*), and the communes concluded an agreement with the county delegating the task to the county. According to the Head of the Jaworze commune, of which the commune is a member of Beskidian County and Communes Unions, 'until the Beskidian County and Communes Union was established, the Bielski County was responsible for local public transport, and it was financed by communes (under an agreement). Nowadays, we are entering a new reality. The communes of Beskidian County and Communes Union are becoming a full-fledged entity co-deciding on the tasks implementation in the field of public transport, and the Beskidian County and Communes Union is becoming the organizer of public transport in our area. Thus, communes, and not only county, acquire the right to control the way this task is performed, which has not been the case so far.'¹⁶⁷

Currently, transports are organized on the territory of all communes belonging to the Bielski County (*Powiat Bielski*) and on the area of 4 communes that are not involved to the union on the basis of concluded agreements. All vehicles are insured with free Wi-Fi Internet access. From 1 January 2018, people over the age of 70 may travel free of charge by public transport organized by the union.

The union also obtains external funds originating in the European Union and the Polish Government. Therefore, modern ecological vehicles powered by compressed natural gas (CNG) can be purchased. In return, 17 diesel buses will be scrapped, which will positively affect the environment, thus contributing to the low-emission promotion.¹⁶⁸

Assessment of the Practice

The intergovernmental form of cooperation becomes increasingly significant. For instance, another similar union is in the process of being created in the area of Wielkopolska Voivoidship. 23 local government units will be included with the number of 5 counties (*powiats*) and 18 communes (*gminas*). However, there will be a significant difference from the example discussed above. Namely, the new union will also include a centrally located city with county (*powiat*) rights, i.e. the City of Poznań, which is the fifth largest city in Poland with 533,830 inhabitants.

¹⁶⁷ Statement of the Mayor of the Jaworze commune, Radosław Ostalkiewicz, of 24 April 2018, <<https://ostalkiewicz.com/2018/04/24/nowy-pks/>> accessed 20.09.2021

¹⁶⁸ 'Report on the State of the Bielsko County for 2019' (Bielsko County 2019) <https://www.powiat.bielsko.pl/bielsko_powiat_2019/web/uploads/temp/strony/strona_326/text/Raport%20o%20stanie%20Powiatu%20Bielskiego%20%20za%202019.pdf> accessed 15 January 2021.

In 2019, the Mayor of Poznań informed neighboring local governments about the bad financial results of the local transport Motor Transport Company (*Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacji Samochodowej, PKS*). Shutdown was considered in this case as the City of Poznań could not afford to finance bus transport for the neighboring communes and counties not contributing to the costs at all. An agreement was reached and a new county and commune union called Wielkopolski Regional Transport (*Wielkopolski Transport Regionalny*) will be established by April 2021 and be operational in July 2021. Transport costs will be covered by all participants in proportion to the frequency and the length of bus travel in each of the communes and counties.

Figure 18: The border of the planned county-commune union Wielkopolski Regional Transport against the background of the Wielkopolska Voivodeship¹⁶⁹

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Ziemski K and Misiejko A, 'Organizacja publicznego transportu zbiorowego przez jednostki samorządu terytorialnego ze szczególnym uwzględnieniem prawnych aspektów współdziałania' (University of Adam Mickiewicz 2016)

https://repozytorium.amu.edu.pl/bitstream/10593/21982/1/Ziemski%2C%20Misiejko_organizacja%20publicznego%20transportu%20internet.pdf

¹⁶⁹ Own elaboration, with the map taken from Okonek Gminny Internet Porta | www.okonek.pl/asp/pl_start.asp?typ=14&menu=70&strona=1&sub=58.

7.5 The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations

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Relevance of the Practice

The specificity of a unitary state does not require the creation of coordination mechanisms between national and subnational government levels as is the case in federal states. However, there remains the issue of regulating relations between the central government and local self-government and relations between various levels of local self-government.

According to formal rules, local self-government is not a participant in the process of adopting national laws and has no legislative initiative. The only legally guaranteed form of local self-government participation in the process of shaping the state policy are consultations on the bills adopted from the legislative initiative of the central government. This formalized and institutionalized consultation mechanism is applied through Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government, which constitutes a body composed of representatives of the central government and local self-government.¹⁷⁰ According to the relevant legal act,¹⁷¹ the joint commission is a forum for developing a common position of the central government and local self-government. In addition to this formal mechanism, local governments also hold informal contacts and lobbying activities which attempt to influence the actions of the central government and parliament in order to obtain solutions which are favorable to local self-government. In a democratic state, the right to express protest, dissatisfaction and criticism of the government's actions is also obvious. Such activities, however, exceed the possibilities of individual local self-government units. For this reason, local self-government organizations play a key role in this regard (Article 172(1) of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland guarantees the right of association to local self-government units). Apart from local or regional organizations, also nationwide local self-government organizations operate in Poland. The legal position of six such organizations has been strengthened by the fact that they are members of the Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government, and such a composition of the joint commission was decided by the central government.¹⁷²

¹⁷⁰ For more information about the joint commission, see report section 5.1 on Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland.

¹⁷¹ Art 2 of the Act no 90 of 6 May 2005 on the Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self-Government and on the Representatives of the Republic of Poland in the Committee of the Regions of the European Union.

¹⁷² Ordinance of the Council of Ministers no 15 of 29 January 2008 on the Determination of Nationwide Organizations of Local Self-Government Units which are Entitled to Appoint Representatives to Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government.

Due to the fact that there are three levels of local self-government in Poland, and additionally there exists a strong differentiation among the communes themselves (cities, urban-rural communes, rural communes), it was therefore of key importance to indicate the members of the joint commission. Consequently, the commission members include currently representatives of six nationwide organizations: the Union of Polish Metropolises, the Association of Polish Cities, the Association of Small Polish Towns, the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland, the Association of Polish Powiats and the Association of Voivodeships of the Republic of Poland.

As the names of these organizations show, they represent, first of all, individual levels of local self-government (communes, *powiats* and voivodships). Secondly, it can be seen that at the communes' level, we deal with various categories of communes (very large metropolitan cities, cities, small towns, rural communes) whose interests are represented by separate self-government organizations.

Therefore, local self-government functions within the legal framework specified by the central authorities and is the recipient of the government's development plans or financial support programs. General concepts of development have also changed in Poland, from polarization and diffusion concepts to concepts of sustainable development.¹⁷³ Thus, these 'rules of the game' formulated at the central level have fundamental impact on the functioning of local self-government, often having different effects for various categories of local self-government units (general division into the interests of rural communes, urban communes and metropolises). Three nationwide local self-government organizations were selected for the analysis, which are representing different categories of Polish communes and through which the different interests of metropolitan, urban and rural local self-governments are manifested. These are the Union of Polish Metropolises, the Association of Polish Cities and the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland.

Description of the Practice

The Union of Polish Metropolises¹⁷⁴ (*Unia Metropolii Polskich* - UMP) has the legal form of a foundation which was established in 1990, i.e. at the beginning of the systemic transformation in Poland and the reactivation of local self-government at the level of communes (1990). The founders of UMP were the seven largest Polish cities: Gdańsk, Katowice, Lublin, Łódź, Szczecin, Warsaw and Wrocław. Currently, the 12 largest cities in Poland belong to the organization.¹⁷⁵

¹⁷³ Mirska Andżelika, 'State Policy on the Formation and Modernisation of Polish Territorial Structure' in Europäisches Zentrum für Föderalismus-Forschung Tübingen EZFF (ed), *Jahrbuch des Föderalismus 2018: Föderalismus, Subsidiarität und Regionen in Europa* (Nomos 2018).

¹⁷⁴ For more detail, see the respective websites, <<https://metropolie.pl>>; <<https://www.facebook.com/UniaMetropoliiPolskich/>>.

¹⁷⁵ Warsaw - 1.8 million inhabitants; Kraków – 779,000; Wrocław – 693,000; Łódź – 680,000; Poznań - 535,000; Gdańsk – 471,000; Szczecin – 402,000; Bydgoszcz – 348,000; Lublin - 340,000; Białystok - 298,000; Katowice – 293,000; Rzeszów – 196,000. Statistics Poland, 'Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Poland' (2020) <<https://stat.gov.pl/en/topics/statistical-yearbooks/>> accessed 10 July 2021.

The Association of Polish Cities¹⁷⁶ (*Związek Miast Polskich* - ZMP) is a local self-government organization which follows the pre-war traditions (years 1917-1939). The reactivation of ZMP also took place at the beginning of the systemic transformation, in 1991. Currently, 353 cities belong to the ZMP.¹⁷⁷ There are 954 cities¹⁷⁸ in Poland, 302 of which have the status of a separate urban commune.¹⁷⁹ There are also urban-rural communes, which can choose membership not in the Association of Polish Cities, but in another organization, which is the Association of Small Polish Towns (it associates about 130 small towns).¹⁸⁰ Urban-rural communes may also decide to become members of the Union of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland.

The Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland (*Związek Gmin Wiejskich Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej* - ZGW RP) is also an organization with a long historical tradition, which was reactivated in 1992. It is the largest local self-government organization in Poland, currently associating 637 communes (553 of which constitute rural communes and 84 urban-rural communes).¹⁸¹ This means that 36.3 per cent of rural communes and 13.5 per cent of urban-rural communes in Poland are concentrated in this association.

When analyzing the activities of these self-government organizations (analysis of documents, official websites, media activity), it can be concluded that each of them indicates as one of its goals legislative lobbying, i.e. the impact on the content of laws enacted in Poland.

This aspect of activity is most clearly expressed by the Association of Polish Cities. In the charter of the association of 19 January 1991, it was specified that its tasks include:

- representing cities in all common matters on the national and international forum;
- initiating and issuing opinions on draft legal acts concerning local self-governments;
- conducting program, information, consulting and training activities aimed at joint problem solving in the field of individual areas of local municipal self-government activity.¹⁸²

It was stated on the association's website that the Association of Polish Cities fights for the interests of Polish cities. It represents the interests of local municipal self-governments and conducts legislative lobbying on their behalf. It is a nationwide organization which integrates member cities around common goals. It is actively involved in activities supporting local self-

¹⁷⁶ For more detail, see the respective websites, <<https://www.miasta.pl/en>>; <<https://www.facebook.com/ZwiazekMiastPolskich/>>.

¹⁷⁷ For more detail, see the respective website, <<https://www.miasta.pl/miasta>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁷⁸ The granting a locality the status of a town/city, that is changing the type of denotation, e.g. 'village' into 'town' is processed by way of regulation of the Council of Ministers. Art of the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government.

¹⁷⁹ Statistics Poland, 'Area and Population in the Territorial Profile 2021' (2021) 11 <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/ludnosc/powierzchnia-i-ludnosc-w-przekroju-terytorialnym-w-2021-roku,7,18.html>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸⁰ For more detail, see the respective website, <<http://miasteczka.online/ump/>>.

¹⁸¹ For more detail, see the respective website, <<http://www.zgwrp.pl/lista-gmin-czlonkowskich>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸² Statute of the Association of Polish Cities of 19 January 1991, <https://www.miasta.pl/uploads/document/content_file/754/STATUT-2019.pdf> accessed 10 July 2021.

government and decentralization and strives for a better development of Polish cities.¹⁸³ 'ZMP initiates joint actions against legal solutions unfavorable for cities and prepares its own draft amendments to legal acts.'¹⁸⁴

The next local self-government organization, the Union of Polish Metropolises, in its statute of 3 June 2019 lists, among others, the following goals of its activity:

- joint solving of specific problems of big cities;
- cooperation with state authorities as well as national, foreign and international organizations to increase the role of metropolises within the state and in European integration.

UMP wants to achieve these goals by financing, inter alia, preparation of 'all legislative projects, taking into account the special role and scale of problems of metropolis in the state' as well as the preparation of 'seminars, discussions and panels with participation of politicians and experts, dedicated to urban and metropolitan issues'.¹⁸⁵

Similar goals were included in the charter of the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland – ZGW RP in its version of 18 April 2016. They include: 'defending common interests of rural communes, representing the interests of rural and urban-rural communes, representing collective interests of its members before public authorities'.¹⁸⁶ The statute of the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland further states that 'the Association achieves its goals by: representing rural communes on the national and international forum, expressing positions on issues related to the government, economy and organization of communes, initiating and giving opinions on draft legal acts concerning local self-government'. The website of the association states, inter alia, that 'the activities of ZGW RP concern both negotiations with the government, consultations in the parliament, exchange of experiences between members as well as activities aimed at the economic and cultural development of rural communes. Thanks to the association's involvement and lobbying many solutions proposed by the government or parliament, which were unfavorable from the point of view of rural self-governments, were protested and thus effectively blocked'.¹⁸⁷

When analyzing the activities of the above three organizations (forms of activities: speeches, positions, protests, opinions, requests, appeals, etc.) on the basis of their websites and media messages, it should be stated that they are active organizations, responding on an ongoing basis to projects and activities of central authorities. Referring to statistical data, for example, the Association of Polish Cities was the organization which most frequently participated as a guest in the meetings of the Polish Parliament committees (possibility of speaking, giving opinions

¹⁸³ 'About us' (*Association of Polish Cities*, undated) <<https://www.miasta.pl/zysk-dla-miast/>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸⁴ 'Why is it worth joining ZMP?' (*Association of Polish Cities*, undated) <<https://www.miasta.pl/strony/dlaczego-warto-dolaczyc-do-zmp>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸⁵ Statute of UMP, consolidated text of 3 June 2019 <<https://metropolie.pl/o-nas/statut>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸⁶ Art 7 of the Charter of the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland in its version of 18 April 2016 <http://www.zgwrp.pl/attachments/article/1470/broszura_ZO_statut_regulamin_ordynacja.pdf> accessed 5 October 2021.

¹⁸⁷ 'The Mission of the Association' (*Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland*, undated) <<http://www.zgwrp.pl/misja-zwiazku>> accessed 5 October 2021.

on amendments to bills). On the basis of the ranking on the 'Open Lobbying' website,¹⁸⁸ ZMP was recognized as one of the main lobbyists in the parliament. Other organizations recognized as leading lobbyists in the Polish Parliament included the National Council of Agricultural Chambers and the Confederation of Polish Employers 'Lewiatan'.¹⁸⁹

Analyzing the activities of these organizations in the longer term, it can be concluded that in the earlier period, the defense of the particular interests of specific types of communes dominated. An example of such actions was the dispute between the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland and the Association of Polish Cities. The dispute concerned the problem of expanding city boundaries at the expense of neighboring rural communes (or their parts). The procedure of such expansion involves public consultations, but the final decision is made by the central government.¹⁹⁰ The Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland consistently protested against such a strategy of urban development, taking place by incorporating some rural communes (or their parts) within the city limits. On the other hand, the Association of Polish Cities supported this method of developing cities.¹⁹¹

Assessment of the Practice

In recent months, we have been observing joint and intensified activity of these organizations in relation to the action plans of the central government. The current situation results from the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic and the actions of the central government, which, according to local self-government units, led to the impairment of local self-government in Poland through recentralization tendencies.

An example of such joint activity constitutes, for example, the 'Common Position of Polish National Local Self-Government Organizations on the Financing of Education of 17 June 2020', which is an appeal to the central authorities for higher financing of education: 'For many years, local self-governments have been struggling with the problem of insufficient financing of educational tasks from the state budget'.¹⁹²

Another problem in which local self-government organizations have become strongly involved is the socio-economic program prepared by the central government to counteract the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Union of Polish Metropolises is particularly active here. It has shown in its analyses that the changes proposed by the government will have a very negative

¹⁸⁸ 'About us' (*Jawny Lobbying*, 2019) <<https://jawnylobbying.pl/about-us/>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁸⁹ 'Diagrams' (*Jawny Lobbying*, 2019) <<https://jawnylobbying.pl/wykresy/>>; Michał Wroński, 'Związek Miast Polskich i Związek Powiatów Polskich w Top 6 lobbystów w Sejmie' (*Portal Samorządowy*, 23 December 2019) <<https://www.portalsamorzadowy.pl/komunikacja-spoleczna/zwiazek-miast-polskich-i-zwiazek-powiatow-polskich-w-top-6-lobbystow-w-sejmie,141951.html>> accessed 10 July 2021.

¹⁹⁰ Art 4(a) and 5(a) of the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government.

¹⁹¹ For more information, see report section 6.1 on Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expense of the Rural Area.

¹⁹² 'Position of Nationwide Local Government Organizations on Financing Education' (2020) <https://www.miasta.pl/uploads/attachment/file/3557/Stanowisko_o_wiata_17_czerwca_220.pdf> accessed 30 July 2021.

impact, first of all on the budgets of the largest cities in Poland.¹⁹³ A similar position is represented by the Association of Polish Cities, indicating that the implementation of this plan will result in financial problems for Polish cities.¹⁹⁴

According to experts' assessments,¹⁹⁵ the role of local self-government organizations will increase, especially in the situation of the crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. The more self-government is exposed to the processes of recentralization, the more active local self-government organizations are and will be. These organizations constitute an important mechanism of dialogue between the government and local self-government as well as the mechanism through which the public is informed about the situation of local self-government in Poland.

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Kramer P and others, 'Advocacy and Lobbying by a Local Government Association (LGA)' (VNG International 2008) <<https://www.local2030.org/library/327/Advocacy-and-Lobbying-by-a-Local-Government-Association.pdf>>

¹⁹³ Michał Cyrankiewicz-Gortyński, 'Za Polski Ład zapłacą miasta i gminy' (*Union of Polish Metropolises*, 29 July 2021) <<https://metropolie.pl/arttykul/za-polski-lad-zaplaca-miasta-i-gminy>> accessed 30 July 2021.

¹⁹⁴ Zygmunt Frankiewicz, 'Najnowsze stanowisko ZMP w sprawie „Polskiego Ładu”' (*Association of Polish Cities*, 15 September 2021) <<https://www.miasta.pl/aktualnosci/najnowsze-stanowisko-zmp-w-sprawie-polskiego-ladu>> accessed 15 September 2021.

¹⁹⁵ Experts responded to the problem during the Workshop on 01/07/2021. This subject was also addressed in the interview with a representative of the Union of Polish Metropolises on 28.07.2021 (the record of the statements in the interview is attached to the research).

8. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Croatia

8.1 The System of Local Government in Croatia

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Types of Local Governments

Croatia has 21 units of regional self-government (*zupanija*), 20 counties and the Croatian Capital City of Zagreb. Each county is divided into a number of local government units. Also, each county has its own representative and executive body elected by popular vote for a term of four years. The City of Zagreb is a special territorial and administrative unit whose responsibilities are regulated by a separate Act on the City of Zagreb. The City of Zagreb has a dual status as a unit of local and regional government unit and thus performs activities within the scope of the city and as a county. It also carries out responsibilities of the state administration. In doing so administrative bodies of the City of Zagreb have the powers and obligations of state administration bodies.

There are 556 units of local government, that is 128 towns (*grad*) and 428 municipalities (*općina*). Towns are local government units typically of urban character with more than 10,000 inhabitants. Exceptions apply in case of historical, economic or geospatial reasons. Municipalities are local government units of rural character with less than 10,000 inhabitants. Each town and municipality has its own representative and executive body elected by popular vote for a term of four years. Each local government unit is further divided into one or more settlements regardless urban or rural. One or more settlements are represented by sub-local government entities called neighborhood councils with elected representatives which serve on non-professional terms. Some towns and some municipalities have only one neighborhood council. Towns and municipalities have basically the same responsibilities, except for towns in which counties have their administrative seat and towns with a population above 30,000 inhabitants. The latter are referred to as 'large towns' and have additional responsibilities. Seats of county are generally the largest towns within a county. There are only four large towns which are not the seat of a county.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right to local and regional self-government is guaranteed by Article 128 of the Croatian Constitution, according to which '[c]itizens shall be guaranteed the right to local and regional self-government' and this right 'shall be exercised through local and/or regional representative bodies', as well as citizens' direct participation in the administration of local affairs.

The rights specified in this Article shall be exercised by Croatian and European Union nationals in compliance with law and EU *acquis communautaire*.

The right to local government is further prescribed in national legislation such as the general Local Government Act, Local Government Financing Act, etc. The Croatian system of local self-government is based on the principle of autonomy of government and the principle of subsidiarity. The European Charter of Local Self-Government has been fully ratified by the Croatian Parliament. Croatian local governments have a judicially enforceable right to local self-government before the Constitutional Court and other judiciary bodies.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Local authorities have comprehensive responsibilities which are enumerated in the Constitution and further prescribed by the general Local Government Act. Local government units perform tasks of local importance which directly affect needs of the citizens and which are not assigned to state bodies by the Constitution or other laws, and especially the tasks referring to organization of settlement and housing; spatial and urban planning; utility services; child-care; primary health protection; social welfare; elementary education; culture, physical culture and sports; consumer protection; environment protection; fire and civil protection; maintenance of municipal roads and traffic management. In addition to these competences, large towns also have responsibilities related to maintenance of local public roads and construction permits.

Regional government units carry out affairs of regional importance which are not assigned to central bodies by the Constitution or other laws. The scope of counties' responsibilities can be self-managing and entrusted (government affairs). Counties are tasked with performing the following tasks: general public administration services; primary and secondary education; healthcare; regional and urban planning; economic development; environmental protection; transport and traffic infrastructure; management of the network of educational, medical, social welfare, and cultural institutions; administration pertaining to agriculture, forestry, mining, and industry; management of road transport infrastructure; construction permitting, excluding the area of big cities and a county seat city.

Re-assignment of responsibilities between individual local and regional governments is allowed pending approval of the representative bodies of both government units. Out of 556 local government units some 8-10 local governments have taken over such responsibilities. Certain restrictions apply such as the ability to fund a specific responsibility (in case of most of responsibilities) and a minimum number of inhabitants (8,000 inhabitants for management of elementary education).

Political and Social Context in Croatia

The Croatian population of 4.2 million is predominantly urban with 71 per cent of the total population living in towns which cover 39 per cent of total territory. The remaining 29 per cent of the total population are scattered through municipalities which cover 61 per cent of

Croatian territory. According to the 2011 Census, 19 per cent of the population lives in Zagreb, the capital city of Croatia. Population density is 76 inhabitants per square kilometer (139 inhabitants per square kilometer in towns, 36 in municipalities).

National parties dominate local level of government. In 2009, direct elections of a mayor were used for the first time, replacing the former system in which a representative body elected a mayor. But this did not significantly change the political landscape at the local level. The share of incumbents who lost in the 2017 elections was 40 per cent in towns and 30 per cent in municipalities, but national parties still dominate local level of government. In the 2017 elections a group of non-aligned mayors raised, making them the second largest 'political' group at the local level with a share of 15 per cent of the total number of town/municipal mayors.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 2014

Law no 110/2015 on Territories of Counties, Cities and Municipalities

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Ministry of Administration of the Republic of Croatia, 'Local and territorial (regional) Self-Government' <<https://uprava.gov.hr/o-ministarstvu/ustrojstvo/5-uprava-za-politicki-sustav-i-organizaciju-uprave-1075/lokalna-i-podrucna-regionalna-samouprava/842>>

8.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Croatia: An Introduction

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

The Croatian intergovernmental legal framework contains a number of provisions related to distribution of competencies, local government autonomy, intergovernmental dialogue or consultation and legal remedies.

Croatia has ratified the European Charter for Local Self-Government in 1997 partially and 2008 fully. The Charter provides for full and exclusive transfer of competencies to the government level closest to the citizens, considering efficiency of service provision; adequate fiscal resources; consultation, supervision, right to associate, boundaries protection and legal protection.

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia provides a general competencies framework for local government which is further elaborated in the Law on Local and Regional Government and detailed in sectoral legislation. Distribution of fiscal resources, supervision and legal remedies are prescribed in the same fashion. In addition to general and detailed provisions, legal protection of local governments is additionally prescribed in constitutional law on Constitutional Court. Constitutional laws can be passed and amended by 2/3 majority of the parliament. Consultations among government levels and with the public are also prescribed in aforesaid legislation and further elaborated in the Law on Access to the Information. The right to associate is defined in the Law on Local and Regional Government, allowing local governments to establish national associations of local or regional governments should more than half of local or regional governments decide to do so.

The Croatian governance system is a three-tier system – national, regional and local government. National level counterparts in broadest terms are central government, legislature and judiciary. Regional government counterparts are primarily counties and their budgetary users. Local level counterparts are two distinct types of local governments – urban and rural - and their budgetary users and utility companies.

Intergovernmental relations in Croatia take various forms both in terms of vertical or horizontal relations. Having a three-tier governance system, vertical relations come in various forms from national to subnational, national to local, national to regional or regional to local, and vice versa, among any and all of aforesaid counterparts.

Horizontal relations are primarily any of the inter-municipal cooperation formats – joint utility companies, joint budgetary users or joint municipal departments or recently developed project agglomerations.

Most common vertical intergovernmental relations take place within legislative process framework and execution of competencies. Over the course of past few decades, the legislative process had undergone major changes in its form and dynamics. Some fifteen years of Croatian independence, the legislative process was mostly a national governance affair with rather limited input from the general public, which started to change during the following decade. Opening towards public input was of limited effect due to the fact that national

government and parliament had to ramp-up the legislative process in order to timely adopt, transpose and implement EU *acquis communautaire*. Upon completion of adoption of the *acquis* and joining the EU, the legislative process decreased in pace allowing for substantial input from the general public and interested parties. An important cornerstone of the legislative process is the Parliamentary Board for Local Governments which involves members of the parliament as well as local and regional governments in discussion with the representatives of the government.

Aforesaid legislative process coupled with centralistic governance and fragmented subnational government had created an intertwined and overlapping matrix of competencies of three distinct levels of governance in public service provision. Such complex distribution of competencies, sometimes bordering with or crossing local autonomy lines, inevitably leads to intergovernmental issues and inefficiencies in public service provision. In such cases concerned levels of government often call for amendments to the legislation or legal remedies.

Intergovernmental judiciary relations are infrequent but tend to change the intergovernmental landscape when successfully executed by the local governments.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 4/2008 on Ratification of European Charter of Local Self-Government

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 2014

Law no 85/2015 on Access to the Information

Law no 73/2017 on Referenda and Other Means of Personal Participation in State and Local Affairs

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Kopric I, 'Widening the Scope of Local Self-Government Powers and Narrowing Central Government Supervision' (2000) *Hrvatska javna uprava* 391

8.3 Institutionalization of Intergovernmental Relations in Croatia

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Relevance of the Practice

There are two levels of subnational governments in Croatia, regional (counties) and local (cities and municipalities). Competencies and finance differ significantly between regional and local governments, although large cities have taken over some of the competencies of the regional government. There are many similarities in competencies of cities (urban) and municipalities (rural) local governments as well as funding arrangements. However, the underlying economic and demographic factors are distorting service provision levels and fiscal capacities of cities and municipalities.

Three types of subnational entities are involved in informal or formal legislative processes in order to realign the structure of competencies or improve fiscal capacities of respective regional or local governments. Large cities and regional governments could distort the competency-finance matrix due to their relative political and economic weight thus widening the urban-rural divide.

A highly polarized political environment makes it rather difficult for an individual or a smaller group of politically aligned or likeminded local governments to successfully address national policy or legislative issues since such efforts are commonly observed with political bias or through a prism of potential political gains. Fragmentation of the local government landscape further derails any such individual or small group activities because of relatively limited political influence of executives of small and economically minor local government units.

Institutionalization of intergovernmental relations is one of the vehicles used in order to establish a non-partisan and transparent policy process that balances the interests of urban and rural communities or lagging and developed areas.

Description of the Practice

When it comes to institutionalization of intergovernmental relations and balancing of urban-rural interplay, Parliament is one of the key institutions tasked with this function. Therefore, it is essential to establish a proper balance among key actors of intergovernmental dialogue at the parliamentary level in order to safeguard interest of all parties involved.

A three-level mechanism of institutionalized intergovernmental relations in the parliament is the Parliamentary Board for Local Government. The primary task of the board is to prepare or discuss draft legislation and legislative initiatives and provide advice or amendments on proposed legislation to the parliament. The board can also discuss citizens' complaints and proposals related to local governance.

The board can hire, involve scientific or other organizations and individuals in preparation of the proposals or reviewing acts, or propose to the government to entrust specific ministries with such a task. The board is also authorized to carry out public hearings related to proposed acts, parts of the acts or resolving an issue of public interest. It can establish sub-committees or task forces to carry out some of those tasks.

Key areas of operation of the board include the structure and competencies of local governments; founding, termination and amalgamation of local government units; finance and legal issues related to local public servants.

The Ordinance of the Parliament prescribes that the board has a chairman, deputy chairman and eleven members appointed from the members of the parliament for duration of a term at the parliament. Additional nine members are representatives of the four largest cities, two counties and two municipalities (one continental, one coastal) and one lawyer. Although the Ordinance of the Parliament does not provide a seat for representatives of local government associations (LGA), the board has been inviting representatives of LGAs to all of its meetings for over a decade.

There are three national voluntary associations of local governments in Croatia, one for each type of subnational government – counties, cities and municipalities – as prescribed by the Law on Local and Regional Self-Government. The County Association represents all 21 counties, the Cities Association represents 126 out of 128 cities and the Municipal Association represents 328 out of 428 municipalities.

Local government associations in Croatia represent interests of their members before national authorities, the legislature and the Constitutional Court. In a highly polarized national political environment and a fragmented local government landscape, LGAs are the non-partisan and uniform voice of local governments which contributes to consensus building and the protection of local government interests. Sound LGA processes and policies in the legislative process contribute to a reduction of the urban-rural divide. LGA provides influential vote to small local governments by building policy consensus among most or all local governments of different political affiliations and economic power, and presenting or advocating for those policies in non-partisan fashion at the national level.

LGA executive boards are tasked with regular legislative policy consensus building. County and municipal associations' executive boards are comprised by one member from each county. Due to the fact that cities in Croatia range from large urban units to small units which equivalent municipalities, the executive board of the Association of Cities is comprised of all seat-of-county cities and one other city from each county elected by the cities from that county. Such an executive boards structure helps maintain territorial, political and urban-rural consensus over legislative policy.

Croatia partially ratified the European Charter for Local Self-Government in 1997, leaving out some of the provisions LGAs considered critical for local governments. LGAs advocated before the line ministry for full ratification of the Charter in 2007/08 with no success. Therefore, in 2008, LGAs turned to the Parliamentary Board for Local Government for the full ratification of the European Charter for Local Self-Government. The board was receptive to the effort, which prompted the government to prepare amendments to the Law on Ratification of the European Charter and submit it to the parliamentary procedure. The Charter was fully ratified in 2008.

Ratification of the Charter included Article 9(5) which provides for the institution of financial equalization procedures for protection of financially weaker local government units. Generally, small towns and municipalities are fiscally lagging behind larger cities due to economic and demographic reasons which leads to a vicious cycle of increasing urbanization and widening of the urban-rural divide. Based on Article 9(5) of the Charter, the LGA initiated an expert study for fiscal equalization in 2011 and advocated for the institution of financial equalization. The government passed the legislation instituting financial equalization in 2017.

As previously mentioned, the Parliamentary Board for Local Government has an advisory role in Parliament and Parliament can overturn or ignore the advices of the board. Ignoring broadly accepted, non-partisan advice of the LGAs and/or advice of the board, the parliament on occasion passes a legislation violating local government autonomy or adequacy of financial resources guaranteed by the European Charter and the Constitution.

Should any of the LGAs find such a violation is critical, it can file a motion with the Constitutional Court requesting legislation review. The constitutional law on the Constitutional Court allows any individual or organization to file a motion with the Constitutional Court which will review it in a regular process that can take several years to complete. The constitutional law enables local councils to file a motion with the Constitutional Court for resolution within 30 days, should the issue relate to local government structure, competencies or finance. Therefore, LGAs can put a motion forward and provide local councils with a draft motion with request to submit it to the Constitutional Court to expedite the procedure.

In 2016 the parliament passed two laws, the Defense Law and the State Asset Management Law, despite objections of the Association that the laws are violating the right of local governments to freely dispose of own revenues and that the parliament would cross the boundaries of its legislative powers by approving such legislation. The laws exempted state and military facilities from paying the communal fee (a form of property tax or infrastructure impact tax) which is local government own source revenue. The Association filed two motions with the Constitutional Court and asked local councils to support the motion. Five local councils and the County Association supported one motion. In 2017 the Constitutional Court ruled that the parliament actually crossed the boundaries of its legislative powers and the laws violated the right of local governments to freely dispose of local revenues and extensively explained the issue of local government fiscal autonomy for future reference.

However, in 2018 the parliament once again violated the fiscal autonomy of local governments by exempting state and military structures from paying the communal fee, despite extensive efforts of the LGAs to explain the relevant ministry that such regulation was already a subject to constitutional review. Two local governments submitted the motion for review to the Constitutional Court and the Court swiftly confirmed that the law is violating local government fiscal autonomy.

Assessment of the Practice

The examples of successful and unsuccessful intergovernmental dialogue presented above illustrate the two sides of the intergovernmental relations' spectrum in Croatia. High level

institutional intergovernmental relations mechanisms can be mission-critical in pushing forward broadly accepted norms and standards which are sometimes a precondition for improving overall local government environment, including fiscal equalization mechanisms aimed at reducing disparities among urban and rural local governments.

The existence of such advisory mechanisms does not guarantee legislation quality but it does allow different parties, irrespective of their political or economic power, to raise awareness of other stakeholders prior to legislative change. In extreme cases, seeking legal protection from the Court and setting a precedent, can also be seen as an input into (future) intergovernmental dialogue.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 2014

Law no 4/2008 on Ratification of European Charter of Local Self-Government

Law no 85/2015 on Access to the Information

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Bajo A, Bronić M and Primorac M, 'Oblikovanje modela vodoravnog fiskalnog izravnanja u Republici Hrvatskoj' (2012) Udruga gradova

Koprić I, 'Widening the Scope of Local Self-Government Powers and Narrowing Central Government Supervision' (2000) Hrvatska javna uprava 391

Alliance of the Association of Cities and the Association of Municipalities, 'Europska povelja o lokalnoj samoupravi' (*Stari grad*, 2008) <<https://stari-grad.hr/?show=11437&nid=17893>>

HINA, 'Ustavni sud – nema poskupljenja odvoza smeća' (*Lider Media*, 30 January 2020) <<https://lider.media/poslovna-scena/hrvatska/ustavni-sud-nema-poskupljenja-odvoza-smeca-129898>>

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Runtić D, 'Preoblikovanje komunalne naknade i doprinosa u općini prihod' (*Udruga gradova*, 6 March 2012), <<https://www.udruga-gradova.hr/preoblikovanje-komunalne-naknade-i-doprinosu-u-opci-prihod/>>

9. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania

9.1 The System of Local Government in Albania

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Types of Local Governments

With the 2014 Territorial and Administrative Reform (TAR)¹⁹⁶, in Albania there are two types of local self-governments, i.e. the basic level of local self-government consisting in 61 municipalities (*Bashkia*), and the second tier of local self-government made up of 12 regions (*Qarku*).

Municipalities comprise also administrative units, which can be towns and/or villages. In most cases, the administrative units are the former rural communes that were amalgamated with the TAR with their closest and cultural and historical urban centers. The Municipality of Tirana, for example, is subdivided in 24 administrative units, i.e. 11 subdivisions of the former (urban) municipality and 13 (rural) communes that were amalgamated to Tirana with the TAR. The administration of these units is part of the municipal administration and is directed by an administrator who is appointed and dismissed by the mayor. Towns may be divided into smaller units called quarters (*lagje*). As a rule, a quarter can be established in territories with over 20,000 residents. A town's division into quarters and its territory shall be approved upon a decision of the municipal council.

The regions, the second-tier local self-governments in Albania, were and continue to be entrusted with only few general responsibilities for 'coordination and harmonization' of regional policies with national policies and they may also perform any function that is mandated to them by one or more municipalities within the region or the central government. In practice, the regions do not perform any significant responsibility, other than some administrative tasks delegated by the national government.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right of local governments to self-government is enshrined in Article 13 of the Constitution of Albania and the Law on Local Self-Government. The constitution prescribes that local government in Albania is based on the principle of decentralization of powers and is exercised according to the principle of local autonomy. The constitutional standing of the second-tier of

¹⁹⁶ Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania.

local self-government, the regional council (*Këshilli i Qarkut*), is the same as for municipalities, regardless of the fact that they have only a few 'coordination' own responsibilities. Only the municipal council (*Këshilli Bashkiak*) is directly elected. The regional council is composed of members from the elected bodies of the municipalities that make up the region, i.e. mayors and other members that are elected from among municipal councilors of the municipalities that compose the region.

The Law on Local Self-Government prescribes the right and the ability of local governments in Albania to regulate and manage public affairs under their own responsibility, within the limits of the law. The exercise of the right of self-government is guaranteed by additional rights of local governments as juridical persons, the right to own and dispose of property, to raise revenues and make expenditures, to perform economic activity, to cooperate with other local governments, etc. The Law on Local Self-Government prescribes also the basic principles of local government finances, according to which, local governments 'shall be entitled, within national financial policies, to adequate financial resources, commensurate with the responsibilities provided for by the Law' (Article 34).¹⁹⁷

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

All municipalities are entrusted with general competences to carry out all responsibilities relevant to the local community (as prescribed by law), and any other responsibility that is not specifically assigned (by law) to another level of government. Local governments are entrusted with own and delegated functions and responsibilities. Local self-governments have own responsibilities in the core public services and public infrastructure, in the field of education, social protection, culture, recreation and sports, environmental protection, agriculture, rural development, forests and pastures and protection of nature and biodiversity, local economic development and public order and safety including fire protection. Although these are all 'own' local matters, the degree of political and administrative and fiscal powers decentralized to local governments varies significantly from function to function and in any case, in performing these functions, local governments should also respect regional and national policies and standards for service delivery.

The spirit of the new Law on Local Self-Government entails symmetric decentralization of exclusive functions to all new 61 municipalities, regardless of size, capacity or any other condition that may affect service delivery for particular functions. However, the law introduces also the possibility of asymmetrical decentralization to specific municipalities. However, the transfer of specific responsibilities to specific local governments shall be regulated through a separate law.¹⁹⁸ In practice there are a number of cases of asymmetries through transfers of competences to specific local governments for specific purposes, either through a specific law, government decree or a more simple Memorandum of Cooperation between different central and local governments. Examples include the transfer of responsibilities for operating and

¹⁹⁷ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government, Art 34.

¹⁹⁸ Law no 139/2015, dated 17 December 2015, on Local Self-Government, Official Gazette No 249, p16963, Art 21.

maintaining pre-university students' dormitories, the operation of certain social service centers that were previously operated by a specific line ministry and public order, as the municipal police in Tirana may impose fines for the irregular parking within the territory of the municipality, which is a national police competence.

Political and Social Context in Albania

Albania has a relatively young history of democratic local self-government. While an independent country since 1912, for about half a century (1944-1990), Albania suffered a severe totalitarian regime, during which local government meant simply 'local structures of the (central) government'. Albania began the journey of political and administrative decentralization in 1992 with the first local democratic elections. As in many other ex-communist countries, the early reform processes simply focused on laying down the basic concepts and legal framework for decentralization and local self-government to counter a half century legacy of repressive and non-democratic institutions.¹⁹⁹ In the early 2000s Albania adopted decentralization reforms that saw the consolidation of local responsibilities and the introduction of basic instruments for the financing of local responsibilities. The reforms enacted between 2014 and 2017, have been even more impactful. In 2014, the Government of Albania (GoA) consolidated 373 urban and rural local governments into 61 municipalities. In 2015, Parliament passed a new Law on Local Self-Government (LSGL)²⁰⁰ and a new Law on Local Self-Government Finance (LSGFL).²⁰¹ These laws were considered as critical components of a larger strategic plan to expand the role of democratically-elected local governments in Albania by creating larger municipalities and giving them more responsibilities and resources.²⁰²

Following the collapse of the communist regime, the political landscape is dominated by two major parties, the Democratic Party (DP) and the Social Party (SP). The third largest political party is the Socialist Movement for Integration (SMI). The 2013 general elections were won by a coalition between the SP and the SMI that governed together until the general elections of 2017, since when the SP is governing alone. Local politics is controlled by these three major parties. There have been only a few cases of an independent candidate running a local government as a mayor. The latest case when independent mayors run and took office is the local elections of 2007. Between 2007 and 2011 there have been 12 independent mayors out of 373. After 2011, there have been no cases of independent mayors taking office in Albania.

Regarding the social context of local government, it is important to note the massive number of Albanians that have left the country (but that still have Albanian citizenship) since the early 1990s. Only between 2014 and 2018, about 200,000 Albanians have emigrated while about

¹⁹⁹ Stafa Elton and Xhumari Merita, 'Albania: Aligning Territorial and Fiscal Decentralisation' in William Bartlett, Sanja Kmezić and Katarina Đulić (eds), *Fiscal Decentralisation, Local Government and Policy Reversals in Southeastern Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan 2018).

²⁰⁰ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government (LSGL).

²⁰¹ Law no 68/2017 on Local Self-Government Finance (LSGFL).

²⁰² Government of Albania, 'National Crosscutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Government' (adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers no 691 of 29 July 2015).

100,000 have immigrated.²⁰³ As for internal population movements, the 2011 census ascertained that the population living in urban areas for the first time exceeded the population living in rural areas. The resident population in urban areas was 53.5 per cent, while 46.5 per cent lived in rural areas.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania

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Stafa E and Xhumari M, 'Albania: Aligning Territorial and Fiscal Decentralisation' in William Bartlett, Sanja Kmezić and Katarina Đulić (eds), *Fiscal Decentralisation, Local Government and Policy Reversals in Southeastern Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan 2018)

²⁰³ Instat, 'Migration and Migrant Integration' (Instat Institute of Statistics)

<http://www.instat.gov.al/al/temat/treguesit-demografik%C3%AB-dhe-social%C3%AB/migracioni-dhe-integrimi-i-migrant%C3%ABve/#tab2>.

9.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Intergovernmental relations refer to all the processes, mechanisms and institutions in place in a given country through which the various levels of government interact and relate with one another to exercise government power and achieve common or concurrent policy purposes.²⁰⁴ The nature and intensity of intergovernmental relations may differ substantially from country to country depending on the form of the political and legal system, levels of government, territorial and administrative division, socio-economic development, history and tradition, political climate, legal framework etc. Intergovernmental relations in Albania are characterized by both formal as well as informal structures, institutions and processes that build on mechanisms of both supervision and cooperation. As a general rule, Albania's Constitution provides the basic architecture of intergovernmental relations between the various levels of government, while more detailed relations are regulated by law and/or informal practices of exchange and cooperation. A key role in intergovernmental relations, is dedicated to the Associations of Local Authorities in Albania and more recently to the Agency for the Support of Local Self-Government and the Consultative Council between the Central and Local Governments. Similarly, also line ministries and local governments directly play a key role in the regulation and implementation of specific sectoral policies that cross-cut with local government responsibilities.

Within such formal and informal architecture, the different political and economic powers of urban and rural local self-governments may result in a different impact on intergovernmental relations. In fact, larger and more urban local governments are more actively represented in intergovernmental relations. In addition, the proximity of the institutions of Capital City of Tirana with the institutions of the central government, plays a key role in the fact that Tirana is represented in most of the intergovernmental working groups for sectoral policy reforms, as opposed to smaller and more rural local governments. To some extent this is explained also by the different capacities. This is particularly true in the design and revision of intergovernmental fiscal and financial systems that should take into consideration the needs of both urban and rural subnational governments. Furthermore, the political landscape and personalities involved in the key formal institutions definitively play a role in the effectiveness of both formal and informal channels of interaction, even when there is a long-standing and well-established tradition of interaction.

With decentralization processes going on for decades in Albania, local self-governments have become responsible for many public responsibilities which were previously considered an exclusive competence of national governments. This has necessitated a revision of intergovernmental relations and accountabilities. Socio-demographic changes and the movement of citizens from rural to urban areas impose severe pressures on the relationships,

²⁰⁴ John Philimore, 'Understanding Intergovernmental Relations: Key Features and Trends' (2013) 72 *Australian Journal of Public Administration* 228.

responsibilities and capacities of urban and rural local self-government to deliver public services, necessitating a recurrent revision of intergovernmental fiscal relations.

Local Government Associations (LGAs) in Albania have a key role in the intergovernmental relations as they could contribute to consensus building and cooperation, while representing the interests of both urban and rural areas of the newly consolidated local governments. However, the role and impact of LGAs, in addition to tradition and legal statuses is greatly affected by their financial stability; internal democracy in decision-making to effectively represent the potential urban-rural divide and interplay; political climate and polarization; territorial and administrative divisions and reforms; etc.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

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Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Philimore J, 'Understanding Intergovernmental Relations: Key Features and Trends' (2013) 72 Australian Journal of Public Administration 228

9.3 Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination: CLFCC

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Relevance of the Practice

The new Law on Local Self-Government rules that intergovernmental relations in Albania are based on the principle of subsidiarity, consultation and cooperation and that the national government is legally obliged to consult with local self-government units on policies, legislation and norms that have a direct impact on local self-government.²⁰⁵ Furthermore, such consultation is performed through the associations representing local self-governments. From this perspective, intergovernmental dialogue and consultation, as a key element for improved governance, in Albania is directly related to the functioning of Local Government Associations (LGAs). On other hand, in practice, the political landscape in Albania remains constantly tense and highly polarized along party lines resulting in an inability to achieve consensus and forge a unified position on important issues. LGAs, too, remain bifurcated on political lines, and are not able to contribute to the consensus building process.²⁰⁶ The boycott of the opposition in the June 2019 local elections, has further exacerbated the political environment in Albania.

Intergovernmental relations are therefore under continuous pressure. Historically in Albania there have been three LGAs, representing the interests of their constituent communes (Association of Albanian Communes – AAC), municipalities (Association of Albanian Municipalities – AAM) and regions (Association of Regional Councils – ARC). AAC and AAM were created in 1993 and their constituents were all communes and all municipalities in Albania, regardless of the political affiliation of the mayor. In 2009, because of the political tensions, socialist mayors established the Association for Local Autonomy in Albania (ALAA), as a political response to the national government and the inability of AAM leadership to represent the interest of their socialist constituent municipalities, in front of a continuous reduction of local government tax powers and grants. As a result, ALAA continues to represent the interests of socialist mayors, while AAM represents the interests of the center-right democrat mayors. Since then, the participation of the local government associations in the process of consultation with the central government has been carried out, at best, on an ad-hoc basis.²⁰⁷ Further, with the amalgamation of the communes in municipalities with the 2014 Territorial and Administrative Reform, AAC ceased to exist further reducing the scope for bi-partisan

²⁰⁵ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government, Art 10.

²⁰⁶ Peter Clavelle, 'A Perspective on Decentralization in Albania' (Internal Working Document, USAID's Planning and Local Governance Project in Albania PLGP 2017).

²⁰⁷ *ibid.*

dialogue and the opportunities to defend the interests of the rural areas of the new municipalities.

Description of the Practice

To respond to such challenges, a growing focus from Albania's development partners was dedicated to building bi-partisan mechanisms of cooperation and coordination between the various levels of government and the local government associations regardless of their political affiliation. Under the auspices of the new Law on Local Self-Government in 2016, with a Government Decree²⁰⁸ it was established the Central/Local Government Consultative Council, to serve as a non-partisan forum between central and local government officials. The Consultative Council is Albania's first formal structure obliging the central government to consult with local government authorities on draft-policies, draft-laws and other matters affecting local governance. To be sure, before the introduction of the Council, consultation took place through a direct exchange between the national government and the local government associations.

In terms of structures and participating institutions, the Council is composed of 20 members, with an equal participation of members, of which nine representatives of the central government (deputy ministers) and eleven representatives of the local government as follows: nine deputy ministers; the president of the ALAA and two mayors representing ALAA; the president of AAM and two mayors representing AAM; the president of the RCA and two regional council chairmen; the executive director of ALAA and the executive director of AAM. The Deputy Minister of Interior, that covers local governance issues within the government, co-chairs the Consultative Council, together with one of the presidents of the LGAs, on a rotation basis, starting from the LGA that has a larger number of members. The Consultative Council is supported by a technical secretariat, which is the Central Government's Agency for the Support of Local Self-Government, recently established as well to support the implementation of decentralization reforms. As the Consultative Council is obliged to consult also on fiscal and financial matters of importance to local governments, the Ministry of Finance and Economy serves as a technical secretariat.

The legal framework reads that the consultation process within the Council shall be based on: (i) the principles of 'information', by making available to LGAs and all their members all the draft-policies, draft-laws, draft-decrees and draft-strategies that shall be put forward by the central government, before their approval by the government and parliament'; (ii) on the principles of 'consultation' through exchanging, discussing, and putting forward proposals on the draft-policies, draft-laws, draft-decrees and draft-strategies put forward by the central government and that have an impact on local governments; (iii) on the principle of 'engagement' of the LGAs and local self-governments' themselves in the processes of drafting and approving public policies; (iv) on the principle of 'constructive dialogue and cooperation' with all LGAs.

²⁰⁸ Decision of the Council of Ministers no 910/2016 on the Organization and Functioning of the Consultative Council between the Central Government and Local Self-Governments.

Assessment of the Practice

The establishment of the Council holds the promise of improved climate of cooperation between central and local authorities in Albania. The government and many development partners consider the Council as ‘an important milestone’ for local democracy in Albania.²⁰⁹ The results of the first three years of operation of the Council are diverging. From one perspective, through the Council, the number of laws and bylaws that are consulted with local governments has increased exponentially. This could be considered an improvement in intergovernmental dialogue and consultation. On the other hand, effective intergovernmental dialogue and consultation is not a numerical issue. Indeed, many have raised the concern that the discussions in the Council are mostly formal, as the vast majority of its members from both the central and local government level come from the same political party and therefore discussions on core issues and problems are regularly avoided.²¹⁰ The attendance and participation of the Council’s members in the Council’s meetings is also an issue.

There are a number of issues that still need to be addressed, such as the mechanisms in place for setting up the agenda of the Consultative Council meeting, meaning the draft-policies to be discussed – to date, the agenda is set in a closed manner by the Technical Secretariat. This approach forces local governments to discuss what is decided by Technical Secretariat or the line ministries, which may not necessarily be their priority. Over time this would cause fatigue and reduced interest to participate. Secondly, and equally important, some follow up procedures should be put in place, securing the actual implementation of decisions or local government’ proposals so that LGAs and local governments feel that participation in the Consultative Council meeting leads to action and that their efforts and proposals are taken into consideration and are followed up. The frequent organization of the meetings on a monthly basis, and the very dense agenda leave little room for discussions. And even when such room is provided, local government voice is still very much divided on political affiliation. Some observers consider the Consultative Council more like another instrument at the disposal of the central government and a way to circumvent LGAs, in particular the one representing the interests of those local governments affiliated with the opposition.

There are no major differences as regard how the Consultative Council discusses issues that affect urban and rural local governments. Unfortunately, to date little attention is being paid to the urban and rural divide in Albania, although some concerns are emerging, because the gains of the Territorial and Administrative Reform and the other decentralization reforms

²⁰⁹ Bekim Murati, ‘Intergovernmental Dialogue and Consultation Lead to Better Policies’ (XI Newsletter, USAID PLGP 2019) <https://www.plgp.al/wp-content/uploads/PLGP-Newsletter-11-English_web.pdf> accessed 19 May 2019.

²¹⁰ Haxhimali A, ‘Local Government in Albania. Status Report’ (Albanian Association of Municipalities 2019)

enacted recently, are uneven across municipalities and there are questions about whether some of them are adequately servicing their newly incorporated rural areas.²¹¹

On a more general note, it is important to highlight that the Consultative Council should be seen as an instrument to complement the role and work of the LGAs, which remain the key interlocutors for the national government in particular in the early stages of the design of public policies. When policies are presented to the Council, they are already in their pre-final form. On this end, LGAs play a fundamental role in the intergovernmental relations in Albania and the quality and effectiveness of the intergovernmental relations depend on the effective functioning of the associations.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Decision of the Council of Ministers no 910/2016 on the Organization and Functioning of the Consultative Council between the Central Government and Local Self-Governments

Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

— ‘Mechanisms and opportunities to support and promote the Central Government and Local Self-government Consultative Council (CC) of Albania’ (Research Paper, Council of Europe, October 2018)

Clavelle P, ‘A Perspective on Decentralization in Albania’ (Internal Working Document, USAID’s Planning and Local Governance Project in Albania PLGP 2017)

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Philimore J, ‘Understanding Intergovernmental Relations: Key Features and Trends’ (2013) 72 Australian Journal of Public Administration 228

United Nations Development Program (UNDP) Office in Albania, ‘Governance Perception in a Reforming Albania: Nationwide Local Governance Mapping in Albania 2020’ (Survey conducted by IDRA Research & Consulting and Human Development Promotion Center (HDPC) 2020)

²¹¹ United Nations Development Program (UNDP) Office in Albania, ‘Governance Perception in a Reforming Albania: Nationwide Local Governance Mapping in Albania 2020’ (Survey conducted by IDRA Research & Consulting and Human Development Promotion Center (HDPC) 2020)

10. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Moldova

10.1 The System of Local Government in Moldova

Viorel Girbu, *Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova, NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Types of Local Governments

The Republic of Moldova is organized in *rayons*, cities, villages and the Autonomous Region of Gagauzia. The administrative and territorial organization of the country is based on two levels: villages (communes), sectors (of the Chisinau municipality) and cities (municipalities) constitute the first level; *rayons*, Chisinau municipality and Balti municipality constitute the second level. Chisinau municipality is the capital city of the country and its status is regulated by the organic law. Urban localities are classified on four ranks according to a list of indicators that describe their level of social and economic development. Cities that meet specific requirements established by law could be assigned with the status of a municipality.

A total number of 32 *rayons* and 1495 localities (from which 32 are part of the Autonomous Region of Gagauzia) exist in Moldova (excluding the breakaway Transnistrian Region of Moldova). From the total list of localities, 66 are urban localities, including 53 cities and 13 municipalities and 832 are rural localities. 597 localities do not have own administration as they are part of a bigger administrative entity.

Legal Status of Local Governments

In fulfilling their competences, the local public administration authorities have autonomy, enshrined and guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, the European Charter of Local Self-Government and by other treaties to which the Republic of Moldova is a party. According to Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, 'public administration in the administrative-territorial units is based on the principles of local autonomy, decentralization of public services, eligibility of the local public administration authorities and consultation of citizens in the local issues of special interest.'

The public administration authorities, through whom local autonomy is exercised in villages and cities, are the elected local councils and the elected mayors. Local councils and mayors act, under the conditions of the law, as autonomous administrative authorities and manage public affairs of villages and cities. The *rayon* council coordinates the activity of the village and city councils in order to realize the public services of district interest. The *rayon* council is elected and functions according to the law.

The relations between the local public authorities are based on the principles of autonomy, legality and collaboration in solving common problems. In order to ensure local autonomy, the local public administration authorities elaborate, approve and manage autonomously their budgets and have the right to implement local taxes and to establish their amount according to the law.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

For the first-level local authorities, the following own fields of activity are established:

- urban planning and management of green areas of local interest;
- collection and management of household waste, including the cleaning and maintenance of land for their storage;
- distribution of drinking water, construction and maintenance of sewage and wastewater treatment systems;
- construction, maintenance and lighting of local public streets and roads, local public transport;
- arrangement and maintenance of cemeteries;
- administration of goods from local public and private domains;
- construction, management, maintenance and equipping of pre-school and out-of-school institutions (nurseries, kindergartens, art schools, music);
- development and management of urban gas and heat distribution networks;
- cultural, sporting, recreational and youth activities, as well as the planning, development and management of the infrastructures necessary for these types of activities;
- arranging agricultural markets, commercial spaces;
- carrying out any other measures necessary for the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- establishment and management of municipal enterprises and organization of any other activity necessary for the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- the construction of houses and the granting of other types of facilities for the socially vulnerable population, as well as for other categories of the population;
- organization of territorial services (stations) of rescuers and firefighters, contributing, in accordance with the law, to the protection of the cultural heritage and monuments in the administered territory.

For the second-level local public authorities, the following own fields of activity are established:

- administration of assets in the public and private areas of the district;
- planning and administering the construction, maintenance and management works of some public objectives of *rayon* interest;
- construction, administration and repair of the roads of district interest, as well as of the road infrastructure;
- organization of passenger car transport, administration of buses and car stations of *rayon* interest;

- establishing a general framework for the development of the territory at *rayon* level and the protection of the forests of *rayon* interest;
- supporting and stimulating the initiatives regarding the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- elaboration and implementation of the projects of construction of the interurban gas pipelines (including the medium pressure gas pipelines), of other thermo-energetic objectives with local destination;
- maintenance of primary schools, kindergartens and high schools, vocational secondary education institutions, boarding schools and boarding schools with special regime, other institutions in the field of education that serve the population of the respective district, as well as other methodical activities from the field;
- administration of cultural, tourism and sports institutions of *rayon* interest, other cultural and sporting activities of *rayon* interest;
- administration of municipal enterprises of district interest;
- administration of social assistance units of district interest;
- development and management of community social services for socially vulnerable categories, monitoring the quality of social services;
- contribution, under the conditions of the law, to the protection of the cultural heritage and monuments in the administered territory.

Local public authorities of the first and second levels, within the limits of the law, have full freedom of action in the regulation and management of any matter of local interest which is not assigned to another authority. Other competences specific to the local public authorities can only be assigned to them by law.

The competences pertaining to the central public authorities can be delegated to the local public authorities by the first and second levels, respecting the criteria of efficiency and economic rationality. The delegation of powers may be performed by the parliament. The delegation of powers may concern all local public authorities of the first and second levels (general delegation) or only some local public authorities. The delegation of powers shall be accompanied by the provision of the necessary and sufficient financial resources for their realization.

Political and Social Context in Moldova

The resident population of the Republic of Moldova at the beginning of 2019 was 2.68 million, decreasing by 1.8 per cent compared to the same period of 2018. The main reason for the decrease in the number of the resident population is negative net migration that increased from –24,600 people in 2014 to –48,600 people in 2018. As far as internal population movements are concerned, about 57 per cent of the population lives in rural areas. According to the 2014 census, about 17 per cent of the population lives in the capital city of the country, Chisinau municipality.

The general local elections, the 7th electoral exercise since the proclamation of the independence of the Republic of Moldova, took place in 2019 throughout the territory of the

country, including in the localities of Gagauzia, except for the settlements under the control of the unrecognized administration in Transnistria. The highest number of mayors come from the social-democratic Democratic Party of Moldova (261), the former ruling party of Moldova, followed by the Party of Socialists of the Republic of Moldova (206) that are currently governing the country and representatives of the opposition electoral block ACUM (172) and SOR party (43). A total number of 112 city halls are led by independent candidates and a remaining 99 city halls are led by extra-parliamentary political parties.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, 1994

Law no 764/2001 on Administrative-Territorial Organization of the Republic of Moldova

Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization

Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration

10.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Moldova: An Introduction

Viorel Girbu, *Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova, NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Intergovernmental relations in Moldova are regulated according to the Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration. According to Article 6 of this law, the local and district councils, mayors and district presidents are autonomous administrative authorities, solving the public affairs of villages (communes), cities (municipalities) and districts. The relations between the central and local public authorities are based on the principles of autonomy, legality, transparency and collaboration in solving common problems. There is no relation of subordination between the central and local authorities, and between the first level and the second level public authorities, except for the cases provided by law. Any administrative control exercised over the activity carried out by the local public authorities must not pursue another purpose than ensuring the observance of legality and of constitutional principles, and the control of opportunity may aim only at achieving the competences delegated to local public authorities (LPAs), under the law. The central public administration authorities consult the representative associations of the LPA authorities in the issues related to the local public administration.

The principle of consultation on the issues related to the local public administration is an important reference in the intergovernmental relations in Moldova. This principle is stated also by the Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization that refers to the principle of institutional dialogue, as a situation which involves informing and consulting, in due time, local public authorities, in the planning and decision-making process, through their associative structures, on any issues that concern them directly or are related to the process of administrative decentralization.

To facilitate intergovernmental dialogue and consultations, the Law on Administrative Decentralization prescribed the creation of the Joint Decentralization Commission. Such a parity commission in the area of decentralization with the participation of the representatives of LPA associations was created in 2008.²¹² The Commission is composed of representatives of the national and local governments, to ensure communication and institutionalized dialogue between the central government and LPAs. Nevertheless, for a long time, the lack of a unified voice of local authorities has negatively influenced advocacy for local government reforms.

The Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova (CALM) plays a fundamental role in intergovernmental relations in Moldova. CALM was constituted in March 2010,²¹³ by territorial administrative units organized under the law as towns and villages and by their professional associations. This level of membership provides both capacity and political consolidation. Nowadays CALM is the largest and most representative association of local authorities in

²¹² Government Decree no 93/2008, substituted by the Government Decree no 608/2010.

²¹³ 'About us' (*Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova*, last updated 2021) <<https://www.calm.md/despre-noi/>>.

Moldova. It provides legal advice and supports local autonomy and decentralization. CALM represents 800 LPAs as members with full rights out of the 898 existing in Moldova. Even after the establishment of CALM, it took many years before the voice of local authorities became sufficiently important, heard and taken into account by central authorities.

Despite CALM being an active player in the area of decentralization and having now a high degree of representability of first level LPAs, dialog and intergovernmental relations between local and the central governments remains challenging. Due to political instability and the lack of political commitment to advance reforms, the Joint Decentralization Commission has not been able to serve as a successful platform for intergovernmental relations. Following an opinion expressed by CALM, '[u]nfortunately, all communication, consultation and dialogue between LPA/CALM and the government has disappeared. And the current legal format of communication and dialogue between central and local authorities has proven to be non-functional, selective and formal.'²¹⁴ Recent Post-monitoring assessments developed by the Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe enforced this ascertainment, stating that '[o]f special concern was the fact that no appropriate consultation mechanisms could be identified between central government and local authorities.'

During 2017, in spite of the fact that this was a decisive year for the implementation of the Decentralization Strategy and other commitments in the field of decentralization and strengthening local autonomy, the Joint Decentralization Commission has not convened at all. Intergovernmental relations over the past three years continued to be formal, with central authorities preferring to unilaterally promote their political vision, through the development of the legislation without proper consideration of the interests of the LPAs, in the areas that target also the interests of the local communities.

Overall, intergovernmental consultation mechanisms are not sufficiently institutionalized and consolidated in Moldova. However, some progress in the institutionalized dialogue between CALM and the government is observed. CALM obtained the right to attend the weekly meetings of the Government Cabinet and the meetings of the Committee of General Secretaries of the Government (the structure which initially examines the draft normative acts before their approval by the government). Similarly, dialogue with parliamentary commissions has been consolidated and institutional dialogue with ministries and public agencies has been established.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization

Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration

²¹⁴ 'Congresul Autorităților Locale, extrem de îngrijorat de starea democrației locale' (*Stiri MD*, 1 December 2017) <<https://stiri.md/article/social/congresul-autoritatilor-locale-extrem-de-ingrijorat-de-starea-democratiei-locale>>.

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe, 'Post-Monitoring Report on the Republic of Moldova' (2020)

10.3 Inter- and Intragovernmental Relations through the Professional Networks of the Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova

Viorel Girbu, *Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova, NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Relevance of the Practice

While achieving consensus on major policy areas between levels of government has proven quite challenging, yet, there are also cases where it is easier to find a common ground for both, central and local authorities to achieve a workable solution for local communities. In order to overcome difficulties at the strategical level, and to boost cooperation and communication between central and local constituencies, during 2019 the Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova (CALM) has developed professional networks of local authorities. These networks are represented by professionals from both the urban and rural local administrations. This provides fertile ground for mutual cooperation and effort in order to achieve solutions, regardless the differences that exist between urban and rural local governments in terms of needs and priorities.

The professional networks of CALM play an important role in intergovernmental relations with regard to specific thematic areas such as local public finance management, local tax administration and land management. Also, being member of the network provides the opportunity to share experiences and gather new knowledge in a continuing changing environment. The functions of the network of professionals therefore include the preservation of collective experience, communication and mutual assistance among members as one of the major goals of the network.

Description of the Practice

To address technical issues that concern local public authorities (LPAs), CALM has established four professional networks covering the domain of public accounting, tax collection, land management and mayors' secretaries. These professional networks were based upon experience accumulated by CALM in managing the network of women mayors and the network of cities that were previously developed. The issues addressed by the professional networks refer to domains like organization of the work of the respective professionals, legal regulation, IT solutions and systems etc. Identification of bottlenecks and malfunctions, and the final improvement of performance, through a joint cooperation across levels of government is the common goal of all the networks. From this perspective, the network addresses also issues related to the urban/rural divide, given specificity of mostly small rural communities in Moldova.

The members of the networks are professionals employed in the domain that concerns the respective network. Expertise in the thematic area is one of the key criteria for membership in the network, regardless of the size of the represented community. This proves to be an efficient way of organization to overcome the problematic realities of the urban-rural divide and interplay.

The networks are organized according to the statute of CALM. Each locality, which is a member of CALM, regardless of size, can decide on delegation of professionals from the local administration to take part in activities of the respective professional network. There are no additional requirements. Each network is entitled with the right to elect its leadership. The networks in this respect have full autonomy regarding their own organization and activity. Local authorities that are not represented in CALM can also delegate their representative professionals to be part of the network, although without the right to vote.

The professional networks are oriented to tackling specific challenges encountered by LPAs in the delivery of services to citizens. Once a problem is identified, a short survey is organized to gather the experience of other members of the network on the topic. Frequently, obstacles faced in daily activity can be solved by sharing the experience of the most versed members of the network. In the case of a systemic problem, members of the network, with the support of CALM's secretariat, develop a detailed description of the problem which is then sent to the competent central authority in order to find a solution. This approach obtained a positive assessment also from the central authorities.

The major goals of the network relate to:

- promoting, defending and representing the general professional rights and interests of its members, in relations with public authorities and national and international organizations, through CALM;
- ensuring the protection of the rights and interests of its members; defending and promoting the specific professional rights and interests of its members in the decision-making process at national level;
- addressing issues of importance to local public administrations;
- submitting appropriate policy recommendations to CALM governing bodies, government decision-makers and service delivery institutions;
- ensuring the connection with the governing bodies of CALM, with reference to the subjects that affect the activity of its members;
- assisting its members in the planning and implementation of programs, which address important issues affecting their work in local communities;
- increasing the professional capacities of its members through the development of study and training programs, as well as professional development courses; establishing a mentoring system for its members with little experience and, in particular, providing the necessary training and assistance;
- establishing partnerships with other organizations and public institutions, for the promotion of professional rights and interests;
- organizing study visits and exchanges of experience, including at international level;
- fostering and facilitating the cooperation of its members with professionals from similar organizations at national and international level;

- establishing a communication network for its members, as a means of disseminating information and exchanging views, including at international level;
- ensuring regular information about the activities of the network, as well as contributing columns or interviews to CALM's newspaper 'Voice of Local Authorities'.

During 2020, the network of accountants and network of tax collectors organized two meetings bringing together about 100 professionals from each of the networks and representatives of the state organizations, including the Ministry of Finance, State Chancellery, Agency of Public Services and State Fiscal Service. The exchanges have proved very effective in providing an opportunity to both levels of government to speak about challenges faced by first-tier local governments and measures approved by the national government.

While the Ministry of Finance of Moldova has an established practice of institutional exchanges with second-tier local governments, there is no practice of coordination and exchange with first-tier local governments, which are in this way neglected and forced to resort to second-tier LPAs for coordination with the Ministry. From this perspective, CALM professional forum meetings provided an opportunity for first-tier LPAs to better present the situation in local communities, specifically in small, remote rural localities, to the central government authorities.

Assessment of the Practice

There are already a few events organized by each of the networks. This practice initiated during 2019 and continued since then. The usage of the common online and virtual communication platforms by the members of the network is encouraging. The participants of the platforms share their opinion, experiences and provide advice on the questions raised by its members. The platform is used almost on a daily basis proving its utility as a tool for exchanging experiences and communicating deficiencies in its domain. Some of the problems that emerged through discussions on the communication platform have already found a solution, as it is for example improving functionality of the 'E-DOCPLAT' program that is mandatory in the activity of accountants within the LPAs in Moldova.

The experience of communication based on the virtual platforms proved efficient during the current epidemiological crisis. Throughout 2020, there have been several virtual meetings between the members of the network and representatives of the central authorities. Following these meetings professionals from the local administration found guidance on how to find a proper solution on current issues that emerged as a result of the crisis. Similarly, central authorities used these platforms in order to get better understanding on the challenges faced by local communities and thereby inform decisions at the national level.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Website of the CALM Accountants Network, <<https://www.calm.md/categorie/reteaua-contabililor-din-cadrul-calm/>>

Website of the Professional Network of Specialists in Tax Collection,
<<https://www.calm.md/categorie/reteaua-profesionala-a-specialistilor-in-percepere-fiscala/>>

Website of the Professional Network of Specialists in the Field of Land Ownership Regulation within CALM, <<https://www.calm.md/categorie/reteaua-profesionala-a-specialistilor-in-domeniul-reglementarii-proprietatii-funciare-din-cadrul-calm/>>

Website of CALM Secretaries, <<https://www.calm.md/categorie/reteaua-secretarilor-din-cadrul-calm/>>

11. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in South Africa

11.1 The System of Local Government in South Africa

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Types of Local Governments

South Africa has a multilevel system of government organised at national, provincial and local level. There are nine provincial governments while the local sphere of government is constituted by 257 municipalities. The 1996 Constitution of South Africa recognises three categories of municipalities – Category A, B and C.²¹⁵ Metropolitan municipalities (Category A) have exclusive municipal executive and legislative authority in their respective areas of jurisdiction. Local municipalities (Category B), which currently total 205, share their municipal executive and legislative authority with district municipalities (Category C) within the relevant area they fall. District municipalities exercise their municipal executive and legislative authority in an area that covers more than one local municipality. These umbrella municipalities (currently 44) were established, among other reasons, to provide support and maximise on economies of scale in areas where there are low capacity municipalities. At policy level, the three broad categories of municipalities (A, B and C) are further broken down into seven sub-categories namely:

- A - metropolitan municipalities;
- B1 - secondary cities, local municipalities with the largest budgets;
- B2 - local municipalities with a large town as core;
- B3 - local municipalities with small towns, with relatively small population and significant proportion of urban population but with no large town as core;
- B4 - local municipalities which are mainly rural with communal tenure and with, at most, one or two small towns in their area;
- C1 - district municipalities which are not water services authorities; and
- C2 - district municipalities which are water services authorities.

National departments often make use of this sub-classification when dealing with municipalities.

The Constitution assigns to local government service delivery responsibilities and a development mandate. It equips local government with a variety of powers – legislative (the power to adopt by-laws), executive, fiscal, budget and administrative powers - to enable the delivery of these responsibilities and obligations. The functional areas of local government are enumerated in Schedule 4 (part B) and Schedule 5 (part B) of the Constitution. These schedules

²¹⁵ See Sec 155(1) of the Constitution.

list matters, such as water supply, and electricity reticulation, land use planning, municipal health, local roads, and refuse removal. The principles of subsidiarity and assignment recognised in the Constitution provide opportunities for municipalities to exercise additional functions.

Legal Status of Local Governments

Unlike in many countries, local government is recognised in the Constitution of South Africa as a sphere of government.²¹⁶ Thus, the existence of the institution of local government is not dependent on the goodwill of the national and provincial governments. This security of existence is extended to individual municipalities which may not be arbitrarily abolished or merged. Such abolishment or merger can only take place in terms of law and subject to oversight procedures that include the role of an independent body, the Municipal Demarcation Board.

The autonomy of municipalities is constitutionally recognised and can be enforced through the courts. Municipalities have a right to govern their respective areas and this right is only limited by the Constitution. The national and provincial governments may, however, regulate the exercise of this right but subject to limitations imposed by the Constitution. For instance, such regulation mainly takes the form of framework legislation that may not go to the 'core' of municipal functions as that is reserved for the legislative authority of municipal councils. National and provincial governments are further prohibited from impeding or compromising a municipality's ability to exercise this right whether by legislative or other means (Section 151(4) of the Constitution). Thus, it can be observed that unlike in many other countries, the Constitution of South Africa entrenches the existence and autonomy of local government that is jealously guarded by the courts in practice.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As explained above, there are three categories of municipalities in South Africa – metropolitan, local and district. The Constitution allocates to all metropolitan municipalities equal powers and functions. As opposed to metropolitan municipalities that have exclusive executive and legislative authority in their areas of jurisdiction, legislation and policy defines the division of responsibilities between district and local municipalities. As stated above, within the category of district municipalities there are those that have been designated as water services authorities and those that are not.

The Constitution entrenches the principles of subsidiarity and assignment which if implemented can also result in municipalities within and across categories exercising varying powers. Section 156(4) of the Constitution requires the national and provincial governments to assign to a municipality any of their functions if the function can 'most effectively be administered locally and the municipality has the capacity to administer it'. This provision is

²¹⁶ See Sec 40(1) of the Constitution.

being implemented with respect to some functional areas of the national and provincial governments. For example, metropolitan municipalities, which tend to have significant capacity, are already involved in the delivery of housing even though it is a national and provincial competence. Thus, there is a fair degree of asymmetry in the South African system of local government.

However, the Constitution does not explicitly state that the asymmetry at local level is strictly there to respond to the urban-rural distinction. In practice, nonetheless, district municipalities generally operate in rural and semi-rural areas while metropolitan municipalities and secondary cities (B1) govern in mostly urban areas. Thus, it can be concluded that the local government system is designed in such a way that enables it to respond or adjust to the urban-rural interplay, among other differences present at the local level.

Political and Social Context in South Africa

The ushering of a democratic era in 1994 brought hope to a country that had been ravaged by years of apartheid. Under apartheid, the state, economy and society were organised strictly on the basis of race.²¹⁷ The system benefited whites while the majority black population, as well as the minority Indian/Asian and coloured minority groups, were marginalised, deprived of equal economic opportunities and political representation to a different degree, and the former relegated to third class citizens. Since coming to power in 1994, under the leadership of Nelson Mandela, the majority led government of the African National Congress (ANC) has been confronted with a major challenge of undoing or redressing the injustices and legacy of apartheid. A variety of transformation interventions have been adopted in line with the demands of one of the most transformative constitutions in the world, the 1996 Constitution.

These interventions have recorded successes in some areas while failures are common in a number of areas, such as spatial transformation, with apartheid spatial landscape largely remaining intact 27 years after the end of apartheid.²¹⁸ Corruption and skills deficit, among other problems, continue to undermine the capability of the state to meet its obligation and development priorities at all levels of government.²¹⁹ The slow growth of one of Africa's largest economies has not made the situation any better. South Africa's GDP is estimated to grow by merely 1.5, 1.7 and 2.1 per cent in 2019, 2020 and 2021, respectively.²²⁰ The unemployment rate, which in the second quarter of 2019 stood at 29 per cent, is another indicator of an economy in trouble.²²¹ It is thus without doubt that the economy is failing to generate sufficient resources, at a faster rate, for the state to cater for the needs of its estimated 58,78

²¹⁷ See Nico Steytler and Jaap de Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2009) 1-3 to 1-9.

²¹⁸ Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood, 'Introduction' in Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood (eds), *The Journey to Transform Local Government* (Juta 2019) 1.

²¹⁹ See Patricia Ntliziywana, 'Professionalisation of Local Government in South Africa' in Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood (eds), *The Journey to Transform Local Government* (Juta 2019) 59.

²²⁰ National Treasury, 'Municipal Budget Circular for the 2019/20 MTREF' (MFMA Circular no 94, Municipal Finance Management Act No 56 of 2003, May 2019) 2.

²²¹ Statistics South Africa (2019) <<http://www.statssa.gov.za/>> accessed 30 July 2019.

million population (mid 2019 estimate).²²² This partially explains why poverty remains widespread, inequalities continue to deepen and universal access to basic services remains a dream for many South Africans.

The citizens have been impatient with the ANC government's performance in the last few years.²²³ The political dominance of the ANC, reflected by, among other things, its two-thirds majority in the National Assembly in the early years of the democratic era, has slowly been eroded. In the 2019 elections, the ruling party won by 56 per cent of the national vote and narrowly won Gauteng province while the opposition, Democratic Alliance, kept its majority in the Western Cape province. At local government level, after the 2016 local government elections, the ruling party is no longer in control of four key metropolitan municipalities. Of the four, one is the legislative capital (City of Cape Town), the other is the administrative capital (Tshwane) while the City of Johannesburg is the economic hub of the country. Some form of coalition governments were formed in Johannesburg, Tshwane and Nelson Mandela Bay following the failure by any of the political parties to acquire a majority in these municipalities.

The metropolitan regions and cities remain key attraction points for people from rural areas in search for better economic opportunities. By 2017, over 67 per cent of the total population of South Africa was already residing in urban areas, including cities.²²⁴ Consequently, rural areas have been left with a thin base to tap resources such as skilled manpower, a development which undermines their capacity to deliver. On the other hand, the infrastructure in these metropolitan areas is overwhelmed by the large-scale inward emigration and is failing to cope, as a result. For instance, a significant number of the population in these metropolitan regions still resides in informal settlements with no or limited access to basic public services. Even if such services were to be provided, a large portion of people in these areas are not able to pay due to incapacity. Thus, local government, which is positioned at the heart of state public service delivery in South Africa,²²⁵ continues to face a variety of challenges, which are both within and outside of its control.

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²²² *ibid.*

²²³ See Ntliziywana, 'Professionalisation of Local Government in South Africa', above, 59, 61, 63.

²²⁴ See Statista, 'South Africa: Urbanization from 2009 to 2019' (*Statista*, 2020)

<<https://www.statista.com/statistics/455931/urbanization-in-south-africa/>> accessed 9 December 2019.

²²⁵ See Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 1-3.

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11.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in South Africa: An Introduction

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The Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act (IGRFA) establishes lines of communication and provides the institutional framework for interaction between national, provincial, and local spheres of government and all other organs of state.²²⁶ The IGRFA aims to provide certainty, coherence, transparency and stability and to facilitate effective and coherent developmental outcomes as envisaged by the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996. Section 40(1) describes the three spheres of government as ‘distinctive, interdependent and interrelated’. Each sphere has autonomy to make final decisions within its areas of competence and there is a two-way relationship of regulation and oversight in order to be a coherent government.²²⁷ The two main approaches to IGR are supervision and cooperation (Sections 100 and 139 of the Constitution).

Supervision

Section 151(3) of the Constitution stipulates that ‘a municipality has a right to govern, on its own initiative, the local government affairs of its community, subject to national and provincial legislation’. Further, Section 156 (1) grants exclusive legislative and executive authority to pass by-laws and administer local government matters listed in Schedules 4B and 5B, and any matters assigned by national or provincial government. However, National and provincial governments have legislative and executive authority to ensure that local governments perform their functions effectively in relation to matters listed in Schedules 4 and 5 (Sections 156(1) and 155(7) of the Constitution). This includes first, the power to ‘regulate’, which in the context of local government was interpreted by the Constitutional Court in the *Habitat* as follows: ‘It follows that “regulating” in Section 155(7) means creating norms and guidelines for the exercise of a power or the performance of a function. It does not mean the usurpation of the power or the performance of the function itself. This is because the power of regulation is afforded to national and provincial government in order “to see to the effective performance by municipalities of their functions”’. The constitutional scheme does not envisage the province employing appellate power over municipalities’ exercise of their planning functions. This is so even where the zoning, subdivision or land-use permission has province-wide implications.’²²⁸ Secondly, the national and provincial governments ‘monitor’ municipalities, which includes

²²⁶ Act 13 of 2005.

²²⁷ Nico Steytler, Yonatan Fessha and Coel Kirkby, ‘Status Quo Report on Intergovernmental Relations Regarding Local Government’ (Community Law Center CAGE Project, now Dullah Omar Institute 2006) <<https://dullahomarinate.org.za/multilevel-govt/publications/status-quo-report-on-provincial-local-igr.pdf>> accessed 30 July 2019.

²²⁸ Nico Steytler and Jaap de Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2018) 5-24 (12A); *Minister of Local Government, Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, Western Cape v The Habitat Council and Others; Minister of Local Government, Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, Western Cape v City of Cape Town and Others* 2014 (5) BCLR 591 (CC) (Habitat CC) [22].

promoting the development of local capacity in order for local governments to perform their functions and to manage their affairs (Section 155(6)(a) of the Constitution).²²⁹ Thirdly, national and provincial governments have powers to 'intervene' in municipalities that fail to fulfil their constitutional or legislative obligations. There are four types of interventions: regular, discretionary 'serious financial problems', mandatory budgetary interventions, and mandatory 'financial crisis' interventions (Section 139 of the Constitution). The Municipal Systems Act (MSA) and Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) contain further provisions pertaining to the monitoring powers of provincial and national government over local government.²³⁰

Cooperation

Chapter 3 of the Constitution sets out general values and principles for cooperation such as mutual trust and good faith (Section 41 (1)(h)). All three spheres are required to build friendly relations, assist and support each other, coordinate actions and legislation, adhere to procedures, avoid legal proceedings against each other, and inform and consult each other on matters of common interest (Section 41(1)(h) of the Constitution). IGRFA established IGR forums and institutions that facilitate the realisation of these normative principles, for example, through compulsory IGR procedures such as the Division of Revenue Act which must go through each sphere of government (through participatory processes for local government, and legislative processes for provincial and national government) before it becomes law. Although Section 4 IGRFA stipulates that the objects of the act are to create a coherent government, the act focuses on IGR structures as opposed to principles; hierarchies are embedded in some of the IGR structures and national government is dominant in steering IGR, making IGR an object of the centre, and not a collaboration of equal partners.²³¹ Further, the principles are normative, and in certain instances, such as in *Ngwathe Local Municipality v Eskom Holdings SoC Ltd and Others*,²³² perceived failure to implement the principles of cooperation may lead to litigation. In this case, the local Municipality of Ngwathe failed to pay its electricity bill to Eskom, and when Eskom threatened to disconnect the electricity supply, Ngwathe local municipality instituted legal action on the basis that Eskom, as an organ of state, had a legal obligation to respect the functional or institutional integrity of Ngwathe local municipality.

Intergovernmental Forums and Institutions

The IGRFA creates intergovernmental forums, where executives of the three spheres of government meet (Section 41(2) of the Constitution). Deemed as the main coordinating body at national level, the President's Coordinating Council (PCC) consists of the President, the Deputy President, relevant Ministers in the Presidency, Finance and Public Service respectively, Premiers from each of the nine provinces and a municipal councillor designated by SALGA. The PCC is a consultative forum for the President to raise matters of national interest with

²²⁹ See also Secs 105 and 106 of the Municipal Systems Act (MSA) 32 of 2000.

²³⁰ MSA Act 32 of 2000; Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) 56 of 2003.

²³¹ Nico Steytler; 'Cooperative and Coercive Models of Intergovernmental Relations: A South African Case Study' in Thomas J Courchene and others (eds), *The Federal Idea: Essays in Honour of Ronald L. Watts* (1 ed, Queen's School of Policy Studies 2011).

²³² [2015] ZAFSHC 104 (28 May 2015).

provinces and organised local government, to consult them on the implementation of national policy, co-ordination and alignment of priorities, and to discuss strategic priorities inter alia. Because the PCC is hierarchical, it tends to be a forum for the President to tell provinces and municipalities what to do, and to detect failures by provinces and municipalities. This leaves very little room for SALGA to make substantial contributions, and if it does, it is difficult to see these translated into policy reform as the agenda is set by the President in terms of Section 8(1)b IGRFA. However, proposals for the agenda can be submitted to the Minister in the Presidency. The IGRFA requires only one member of SALGA to be in attendance- the municipal councillor. The municipal councillor is selected from among SALGA members (as SALGA is organised local government and represents all municipalities in South Africa). The IGRFA does not specify the frequency of meetings of the PCC, but it simply requires that the PCC meets, at the behest of the President of the Republic (Section 8(1)(a)), to oversee and ensure alignment between the spheres and implementation of national policies and legislation.

Further, each national department has a national IGR forum where Ministers meet with Members of the (Provincial) Executive (MinMECs) and a national councillor from SALGA, provided the subject matter of the specific MinMec deals with a matter assigned to local governments in terms of Schedule 4B or 5B. Section 18 IGRFA stipulates that MinMECs are a consultative forum 'for' the relevant cabinet member to facilitate alignment between the national and provincial spheres on topical or sectoral issues. MinMECs are hierarchical and can become 'instruments of centralised control' and 'vehicles of command'.²³³ There is also a variation called the Local Government Ministerial and Member of the (provincial) Executive forum (LGMinMEC), which invites local government into joint sessions with the provincial and national executive.²³⁴ The reports of the MinMEC must be submitted to the President's Coordinating Council. In this way, issues raised by provincial MEC and SALGA will be presented to the President through the PCC.

The Premier's IGR Forum (PIF) is a horizontal forum for the Premier and mayors of district and metropolitan municipalities. The PIF comprises of the Premier of a specific province, provincial cabinet members, mayors of metropolitan and district municipalities, and a representative of SALGA. Unlike the PCC and MinMECs, the PIF is a forum for the premier 'and' local government in the relevant province, and the PIF is inherently and in practice, consultative and egalitarian. One of the crucial ways in which SALGA's voice can influence law and policy is that the PIF may discuss draft legislation and draft national policies relating to matters that affect provinces and/or local governments. The Premier sets the agenda, and meeting dates, but proposals for the agenda can be submitted to Premier ahead of the PIF. In practice, each province sets its own frequency of meetings, some meeting twice a year and other four times a year or as the need arises.

The District Intergovernmental Forum (DIF) is a forum for the district mayor and local mayors in his/her jurisdiction. Intergovernmental institutions such as the Budget Council (which is part

²³³ Nico Steytler, 'National Cohesion and Intergovernmental Relations in South Africa' in Nico Steytler and Yash Pal-Ghai (eds), *Kenyan-South African Dialogue on Devolution* (Juta 2016) 313.

²³⁴ Derek Powell, 'Constructing a Developmental State in South Africa: The Corporatisation of Intergovernmental Relations' in Johanne Poirier, Cheryl Saunders and John Kincaid (eds), *Intergovernmental Relations in Federal Systems* (Oxford University Press 2015) 327.

of the finance MinMEC), the Budget Forum of Local Government, the National Council of Provinces and the Financial and Fiscal Commission (FFC) also bring the three spheres of government together.

Organised Local Government

South African Local Government Association (SALGA) and its provincial affiliates are recognised as organised local government and represent all 257 municipalities in the country in terms of the Organised Local Government Act.²³⁵ SALGA plays a crucial role of representing local government in IGR forums.²³⁶ However, SALGA has the difficult task of representing the interests of both urban and rural municipalities, which are often different, and are sometimes at odds with each other. Decision-making at national level in SALGA is done by SALGA's national executive, elected by the SALGA national conference. SALGA executive committee comprises of the chairperson of SALGA, 3 deputies, 6 additional members, provincial chairpersons of SALGA (ex officio), and the head of the administration (who has no vote) and optionally, three additional members. The meetings of SALGA national executive are once every three months, and when the need arises (clause 12.4.2 SALGA Constitution). The Constitution of SALGA empowers the national executive to make representations to provincial and national government (clause 12.7.5) and to determine the representation of SALGA in all national IGR structures and other national forums and such representatives have power to make decisions in these structures and forums, but they must report back to the national executive quarterly (clause 12.7.14).

At the provincial level, decision-making is done by the SALGA provincial executive committee elected by the provincial members' assembly. The SALGA provincial executive committee comprises of the Chairperson, three deputies and six additional members (it may co-opt three additional members). Similarly, the SALGA provincial executive committee meets once every three months, and when the need arises. All municipalities in the province must be represented on the provincial executive committee. The SALGA Constitution empowers SALGA provincial executive committee to make representations to provincial government (clause 21.6.3), and to determine SALGA representation in provincial IGR structures and other forums, and such representatives have power to make decisions, but must report back to the provincial executive committee (clause 21.6.2). SALGA engages and lobbies for local government in Parliament through the portfolio committees of National Assembly (NA) (Section 163 of the Constitution). Section 163 of the Constitution enables SALGA to participate in all meetings of the National Council of Provinces (NCOP) Select Committees, NCOP plenary debates, joint sittings of NCOP and NA, NCOP Local Government Week and SALGA can designate 10 councillors to hold part-time seats in the NCOP. Although legislation does not invite SALGA into provincial legislatures, some provincial legislatures accommodate the participation of SALGA.²³⁷ Thus SALGA gives local governments a voice in the NCOP and in some provincial legislatures.

Intergovernmental Relations Mechanisms

²³⁵ Act 52 of 1997.

²³⁶ National Treasury: Budget Technical Forum and Winter Budget Forum; Department of Works: Technical and Political MINMEC; Department of Safety and Security: Safety and Security Technical and Political MINMEC.

²³⁷ SALGA, 'Organised Local Government in Parliament and Provincial Legislatures' (unpublished paper 2013) 9.

There are IGR mechanisms for budgeting, planning and implementation, such as implementation protocols and integrated development planning (IDP). Each municipality is required to develop an IDP in consultation with local communities, and in alignment with national and provincial strategic development plans.²³⁸ The MFMA and the Constitution further regulate intergovernmental fiscal relations (IGFR). SALGA participates in fiscal IGR in its role as organised local government.²³⁹

Dispute Resolution

There are mechanisms for intergovernmental dispute resolution. Section 41 requires all three spheres of government to take 'every reasonable effort' to settle disputes out of court and to use litigation only as a last resort. Furthermore, courts may refer matters back to allow alternative dispute resolution (ADR) through political processes if litigation was instituted prematurely. There are also mechanisms to resolve conflicting legislation in order to ensure coherence in the legislative framework.

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Municipal Finance and Management Act 56 of 2003

Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act (IGRFA) 13 of 2005

²³⁸ Secs 24 and 26 MSA 32 of 2000; Department of Provincial and Local Government, 'The Implementation of the Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act: An Inaugural Report 2005/6-2006/7' (Government of South Africa 2007) 38.

²³⁹ Secs 9 and 10 of the MSA Act 32 of 2000; Sec 35 Public Finance Management Act 1 of 1999.

11.3 Intergovernmental Cooperation in Fiscal and Financial Management: Bulk Resources for Municipal Services

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Relevance of the Practice

The Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) requires extensive consultation before an organ of state can increase the price of a bulk resource supplied to a municipality or municipal entity. This forms part of government's effort to ensure consistent policy implementation and achievement of macro-economic objectives. This process is comprehensive and must be completed timely and contain motivations to be tabled in Parliament or the relevant provincial legislature. Careful planning is required to meet the obligations of the MFMA before the pricing amendments can take effect.

Local government is generally the major provider of essential services to communities and so their ongoing financial sustainability is important in meeting national objectives. All municipal budgets must be introduced and put forward for debate and approval in council no later than 31 March each year and adopted before 1 July which provides improved certainty in the process. As the purchase of bulk services makes up a significant component of municipal expenditure (roughly 25 per cent) and will impact directly on the tariff policies adopted by council, it is imperative to coordinate and finalise the pricing from bulk resource providers in a timely manner. Municipalities and bulk service providers are encouraged to take into account the government's broad economic objectives and adhere to the inflation targets when concluding their bulk and retail tariffs. Related mainly to report section 2 on local responsibilities, section 3 on local finances, section 5 on intergovernmental relations and section 6 on people's participation, this practice note is relevant for the LoGov-project to the extent that it affects bulk municipal services, municipal budgeting and consultation with communities as well as how other organs of state plan and cooperate with one another on matters of national interest.

Description of the Practice

According to Circular no 23 of the MFMA, the water boards should demonstrate how they have taken into consideration SALGA and National Treasury comments before the proposed tariffs can be passed. In response to this requirement, SALGA annually undertakes the review of the water boards' proposed tariffs. The 2019/20 review included analysis of documents submitted by water boards consisting of the proposed tariff submission to SALGA and business plans. The MFMA provides two significant features in relation to the provision of electricity, water and other bulk resources to municipalities and municipal entities. Firstly, if an organ of state intends

to increase the price of such resources, it must undertake a comprehensive consultation process, which must be completed on or before 15 March in any year. Secondly and to complement the consultation process, National Treasury is required to monitor the pricing structures and payments made by municipalities and municipal entities to organs of state for the supply of bulk resources. To do this, organs of state are required to submit monthly statements to National Treasury setting out payments received, arrears and any action taken to recover arrears from municipalities and municipal entities (Section 41). Table 1 describes the practice regarding the approvals for bulk water service providers' tariffs.

Table 1: Description of the practice- bulk resources for municipal services (Water)²⁴⁰

Action	Date
Department of Water Services (DWS) provides resources for 3 consecutive years to water service providers	Prior 15 September
Bulk water service provider calculates tariff	Prior 30 September
Consultation with water services authorities	Oct & November
DWS preliminary review meeting of bulk water service provider's tariffs	November
Bulk water service provider's submission to the National Treasury (NT) & SALGA requesting written comments	Prior 7 December
SALGA and NT to provide comments	Prior 25 January
Formal submission to DWS including comments by SALGA, municipalities & NT	After 25 January
Bulk water service provider's tariffs tabled in Parliament	15 February
Any amendments to tariffs are tabled in Parliament	1 March
Water service providers are notified of tariff increase in writing	15 March
Water services authority tariff determination process:	
Water services authorities to comply with other regulatory processes	After 15 March
Water services authorities to table draft budget before municipal council	Prior 31 March
Implementation by water services authorities	1 July
Water services authorities submit pro-forma statements on water and sanitation tariff determination to DWS as reflected in norms and standards	Immediately after 1 July

Assessment of the Practice

From SALGA's perspective, the main objective of the analysis was to assess applications received from water boards for tariff increases for the 2019/20 financial year. SALGA undertook to comment on these applications with a view to protect the interests of the municipalities that are served by water boards. In undertaking this analysis, SALGA took into consideration that bulk water tariff increases are required in order to ensure that water boards remain financially sustainable, but this must be balanced with the need to ensure that water remains affordable to municipalities and, ultimately, the end users. The main historic challenge with regards to SALGA's participation in bulk water IGR processes (specifically, in the tariff increase consultations with local government, by the water boards as regulated through the

²⁴⁰ National Treasury, 'Schedule 3: Norms and Standards in Respect of Tariffs for Bulk Water Services Supplied by Bulk Water Services Providers or Regional Bulk Water Utilities to other Water Services Institutions' (Government Gazette No 39411, Republic of South Africa, 13 November 2015) 123.

MFMA) has been the lack of consultation with municipalities which made the submissions and comments weak. The challenge of SALGA to fully represent local governments often resulted in unaffordable tariffs being imposed on local governments, which in turn, passed on the costs to consumers through service charges. From the Treasury perspective, SALGA's involvement in the tariff consultations for bulk water services allows for the monitoring of the pricing structure of the organs of state for the supply of electricity, water or any other bulk resources to municipalities and municipal entities as well as payments made for such bulk resources. Another challenge more broadly is that there seems to be no 'board' as such that is formally responsible for regulating water boards, unlike electricity which has a clear regulator. It is therefore especially important to ensure that submissions by SALGA are taken into account as SALGA is in a way playing a monitoring role although it is also representing local governments in the budget forum.

The practice is one of the useful means to ensure local government budgets are credible to the extent that they are based on realistically anticipated revenues and expenditures. For example, following the review, SALGA rejected eight out of nine tariff submissions from the water boards and urged them to take into consideration the points of reservation SALGA made against their tariff proposals for the 2019/20 financial year. This was premised on the review which revealed that overall, the tariff increases requested by water boards were extremely high and unaffordable to the local government sphere. Largely, the high tariffs were attributable to high input costs, unrealistic demand projections that did not match historical actual consumption of the service etc.²⁴¹ There is differentiation in terms of how the practice works in urban and rural settings in that, rural municipalities pay higher tariffs due to higher costs of service provision (topography is the main cost driver). This further exacerbates the financial constraints affecting most rural municipalities characterised by poor or no revenue base and places an additional burden on the national fiscus.

While SALGA made input, the extent to which its recommendations (as the voice of local government) have been taken into consideration reveals a loophole in the IGR system which in turn affects both rural local governments (RLG) and urban local governments (ULG) negatively. The water boards do not always implement the comments / inputs from both SALGA and National Treasury, and consultation is a compliance driven exercise that is often not done in good faith and consultation from SALGA's view.²⁴²

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996

Organised Local Government Act 52 of 1997

²⁴¹ This is based on SALGA's own assessment reports which are not published, but are presented to Parliament and water boards as part of the consultation process.

²⁴² This is based on SALGA's own assessment reports which are not published, but are presented to Parliament and water boards as part of the consultation process.

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Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000
Municipal Finance Management Act 56 of 2003
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11.4 Intergovernmental Relations through the Lenses of the Intergovernmental Division of Revenue

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Relevance of the Practice

Division of revenue (DOR) in South Africa is an intergovernmental (IGR) fiscal process in which the national, provincial and organized local government – the South African Local Government Association (SALGA) - as well as the Financial and Fiscal Commission (FFC) play important roles. The Division of Revenue is guided by Section 214 read with Section 227 of the Constitution, which require national government to allocate an equitable share of revenue to provinces and local government from the National Revenue Fund. This allocation of revenue must be done by way of an Act of Parliament – the Division of Revenue Act (DORA). DORA is a money bill, meaning it deals with financial matters and therefore must be approved by both the National Assembly and the National Council of Provinces in terms of Sections 75 and 77 of the Constitution. However, the DORA may not be passed without undergoing a consultative IGR process, wherein the provincial government, organized local government (representing all municipalities, urban and rural) and the Financial and Fiscal Commission are consulted and their recommendations considered (Section 214(2) of the Constitution). The Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations Act establishes the Local Budget Forum for the purpose of consultation with organized local government, and the Budget Council for consultation with the provinces. The division of revenue is an important process which determines the resources that will be made available to local governments in the following year for the fulfilment of their constitutional mandates. The local and provincial equitable share are determined through a formula. This section will now turn its focus to the local sphere of government. The local equitable share varies from municipality to municipality, and ranges from about 10 to 80 per cent of municipal revenue depending on the municipality, and constitutes about 5 per cent of national revenue. Municipalities raise about 60-90 per cent of their own revenue depending on the municipality's capacity, such that metropolitan municipalities often raise the bulk of their revenue, whereas smaller, and especially rural municipalities tend to rely quite heavily on national transfers as they have fewer opportunities for sourcing own revenue and less diversified revenue collection avenues.

Description of the Practice

The Division of Revenue in terms of Section 214 of the Constitution is an interesting feature of the post-Apartheid dispensation in that it marks more clearly, the recognition of local government as a separate sphere of government, having original powers, and fiscal autonomy to enable it to exercise those powers and perform its listed functions. Whereas in the previous dispensation local governments were creatures of statute, subsidiary to provincial governments, in the new (final 1996) Constitution, local government receives national

transfers directly from national government, and also has authority to raise its own revenue through various taxes. It also highlights the distinction between types of local government, as in the first cycle of the DORA metropolitan municipalities and local municipalities received an equitable share allocation, but districts were excluded, until it was rectified in the following year, in response to litigation instituted by district governments.

The Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations Act 97 of 1997 establishes the Local Government Budget Forum as a consultative forum in which local government issues are discussed, and it sets out the process for the division of revenue. Section 8 of the IGR Fiscal Relations Act requires the Division of Revenue Bill to be tabled annually, setting out the allocations to local government (including the equitable share as well as conditional and unconditional grants). The Budget Forum is composed of the Minister of Finance, members of the provincial executive councils (MECs) responsible for finance and organized local government, which is the South African Local Government Association (SALGA). SALGA national branch nominates five representatives, while SALGA provincial branches nominate one representative per province to the Budget Forum. These representatives from SALGA represent both urban and rural municipalities, and they represent all categories of municipalities, that is metropolitan cities, secondary cities, small towns and rural areas. In other words, there is no separate forum for different categories of municipalities, the same IGR forum accommodates all 257 municipalities, and SALGA must find a way to represent their interests. This is obviously not an easy task as the municipalities are diverse and asymmetric in terms of their constitutional and legislative powers and functions. On one hand, the fact that SALGA represents urban and rural municipalities alike in the Budget Forum is an equalizer in the sense that it can place less capacitated municipalities such as rural areas on an equal footing to have their concerns heard, and it can increase their bargaining power in consultations with the national minister, and provincial executive through economies of scale. The Budget Forum is a cooperation forum, and therefore no issues of supervision are likely to arise in the Budget Forum, although it can play a dispute settlement function. Although the Budget Forum is not a decision-making forum as such, and cannot make binding legal decisions, Parliament has an obligation to consider the recommendations of the FFC. Which makes the FFC an additional tool to amplify the voices of organized local government, and present a balanced objective view, devoid of party politics in principle.

The FFC, which is an independent constitutional body is required to make submissions and Parliament is required to take into account various considerations including developmental and other needs of local government and municipalities (Section 214 of the Constitution). However, after the consultations, the final decision-making on the division of revenue lies with Parliament, which consists of the National Assembly and the National Council of Provinces.

Further, although organized local government is permitted to attend the NCOP, it does not have any vote. It is argued that it would be better if capable municipalities, such as metropolitan municipalities were able to participate in the Budget Forum directly, and represent their own interests because they have very large budgets and typically have the capacity to represent their own interests well. Moreover, the concerns of metropolitan municipalities are likely to be different from those of local or district municipalities, especially those districts and local municipalities in rural areas. The main difference between the urban and rural municipalities in this process lies in the categories used in the calculation of the

equitable share, which takes into account various factors such as basic services that the municipality is to provide, capacity to raise own revenue, and predictability of division of revenue. Based on these considerations, the allocations to urban and rural municipalities are likely to differ significantly, and it is SALGA's role to flag revenue concerns on behalf of all its members.

The DORA is based on the ability to raise revenue and the nature of spending required to fulfil constitutional obligations. This means in practice that metropolitan cities and some secondary cities are more likely to get a bigger piece of the cake than other smaller and rural municipalities. Secondly, the local equitable share (LES) formula enables municipalities to provide basic services to indigent persons in their municipalities, and enables municipalities with low own revenue, such as category B3 and B4 (rural) municipalities to afford administrative costs and exercise core functions through the institutional and community services components.²⁴³ For example, while rural municipalities have taxing powers in relation to property tax, most rural property is communally owned and tax exempt, so rural municipalities have a smaller tax base and are unable to generate significant own source revenue. This financial autonomy comes with a responsibility because it makes municipalities more directly accountable to their communities. Further, although the DORA is based on anticipated national revenue, the amounts allocated to local government are fixed, such that if the national government fails to raise the anticipated revenue, it bears the shortfall and not the local governments. Thus, this process is crucial to local governments.

Revenue allocation affects several report sections as revenue determines the resources that will be available for the implementation of service delivery (section 2 on local responsibilities), implementation of integrated development plans (section 6 on people's participation), and it deals with finances (section 3 on local finances).

Assessment of the Practice

The objectives of the Budget Forum are to create an IGR forum in which national, provincial and organized local government can consult on fiscal, budgetary and financial matters affecting the local sphere of government, and any proposed legislation or policy with financial implications on local government (Section 6 IGR Fiscal Relations Act).

While the Budget Forum broadly meets its objectives as noted above, the fact that the outcomes of the Budget Forum are not binding, and the FFC can only make recommendations, tends to leave most of the power to the national and provincial government, which sit in the

²⁴³ The Municipal Demarcation Board defines municipal categories as follows: 'B1: Secondary cities: the 19 (9%) local municipalities with the largest budgets. B2: 26 (12%) municipalities with a large town as core. B3: 101 (49%) municipalities with relatively small populations and a significant proportion of urban population but with no large town as core. B4: 59 (29%) Municipalities which are mainly rural with, at most, one or two small towns in their area. C1: 23 (52%) of the district municipalities that are not water services providers and generally have few service delivery functions. C2: 21 (38%) of the district municipalities that are water services providers and often have substantial obligations'. Municipal Demarcation Board, 'Municipal Powers and Functions Capacity Assessment' (2018) <<http://www.demarcation.org.za/site/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/MDB-capacity-assessment-Executive-Summary-FINAL-1.pdf>> accessed 30 October 2020.

two houses of Parliament. The fact that SALGA does not have a vote in the NCOP further weakens the position of both urban and rural local governments alike in terms of Section 163(b). SALGA is mandated to represent all 257 municipalities, however, the vast differences and inequality between rural and urban municipalities make it difficult for SALGA to represent their unique interests adequately. One of the reasons for this is that SALGA's elected executive committee members (which are the national and provincial representatives) who participate in the Budget Forum, sometimes have difficulty obtaining their members' full mandate if municipalities fail to participate in scheduled meetings and workshops to voice their concerns ahead of the Budget Forum. In instances where SALGA is unable to obtain the mandate from some of its members, this may undermine the aims of the fiscal IGR process that culminates in the division of revenue. Additionally, it presents an opportunity for larger municipalities to assert their interests as they are more likely to submit their mandates to SALGA than smaller, and rural or otherwise less resourced municipalities.

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11.5 Intergovernmental Relations in Integrated Development Planning

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Relevance of the Practice

This practice deals with integrated development planning which is an intergovernmental process involving all three spheres of government – national, provincial and local. Municipal planning is done through a document called the Integrated Development Plan (IDP). Each municipality is required to prepare and adopt its IDP through a process that allows for public participation and this applies uniformly across urban and rural municipalities.²⁴⁴ The purpose of the IDP is to prepare a strategy for long-term development of the municipality and align this strategy with the resources available to that municipality and to align local municipality's development plans with those of the districts within which the local municipality falls, as well as to align the development plans of all three spheres of government. The IDP is particularly important in the context of South Africa because it seeks to advance socio-economic development and achieve transformation at the local level. First, it pays attention to the municipalities that are lagging behind in terms of service delivery; therefore, in this sense the IDP process is important because it places rural municipalities in the limelight as most rural municipalities have infrastructure backlogs. Secondly, the IDP facilitates the fulfilment of constitutional imperatives of the 'developmental local government' in terms of Section 152 of the Constitution. It also enables municipalities to 'structure and manage [their] administration and budgeting and planning processes to give priority to the basic needs of the community, and to promote the social and economic development of the community' and to 'participate in national and provincial development programmes'. The IDP thus brings to life the development mandate of local governments as set out in Section 152 of the Constitution, and is especially important in the relationship between a district municipality and the local municipalities within the area of the district.

Additionally, the IDP is a process through which the monitoring and support role of provinces with regard to municipalities is highlighted. Section 154(1) of the Constitution requires the national and provincial governments to 'support and strengthen the capacity of municipalities to manage their own affairs, to exercise their powers and perform their functions'. Although the province cannot change the municipal IDPs, it is required to provide guidance by submitting comments to the municipalities and the municipalities have an obligation to consider those comments. This is in line with the principles of cooperative governments set out in Section 41 of the Constitution. The IDP process also highlights the supervisory role of provincial and national governments in that the municipalities are obligated to report on their performance to the member of the provincial executive responsible for local government, and submit their reports to the (national) Auditor General. The key legislative instruments are the Constitution

²⁴⁴ See report section 6.3. on Municipal Budgeting and Planning during Covid-19.

and the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000 (MSA). The White Paper on Local Government, 1998 is the key policy document on the IDP, and it is supported by policies on spatial planning, integrated transport and housing. Practitioners in the field suggest that there is inconsistency and a disconnect between development planning by local, provincial and national government, which undermines national efforts towards coordinated development. This is one of the reasons that support the shift towards a district-led development model (explained in report section 4.4).

What Goes into the IDP?

Section 23 of the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000 (MSA) requires municipal planning to be development-oriented. The IDP must contain the municipal council's long-term vision for 'critical development and internal transformation needs'. The IDP must align with the provincial and national sectoral plans and all legislation that is binding on municipalities (legislation must be enacted within the functional areas set out in Schedules 4 and 5 of the Constitution). The IDP must also set out the municipality's spatial development framework together with basic guidelines for the land use management system of the municipality (spatial planning is a crucial issue and is discussed under the preliminary assessment of the practice).

Description of the Practice

Section 25 MSA sets out the procedure for the adoption of IDPs. First, every municipal council must adopt an IDP for its municipality within the prescribed period. The IDP must link, integrate and coordinate the strategic plans of the municipality, align the strategic plan with resources, constitute the basis of the municipal budget, and align with national and provincial legislation and development plans. If a municipal council is dissolved, the new council may adopt the existing IDP or adopt a new IDP. National and provincial development plans must holistically align with the IDPs and vice versa. It facilitates community participation in the creation of the IDP, and they can use the same IDP to hold the municipality to account. The IDPs are thus political and transformative in their nature. Rural municipalities typically fall within the area of a district municipality, together with other local municipalities, which may be urban or rural. Section 155(1) of the Constitution stipulates that districts have legislative and executive authority in an area that includes more than one municipality and that local municipalities share their executive and legislative authority with the district municipality in whose area they fall under. This is a two-tiered hierarchical relationship between two types of local government, one with more powers than the other.

Process Flow

Politically, the constitutional negotiations of 1993 did not necessarily give local governments much power, but they did set constitutional principles which then led to the entrenched devolution of powers to local government. The IDP came because of significant transformative policy developments at the end of apartheid. The first policy being the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP), which was the African National Congress' manifesto in 1994. Its aim was to dismantle the institutional apartheid frameworks to create racially and economically integrated cities (and municipalities). The Development Facilitation Act 67 of 1995 and policy document- Urban Development Framework, 1997 framed the beginnings of development policy for local government. The White Paper on Local Government, 1998 introduced the IDP, and finally placed local governments at the epicentre of development, and provided for development that is integrated not only in terms of persons – i.e. race, but also in terms of accessibility of economic activity and multi-sectoral development planning, across the three spheres of government.

The Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000 which followed, furthered the agenda of the White Paper by placing municipal development needs at the centre, and enabling local governments to be the drivers of local economic development, such that sectoral budgetary allocations should reflect the strategic priority areas of the specific municipality as opposed to sector priorities. However, these local priorities are supposed to not only co-exist, but also be in alignment with the national and provincial priorities and development plans and they must be in line with the principles of cooperative government set out in Section 41 of the Constitution and 'cooperation' as required in Section 24 of the Municipal Systems Act. Unfortunately, one of the criticisms of the IDP process is that local and provincial development plans tend to be a cross purposes, and are not often aligned, and that there is no formal IGR structure for consultations on development planning among the three spheres, or even among two, such as between the local and provincial government. Further, Wright argues that South Africa has an 'overlapping-authority' model of IGR in which substantial areas of government functions involve all three spheres of government partly due to concurrent powers, there are few areas of independent autonomy, the overarching principles of cooperation and coordination tend to limit the power and influence available to each sphere of government.²⁴⁵ When development priorities at different levels of government are mismatched, this can create challenges.

The case of *Macsand (Pty) Ltd v City of Cape Town and Others* illustrates the divergent priorities of governments at different levels. In this case, Macsand sought to conduct mining operations in terms of a mining permit issued by the national government. However, Macsand did not apply for a local permit to conduct the operations before it began operating. The City of Cape Town then sought an interdict from the High Court of Cape Town to prevent Macsand from mining without a land use permit from the City of Cape Town, and doing so in an area designated by the City as a residential area. The lack of coordination and alignment between the national and local government created legal costs which could have been avoided through consultations ahead of issuing the permit. It also shows that the 'previous' hierarchy between the three spheres is still quite visible and often national or provincial government will try to

²⁴⁵ P Mbecke and SK Mokoena, 'Fixing the Nexus between Intergovernmental Relations and Integrated Development Plans for Socio-Economic Development: Case of South Africa' (2016) 9(3) African Journal of Public Affairs 99.

assert their powers over local governments' development plans. The City of Cape Town is a metropolitan city, with a vibrant economy, well resourced, and raises most of its revenue from own sources. It therefore had the muscle to reject a decision made by the national government that affected a local competence. The situation could have been very different for a rural municipality, with little or no own source revenue, and reliant on transfers from the national government.

The success of the IDP is highly dependent on the collaboration, coordination, cooperation and full participation of each sphere of government, and the meaningful involvement/engagement with local communities (meaning residents, rates payers, civil society organisations and visitors).²⁴⁶ However, metropolitan cities and urban cities and towns may have more economic or political power than smaller towns and rural areas to assert their local priorities in the face of national and provincial development plans. Moreover, the issue of local government capacity is pervasive as there are often skills and capacity shortages in rural areas to develop the IDP and implement it.

The process of adopting the IDP requires intergovernmental supervision and cooperation. The process is designed to allow on one hand, bottom up community-inclusive local development strategies integrated into provincial and national development strategies, and on the other hand, a top-down monitoring and supervision process. The mechanisms for supervision and cooperation generally apply to urban and rural municipalities in the same manner because the law is framed in terms of the spheres of government and not in terms of categories of local government.

In terms of decision-making, although the municipal council has the responsibility to adopt the IDP, the Member of the (provincial) Executive Committee for Local Government (MEC) has a duty to review the IDP procedurally and substantively at different intervals. The role of the MEC is not to amend the IDP, but to assess the performance of the municipality and compliance with its own IDP by reviewing the key performance indicators, and key performance areas in the IDP and then the MEC can make recommendations. However, in some places, the framing of the law acknowledges asymmetry. For example, provinces are required to take into account the capacity of the municipalities within their province when reviewing municipal IDPs. This implies that an MEC might review a secondary city, which has big budgets and robust economic activity more strictly than a local rural municipality if the MEC takes into account the lack of technical capacity and resources at the rural level.

Assessment of the Practice

Despite this noble approach to planning and gains thus far experienced, several municipalities have struggled with developing meaningful strategic IDPs, and instead many simply have wish lists as opposed to multi-year financial strategies. Success can perhaps be noted from the perspective of municipal staff whose performance is annually reviewed in terms of IDP key performance areas. The IDP improves on the Urban Development Framework because it does not focus on urban municipalities alone; it also applies to rural municipalities. This means rural

²⁴⁶ *ibid.*

municipalities have an opportunity to advance and indeed prioritise their own key strategic issues. However, lack of capacity to prepare and implement the IDP continues to be a strain at rural municipalities. Organized local government is not involved in this process. Although the municipal council makes the final decision on the content of the IDP, community members hold the power to influence the content of the IDP through statutory public participation processes. The IDP is theoretically not influenced by the national or provincial government in terms of drafting it. However, because there has to be coherence and alignment across all spheres and across various sectors, the national and provincial spheres do in fact influence or at least set the parameters within which local governments IDPs can be framed. Moreover, rural municipalities have little muscle to push back if national and provincial priorities undermine rural municipality development strategies. For example, in *Maccsand (Pty) Ltd v City of Cape Town and Others* (CCT103/11) (CC) [2012], noted above, the City of Cape Town was able to put its foot down on land use planning permits. In the case a mining investor had been granted a mining permit in Cape Town in an area planned for residential use by the local government. The Court held that where the national government grants mining permits (a national competence) this does not do away with the requirement to comply with municipal land use permits, and thus the mining operations by Maccsand (Pty) Ltd could not proceed pending the said municipal permit. It would be very unlikely that a rural municipality in the same situation would have had the same 'muscle' to challenge the national government, and the outcome would likely have been different. One of criticisms of the IDP is that there is no formalized IGR structure for provinces and municipalities to engage on IDPs and align their priorities and efforts.²⁴⁷ This tends to support the calls for a district development model as an alternative which can facilitate coordinated or joint development planning at the district level.²⁴⁸

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²⁴⁷ Mbecke and Mokoena, 'Fixing the Nexus between Intergovernmental Relations and Integrated Development Plans for Socio-Economic Development', above.

²⁴⁸ See report section 4.4. on a District Coordinated Development Model.

Steytler N and de Visser J, Local Government Law of South Africa (issue 11, LexisNexis 2018)

12. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia

12.1 The System of Local Government in Ethiopia

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Types of Local Governments

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) Constitution has established a federal state structure composed of nine ethnic based constituent units namely: Tigray, Afar, Amhara, Oromia, Somali, Benishangul/Gumuz, Gmbella, Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples (SNNP) and Harari. Ethiopia is a dual federal state since Article 50(1) of the Constitution stipulates as The Federal democratic Republic of Ethiopia comprises the federal government and the state members. Local government is not explicitly stipulated by the Federal Constitution which remains almost silent. This paves the way to the constituent units to enjoy unlimited constitutional space in the area. Article 50(4) of the federal Constitution merely states that 'State government shall be established at the state and other administrative levels that they (i.e. the regional states) find necessary'. In fact, the second sentence of the article gives a specific federal mandate to the region and reads 'Adequate power shall be granted to the lowest units of government to enable the people to participate directly in the administration of such units'. This implies the Constitution has implicitly provided for the establishment of non-ethnic local governments.

In addition, Article 39(3) states that Every Nation, Nationality and People in Ethiopia has the right to a full measure of self-government which includes the right to establish institutions of government in the territory that it inhabits'. According to this article, local governments are established along ethnic lines for ethnic groups which are basically 'ethnic local government'.²⁴⁹ Here, the Federal Constitution poses a duty on the regional states to realize genuine self-government and ample amount of decentralization of power to the local levels. Accordingly, all regional state constitutions have provisions related to local government with a relative uniformity.

As mentioned above, the constitutional recognition of local government in Ethiopia has remained debatable. Despite this debate, local governments are constitutionally recognized at least implicitly. If one gets a closer look to the provisions of the Federal Constitution, it envisaged the establishment of two kinds of local governments: ethnic and regular.²⁵⁰ These

²⁴⁹ Zemelak A Ayele and Yonatan T Fessha, 'The Constitutional Status of Local Government in Federal Systems: The Case of Ethiopia' (2012) 58 *Africa Today* 89, 93.

²⁵⁰ Zemelak A Ayele, 'The Existence of Local Government and its Institutional Security within Ethiopia's Federal System' in Asnake Kefale and Assefa Fiseha (eds), *Federalism and Local Government in Ethiopia* (UNDP and Center for Federal Studies 2015) 203.

two categories of local governments have two distinct objectives.²⁵¹ Ethnic local governments aim at realizing the self-determination rights stipulated under Article 39(3) of the Federal Constitution. Practically these local governments are established in the name of 'nationality zones' or 'special *woreda*' in all regional states except Oromia, Harari and Somali. On the other hand, the regular local governments are established by the regional states as per the Federal Constitution's provision of Article 50(4) in the name of *zone*, *woreda* (city/town administration) and *kebele*.

Regarding administrative structure, all regional states, except Harari²⁵², are composed of three levels of local governments: nationality (*zone*), special (*woreda*) and *kebele*. Nationality *zones*, *woredas*, special *woredas* and *kebeles* have three tiers of institutional structure composed of a council; administrative council and judicial body.²⁵³ Zones are administrative levels just below the regional state comprising a number of districts (*woredas*) or urban centers. Unlike nationality *zones*, regular zones are founded by ordinary legislation with no council in Amhara, Oromia, Somali, Afar and Tigray regional states. It is a deconcentrated administrative body of the regional state. The *woreda* is the local government level standing next to the zone, encompassing *kebeles* and administratively subordinate and accountable to both the zone and regional state. *Kebele* is the lowest local government level included in all regional state constitutions. There are two categories of urban local governments: cities and towns. 'Cities' signifies the two cities under the federal jurisdiction (Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa). There are urban centers named by the legislations of their respective regional state councils. Towns are urban centers located beneath the zonal administrative structure and ranges from small to large based on their population size. Unlike others, small and medium towns may have a *woreda* status and in each *woreda*, there is a town from which the *woreda* is administered.²⁵⁴

Legal Status of Local Governments

Institutional security of local government is a crucial element of political autonomy of local government.²⁵⁵ In order to protect the existence of local government as a sphere or level of government from the encroachment of the central government, constitutional recognition is recommended as an effective formal mechanism.²⁵⁶ Political autonomy also entails uninterrupted existence of local government. The constitutional recognition of local government as an autonomous level of government does not only resist the intrusions from other levels but it also enhances the political and economic role that local government ought to play. Accordingly, local government administrations are supposed to be autonomous units.

²⁵¹ *ibid.*

²⁵² Harary regional state is composed of only two levels of governments: regional state and *kebele*.

²⁵³ Christophe Van der Beken, *Completing the Constitutional Architecture: A Comparative Analysis of Subnational Constitutions in Ethiopia* (Addis Ababa University Press 2017) 141.

²⁵⁴ WSUP Advisory, 'Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia' (Draft Situational Analysis for Ethiopia's IUSHS) 20.

²⁵⁵ Ayele, 'The Existence of Local Government and its Institutional Security within Ethiopia's Federal System', above, 202.

²⁵⁶ *ibid.*

However, no constitutionally entrenched functions meet the above standards in the Ethiopian federal tradition. The Federal Constitution leaves this to the regional states to determine tiers, powers and functions.

As an element of political autonomy, local government functional competencies should be original, clearly defined, and development-related.²⁵⁷ This is usually achieved through providing constitutional guarantees and full power to local governments on those functions. Considering the dual nature of the Ethiopian Constitution, local government units do not have original functions.²⁵⁸ Rather their functions are determined by regional states.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Despite the fact that both typologies of local governments lack original autonomy, there is some kind of asymmetry between urban local governments and other regular (*woreda*) and ethnic (nationality zone and special *woreda*) local governments. The state constitutions constrained the councils of the latter in law-making powers. On the other hand, urban councils are empowered to issue policy and regulations of their own.²⁵⁹ Accordingly, medium and large towns have enjoyed special status as compared to *woreda* governments having larger population. Moreover, a kind of paradox has arisen as the city councils which are under the supervision of the nationality *zone* council have a law-making power while the latter is restricted to its specific implementation guidelines.

Political and Social Context in Ethiopia

Ethiopia had entered in to the process of decentralization before a formal federal arrangement was endorsed in 1995. The Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF), the incumbent political party since 1991, encouraged the establishment of local government units along ethnic lines. This was deemed to be a necessary response to accommodate diversity which was considered to be the most pressing challenge of the country.²⁶⁰ Proclamation number 7/1992 was instrumental for the beginning of the first phase of decentralization (1991-2001). The Proclamation also laid down the foundation for the Federal Constitution. It had listed 64 ethnic groups to establish their own ethnic self-administration.²⁶¹ After ten years, the party realized that emphasizing only ethnicity leads to inefficiency in ensuring development and equitable service delivery and engaged in the further creation of new local governments

²⁵⁷ Zemelak A Ayele, 'Decentralization, Development and Accommodation of Ethnic Minorities: The Case of Ethiopia' (Doctoral dissertation, University of Western Cape 2012) 55.

²⁵⁸ *ibid* 488.

²⁵⁹ Van der Beken, *Completing the Constitutional Architecture*, above, 187.

²⁶⁰ Zemelak A Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia' (2014) 6 Perspectives on Federalism 89, 109.

²⁶¹ National/Regional Self Governments Establishment Proclamation no 7/1992, Art 3, Federal Negarit Gazeta, No 2.

and at some degree amalgamates certain of the existing ones.²⁶² Indeed, in 2001, the District Level Decentralization Program (DLDP) launched by the federal government, administrative convenience, good governance and development issues began to be the salient justifications for strengthening the decentralization process.

Currently, there are no less than 60 political parties registered in Ethiopia. Based on their constituency, political parties often classified in to three: national, regional and local parties. They also could be categorized in to three based on their political programs: EPRDF, incumbent party and composed of four ethnic based parties representing regional states of, Amhara, Tigray, Oromiya and Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples.²⁶³ EPRDF's affiliates are five in number which comprise Afar, Somali, Benishangul-Gumuz, Gmbella and Harari regional states.²⁶⁴ These parties are ethnic based and not opposition parties following EPRDF's ideological orientation. Except a few, most of the opposition parties are ethnic based; their constituencies are regional and local governments. Ethnic based local parties are mostly oppositions mainly seeking either regional statehood or new ethnic local government status. Member parties of EPRDF are represented by an equal number of people both in its executive committees and despite the obvious difference in population size each party is supposed to represent. Moreover, many agree that the TPLF was the most influential member of EPRDF.²⁶⁵ The party structure which controls all levels of government and its decision-making procedures on the principle of 'democratic centralism' affected local government creation and undermines the role of regional states in creating local government systems based on their circumstances.²⁶⁶ Following the 2016 protests in the country an increasing party fragmentation within EPRDF has been seen. This political dynamic changed the previous centralized nature of the party and TPLF has been relegated from its core position in the party.²⁶⁷ Enjoying this political liberalization opposition ethnic based local parties are getting more assertive in their claim of new territorial autonomy.

A City/Town administration, as the term implies, is established in urban areas. Based on classification, urban centers of Ethiopia are classified in five categories ranging from small towns to metropolitan City of Addis Ababa based on demographic size. According to Situational Analysis of IUSHS, the population size of small towns ranges from 2,000 to 20,000 people and constitute 80 per cent of total number of towns and only 33 per cent of urban population. The medium-sized towns range between 20,000 and 50,000, and hold 25 per cent of the urban

²⁶² Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia', above, 109.

²⁶³ Amhara National Democratic Movement (ANDM) currently called Amhara Democratic Party/ADP/. Tigray People Liberation Front (TPLF), the Oromo Peoples' Democratic Organization (OPDO) currently called Oromo Democratic Party/ODP/, and the Southern Ethiopian Peoples' Democratic Movement (SEPDM).

²⁶⁴ Afar National Democratic Party (ANDP), Somali People's Democratic Party (SPDP), Benishangul-Gumuz Peoples Democratic Party (BGPDP), Gambela people's Unity Democratic Movement (GPUDM), and Harari National League (HNL).

²⁶⁵ Following party fragmentations, this has been confirmed by the leaders of the remaining member parties as there was no equal power balance within and TPLF took the upper hand in decision-making and even interfering in the internal affairs of each member parties.

²⁶⁶ Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia', above, 90.

²⁶⁷ Currently, the regional parties except TPLF and all affiliate parties have been merged in to one monolithic national party in the name of Prosperity Party.

population. Large-sized towns range between 50,000 and 100,000 people. There are 13 mega towns with a population between 100,000 and 500,000 people each. Addis Ababa is the only city in the country that hosts over 500,000 with about 3.5 million residents.²⁶⁸

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WSUP Advisory, 'Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia' (Draft Situational Analysis for Ethiopia's IUSHS, 2015)

²⁶⁸ WSUP, 'Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia'.

12.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia: An Introduction

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Intergovernmental Relations (IGR) is an important body of activities or interactions occurring between governmental units of all types and orders, and how these orders/spheres of government communicate and collaborate with each other.²⁶⁹ Being one of the principles that distinguishes federal systems from the non-federal ones,²⁷⁰ IGR is an institutional and pragmatic device for dealing with the intricate relations in a multilevel setting. Particularly, Agranoff states:

‘Local governments are inextricably linked vertically to states and to their general governments through ranges of national-state programs, legal and fiscal considerations and horizontally linked with associated local governments and NGOs through partnering, contracting or other forms of externalization.’²⁷¹

De Villiers²⁷² also puts that modern-day governments require the mechanisms and institutions of IGRs so as to implement policies and programs, maximize the standard of service delivery and optimally utilize scarce resources.

Local government basically shoulder two responsibilities. On the one hand, they have to perform as autonomous local self-governing entity. On the other hand, the same local governments are often responsible for implementing policies as an agent of the subnational and federal governments. At the interface of these dual roles of the local governments is IGRs either in the form of supervision and cooperation. Apart from federalism that shapes the urban governance and politics through the constitutional, territorial and political framework, the process of urbanization is another force that influences the governance of urban spaces. To this end, IGR can be presented –both in principle and practice– as an institutional mechanism to overcome the politically divided but functionally interconnected multilevel arrangements and to moderate the often subordinate status of local governments.

In fact, developed and mature federations like Switzerland have put settled systems of local governmental institutions and use intergovernmental bodies and forums for addressing their local demands.²⁷³ In contrast, in the context of Ethiopia, the involvement of urban local governments (ULGs) in IGRs is more of a requirement than for rural local government (RLGs) because urbanization has already brought a formidable internal change to the federal system.

²⁶⁹ Deil Wright, *Understanding Intergovernmental Relations* (3rd edn, Brooks/Cole 1988).

²⁷⁰ Allen Trench, ‘Intergovernmental Relations: In Search of a Theory’ in Scott Greer (ed), *Territory, Democracy and Justice: Regionalism and Federalism in Western Democracies* (Palgrave Macmillan 2006).

²⁷¹ Robert Agranoff, ‘Local Governments in Federal Systems: Intergovernmental Relations in the Governance Era’ (22nd IPSA World Congress, Madrid, July 2012) 1.

²⁷² Bertus de Villiers, ‘Codification of “Intergovernmental relations” by way of Legislation: The Experiences of South Africa and Potential Lessons for Young Multitiered Systems’ (2012) 72 *ZaöRV* 671.

²⁷³ Bulliard Pascal, ‘Local Government in Switzerland’ in Nico Steytler (ed), *The Place and Role of Local Governments in Federal Systems* (Konrad Adenauer-Stiftung 2005); Wolf Linder, *Swiss Democracy. Possible Solutions to Conflict in Multicultural Societies* (3rd edn, Palgrave Macmillan 2010).

The first internal challenge stems from the fact that urbanization often appropriates a large area of land beyond municipal boundary as economic and functional spaces. This in turn raises land use and local boundary disputes between the city and neighboring rural local governments. The other challenge is related to the demographic pressure due to rural to urban migration process of urbanization in Ethiopia. According to the official estimates about 50 per cent of urban population growth in Ethiopia is accounted for by rural-urban migration. Both the horizontal physical expansion and migration induced pace of urbanization have produced different problems including informal housing, land use and local boundary disputes. It is however clear that a single ULG cannot handle these problems. The ULG needs cooperation from neighboring local government and supra-local governments for addressing the mismatch between municipal boundary and urban functional area. It is this condition that brings the IGRs imperative.

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12.3 Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations

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Relevance of the Practice

Two main forces – federalism and urbanization – shape the relationship between urban and rural local governments in the federal system of Ethiopia. On the one hand, federalism sets territorial, institutional and political frameworks in Ethiopia. It has established institutionally fragmented but functionally interconnected local governments, making the participation of local governments in the overall system of intergovernmental relations in the federation of Ethiopia inevitable. On the other hand, urbanization in Ethiopia is characterized by rapid and mostly informal outward expansion. This has brought a number of problems ranging from competing local administrations, conflicting interests over land use management to ambiguous jurisdictional boundary expansion. Any further effort to resolve these problems of governance requires clear principles and institutions of urban and rural local governments relations. To this end, the practice of Ethiopian Cities Association (Ethiopia Urban Forum) and Urban-Rural Relation are practices worth to be discussed.

Description of the Practice

The Ethiopian Cities Association (ECA), which was launched in 2009, is a legally registered and licensed entity pursuant to the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Charities and Societies Proclamation no 621/2009 Article 68(1).²⁷⁴ In this regard, the Federal Ministry of Works and Urban Development have partnered with *Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit* (GIZ) and the World Bank (WB) for the project ‘Establishment of the Ethiopian Cities Association and Strengthening and Supporting its Operations’ that was first planned to be active from 2008 to 2011.²⁷⁵

The rapid urbanization and the huge challenges it has brought upon governance and service provision of cities in Ethiopia, was claimed to be the base for foundation of ECA. ECA was therefore meant ‘to serve as a urban forum/platform for policymakers’, authorities, stakeholders and cities to exchange experiences, and create awareness about urban development’.²⁷⁶ It has aimed to serve as a platform for knowledge exchange among city

²⁷⁴ Website of the Ethiopian Cities Association, <<http://www.ethiopiancities.org/>>.

²⁷⁵ ‘Expanding Ethiopian Cities Network Fosters Peer-to-Peer Learning’ (*Cities Alliance*, 25 January 2019) <<https://citiesalliance.org/resources/knowledge/project-case-studies/expanding-ethiopian-cities-network-fosters-peer-peer>>.

²⁷⁶ ‘About the ECA’ (*Ethiopian Cities Association*, 2013) <<http://www.ethiopiancities.org/>>.

administrators and improve slum upgrading and city plan implementations.²⁷⁷ ECA, as urban platform, aims at ‘experience sharing and learning among cities to encourage a healthy and competitive atmosphere’ among the cities/urban centers of Ethiopia.²⁷⁸ As expressed by the supporting organization like Cities Alliance,²⁷⁹ apart from knowledge sharing, it has focused on providing ‘technical assistance and establishing cooperative relationships with other international networks.’

ECA is composed of three structures: general assembly, board and secretariat. The general assembly is the supreme organ of the association that elects the Board from members of the ECA. It is also the organ that approves strategic plans and budgets as well as approves and/or amends the statute and bylaws of the association and decides on the dissolution of the association when deemed necessary.²⁸⁰ The board on the other hand has an oversight role and ensures that all organs and members of the association implement its decisions. The board, comprised of nine-member cities, also appoints and/or dismisses the secretary and the department heads of the ECA’s secretariat, while a secretariat is responsible for implementing the decisions of the general assembly and the board of the ECA.²⁸¹

The first event of the ECA came out in on 22 October, 2009 as ‘Ethiopian Cities Day’ with 19 members attending the event in Addis Ababa, the hosting city. It was organized by the Federal Ministry of Works and Urban Development in partnership with the German Organisation for Technical Cooperation (GTZ) Urban Governance and Decentralisation Programme, the Cities Alliance, and the Addis Ababa-based Corporate Media and Communication.

Later on there was a felt need to change the name ‘Ethiopian Cities Day’ into Ethiopian Cities Week (ECW) because a single day couldn’t suffice for the forum. The ECW was also renamed as the ‘Ethiopia Urban Forum’ in 2014, encompasses a number of events such as Panel discussion, plenary session, exhibition, and best-practices competitions.²⁸² The ECW particularly dwells on how to implement and institutionalize lessons learned from the Urban Local Government Development Programme (ULGDP), a major World Bank-financed capacity-building and infrastructure development program in which many ECA member cities are participating.²⁸³ The two events-Panel and plenary discussions-have been undertaken by different urban specialists from different universities in Ethiopia along with participation of

²⁷⁷ ‘Expanding Ethiopian Cities Network Fosters Peer-to-Peer Learning’ (*Cities Alliance*, 25 January 2019) <<https://citiesalliance.org/resources/knowledge/project-case-studies/expanding-ethiopian-cities-network-fosters-peer-peer>>.

²⁷⁸ ‘Report on Ethiopian National Urban Forum’ <[https://unhabitat.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/ Report-on-Ethiopian-National-Urban-Forum](https://unhabitat.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/Report-on-Ethiopian-National-Urban-Forum)>.

²⁷⁹ ‘Expanding Ethiopian Cities Network Fosters Peer-to-Peer Learning’ (*Cities Alliance*, 25 January 2019) <<https://citiesalliance.org/resources/knowledge/project-case-studies/expanding-ethiopian-cities-network-fosters-peer-peer>>.

²⁸⁰ ‘Governance Structure’ (*Ethiopian Cities Association*, 2013) <<http://www.ethiopiancities.org/index.php/en/about-eca/eca-structure>>.

²⁸¹ *ibid.*

²⁸² ‘Expanding Ethiopian Cities Network Fosters Peer-to-Peer Learning’ (*Cities Alliance*, 25 January 2019) <<https://citiesalliance.org/resources/knowledge/project-case-studies/expanding-ethiopian-cities-network-fosters-peer-peer>>.

²⁸³ *ibid.*

pertinent professionals from the UN-Habitat.²⁸⁴ For the exhibition part, the participating cities display their cases and experiences in separate tents on the open field. The forum was said to be annual event when it was launched in 2009 and was performed annually up until the 6th round in 2014 which was hosted by Dire Dawa City. Afterwards, only two urban forums every two years were conducted.

It would be fair to ask what objectives have been achieved by ECW/urban forums. So far, the forum has been preparing some workshops on urban development issues along with exhibitions from different cities at the member city hosting the ECW. According to the ECA and the partnering organization like Cities Alliance, the association has greatly been benefitting the member cities through informal cooperation that was already taking place among certain cities. The Forums have also been instrumental for promoting ‘the culture and traditional assets and heritages of the people as well as strengthening the city to city relations in exchanging experience and learn from each other’.²⁸⁵ The increasing relevance of ECA has been reflected even by the change of names of the event that was started as ‘Ethiopian cities day’ which was later changed to ‘Ethiopian cities week’, and now this forum is been addressed as ‘national urban forum.’

Nonetheless, one would barely find a coherent guideline and settled principles of IGRs among the three –federal, regional and urban local governments (ULGs/cities) with regard to Urban forums and ECA. Constitutionally speaking, the federal government has no direct contact with ULGs except the two chartered Cities, namely Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa. Paradoxically, it has been the federal executive organ, namely the Ministry of Urban Development that has been the key actor (along with the partnering International Organizations like Cities Alliance) behind the establishment of the ECA and undertaking urban forums. But the place of regional states, the level of the government that establishes ULGs, in ECA and the preparation of the forums is blurred. In fact, the last eight ECW/urban forums were conducted due to the key role of the dominant party system and its democratic centralism based decision-making, party channel IGR and the inseparable relation between party and the government. Hence, the continuity of this forum as permanent multi-stakeholder’s platform transcending the life of the ruling party-EPRDF would remain a suspect.

In another register, all the regional states’ city proclamations have some provisions governing cities associations within their regional state. To cite some examples in this regard, Article 51(1) of the Proclamation no 65/2003 of Oromia regional state, provides that cities in the region may set up their own regional association and actively participate in the operation thereof. Moreover, the association has been given important functions such as inter-city cooperation through exchange of resources, experiences and ideas. The association serves as a forum for the provision of trainings and support for building the capacity of their members; and works towards promoting development of the cities as a whole. The association may also represent cities collectively and express their views on matters of common interest. It can also create and strengthen good working relation within cities in the region and outside. City associations

²⁸⁴ UN-Habitat, ‘Report on Ethiopian National Urban Forum’ (2014) <<https://uni.unhabitat.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/Report-on-Ethiopian-National-Urban-Forum.pdf>>.

²⁸⁵ Jantirar Abay Yigzaw, Minister of Federal Urban Development (9th Ethiopian City Forum, Jigjiga, February 2019).

work in consultation with the Urban Development and Industry Bureau of Oromia.²⁸⁶ Likewise, Article 57 of the Proclamation no 69/2007 of the Benishangul Gumuz Regional State for Urban Establishment and definition of Powers and Duties of urban center in the region states that 'City administrations and municipalities have the right to establish and organize associations and actively participate in their operations.' The regional cities associations were envisioned to function as a forum for exchange of resources, experiences, ideas and expression of matters of common interest. However, the regional city associations have not been established in the regional states, and hence the cities lack institutional mechanisms for advancing their common interests without the interference of their regional states.

The other important practice which is worth describing is the urban-rural local governments relation. In Ethiopia, urbanization has long been identified as migration-led urbanization rather than industry-led urbanization. The studies on census data have affirmed that rural-urban migration is the driving force of urbanization in Ethiopia, and almost half of the urban population is accounted by rampant migration-mainly rural to urban mobility.²⁸⁷ This migration led urbanization process has produced unbalanced towns/cities sizes and inequitable spatial distribution of urban centers across the country.

One of the estimates for the rapid rate of urbanization accounts up to 6 per cent per year.²⁸⁸ The proportion of urban population was only 6 per cent in the 1960, 11 per cent in 1984, 14 per cent in 1994, and 17.2 per cent in 2013 and projected to be 30 per cent in 2025.²⁸⁹ Because of the change in the designation of settlements as urban localities, Ethiopia has also shown a tremendous increase in the number of urban centers: 1,525 urban settlements as of 2015.²⁹⁰ This rapid urbanization confronts with rural local governments because rapid urbanization appropriates a large portion of the neighboring rural territory as its economic and functional hinterlands. Moreover, inasmuch as urbanization is not concomitant with industrialization and sustained economic growth, this urbanization has created pressure on extant infrastructures and demand for more services including housing, transport, education etc.

The development plans/policies of Ethiopia have followed rural bias at one point and urban bias at another time, which shows unbalanced development policy orientation between urban and rural areas. At policy level, the federal government tends to understand the need to create mutual urban-rural linkages. As the Ministry of Urban Development and Housing Construction reports, the government has employed a number of mechanisms to develop rural and urban linkages including the liberalization policy related to input and output marketing facilitates, the promotion of agro-processing industries and micro enterprises and the development of small towns and rural service centers, Road Sector Development Program (RSDP) for assessing the

²⁸⁶ Art 52(1-6) of Proclamation no 65/2003 for establishment of Urban Local Governments of Oromia.

²⁸⁷ Tsegaye Tegenu, 'Urbanization in Ethiopia: Study on Growth, Patterns, Functions and Alternative Policy Strategy' (Department of Human Geography, Stockholm University 2010) <<https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva/>>.

²⁸⁸ Paul Dorosh and Emily Schmidt, 'The Rural-Urban Transformation in Ethiopia' (IFPRI Ethiopia Strategy Support program 2 Working Paper no 13 and World Bank 2010)

²⁸⁹ Ministry of Urban Development, Housing & Construction MUDHCo, 'National Report on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development, Final Report' (2015).

²⁹⁰ *ibid.*

rural sector and so on.²⁹¹ Yet, the rural spaces surrounding cities remained largely under the negative impact of horizontal urban expansion, including demands for more land for the different urban functions (such as housing, infrastructure and other social services), dislocation of farmers, loss of farm lands and increased pressure on public services and utilities.

All the regional states' city proclamations make some provisions for governing urban and rural local governments relation. Some city proclamations²⁹² like that of Oromia set the terms of IGR between the urban/city and rural/district governments. Accordingly, a joint committee shall be created for performing two key functions: first, it identifies issues of mutual interest and sets strategies to jointly address and strengthen the urban-rural economic interaction; and second, it amicably settles boundary disputes between the urban and the concerned hinterland or adjoining rural areas. If the committee fails to settle the dispute, the Regional Government Executive Council has the final authority to resolve the case.

Although both regional city proclamations and urban development policy papers underscore the need for mutual urban-rural linkages in the Ethiopian federation, the interaction between the city and its neighboring rural local government has become a matter of pressing concern for dealing with factors of rapid urbanization that drives urban expansion farther into rural areas complicating land management, local jurisdictional boundaries, and the ethno-territorial claims. Also, there has been institutional and functional decoupling of urban and rural local governments due to unbalanced national policy orientation from the central/federal government in Ethiopia.

The practice however suggests that there is a felt need to enlarge the municipal borders, the city administrations often influence the neighboring rural communities, and this reveals the weakness of the urban and rural local governments relation. The committee is, in fact, supposed to moderate the effects of urbanization/urban expansion on the surrounding rural land. In the meantime, it has to be noted that the interaction between the city and the surrounding rural district administrations does not take place following the clear guidelines and institutions of IGRs but becomes operational on party channel/structure and personal relationship between the key executives of the city and rural district administrations. Had it not been for the political party channel, the urban and rural local governments cannot easily make horizontal relations because they have different legal statues and upward accountability lines.

This study suggests the need for clear institutional and structural relationship between urban and rural local governments in order to collaborate in the service deliveries as well as manage mutual risks that affect both urban and rural administrations. This institutional relation could also have the advantage of managing urbanization which has been characterized by rapid, largely unplanned and horizontal expansion beyond the municipal boundary. Therefore, creating specific IGR forums involving the participants from the city, rural district, and regional governments is worth recommending.

²⁹¹ *ibid.*

²⁹² Art 28(2) of Proclamation no 65/2003.

Assessment of the Practice

The establishment of Ethiopian Cities Association (ECA) in 2009 could be taken as an important move to address urban and urbanization generated issues in the federal system of Ethiopia. Nonetheless, there are a number of issues that are missing to make the ECA and the urban forums/cities week events a sustainable consultative forum. The association has been under the strong influence if not under a complete order of the federal executive or the Ministry of Urban Development. The partnering/outside funding sources come through the Ministry of Urban Development, and it has been this federal executive who actually plays the key role in setting the agenda and direction for the urban forums. This approach forces the ECA to work in line with the framework set by this federal body. Hence, the forum has barely served as independent institution of ULGs that put forth the demands of ULGs free from the federal government intervention. The Urban forum and ECA have not come to the status that it could influence the federal urban policy.

Instead, the federal government tends to use the urban forums as a mechanism of directly contacting the urban local governments but there is no explicit constitutional provision that enables the federal government to make direct relation with the urban local governments except the federal capital, Addis Ababa. The relation of regional state governments, as a level of government that legislate on the statuses of the ULGs in their jurisdiction, to the ECA and in the urban forums have been blurred. Although most of the urban problems cannot be resolved without cooperation of the rural local governments (RLGs), we have not witnessed the participation of RLGs in the national urban forums. Little attention is given to the RLGs relevance for resolving the problems of the Ethiopian urbanization which is mainly characterized by rapid, informal and horizontal expansion. Though the process of urbanization makes ULGs not only interrelated to RLGs but also the former cannot properly function without the later, neither RLGs participate in the national urban forums nor association of RLGs has been established in Ethiopia. In short, the sustainability of the urban forum as permanent multi-stakeholder's platform transcending the life of the ruling party-EPRDF would remain uncertain if different political parties win election and rule over different levels of the government in the federation.

On the other hand, both the urban development policy papers and regional states' city proclamations underscore the need to establish mutual urban-rural linkages. Contrary to the policy and city proclamations, the rural spaces surrounding cities remained largely under the negative impact of horizontal urban expansion and the RLGs often complain that they lose suburban spaces to ULGs. There has been top-down decision-making process to expand ULGs boundary by converting rural land into urban space. Some RLGs criticized the inclusion of some of their sub-rural local units adjacent to cities because this has further weakened the revenue capacity of their RLG as a number of local revenue sources were gone with the departure of

these sub-rural units.²⁹³ In this perspective, the urban boundary expansion and the demarcation of boundary between urban and rural has not been well considered from its impact on RLG's revenue or income from land fees. The Ad hoc committees usually established for the urban expansion and demarcation of municipal boundary have been favoring the urban interests. For example, the initiation to establish the Ad-hoc committees in regional states like Oromia state come from the regional state level and the concerned ULGs and RLGs are required to act in accordance with the instruction from the regional government. The decision that the Ad-hoc committee reaches is based on the instruction from the regional state's concerned institution such as the urban land development and management agency. In fact, it has been the ruling political party channel that decides on the matter, and therefore, the ULGs and RLGs are required to match the order from the regional state and the ruling party.²⁹⁴

The age-old understanding of urban place as 'superior', different from the rural area and the policy favor to urban issues remains lingering in the urban-rural divide- the urban issues are still disposed by political culture of looking urban as modern and better than rural. Depending on the regional political solidarity and electoral contingencies, the regional states were trying to set the framework between urban and rural local governments. As a result, the relation between these local governments within the regional states becomes strong or lose depending on the regional political dynamics.

Beyond the informal/personal and party channel-based relationship for crises management between city and surrounding RLGs, one hardly finds settled principles and institutions of interaction between urban and rural local governments in Ethiopia. It has been this institutional failure between urban and rural local governments that has contributed for rapid and informal urbanization. This process of urbanization in turn has complicated matters related to land use planning, basic service deliveries and have often produced blurry and overlapping jurisdictional boundaries.

Indeed, the national urban development policy documents²⁹⁵ have foreseen the need for mutual linkages between urban and rural local governments. The implementation of these policies, however, could not realize mutual benefits between urban and rural local governments. Despite the policy documents, the political actors and the bureaucracy have remained true to urban bias policy and urban centers have been considered superior areas compared to their rural counterparts. To reverse this, there is a need to develop strong institutional and functional relations between urban and rural local governments. It is also important to reconsider the upward accountability lines of the urban and rural local governments in a way that enables these local governments to have horizontal intergovernmental interactions.

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12.4 Changing Urban Place Names in Post 2018 Amhara National Regional State: The View from Bahir Dar City

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Relevance of the Practice

Following the Amhara protests of 2016 and the subsequent party fragmentation within the Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF), the local political dynamics have changed in Amhara National Regional State. This somehow began to affect the institutions of both the regional and local governments. The endorsement of questions rallying behind the Amhara protests and afterward by the regional party led to some manifestations witnessed in the formal governmental institutions. The development of Amhara ethnonationalism has pushed the regular local government councils to pass identity-motivated decisions such as changing the name of local governments themselves (name of *woredas*, sub-cities, and *kebeles*), and erecting monuments of presumed heroes of the local population. These persons were disgraced by the EPRDF government as members of the oppressive ruling class. Some of the decisions have been sent to the regional state council to inform about changes.²⁹⁶ Considering the Amhara Regional State Constitution does not give detailed provisions on local government functions; the renaming of streets and local areas is a kind of emerging issue that might broaden the competencies of regular local governments to exercise such competencies largely related to identity matters.

In this report entry, the practice of renaming since the 2018 political 'reform' over toponyms in Bahir Dar City has been assessed. Even though there is a lack of clear criteria and guidelines in the legal constitutional regime of the regional state regarding the competencies of urban local governments in (re)naming places, one can learn from other federations or devolved systems like South Africa, that the power lies under the jurisdictions of municipality councils. In Bahir Dar city, renaming practice has been pushed through by both the lowest level of urban local government and the regional executive office while the city council remained idle. Hence besides being curious about whose competence and policy, guideline, and criteria to be followed, public participation in the renaming practice is also crucial in assessing such a local government practice.

Description of the Practice

The ethnicity of other ethnic groups has centered on the discourse of Amhara domination with roots going back to the students' movement of the 1960s/70s, and ultimately to the territorial

²⁹⁶ Interview with Worksemu Mamo, Amhara Regional Council's Speaker (Bahir Dar, 23 December, 2020).

expansions of Menelik II and the birth of modern Ethiopia at the end of the 19th century. The issue of Amhara ethnicity emerged in Ethiopian political discourse since the 1990s among the Amhara elites. Since this time the subject of Amhara continued to be sensitive and debatable among both the political and academic elites. Currently, the Amhara ethnonationalism has emerged in the sense of reactive ethnicity as a result of othering. This emanated from the 'national oppression thesis' of the 1960s which created deep-seated insecurity who have been vulnerable to attacks by other ethnic groups. Acquiring a similar ideology, the regional party, Ethiopian Peoples' Democratic Movement (EPDM) which later changed its name to Amhara National Democratic Movement (ANDM), had followed a political ideology that demonizes the former rulers of Ethiopia and their deeds and turns its back to those showing empathy towards them as labeled as *timkihtagna* (chauvinist). This was clearly seen in the land redistribution campaign arguably held only in the Amhara region after Dergue's proclamation for land distribution in March 1975. Ege rightly points out the character of the governance system from the view of land redistribution practice. He writes that '[t]he basic feature of the redistribution was its peculiar class analysis, which stigmatized the officials of the preceding regimes as oppressors but ironically enough lumped the current officials together with the oppressed peasants, without further criteria needed'.²⁹⁷ The class analysis of political mobilization of the regional government accompanied by EPRDF's narrative of an Amhara oppressive ruling class has led to an engagement in disgracing and destructing the legacies of the pre-1991 regimes.

The names 'Ginbot 20' and 'Hidar 11' are notoriously coined as names of sub-cities, schools, an airport, health centers, greeneries, and recreational places in urban centers of Amhara Regional State in the last three decades. The names are signifying just a month and date. Ginbot 20 refers to the day on which EPRDF seized Addis Ababa defeating the Dergue regime and Hidar 11 is the month and date on which the EPDM was established.²⁹⁸ The Amhara activists strongly argued that the Amhara people have not benefited from the Ginbot 20 victory. Rather it should be considered as the day on which the suffering of the people just began, accompanied by a state system that was instituted on the basis of narratives of an oppressive Amhara nation and other oppressed nationalities. Most people of the regional state have perceived ANDM as a trusteeship governor of the Tigray People's Liberation Front (TPLF) on the Amhara people and it was shy in struggling against TPLF's motives which were costly to Amhara. Hence the date the party was established is not worthy to celebrate by the Amhara people.

This was accentuated by the Amhara protests and the unfolding Amhara activism forced the regional government to embark upon changing names hated by such public mobilization. In Bahir Dar City, two sub-cities names were immediately changed by the same council. The first sub-city was formerly known as Hidar 11 and then changed into Atse Tweodros, the name of an Ethiopian emperor (1855-1868) with whom the modern history of Ethiopia is associated.

²⁹⁷ Svein Ege, 'Peasant Participation in Land Reform: The Amhara Land Redistribution of 1997' in Siegfried Pausewang and Bahru Zewde (eds), *Ethiopia: The Challenge of Democracy from Below* (Forum of Social Studies 2002).

²⁹⁸ The names Ginbot 20 and Hidar 11 are just Amharic terms within Ethiopian calendar which stand for 28 May and 20 November respectively. The EPDM, which was renamed ANDM in 1994, was a coalition member of the EPRDF which has administered the Amhara region. In late 2018 it rebranded itself and acquired a short-lived name called Amhara Democratic Party (APP) until it merged into a party replacing the EPRDF, Prosperity Party (PP).

The second sub-city's name Ginbot 20 was replaced by Menelik II, an emperor of Ethiopia (1889-1913). The present shape and size of Ethiopia were crystallized by emperor Menelik II. The renaming was not made by the city council. Rather it was decided by the council of the sub-city structurally found beneath the city council. Information obtained from Bahir Dar city council indicates that the sub-cities merely notify them by letter about the renaming. The fact is that there are no clearly defined functions provided to the city council regarding the (re)naming of institutions, streets, and other physical features. Hence, the issue of renaming does not seem a planned and well-initiated measure of the sub-city. It was made for the sake of calming down the protest of the people by avoiding the EPRDF memoirs from the sight of them.²⁹⁹ Glorifying the former rulers of Ethiopia has become the center of Amhara activism. Hence, the local councils have been replacing those names imposed by EPRDF by the two renowned kings of Ethiopia: Atse Tewodros and Menelik II.

Besides the sub-cities, renaming has occurred in two further places in Bahir Dar City: the airport and one main street. Formerly the airport was named Dejasmach Belay Zeleke, a heroic patriot in the resistance against Italian occupation (1936-1941) until it was replaced by the name Ginbot 20 by the ANDM-led regional government. After three names for the change had been proposed, discussed and 'voted' by the public via social media and popular consultation, the former name was restored. The main street, starting from the bridge of Blue Nile, commonly known in Amharic Abay river to the eastward way out of the city, was named Nehassie 1 Martyrs Road for the commemoration of youths massacred in gunshots by security forces during the Amhara protests on August 8, 2016. The renaming practice was not decided by the city council but by the regional executive office.³⁰⁰ In addition to the practice of renaming the sub-cities themselves, the names of *kebeles* have been changed by the residents themselves. Two *kebeles* under the Atse Twodrossub-city changed their names and their decisions were endorsed by the council of the sub-city. The sub-cities seem to have no plan to embark on the naming of places on their own initiative. They only act on specific issues raised by the residents. They do not consider the issue of naming and renaming as one of the functions of the local councils and they are reluctant to plan further activities based on clear guidelines and procedures.³⁰¹ The city council also found itself in the same disposition as the sub-cities. And it has been looking idly at the acts of both levels of government, the regional executive and the sub-cities, without any reactions regarding the renaming of places.

Assessment of the Practice

Place naming is usually understood as one element of a broader political project concerned with governmentality, state formation and nation-building.³⁰² The act of (re)naming places by EPRDF in commemoration of its two historic days can be seen as a means to entrench its

²⁹⁹ Interview with Yitbarek Tesfaye, Speaker of Atse Tewodros sub city council (Bahir Dar, 14 April 2021).

³⁰⁰ Interview with a legal expert of the Bahir Dar City council (Bahir Dar, 9 April 2021).

³⁰¹ Interview with Yitbarek Tesfaye Speaker of *Atse Tewodros* sub-city council (Bahir Dar, 14 April 2021).

³⁰² Duncan Light and Craig Young, 'The Politics of Toponymic Continuity: The Limits of Change and the ongoing Lives of Street Names' in Reuben Rose-Redwood, Derek Alderman and Maoz Azaryahu (eds), *The Political Life of Urban Streetscapes: Naming, Politics and Place* (Routledge 2018).

political aspirations and project in the minds of the public and to thereby achieve ideological legitimation. Urban place naming is also instrumental to substantiate a particular set of political values and the ruling socio-political order in the urban climate. Place names in urban centers are formed in particular political contexts so that they are subject to change along with political dynamics. When new regimes with different political aspirations and values take power, names are no longer compatible with the new political order.³⁰³ Accordingly, it was not only the local populations that questioned the names of their local area because they do not express their history and values, but it was also due to the regional government dropping the EPRDF ideology of 'Revolutionary Democracy' that the renaming practice was pushed through despite the absence of related laws and guidelines. According to data obtained from the sub-city council, after renaming there was no complaining from the people and the authorities believed their decisions were not only in line with the new political direction but also in the interest of the local population. Given the renaming practice was largely considered as a restoration of the past memory denigrated by the EPRDF regime, it can also be said that it satisfied the identity question of the local population. This move might be justifiable since 'place names are outward manifestation of how people perceive themselves, both their history and value system'.³⁰⁴

Post-apartheid South Africa has experienced numerous place name changes. The unfolding renaming process was initiated by the African National Congress (ANC)-ruled government and backed by an institution called South Africa Geographical Names Council (SAGNC).³⁰⁵ The institution issued guidelines aiming to 'eliminate duplication; rectify orthographic errors; accord official recognition to place names commonly used by residents; and to sensitize toponyms to South Africa's democratic values and diverse history'.³⁰⁶ However, no place (re) naming can be made without the municipal council's approval in South Africa.³⁰⁷ The intention of coordinating the local councils with SAGNC is to standardize, transform, and correct toponyms.

In Ethiopia, practices of (re) naming toponyms have been registered since 1991. Most of them are identity-motivated actions that replace the existing names with new ones which were supposedly used by the 'endogenous' local population in the past, until they were changed by the expanding modern state system. However, unlike the experience in South Africa, there are no regulatory mechanisms to identify which kind of names are supposed to be renamed; how the standardizations are maintained; who should decide the renaming, and in what ways the public interest and participation are ensured. The practice of renaming in Bahir Dar City is not the exception. It has been pursued in response to the new political dynamics pushed by Amhara ethnonationalism that emerged in reaction to EPRDF's political values that were perceived to oppose Amhara interests. There are neither policies or guidelines for renaming urban toponyms nor a plan of action towards that. As a result, the renaming practice has been made by government bodies having relatively less consent from the people and the city council

³⁰³ *ibid.*

³⁰⁴ Mcebisi Ndletyana, 'Changing Place Names in Post-Apartheid South Africa: Accounting for the Unevenness' (2012) 38 *Social Dynamics* 87.

³⁰⁵ *ibid.*

³⁰⁶ *ibid.*

³⁰⁷ Art 5 of the Street and Place Making Policy no 4810 of Ingquza Hill Local Municipality, <<http://www.ihlm.gov.za/download/policy/STREET-AND-PLACE-MAKING-POLICY.pdf>>.

has failed to reclaim its mandate. The city council should therefore set a comprehensive policy with guidelines, rules, and procedures for the (re)naming of places under its territorial jurisdictions.

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12.5 Infrastructure Projects in Addis Ababa: Between Self-Government of the Capital City and Federal Intervention

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Relevance of the Practice

Addis Ababa had a controversial and unsettled position and status in the Ethiopian federal matrix. As per Article 49(2) of the 1995 Constitution, it is the seat of the federal government and the capital of the Ethiopian federation. The Constitution further provides that the residents of the city have the right to a ‘a full measure of self-government’ (Art 49(2)). Yet, Article 49(5) of the Constitution also recognizes ‘the special interest’ of the Oromia state in the city since the city is located as an enclave at the heart of the Oromia state. Over 25 years after the promulgation of the Federal Constitution, ‘the special interest’ of the Oromia state in Addis Ababa remains undefined. As far as some politicians of Oromia, the special interest is nothing less than full ownership of the Oromia state over the city which should be translated into complete political and economic control of Oromia over Addis Ababa. For others the special interest of Oromia in Addis is limited to those interests, as explicitly provided in the Constitution, pertaining to ‘the provision of social services or the utilization of natural resources and other similar matters, as well as joint administrative matters’ (Art 49(5)). These interests emanate from the geographical position of the city and can easily be handled through intergovernmental forums. As a federal city, Addis Ababa cannot escape the regulatory and other influence of the federal government. The issue is whether that power of the federal government also includes the power to determine specific infrastructural projects to be implemented in the city. This issue is relevant here since there are several infrastructural projects that are initiated and implemented by the federal government raising jurisdictional issues. The question here is not whether the projects are relevant or useful. It is rather whether the federal government has the competence to plan and implement these projects.

Description of the Practice

There are several projects which are being implemented in Addis Ababa, in the words of Adanech Abiebie, the Deputy Mayor of Addis Ababa, ‘with the initiation and close supervision’ of Abiy Ahmed, the Prime Minister. The projects are undertaken within the framework of ‘beautifying sheger’ (also called Sheger River side projects) which is the brainchild of the Prime Minister. The first project is the ‘Grand Meskel Square-Addis Ababa City Hall project’. This ETB 2.6 billion (EUR 47 million) project covers the area from Addis Ababa City Hall to Meskel Square, the largest public square which lies in the heart of Addis Ababa and where various religious, cultural, and political festivities are conducted. The project involves refurbishing the square, building an underground parking lot, and building roadside greenery works and sidewalks along

the Churchill Avenue which runs from the Addis Ababa City Hall down to Meskel Square. Various parks and green areas are also built in different parts of the city, including the Wodajinet Square (friendship square), the Andinet Park (unity park), and the Entoto Natural Park. These projects involved building different structures including 'various indoor and outdoor facilities, including sport centers, library, restaurants and coffee shops'. The other project is the so-called Abrhot Library, which is expected to be the largest library in the city, if not in Ethiopia. The Adwa Centre is another project being implemented in the city. This project is named after and built as a commemoration of the Adwa Victory in which the Ethiopian forces defeated the Italian invading forces in 1896. The Adwa Centre 'will have a museum, a meeting hall with a capacity of over 2000 people, three smaller auditoriums with a capacity of 400 people, Cinema Theatre, Library, Gym, and Childcare center, among other things'.³⁰⁸

As indicated above, the projects were initiated by the Prime Minister and implemented under his close supervision. He has also produced several documentaries in which he narrates the progress of these projects. The city government had barely any involvement in the planning and implementation of these projects even though the parks will be administered by the city government. Moreover, the costs of the projects are covered by the federal government. In its 2021-22 budget, the federal government has set aside ETB 3.3 billion for Addis Ababa clearly to cover the costs of the project. Addis Ababa never previously received a subsidy from the federal government since it is financially self-sufficient.

It should be stressed here that these projects are long overdue. Moreover, in addition to creating economic opportunities for the city's residents, the projects have transformed the face of the city. It is much more beautiful, clean and there are now several more public spaces in the city which were previously lacking. Thus, there is no disagreement on the importance of the projects. The issue rather is whether the federal government has not encroached into the competences of the Addis Ababa city government by planning, financing, and implementing the above projects in the city. As mentioned, the residents of the city have 'full measure of self-government' (Article 49 of the Constitution) which clearly implies that such kind of projects should be initiated and implemented by duly elected officials of the city. Moreover, as per Proclamation no 361/2003, which defines the powers of the Addis Ababa city government, the initiation and implementation of the kind of projects described above fall within the functional competences of the city. Article 2(4) of the proclamation provides that 'land development and management, city sanitation and beautification' and the like fall within municipal functions of the city government. The city has also the power to adopt its own master plan. In any case building cultural centers, recreational centers, youth centers, museums, parks, libraries, parking lots, public squares and the like fall within general local government functions and the federal government is not expected to be directly involved in such projects.

Assessment of the Practice

³⁰⁸ 'Adwa Center Construction in the Capital Addis Ababa Kicks off' (*Borkena*, 17 July 2019) <<https://borkena.com/2019/07/17/adwa-center-construction-in-the-capital-addis-ababa-kicks-off/>> accessed 18 September 2021.

It is true that Addis Ababa is the capital of the federation. It is not a state. Yet, unlike it is the case for other cities which lie within one of the ten states, there is no state above Addis Ababa to which the city is accountable. It is rather an autonomous city, its direct accountability being to the federal government. The federal government had indeed interest in ensuring that the city is properly managed. It is also within the power of the federal government to legislatively define the functional competences of the city which the former has done with the Proclamation no 361/2003. The federal government does not seem to have the power to dictate specific projects that have to be implemented in the city. This undermines the city's right to 'full measure of self-government'. While the projects are indeed commendable, there is no constitutional and legal basis for the federal government, especially the Prime Minister, to be as involved as it is in relation to these projects.

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13. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Argentina

13.1 The System of Local Government in Argentina

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Types of Local Governments

Argentina is a federal country consisting of 23 provinces and the Capital City of Buenos Aires as a federal district. Their autonomy is enshrined in the Constitution of 1853, which was last time reformed in 1994. According to the Federal Constitution, provinces can vote their own constitutions and laws. They have the power to elect their authorities and organize their own administrations, even in areas of justice and security. In addition, provinces have broad constitutional autonomy in fiscal and spending functions. A delineation of powers between central government and the provincial states is based on the general principle that all provinces have the power of those competences not expressly delegated in the Constitution to the federal state.

The third tier is composed of local governments. As the provinces have a political, administrative, judicial, and financial autonomy, the scope of municipal autonomy is determined by the province in which they are located. That translates into a wide range of definitions and configurations for local governments. Several municipal governments, depending on the provinces, have the authority to draft municipal charters (usually depending on the size of their populations). In some provinces, municipalities include only urban areas around cities, leaving rural areas under the jurisdiction of provincial governments. This translates into serious challenges for the delivery of social services. In others, municipal governments may include several cities and rural areas too.

Departments are an administrative division between provinces and municipalities, which do not have policy functions nor fiscal responsibilities. They mainly have a cadastral and statistical role, but in some provinces, they are also electoral districts to elect provincial representatives.

The adoption of federalism and a decentralized system of government that recognized autonomy to subnational units was the result of civil wars in the 1820s, after independence, and the only possible way to solve the political and economic conflicts in a country of enormous territorial extension.

Legal Status of Local Governments

Both the national Constitution, as amended in 1994, and most of the provincial constitutions explicitly recognize the autonomy of municipalities. According to Article 123 of the Argentine

Constitution, '[e]ach province dictates its own Constitution, in accordance with the provisions of Article 5 ensuring municipal autonomy and regulating its scope and content in the institutional, political, administrative, economic and financial order.' The sanction of several municipal charters (*cartas orgánicas municipales*) marks a progressive increase in the decision-making capacity of the municipalities. But this contrasts with limited administrative capacities to provide services (many of them decentralized at the provincial level) and scarce public resources and tax powers to finance their expenses (mostly concentrated at the national level).³⁰⁹

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Although the Argentinian Constitution establishes a substantial autonomy for subnational tax powers, in practice the provinces have delegated large amounts of responsibility to the national government for the collection of revenue (income taxes, sales, special taxes and taxes on fuel). The resulting revenue concentration contrasts with a process of decentralization of expenditure whereby the responsibility for key social functions is in the provincial hands. The only activities that are the exclusive competence of the national authorities are those related to defense and foreign affairs. In the areas of economic affairs, public security, and social infrastructure, the national government shares responsibility with the provinces, while the latter have exclusive competence in primary and secondary education and local (municipal) organization and services. The Constitution defines a wide area of public services for which national and provincial authorities can participate in the legislation and provision of public services, although the tendency in the last two decades has been for the national government to decentralize direct administration of those functions to the provinces. Therefore, the provinces are currently in charge of most social expenditures (including basic education, health services, poverty programs, housing) and economic infrastructure. Despite this, the national government maintains a significant regulatory power in many of these areas and manages some programs within these sectors, such as social security, social programs for poorer households, and complementary educational programs that subsidize poorer schools.

Given this decentralization of spending and fiscal centralization, there is a high degree of vertical fiscal imbalance. Argentina addresses this large vertical fiscal imbalance through a complex system of intergovernmental transfers. The most important component of this system is the revenue sharing agreement (called *coparticipación*), which is the process by which part of the revenues collected by the central government are transferred to the provinces. Over time, the system has redistributed revenue from the richest central region to the most backward provinces in the northwest and northeast. It has also favored richer and low-density Patagonian provinces. Despite this, the system has corrected part of the large regional income asymmetries among provinces in Argentina. We have to bear in mind that regional inequalities in Argentina are enormous. Formosa, for instance, has a GDP per capita more than 10 times lower than the City of Buenos Aires (2,256 versus USD 23,439). Although it has corrected

³⁰⁹ Monica Iturburu, 'Municipios Argentinos: Potestades y restricciones constitucionales para un nuevo modelo de gestión local' (2nd ed, Instituto Nacional de la Administración Pública 2000) 33.

regional income inequalities, the revenue transfer system has not had a substantial impact on provincial and local welfare indicators, as most social functions depend on the provinces (and are strongly correlated with provincial spending, particularly in social areas).

Political and Social Context in Argentina

The main parties that govern the provinces are the Justicialist Party (PJ), *Cambiemos*, which is the alliance governing the national government (formed by the Radical Civic Union, or UCR, Republican Proposal, or PRO, and other minor parties), and a constellation of minor parties, including the Socialist Party and provincial parties. *Cambiemos* governs four provinces (Buenos Aires, Corrientes, Jujuy and Mendoza) and the City of Buenos Aires. The PJ (in one of its several factions) governs 14 provinces (Catamarca, Chaco, Córdoba, Entre Ríos, Formosa, La Rioja, La Pampa, Salta, San Juan, San Luis, Santa Cruz, Tierra del Fuego, Tucumán, and Santiago del Estero). The socialists govern one province (Santa Fe) and provincial parties govern the other four provinces (Chubut, Misiones, Neuquén and Río Negro). Argentina has 1922 municipalities³¹⁰ governed by these and other national, provincial or local parties.

According to the last census, Argentina has 40,117,096 inhabitants, out of which more than 91 per cent (36,517,332) live in urban areas and the rest (3,599,764) in rural areas. More than 19 million live in 10 cities of more than 500,000 inhabitants, the largest being the metropolitan area of Buenos Aires (with 12,806,866 inhabitants and 31.9 per cent of the population).

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³¹⁰ Iturburu, 'Municipios Argentinos', above, 80.

13.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Argentina: An Introduction

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While the federal government in Argentina has exclusive responsibility for foreign policy, economic regulations, and defense, there are shared powers with the province in the areas of justice, health, education, and social security. Each provincial constitution defines the scope and contents of the responsibilities shared with the federal government, as well as the organization and powers of its local governments.

This legal framework balances the autonomy of subnational units and self-rule of these units with the principles of shared government between them and the central state. In other words, both levels share the capacity for decision-making without consultation with the other level, in an attempt to combine the self-government of regional and/or minority interests, with the government of common national interests. The same dynamic occurs, although with a lower degree of autonomy, between provincial and local governments.

The specific processes, mechanisms, and institutions through which the constitution is put into practice in the interaction between levels of government depend on a multiplicity of political and socioeconomic conditions, including historical tensions and informal traditions. Both formal and informal dynamics regulate federal supervision and intergovernmental cooperation. Communication and coordination among the different levels of government take place in some formal arenas (such as the federal councils for fiscal, education, health issues), and through the federation of municipal authorities, but in many instances they depend on partisan as well as personal or informal relationships.

The decentralization processes and the growing relevance of local identities and interests have placed local politics at the center of federal politics in Argentina, demanding better intergovernmental coordination.

Specifically, in relation to the management of natural resources, the national Constitution in Argentina establishes that the provinces are sovereign over the resources found in their territory. Thus, although the federal government has competence in environmental matters, for example, in relation to the protection of forests and glaciers, decisions about the exploitation of mineral resources depend on the provincial level of government.

In this scenario, local governments have traditionally been little more than recipients and executors of provincial level policies. However, the tendency of recent decades to promote large-scale mining has turned their role into a more complex one. Citizens under their jurisdiction are the ones that will be affected by the potential negative impacts of the activity. Hence, the political alignment or opposition between local and provincial governments is an important factor affecting the degree of organization and mobilization of populations that resist or oppose mining and the implementation of provincial policy in that matter.

13.3 Multilevel Government Cooperation for Open Pit Mining Projects

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Relevance of the Practice

We study two local governments in their relationship with their provincial and national counterparts regarding the installation of open pit mining projects in their respective jurisdictions. The first one is Andalgalá, a small town of 12,000 inhabitants, and the second one Famatina, a tiny community of only 2,500 people.

Both municipalities are located in the northwest of Argentina, have similar political regimes³¹¹ and levels of development (measured by the HDI). However, there is a fundamental difference in relation to open pit mining: La Alumbrera open pit mine is active in one of the provinces, while in the other this type of activity has been resisted. Both provinces differ in their legislation regarding mining, their fiscal regimes, the degree of citizen mobilization, and the pressures the mining sector can exert.³¹²

We will see how, in this context, the political alignment or opposition between local governments and the national and provincial counterparts in their strategy of supporting new mining projects is essential to strengthen citizen mobilization to effectively promote or prevent the establishment of mining companies. Additionally, we will observe if there is any difference regarding the resources to which the communities in the more urban or more rural context have access.

Description of the Practice

Andalgalá is a city of 12,600 inhabitants in the Province of Catamarca,³¹³ located in the northern part of the province, 248 km from the provincial capital. Most of the population worked in agriculture and small-scale mining,³¹⁴ when Bajo La Alumbrera, the first Argentine open pit mine, got installed in the 1990s. Initially, Alumbrera was projected to include a complex network of extraction and industrialization that would take place in the City of Andalgalá, creating jobs and economic development that would continue even after finishing

³¹¹ Jacqueline Behrend, 'Democratización Subnacional: Algunas preguntas teóricas' (2012) 2 POSTData 11.

³¹² Elisabeth Mohle, '¿Cómo se decide sobre el territorio? Gobernanza de conflictos mineros. Los casos de Andalgalá, en Catamarca, y Famatina, en La Rioja (2005-2016)' (Master thesis, Georgetown University 2019).

³¹³ Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 'Censo nacional de población, hogares y viviendas 2010: censo del Bicentenario: resultados definitivos' (INDEC 2012).

³¹⁴ Ministerio de Hacienda y Finanzas Públicas, 'Informes Productivos Provinciales: Catamarca' (República Argentina 2016).

the activities of the mine.³¹⁵ These promises of employment and progress penetrated deeply in a poor province where an important share of their population leave for Buenos Aires and other larger cities in search of employment.³¹⁶ The three levels of governments (national, provincial, and local) aligned their discourses about the benefits of bringing open pit mining to the province. This, together with the real hopes placed on progress by all implicated actors, a certain degree of ignorance of the real impacts of the activity, and the absence of similar experiences in the country, played a role in influencing the community of Andalgalá, who welcomed Alumbreira with open arms.

However, the project that was finally carried out was only the open pit mine, without the ambitious associated industrial complex. Not too much time passed from the beginning of the operations, until the disenchantment with Alumbreira arose. First, the jobs created were much fewer than promised. Second, few royalties were distributed to the local government and there were serious shortages of public works and services.³¹⁷ Third, frustration with sluggish economic growth grew together with an incipient notion of incompatibility of this mega exploitation project with traditional ways of life. Finally, there were several environmental accidents.³¹⁸

Although regulating mining activities is not directly a competence of the local government, all these issues impacted directly on the local community. In 2002 neighbors of Andalgalá organized the assembly *Vecinos por la Vida* (neighbors for life) with the aim of discussing the impact of the mine in their lives. As neighbors organized, pressures on the mayor mounted both to keep social peace and to provide answers to their demands.

In this scenario, by the end of 2009, a local councilor asked for provincial public information regarding mining prospection in the area. He received a report which included the Pilciao 16 that covered a large portion of the City of Andalgalá.³¹⁹ Whether the mayor knew this information beforehand is not clear, but at least publicly, the alignment between levels of governments started to break.

Since then, the assembly strongly mobilized against the project. Its members carried out several protests that were repressed with varying degrees of severity and presented judicial demands that, finally, in 2016 halted the activities in the zone. Opposition to a neighboring mining project in Agua Rica also escalated, despite it had been planned with relative social peace until then.

While the alignment between the national and provincial government continued steadily since the nineties on, the local government started to show some concessions to the growing citizen opposition and left the position of total support the provincial and national counterparts still showed. Both the mayor and the local council proposed referendums to give neighbors the

³¹⁵ Enciclopedia de Ciencia y Tecnología, 'Bajo de la Alumbreira' (2015).

³¹⁶ Lucas Gabriel Christel, 'Resistencias sociales y legislaciones mineras en las provincias argentinas: los casos de Mendoza, Córdoba, Catamarca y San Juan (2003-2009)' (doctoral thesis, Universidad de San Martín 2015).

³¹⁷ *ibid.*

³¹⁸ Hector Oscar Nieva, 'Variación de parámetros geoquímicos, río Vis Vis, Catamarca, Argentina, causas y consecuencias' (Master thesis, Instituto Nacional Politécnico de Lorraine 2002).

³¹⁹ Darío Aranda, 'Andalgalá, la ciudad que fue concesionada' (*Página 12*, 29 March 2010) <<https://www.pagina12.com.ar/diario/elpais/1-142860-2010-03-29.html>>.

formal opportunity to express themselves about the project. None of these initiatives were formally implemented. But in the elections of 2011, the winning mayor was the candidate that had publicly declared himself against the Agua Rica project and that endorsed the mandate to protect natural resources.

From that moment on, the local government differed sharply from the pro-mining discourse and actions that the provincial and national governments endorsed. The city's legislative council unanimously sanctioned an ordinance prohibiting open-pit metal mining activity. This was a powerful political signal, even though the local government has no jurisdictional authority over natural resources and therefore the capacity of such ordinance to effectively prevent mega-mining in the territory is null. The provincial government did not directly endorse the position of the assembly, but social pressures and the support from the local government finally forced the judiciary to stop all activities at the Agua Rica site.

Famatina is an Argentine town with 2,466 inhabitants in the northern section of the Province of La Rioja.³²⁰ This is a region with a significant production in agriculture and booming tourism even though water is incredibly scarce.³²¹ The populations settled in this region developed techniques that allow them to use water efficiently, thus creating a special relationship and an acute awareness of its importance as a scarce resource. This is a key factor in understanding the rapid reaction of people to a mining project that required to use huge amounts of water.

The city neighbors of one of the oldest mines in the country: La Mejicana, an underground gold mine exploited until the early twentieth century when it became economically inefficient. The ruins of this mine remain atop the snow-capped mountains of Famatina as a reminder to the community that gold is gone, but a contaminated site is still there.

For decades, there was no talk about mining in Famatina until a boom in the prices of minerals, new technologies, and legislative changes began to attract large transnational companies.³²² During the early 2000s, the national government strongly supported mining activities, and the Governor of the province initiated talks so that Barrick Gold could begin to exploit the Famatina mountain. In 2004, the Vice President of the Barrick for Latin America, the Governor, the Vice Governor, and the mayors of the neighboring towns of Chilecito and Famatina signed the contract to begin operations. Up to that moment, there was a clear alignment of all relevant actors to promote the new mining project.

The provincial government and the company promised to deliver accurate information on environmental protection policies, to work together with the neighboring communities, and to create several direct and indirect jobs to promote economic development for the entire region. However, cooperation was practically nonexistent: while the provincial government began operations with the mining company, the neighboring population was not consulted or informed about the exploitation, its implications, and progress.

³²⁰ Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INDEC), 'Tablas abreviadas de mortalidad por sexo y edad 2008-2010. Total del país y provincias' (INDEC, Serie Análisis Demográfico N° 37, 2013).

³²¹ Ministerio de Hacienda y Finanzas Públicas, 'Informe Productivo Provincial: La Rioja' (República Argentina 2016).

³²² Lucas Gabriel Christel and Laura Álvarez, 'La puerta de entrada al capital extranjero en el sector minero argentino. Análisis del debate de la ley de Inversiones Mineras (1993)' (2011) 259 *Realidad Económica* 106.

Concerned and aware of the nearby experience of Bajo la Alumbreira, neighbors of Famatina began to learn about open pit mining and to organize opposition against the project. In May 2006, two years after the presentation of the project, they created the Famatina Assembly with the purpose of preventing the beginning of mining operations, as they believed the activity would not bring any progress to the community.

The Mayor of Famatina, who had been present at the time the contract was signed and initially supported the exploitation of the mine, at first distrusted the assembly and its objectives. But soon he learned about the negative impacts of this type of mining and took notice of the important social opposition. He then switched sides and stopped supporting the project and instead backed all the activities the assembly carried out. He coordinated the first blockade against Barrick to prevent its vehicles from reaching the mine.³²³ As a result, the local government ended up actively opposed to the other levels of government.

After a series of failed meetings with provincial officials, the assembly members and the local government launched an active resistance to prevent the exploitation of Famatina. Together, they first expelled Barrick Gold, then Shandong Gold, Osisko, and Midais, until Famatina was finally declared a National Park.

Assessment of the Practice

Cities near large mining projects directly suffer all the social and environmental impacts of this type of economic activity, receiving only a small part of the benefits, being them jobs, royalties, or industrial activity. Local governments, as direct representatives of those communities, are often tensioned between popular demands and the political loyalty to the Governor (and the President).

When installing a new open pit mine, coordination between the three levels of government is essential. In our two cases, there was a clear alignment between the federal and the provincial governments of Catamarca and La Rioja to favor mining activities in the Agua Rica and Famatina projects. Local governments, on the contrary, were more conditioned by the strong opposition of directly affected neighboring communities. In Famatina, the local government supported the Famatina Assembly from the very beginning, while in Andalgalá it changed positions, first from favoring the activity, then to a neutral one, and ends up declaring itself against open pit mining. Thus, while in Famatina the four mining companies were ousted before starting drilling, in Andalgalá, a slower social organization process, the strong presence of Alumbreira, and a more reluctant municipal support only managed to prevent operations at Agua Rica through judicial decisions taken when the mining equipment was ready in the fields.

In sum, the positioning of the local government is of strategic importance. It can either cooperate with the provincial and national governments and the companies and try to demobilize social opposition to guarantee some relative social peace to favor mining; or it can

³²³ Campanas de Palo, 'Lidoro Leiva en el recuerdo de Carina Díaz Moreno' (*Campanas de Palo*, 31 March 2015) <<http://campdepalo.blogspot.com.ar/2015/03/lidoro-leiva-en-el-recuerdo-de-carina.html>> accessed 21 December 2019.

instead support and empower citizen mobilization, making it highly probable that new mining projects will not be implemented.

An important question to address in future research is regarding the causes that explain the differential positioning of local governments when confronted with such conflictive situations. We suggest that it might relate to how local and urban populations have distinct access to resources. For example, in an urban context the availability of information, of networks of diverse actors, the state capacity and the accessible institutions will probably be far more than in a rural context. This would give the contesting communities in a city a wider range of paths to go to fulfil their objectives. In our case we see that while the small town of Famatina seems to only have the option of direct action where the support of the mayor is of crucial importance, in Andalgalá they used different ways to protest the mining project, pursuing the judicial route, for example, where they didn't depend on the clear positioning of the mayor.

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13.4 Intergovernmental Relations in Environmental Policy

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Relevance of the Practice

Environmental policy has been a controversial issue when addressing the possibilities of development in Argentina, due to the contradictions between environmental protection and the productive specialization of the country in international trade. There is a permanent tension between exploiting natural resources for exporting them in the international market and their local use by communities which live in that environment. That tension translates into policy demands towards national and subnational governments³²⁴ and has social and economic consequences on development.³²⁵

In recent years, the Secretary of Environment and Sustainable Development of Argentina determined that the high levels of deforestation in the country were the consequence of agricultural and livestock activities.³²⁶ In 2007, the Federal Congress sanctioned the Law 26.331 or Native Forest Law (NFL) and gave the Environment Federal Council (COFEMA) the authority to establish the provincial obligations in environmental policies. In particular, and as a result of the native forest, provinces have to implement and regulate the Native Forests Territorial Planning (NFTP). This law sets ecological, social, and productive conservation categories for the implementation of NFTP. It also fixes national level standards on the matter (Articles 41 and 124 of the Argentinian Constitution) and obliges Argentina to give access to information on its environment following international regulations.³²⁷

However, the NFLN had also consequences for the most vulnerable sectors living in rural areas and using natural resources for subsistence. This is mainly due to the lack of information and monetary resources required by the state bureaucracy to grant permits for the use of natural resources. The law also meant an increase in the cost of access to legal advice, because the

³²⁴ As of the constitutional reform of 1994 in Argentina, subnational states have the original domain of natural resources.

³²⁵ Kalyani Robbins. *The Law and Policy of Environmental Federalism. A Comparative Analysis* (Edward Elgar 2015); Marta S Juliá, 'La Ley de Protección del Bosque Nativo en Argentina: Algunos Impactos Jurídicos e Institucionales del Proceso de Implementación' (2010) 6 *Pampa: Revista Interuniversitaria de Estudios Territoriales* 169; Kirsten Engel, 'Environmental Federalism: A View from the United States' (discussion paper no 15-28, *Arizona Legal Studies* 2015); Ricardo A Gutiérrez and Fernando Isuani, 'Luces y sombras de la política ambiental argentina entre 1983 y 2013' (2013) 7 *Revista S A A P* 317.

³²⁶ SAyDS – Secretary of Environment and Sustainable Development, 'GEO Argentina 2004' (Ministry of Health and Environment and United Nations Environment Programme 2006) <<http://www.ecopuerto.com/Bicentenario/informes/GEOArgentina2004.pdf>>.

³²⁷ Rio Declaration on Environment and Development of 1992, Rio Agreement on Environment and Sustainable Development, Escazú Agreement, Regional Agreement on Access to Information, Public Participation and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters in Latin America and Caribbean. Juan Martín I Azerrat, 'El Acuerdo Escazú y la accesibilidad a derechos ambientales en la Provincia de Río Negro,

formal requirements for its use do not differentiate between actors or the final use of natural resources. Only the well-informed and resource-capable actors can use the land and therefore also to the social benefits provided by law, mainly harming the populations that use it as a means of subsistence. This practice demonstrates the complex intergovernmental relations in this area.

Also, this practice connects with local finance and local structures, because the provinces receive funds for the application of the national forest law in their provincial territories and this is directly related to local structures. The provinces that are more dependent on natural resources applied this law more quickly.³²⁸ Furthermore, as of the sanction of the national law, the provinces could not deforest until they have applied their corresponding provincial laws.

Description of the Practice

One of the main incentives that led to the approval of the native forest was the economic compensation of the National Fund for the Enrichment and Conservation of Native Forests (NFECNF), a promise for all provinces once they have implemented the territorial ordering of native forests.³²⁹ Articles 30 and 31 regulate the compensation of environmental services through Non-Reimbursable Donations (ANR) to all subnational states that carry out processes of conservation of native forests.

Article 32 of the law establishes the amounts to be received by the provinces for environmental services, subject to the number of hectares with the highest degree of conservation.

In 2010, the central government assigned an item in the national budget to the provinces under the NFECNF. Applicants must submit forest management plans ranging from 10 to 15 years to ensure continuity of resources to beneficiaries. The main objective is to guarantee constant assistance and sustainable production over time. Any type of private sector activity that has an impact on the native forest must have prior authorization from the Forest Directorate. The sectors that have the greatest influence on deforestation and environmental degradation are agriculture and livestock.³³⁰

In turn, an agronomist or forestry engineer must prepare a management plan and present it at the headquarters of the Forest Directorate or at its delegations in the province, according to the requirements and procedures established for each activity.

³²⁸ MAgDS Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development, 'Law no 26,331 on Minimum Budgets for the Environmental Protection of Native Forests. Implementation status summary report' (2016) <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/informe_de_implementacion_2010_-_2016.pdf>.

³²⁹ Made up of 2% of withholdings on exports and 0.3% of the Government Budget.

³³⁰ MAgDS Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development 'Causas e impactos de la deforestación de los bosques nativos de Argentina y propuestas de desarrollo alternativas' (MAyDS 2020) <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/desmontes_y_alternativas-julio27_0.pdf> and SCCDSel Secretary of Climate Change, Sustainable Development and Innovation, 'Tercer informe bienal de actualización de la República Argentina a la Convención Marco de las Naciones Unidas para el Cambio Climático' (2019) <<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ambiente/cambio-climatico/tercer-informe-bienal>>.

In general terms, the NFLN assumes that the target community is in a position to request permits and authorizations, and that the role of the provincial state is to meet those demands. Demand is what guides the destination of funds.

While medium and large producers (those having more than 2,000 hectares) have access to permits and the benefits of the native forest law, indigenous and local communities do not. In most cases, it is due to problems in the access to information and in others due to the legal conditions of land tenure required for the granting of forest management plans.

The native forest law provides mechanisms to support small producers and peasant communities,³³¹ through comprehensive community plans. However, the national state does not have legal mechanisms to require provincial governments to effectively allocate funds to rural communities, and provincial governments justify this practice arguing that the national government does not meet the compromised budget obligations.

Assessment of the Practice

To date, all provinces have implemented their NFTP. One of the objectives of the NFL was the implementation of the NFTP to stop the deforestation derived from Argentina's productive specialization. But it also sought to have a social impact due to the fact that communities that use forests' natural resources as a means of subsistence suffer the damage caused by deforestation. This mainly occurs in the Parque Chaqueño region where the administrative units (departments) most affected by deforestation had a high percentage of indigenous population.³³² In Salta, three departments where 131 indigenous communities live represent 21 per cent of the total deforestation nationwide.³³³ In the Province of Formosa, only one department with 46 indigenous communities concentrates 12 per cent of the national total.³³⁴ In the Province of Chaco, the second department with the highest levels of deforestation accounts for 5 per cent of the national total and 36 indigenous communities live in it.³³⁵

Despite the law, the latest report from the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development reveals that from its implementation until 2018, 2.8 million hectares of native forests were lost; 87 per cent of them corresponding to the Parque Chaqueño. The main cause is the preparation of the soil for agricultural production.³³⁶ Any regulation of the forest could hinder this activity. Hence, the flexibility of the regulation in the provinces with higher levels of deforestation is because the application of the NFTP has an economic incentive behind,

³³¹ Art 21 of the Native Forests National Law no 26,331/2007.

³³² Data from deforestation: Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development (MayDS) and data base for monitoring deforestation in the Argentine Gran Chaco. Built by the Laboratory of Regional Analysis and Remote Sensing of the Faculty of Agronomy of the University of Buenos Aires (UBA), the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA) and the Chaco Argentina Agroforestry Network (REDAF). Data from indigenous communities: National Institute against Discrimination, Xenophobia and Racism (INADI).

³³³ Santa Ana, Orán and Rivadavia departments.

³³⁴ Patiño department.

³³⁵ General Guemes department.

³³⁶ MAyDS – Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development, 'Causas e impactos de la deforestación de los bosques nativos de Argentina y propuestas de desarrollo alternativas' (MayDS 2020).

access to the NFECNF. Then, the areas could be recategorized, mainly those of medium conservation value³³⁷ and thus ‘avoid blame’.³³⁸

The provinces applied different criteria to legislate their NFTP. These must be carried out by public consultations according to ecological, productive and social criteria. Therefore, according to the conservation category, the areas should be classified according to the conservation value in different colors.³³⁹ However, according to the demand for land use, the provinces have varied these criteria, classifying areas with lower conservation value to allow deforestation under apparently legal conditions.³⁴⁰

In sum, it is essential to review the actions of the national state regarding the implementation of the NFL in the provinces, mainly in the Parque Chaqueño, since it currently concentrates 64 per cent of the total native forests in the country,³⁴¹ 69 per cent of deforestation in 2019,³⁴² 50 per cent of the indigenous population,³⁴³ and the highest record of social conflicts associated with land grabbing by foreigners.³⁴⁴ In addition, it represents 46.2 per cent of the 51.2 million hectares under NFTP.

In 2011, COFEMA determined the areas most affected by deforestation to carry out a focused conservation program: ‘Native Forests and Community’ approved on 11 August 2015, by decree no 1645/2015.³⁴⁵ The funds come from a World Bank loan executed by ‘Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD)’ (94 per cent) and the rest are national funds through the Secretary of Environmental Policies and Natural Resources.³⁴⁶ The objective of the program is to promote productive use through the implementation of sustainable forest management plans that benefit small producers, native communities and peasants through

³³⁷ The provincial laws that regulate the NFTP allow the recategorization of conservation areas. In the provinces of the Chaqueño Park this is reflected in: Art 3 Provincial Law 6942; Art 13 Provincial Law 6409; Art 3(g) Provincial Law 1552 and Art 8 Provincial Law 7543.

³³⁸ Ricardo Gutiérrez and Guillermo V Alonso, ‘Gobierno municipal y coordinación interjurisdiccional de políticas públicas’ (2018) 18 Documentos y Aportes en Administración Pública y Gestión Estatal 80, cited in Lucas Figueroa, ‘Coordinación Intergubernamental en políticas ambientales. La ley de Bosques Nativos en las regiones forestales: Parque Chaqueño y Bosque Andino Patagónico’ (2019) 19 Revista documentos y aportes en administración pública y gestión estatal 7.

³³⁹ Red, higher conservation value; yellow, medium conservation value; and green, low conservation value.

³⁴⁰ Jorge Adámoli, Rubén Ginzburg and Sebastián Tortella, ‘Escenarios productivos y ambientales del Chaco Argentino: 1977-2010’ (FCEN-UBA and Fundación Producir Conservando 2011); Quispe Merovich, C and Lottici, MV ‘Los desafíos del Ordenamiento Ambiental del Territorio y los Servicios Ecosistémicos en la Ley de Bosques Nativos. In Laterra P

³⁴¹ MAyDS and data base for monitoring deforestation in the Argentine Gran Chaco. Built by the Laboratory of Regional Analysis and Remote Sensing of the Faculty of Agronomy of the University of Buenos Aires (UBA), the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA) and the Chaco Argentina Agroforestry Network (REDAF).

³⁴² Data of Global Forest Watch, <<https://www.globalforestwatch.org/>>.

³⁴³ National Institute against Discrimination, Xenophobia and Racism (INADI).

³⁴⁴ Agostina Costantino, ‘La extracción del territorio. Extranjerización de la tierra y modo de desarrollo en Argentina (doctoral thesis, FLACSO 2015). Mexico observes that 55.5% of all social conflicts derived from land grabbing by foreigners throughout the country were concentrated in the northwest and northeast on average>.

³⁴⁵ Available at <<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/decreto-1645-2015-250572/texto>>.

³⁴⁶ Available at <<https://www.ar.undp.org/content/argentina/es/home/projects/bosques-nativos/>>; <<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ambiente/bosques/comunidad>>.

comprehensive community plans, where it works with close families, generating an economic circuit of activities and resources provided by the Native Forest to promote its conservation.

Although this is also the objective of the LB (Article 2(c)), the NFECON finances livestock and forestry activities. However, the Nation cannot require the provinces to allocate funds especially to the communities.³⁴⁷The Nation-Province tension is found in the conservation requirements that derive from the National enforcement body towards the Provincial, while the funds for this to happen have not historically arrived since the Law was applied in the province.

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³⁴⁷ Interview carried out with executing technicians of the Native Forests and Communities program, Ministry of the Environment of the Argentine Nation.

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13.5 When Governors Resist in their Territories: Intergovernmental Conflicts Related to Federal Labor Legislation

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Relevance of the Practice

Under what conditions are intergovernmental relations cooperative or conflictive? When do subnational units comply with federal regulations and under what conditions do they resist them? Are there effective mechanisms of conflict resolution and follow-up procedures securing the actual implementation of decisions?

In 2011, Argentine President Cristina Fernandez de Kirchner sent to the National Congress a bill for implementing the so-called Agrarian Labor Regime (informally known as the ‘new statute of the rural laborer’). The bill defined federal regulations related to labor rights in the agricultural sector across the country (such as minimum wage, the maximum of eight hours of working day, paid vacations, prohibition of child labor, appropriate working conditions, among others).³⁴⁸ The most controversial aspect of the new bill was who was in charge of auditing and control: until then, these functions were outsourced to a private company and very much controlled by large agricultural companies in the provinces, in collusion with the rural union (UATRE)^{349, 350} In the new bill, the federal government would be in charge of controlling compliance with the federal laws.

Some governors and provincial senators from provinces with large plantations immediately resisted the bill in Congress.³⁵¹ Despite these pressures, the PJ (Justicialista Party) faction in government (the Victory Front, or FPV) got the numbers it needed and the federal legislation was passed into law 26,727 (Agrarian Labor Regime) in December 2011. After the session in Congress, the Federal Minister of Labor, Carlos Tomada, declared ‘those who opposed the bill the most were those who always had an attitude of disregard and exploitation of rural workers (...) reaching extreme situations of degradation and slavery (...). This is the economic sector

³⁴⁸ These rights had been established in 1944 but were later abolished by a law during the military dictatorship in 1980.

³⁴⁹ In an interview with a high-ranking official of the Federal Ministry of Labor on 24 July 2019, he claimed that ‘you wouldn’t notice the difference between the businessman and the union leader’.

³⁵⁰ Sebastián Premici, ‘Con todos los derechos de los otros trabajadores’ *Página 12* (22 December 2011); — — *De Patronos y Peones* (Acercádonos Ediciones 2016); Interview with high-ranking official in the area of Labor Policy Planning, Federal Ministry of Labor (Buenos Aires, 22 November 2018); Interview with FT, Resistencia (Chaco, 5 April 2019); Interview with high ranking official in the area of Labor Relations, Federal Ministry of Labor, and the National Commission of Agricultural Work (Buenos Aires, 24 July 2019).

³⁵¹ Premici, ‘Con todos los derechos de los otros trabajadores’, above; Interview with the two high ranking officials of the Federal Ministry of Labor (22 November 2018 and 24 July 2019); Interview with former Governor of Chaco (5 April 2019).

with the largest share of informal labor in the country' and 'the previous legislation did nothing to revert that'.³⁵²

After losing the battle in Congress, governors of large plantation provinces played a key role in resisting federal control of this legislation in their territories. These provincial governments were 'committed to protect the productive sector' and were 'worried about the impact on production', arguing also that 'people (in the province) make a living out of this'.³⁵³

Description of the Practice

Which provinces cooperated with the federal government? Which ones conflicted against it? We evaluated the implementation of this federal labor law in two provinces: Chaco and Corrientes. These two are neighboring provinces, historically, economically, and culturally connected, only separated by the Paraná river. In spite of these similarities, Corrientes's economy is mostly agrarian, based on large plantations. The main economic products are traditional crops such as rice, tea, yerba mate, and tobacco. It produces about 70 per cent of the dark tobaccos in the country, almost 50 per cent of the total rice, and about 15 per cent of the total yerba mate.³⁵⁴ Chaco, on the contrary, has a large public sector and historically small agricultural production units, mostly cotton and quebracho. The province had 73 public employees every 1,000 inhabitants in 2015 (Corrientes had 54; the average for the three largest provinces in the country was 38). Agricultural employment represents only 10 per cent of total employment in 2014.

As a result of this economic structure based on small agricultural production units, Chaco's political elites faced fewer pressures from the agri-business sector and had more political autonomy in relation to policies that affect it, such as the regulation of labor rights in the province. Political elites in Corrientes, on the contrary, faced more pressures from agricultural elites, which occupied key positions in the cabinet, such as the Ministry of Production.³⁵⁵

We interviewed one of the federal supervisors of the RENATRE (National Registry of Rural Workers and Employers) who examined work conditions in the agricultural sector and assessed compliance with federal labor laws in Chaco and Corrientes. He stressed that 'the provincial government helped (implementing and complying with federal labor laws) in Chaco' (Franco Capitanich, cousin of the Governor, was in the area of the provincial government coordinating with federal supervisors). When asked about the situation in Corrientes, he replied: 'In Corrientes no; it's complicated in Corrientes. The provincial political power could not be in favor of something that went against their interests'.³⁵⁶

³⁵² — — 'Satisfacción de Tomada' *Página 12* (22 December 2011).

³⁵³ Interview with high ranking official in the area of Labor Relations, Federal Ministry of Labor, and the National Commission of Agricultural Work (Buenos Aires, 24 July 2019).

³⁵⁴ Ministry of Economy and Public Finances and National Directorate for Provincial Affairs, 'Corrientes. Informe Sintético de Caracterización Socio-Productiva' (2018).

³⁵⁵ Lucas González and Marcelo Nazareno, 'Resisting Equality: Subnational State Capture and the Unequal Distribution of Inequality.' (2021) *Comparative Politics* <<https://doi.org/10.5129/001041522X16185909705013>>.

³⁵⁶ Interview with FT, Resistencia (Chaco, 5 April 2019).

Assessment of the Practice

Despite provincial resistance, in a simple but perhaps revealing indicator, Corrientes had 1,399 sanctions due to failure to comply with federal labor regulations.³⁵⁷ Chaco has 48 per cent fewer sanctions than Corrientes (it had 945 sanctions). Provinces of equivalent population have values close to those of Chaco (Santiago del Estero has 913 and Misiones 746 sanctions). We conducted a similar search in April, 2019 and the results are quite consistent: Corrientes had 1,392 sanctions and Chaco 938.³⁵⁸ These results have notable implications for workers, especially informal laborers, in rural areas: conflicts between units of governments affect how federal labor regulations are implemented across the territory.

The cases we analyzed show that provinces with more influential economic elites have lower compliance with federal laws, more conflicts with the federal government, and more repression of federal labor rights. This is so because provincial economic elites resisted redistributive politics in Corrientes more than in Chaco, where the province complied with and supported federal labor laws.

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³⁵⁷ Data collected from the Public Registry of Employers with Labor Sanctions (REPSAL), during October and November, 2018; accessed 27 November 2018.

³⁵⁸ REPSAL site, <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/trabajo/repsal>, accessed 4 April 2019.

14. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India

14.1 The System of Local Government in India

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Types of Local Governments

In India, institutions of local government exist at two levels, local *panchayats* or councils in the rural areas and municipalities in the urban areas. At the rural level, *Panchayati Raj* Institutions (PRIs) consist of three levels: *gram panchayats*, *panchayat samitis* and *zilla parishads*.

A *gram panchayat* can be translated as village council or jury as it is the only grassroots-level institution of PRIs' formalized local self-governance system in India at the village or small-town level. It consists of an elected *sarpanch* (head) and five to twelve elected members. The *gram panchayats* are responsible for the creation of annual development plans, the budget for construction, repairs and maintenance of community assets, *khadi* and village industries³⁵⁹, adult and non-formal education, public health, poverty alleviation, education, cultural activities, rural housing and electrification, promoting agriculture, social welfare and public distribution scheme.

At the intermediate level, the *panchayat samitis* (block panchayats) operate. They work at the *tehsil* or *taluka* level³⁶⁰ known as development block and provide a crucial link of

³⁵⁹ Village and *khadi* industries are based on the concept of *Swadeshi* wherein the use of labour is central and the use of capital is limited, underlying the concept of self-reliance in the economy. These industries rely on local raw materials and local production at small scale.

³⁶⁰ There are two constitutional amendments, 73rd and 74th passed in 1992 which provide a whole scenario of the different levels of local governments at rural and urban level. The 73rd amendment states a three-tier system of *panchayati raj* at the village *panchayat* (*gram*), block (intermediate) level (*panchayat samiti*) and district levels (*zilla parishad*) for a population of more than 20 *lakh* (2 million). *Gram* or village *panchayat* consists of *gram sabha* and members of the village *panchayat* directly elected by the people and headed by the *pradhan* (elected head) village council (*gram sabha*) consist of all the members of the village. Each *gram panchayat* is assisted by four committees that is *samata samiti* (committee for welfare of women and children, scheduled caste and tribes and other backward classes) *vikas samiti* (committee for development in agriculture), *shiksha samiti* (education) and *lokhit* committee (public health and public works). In between *gram panchayat* and *zilla panchayat* is *panchayat samiti* (committee) which forms the main chain of communication between the two. The next level of local government is *zilla parishad*, consisting of all the elected representatives of *gram panchayat* and elected representatives from territorial constituencies in the panchayat, members of legislative assembly and legislative council

The 74th Amendment consists of three bodies of urban governments – *nagar panchayat* which is primarily constituted when the village transitions from rural to urban, municipal council for smaller urban areas, municipal corporations for larger urban areas. Municipal committees are also assisted by ward committees which makes a two-tier system.

communication between *gram panchayat* and district administration. They are also known as *mandal parishad*, *mandal panchayat* and *taluka panchayat* and are primarily made of four-member ex officio bodies bringing together all *sarpanchas* of the development block, the members of parliament (MPs) and MLAs (members of legislative assembly) of the area, and sub-divisional officer (SDOs).³⁶¹ The functions of the *panchayat samitis* are agricultural and land improvement, establishment of primary health centers and primary schools, water and sanitation, village infrastructure (construction of roads etc.), establishment of cooperative societies, water and irrigation management, promotion of animal husbandry, dairy and poultry, social welfare, social activities, technical training, poverty alleviation, promotion and development of cottage and skill industries.

The third level is the *zilla parishad* (district council). *Zilla parishad* or the district council is an elected body consisting of members from state legislatures and the Parliament as explained later. The ex officio chief executive officer of the *zilla parishad* is the additional deputy commissioner who is either from the Indian Administrative Services (IAS) or Provincial Civil Services (PCS) appointed in the state. The *zilla parishad* consists of mainly elected members from demarcated constituencies, the chairpersons of *panchayat samitis*, MPs and MLAs. The member of the *zilla parishad* also acts as chairperson of the *parishads* (councils) that fall in their constituencies from which they are elected for a term of five years. The functions of the *zilla parishad* are planning and administration of development projects for the district, delivery of services and facilities to the village, promotion of agricultural projects such as training new techniques of farming, horticulture, rural housing, electrification, animal husbandry and dairy, promotion of small-scale industries, health and hygiene, education and social welfare. In all the levels of local governments, there are reserved seats for women, scheduled caste, scheduled tribes and other backward classes.

All the institutions of local self-government operate under the principle of democratic decentralization. The rationale of democratic decentralization was to create PRIs in a multi-level framework of governance which are autonomous, democratic and financially strong. It was a step away from a top-down approach to local governance in order to provide self-administration to people in the rural areas. The twenty-nine functions and responsibilities of the PRIs which have been stated above are all enshrined in the Indian Constitution in the Article 243G. The functions are listed in the eleventh Schedule of the Constitution.

At the urban level, there are three types of local bodies, the *nagar nigam* (municipal corporation), *nagar palika* (municipality) and *nagar panchayat* (town *panchayat*). The status of an area decides the provision and implementation of urban local bodies. For an area transitioning from rural to urban, a city council is required. In small urban areas a municipality

³⁶¹ The districts in a state are divided into sub-divisions and the sub-divisional officer (SDOs) oversees these divisions. The SDO is responsible for the administration of these divisions in the districts. There can be two kinds of roles. One in which they are in charge of office work and another, in which they are not bound in an office but are overseeing a range of works such as communicating with people, overlooking implementation of government schemes.

is required and in large urban areas a municipal corporation.³⁶² The functions and powers of urban local bodies vary from state to state. Municipal corporations work and directly interact with the state governments. The head of the corporation is the mayor and the principal executive officer is the municipal commissioner. Municipalities interact with the respective state government through the district collector. The head of the municipality is the president elected by the members of the *palika*. The state government appoints officers such as health or sanitation Inspectors to provide assistance to the president. City councils have a chairman and ward members. The functions assigned to urban local bodies are urban planning and management, provision of health services, education, water management, waste disposal and sanitation, public infrastructure, birth and death registrations, poverty alleviation and delivery of social services.

Legal Status of Local Governments

To realize the goals of democratic decentralization, the government amended the Constitution and passed the 73rd and 74th Amendment Act in 1992. The important aspects of the act were the three-tier system of *panchayati raj* for all states exceeding the population of two millions, the holding every five years of *Panchayat* elections, the reservation of seats for women, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, the appointment of a state finance commission to make recommendations in cognizance with the financial powers of the panchayat and the establishment of district planning committees (DPCs) to prepare development plans for the district as a whole. It also foresaw the establishment of a state election commission to help state governments conducting periodic elections to the PRIs. Similarly, for urban local governments, the 74th Amendment provides a three-tier structure of governance with the municipal wards as the territorial constituencies forming the basic unit of urban local governance.

The scope of powers and functions enshrined in the Constitution envision PRIs to function as institutions of local self-government and to operationalize the devolution of powers which is central to the principle of democratic decentralization. The scope and powers entrusted to PRIs base themselves in the ideals of economic development and social justice. In accordance with the constitutional amendment, the state governments repealed the then existing acts. The 73rd Amendment Act was further extended to the scheduled areas and areas predominantly occupied with tribal population. It was extended through the provisions of *Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas Act, 1996*.

For the urban local bodies, 74th Amendment Act was adopted in 1992 enjoining the government of the day to ensure continuity of the municipalities through a periodic five-year election. Similar to the *Panchayati Raj System*, the urban local bodies have a three-tier system, including the above-mentioned municipal corporations, municipalities and town *panchayats*.

³⁶² Transitioning areas are defined based on how fast a town is developing due to industrialization or agricultural growth or secondary services. The criteria of population and the level of administrative functions is considered too, as big cities such as Delhi, Mumbai and others will have a municipal corporation and smaller towns will have municipalities.

The composition of these councils is decided by state governments respectively. There are reservations of seats for women, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and other backward classes.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The rural and urban government bodies do not have exactly similar scopes of responsibilities. The former are more entrusted with tasks of being regulators, administrators and providers of various services at the local level. The latter have two sets of parts to play. One, the municipal corporation must deliberate on matters related to budget, taxation, pricing of services and others, and two, the municipal commissioner is the executive head and exercises control on various departments such as finance, health etc. For example, the urban local bodies have to look at the jurisdictional domain of various urban areas, their judicial powers, implementation of policies and plans as per the 74th Constitutional Amendment. Despite their differences regarding modes of functioning and the devolution of the powers and authority, both rural and urban local bodies aim at enabling people's participation as a sign of democratic citizenship.

Political and Social Context in India

India has a multiparty parliamentary system of democracy with representatives at the local, state and national levels contesting elections and participating in democratic decision-making process. Both national and state level political parties are involved in the local level governance through their elected representatives in both rural and urban forms of local government. Local government in India is a state subject, however, the central government holds a supervisory role to guide, encourage, engage and assist the states to promote local government and development. Political participation in *panchayati raj* elections has a long tradition of great leaders like Jawaharlal Nehru, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel and Subhash Chand Bose who took active leadership in municipal politics. Thus, politics at local government provides a gateway to national level politics and thereby initiates an active involvement of national and regional parties. The presence of national, state and regional parties at the level of local government maintains a strong party presence which has its bearing on national and state level politics. Political parties are the essence of parliamentary democracy and their role in local governments strengthens the roots of democratic decentralization. According to the World Bank report, in India 65.97 per cent live in rural areas³⁶³ and 34.03 per cent of the population lives in urban areas.³⁶⁴

Local governments have had a tremendous effect in the realization of democracy at the grassroots and at the level of municipalities in the urban areas. Conducting elections at the lowest tier of government has added to the vibrant political culture of India. The trickling down

³⁶³ 'Rural Population (% of Total Population)' (*The World Bank*, 2018)

<<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.RUR.TOTL.ZS>>.

³⁶⁴ 'India - Urban Population (% Of Total)' (*Trading Economics*, 2020) <<https://tradingeconomics.com/india/urban-population-percent-of-total-wb-data.html>>.

of democratic decentralization and power has entrenched the roots of democracy, however, its substantive realization has many hurdles to cross.

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14.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India: An Introduction

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India follows a devolved system of decentralization in which the states are responsible for the devolution of powers to the urban and rural local authorities. At the local level, intergovernmental relationships exist between different tiers of local rural government. The administrative units at each state level have their own historical trajectory and a uniform pattern does not exist for each state. Each state has its own administrative units and structures. Therefore, a certain amount of friction is bound to arise over operational guidelines and implementation for different projects and delivery of services. The state government looks over various projects and plans and decides on the devolution of powers and functions for these activities and projects. A three-tier system works at the local levels which are accountable to state government.³⁶⁵ Similarly, the decentralization of power and decision-making works at all levels from the center to the states.

There are several federal bodies and inter-governmental organizations such as inter-state councils, district boards and committees of various kinds which have been formed from time to time to work towards establishing the intergovernmental relations between the lower and higher levels of administration. In doing so, regional development boards and units are also set up by different states from time to time. With the rapid urbanization that the Indian cities are experiencing, it is imperative that cities act as the main catalyst of development. This level of coordination between center, state and local government is crucial for the development and growth of large cities.

Thus, for the cities to generate 'agglomeration economies', the imbalance between responsibilities and finances must be worked out.³⁶⁶ The relationship between *panchayats*, urban local units and government departments has been a domain of contestation and messy politics.

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³⁶⁵ For more detail, see report section 4.2. on Decentralization and Democratic Governance.

³⁶⁶ Isher J Ahluwalia and others, 'State of Municipal Finances in India' (Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations 2019).

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14.3 Local Governments and their Functioning

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Relevance of the Practice

Inter-governmental relations at all the three levels (central, state and the local) are important in a federal structure like India, so as to deliver the necessary services and needs to the people of the country as a whole. An integrative functioning of all the three levels is imperative for a successful implementation of any practice or a program that the government formulates. The practices that we have taken for this report section are the rural mission (rural local governance) and the smart city mission (urban local governance) which has been discussed in detail below. In the case of both, we have tried to analyze how all the three structures (central, state and local governments) are involved efficiently in delivering the necessary infrastructure and service needs of both the rural and urban population.

Moreover, any practice should follow the principle of subsidiary operation in the distribution of functions among three tiers of government under the principle of decentralization, namely: (i) every activity requires a minimum size for functional efficiency and economy; (ii) the area of benefit should not extend beyond the jurisdiction of the *panchayat* concerned; and (iii) the administrative resources available at that particular level are capable of handling the activity in a competent manner.³⁶⁷

Description of the Practice

Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission (SPMRM) – Rural Local Government

The vision statement of SPMRM is the ‘development of a cluster of villages that preserve and nurture the essence of rural community life with focus on equity and inclusiveness without compromising with the facilities perceived to be essentially urban in nature, thus creating a cluster of “Rurban villages”’.

The mission outcomes are:

- bridging the rural urban divide- economic, technological and those related to facilities and services;
- spreading development in the region;
- attracting investments in the rural areas;
- Stimulating local economic development with emphasis on reduction of poverty and unemployment in rural areas.

³⁶⁷ ‘Decentralisation in India. Challenges & Opportunities’ (Discussion Paper Series 1, United Nations Development Programme)
<https://www.undp.org/content/dam/india/docs/decentralisation_india_challenges_opportunities.pdf>.

A 'rurban cluster', would be a cluster of geographically contiguous villages with a population of about 25,000 to 50,000 in plain and coastal areas and a population of 5,000 to 15,000 in desert, hilly or tribal areas. As far as practicable, clusters of villages would follow administrative convergence units of *gram panchayats* and shall be within a single block/*tehsil* for administrative convenience. Rurban clusters would be developed through the provision of training linked to economic activities, the development of skills and local entrepreneurship and the provision of necessary infrastructure amenities.

The following components are envisaged as desirable components in each cluster:

- skill development training linked to economic activities;
- Agro Processing, Agri Services, Storage and Warehousing;
- a fully equipped mobile health unit;
- the upgrading of school/higher education facilities;
- sanitation;
- the provision of piped water supply;
- solid and liquid waste management;
- village streets and drains;
- street lights;
- inter-village road connectivity;
- public transport;
- LPG gas connections;
- digital literacy;
- Citizen Service Center for the electronic delivery of citizen centric services/*egram* connectivity;
- components pertaining to agriculture and allied activities would be required to be given

In order to achieve the envisaged outcomes, under the National Rurban Mission (NRuM), the state government shall identify the existing Central Sector, Centrally Sponsored and State Government Schemes relevant for the development of the cluster and converge their implementation in an integrated and time-bound manner.

The NRuM institutional framework is hierarchical. The mission envisages the engagement of key stakeholders at the national, state, district and *gram sabha* level for the success of it. At the national level the institutional framework serves to formulate and facilitate the implementation of the mission. At national level, the mission is monitored by an empowered committee which is assisted by an expert group and a national mission directorate. The state institutional frameworks play a key role in implementing the mission and they are expected to identify rurban clusters. Thereafter, the states are expected to implement and to provide support in the operations and maintenance of rurban clusters. A state nodal agency monitors implementation which is assisted by a state technical support agency and a state project monitoring unit. At the district level, the institutional framework helps in empowering decisions, convergence and coordination of various matters. The district framework involves officers of the concerned line departments and heads of the concerned *gram panchayats*. At the cluster level, *gram sabhas* play an active role and they are assisted by rural development professionals.

The implementation of the scheme therefore starts at the central level and ends at the *gram sabha* level, passing through the state and district level government machineries. The state

nodal agency will consult the *panchayati raj* institutions at the *zilla*, *panchayat samiti* and the *gram panchayat* on the NRuM activities to be undertaken in the clusters. The mission should be adopted by the *gram sabhas* of all the participating *gram panchayats* through *gram sabha* and *panchayat samiti* resolutions. *Panchayat Raj* Institution (PRI) members are to be included at all stages of the project cycle from planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and maintenance of assets created during the project period. State governments are requested to ensure the participation of local elected representatives comprising members of parliament (MPs), and members of legislative assemblies (MLAs) etc., whenever 'rurban' projects are inaugurated/launched.

Smart Cities Mission – Urban Local Government

In 2015, the Government of India (Union Government) launched the Smart Cities Mission. The purpose of the Smart Cities Mission is to drive economic growth and improve the quality of life of people by enabling local area development and harnessing technology, especially technology that leads to smart outcomes. Area-based development will transform existing urban areas (retrofit and redevelop), including slums, into better planned ones, thereby improving livability of the whole city. New areas (greenfield) will be developed around cities in order to accommodate the expanding population in urban areas. The application of smart solutions will enable cities to use technology, information and data to improve infrastructure and services. Comprehensive development in this way will improve quality of life, create employment and enhance incomes for all, especially the poor and the disadvantaged, leading to inclusive cities. The focus of Smart Cities Mission is on sustainable and inclusive development and the idea is to look at compact areas and to create a replicable model which will act like a lighthouse to other aspiring cities. There are now 100 cities under the mission.

The implementation of the mission at the city level will be done by a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) created for the purpose. The bulk of smart city initiatives in India are based on area-based development, i.e. the development of new real estate – a function that is not within the obligatory or discretionary function of a municipal body as per the 12th Schedule. Essentially, the SPV would work as a master developer, entering into arrangements with other developers to develop the site for redevelopment, new development or retrofitting, and thereafter exiting the project, having earned its requisite dividend or expended the amounts for capital works. Being a separate corporate body (typically under the 2013 Companies Act), the SPV can take up processes, works and mechanisms which the municipal body may not be empowered to do in terms of law or its processes, such as being able to raise large amounts of debt, enter into joint venture arrangements, lease, purchase or sell assets – most of which, for municipalities, need separate sanction from the state government.

The SPV will plan, appraise, approve, release funds, implement, manage, operate, monitor and evaluate the smart city development projects. Each smart city will have a SPV which will be headed by a full time chief executive officer (CEO) and have nominees of central government, state government and the urban local body (ULB) on its board. The chief executive officer of this SPV, usually a senior bureaucrat appointed by the state government, has a fixed tenure of three years and cannot be replaced without the authorization of the Government of India. The states/ULBs shall ensure that, (i) a dedicated and substantial revenue stream is made available to the SPV so as to make it self-sustainable and could evolve its own credit worthiness for raising additional resources from the market (equity and debt) and (ii) government

contribution for smart cities is used only to create infrastructure that has public benefit outcomes. The execution of projects may be done through joint ventures, subsidiaries, public-private partnership (PPP), turnkey contracts, etc., suitably dovetailed with revenue streams. The SPV will be a limited company at the city-level, in which the state and the ULB will be the promoters having 50:50 equity shareholding. The private sector or financial institutions could be considered for taking equity stake in the SPV, provided the shareholding pattern of 50:50 of the state/union territory (UT) and the ULB is maintained and the state/UT and the ULB together have majority shareholding and control of the SPV. The mission is monitored separately by all the three levels - center, state and city.

The central government used a competition-based method as a means for selecting cities under the Smart Cities Mission and they receive seed funding from both the central and state governments (50:50). Cities competed at the state level with other cities within the state. Then the state-level winner competed at the national level Smart City Challenge. Cities obtaining the highest marks in a particular round were chosen to be part of the mission. This captures the spirit of 'competitive and cooperative federalism'.

Assessment of the Practice

The Rurban Mission is a promising one, which aims at providing urban facilities in terms of infrastructure and services to the rural areas and at the same time creates employment opportunities. The Ministry of Rural Development has identified 300 clusters of 20 villages each across India with population ranging from 25,000 to 50,000 through 'a scientific process of cluster selection which involves an objective analysis at the district, sub-district and village level, of the demography, economy, tourism and pilgrimage significance and transportation corridor impact'.³⁶⁸ The central government should look into the underlying poor institutional capacities adding to the problem of already burdened and understaffed departments working for the rural and urban issues. It is also important to take into consideration the indigenous knowledge system and work modules towards a sustainable livelihood along with the urban infrastructure and services in the villages.

Coming to the Smart City Mission, this had vowed for technology driven cities in urban areas. The Economic Survey 2019 says that as many as 5,151 projects worth more than Rs 2 lakh crore (approximately €35 billion) are being implemented in 100 cities under the government's smart city mission. A smart city is defined as an urban area which uses various types of electronic Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to gather data and to support function and resources for operating a city effectively. This mission has benefitted one section of the society and others who are technologically illiterate and do not get benefits from the program and leading at times to polarization of the population, which in turn leads to unequal technology sharing among people and regions of the country. This must catch the attention of the policy-makers so as to make digital literacy an imperative to really benefit from the mission.

³⁶⁸ Press Information Bureau, 'Union Cabinet Approves Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission to Drive Economic, Social and Infrastructure Development in Rural Areas' (Government of India Cabinet, 16 September 2015).

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15. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Australia

15.1 The System of Local Government in Australia

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Types of Local Governments

Australia is a federation with three levels of government: the Commonwealth (federal/national), states and territories; and local government. Local government is established through the separate constitutions of each state and one territory. Therefore, although councils perform similar functions, there are effectively seven different governance systems across the country.

The size of councils in Australia varies dramatically. The largest is Brisbane City Council in Queensland which serves a community of just over one million people, covers an area of 133,809 ha³⁶⁹ and has an operating budget of over AUD 3 billion.³⁷⁰ In stark contrast, Sandstone Shire Council, in Western Australia, has a population of 81 residents living in an area covering 3,266,650 ha,³⁷¹ comparable to the size of Belgium at 3,300,000 ha.³⁷² Sandstone's expenditure in 2020 was AUD 5.6 million.³⁷³

Reflecting the country's British administrative heritage, local governments across Australia are typically referred to as a 'council', 'city' or 'municipality', 'shire' or 'town' depending on factors such as their size, location, or history. 'County councils' also exist as incorporations of, and controlled by, two or more local governments; established to deliver services usually across rural areas.

Currently there 537 local governments in Australia. This has been reduced from its peak of 1,000 due to ongoing structural reform aimed primarily at improving efficiency and effectiveness. Reduction has mostly been obtained through the process of amalgamation.

Despite often being strongly resisted by local communities and councils, amalgamations have been a significant policy in most Australian jurisdictions over the last two decades. Opposition to amalgamations has been based on numerous factors, such as concerns about loss of local identity and scepticism about purported efficiency gains. Both arguments were central to opposition to the most recent round of council large scale mergers that took place in New South Wales in 2016. At that time the state government pushed a highly controversial program

³⁶⁹ Information retrieved from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (2019).

³⁷⁰ Information retrieved from Brisbane City Council (2020).

³⁷¹ Information retrieved from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (2019).

³⁷² Information retrieved from World Bank (2015).

³⁷³ Information retrieved from Shire of Sandstone (2020).

that was only partially finished, and ultimately abandoned, after community and council resistance derailed the process in a number of locations.

Local government in Australia has traditionally performed a regulatory role, including planning and building approvals, dog and cat management, and food and health inspections. Whilst they tend to have a narrower remit than in many other comparable countries, they also play an important role in community infrastructure such as the provision of local roads and waste management. In recent decades many councils have also extended their economic and community services to include childcare, youth programs, libraries and sport and recreation facilities, and community health activities.

Legal Status of Local Government

Local government is currently not formally recognised in the Australian Constitution. Whilst there has been attempts to amend this, including two referendums, its legal status remains dependent on state legislation. Many of its powers and responsibilities are subordinate to state and national governments, and there is often significant overlap of policy and programs.

These structural arrangements place limits on local government service delivery responsibilities and earnings. Local governments raise revenue from a range of sources including user charges, fines, developer contributions and income from properties, with utilities, waste and recycling services representing the most significant portion of own-revenue raised. However, the only form of tax they can charge is rates. Larger councils have significant income earning capacity and are able to generate around 80 per cent of their income, including waste and recycling charges. In contrast, much smaller councils are increasingly dependent on state and federal government grants.

Commonwealth grants have played a significant role in funding local government since the mid-1970s. However, the historic interpretation of the Australian Constitution was such that funds can only go *via* the state authorities. In this context, funding from the Commonwealth for local government purposes is 'tied', meaning that the state and territories do not have any discretion in how it is to be used. This arrangement was made more complex by a 2009 High Court of Australia decision (*Pape v Commissioner of Taxation*) regarding the Commonwealth's powers to authorise one-off payments to taxpayers. That decision was seen by many to limit the Commonwealth's ability to directly fund local government and remains contentious.

(A)Symmetry of the Local Government System

Australian local governments (councils) are led by elected officials. Generally, elected members act as formal decision-makers for strategic plans, policies and budgets prepared by the executive leadership staff of a council. The nature of these plans is often set out in state and territory legislation.

One form of elected official is the councillor. In addition to their strategic decision-making duties, councillors are also responsible for appointing and overseeing the performance of the

general manager/chief executive officer in accordance with an employment contract. This has become a contentious issue in several locations, with some local governments experiencing a high turnover rate amongst their chief executives. This has created numerous concerns, ranging from claims of councillors excessively interfering in operations, to perceived tenure uncertainty making it difficult to attract quality staff.

Another form of elected official is the mayor. The mayor is typically a ceremonial figure and in most cases is chosen from within the cohort of councillors to act on a rotational basis. There are, however, some differences across the country. For example, mayors in Queensland (and now increasingly in other jurisdictions) are mostly directly elected and have wide powers to prepare major policies and budgets.

Voting in local government elections is compulsory in all locations, excluding South Australia, Tasmania and Western Australia. Councillors are usually members of a political party and local government elections are party political, with the major political parties being represented and generally holding a majority. This is particularly the case within metropolitan areas. In fact, local government is often seen as a training ground for political aspirants. In rural areas, candidates are more likely to run independently, although they may be a member of a political party on a personal level.

Political and Social Context in Australia

The geography of Australia, and its cultural, social and economic history, present specific challenges to local government. This has led to councils lacking a uniform capacity to deliver services.

Rural and regional Australia is facing wide-ranging challenges including an ageing local population, poor infrastructure, limited education and employment opportunities, the drift of young people to urban centres, and more. In many rural towns, local councils provide a significant role as a major employer and service provider within the community therefore their sustainability is central to community wellbeing. This is less likely to be the case in a metropolitan location. Therefore, the role of local government within the community varies greatly, depending on a number of external factors.

The Australian Local Government Association (ALGA), the peak body for councils, identified 5 priority areas in its 2020-23 Strategic Plan which provide a useful guide to issues of contemporary importance to the sector. These are: financial sustainability; roads and infrastructure funding; waste; community resilience and climate change.

The Commonwealth has supported local government through a series of grants programs, as previously mentioned. Much of that funding is for infrastructure. For example, the current main initiatives focus on roads (AUD 7.3b between 2000 and 2019) and regional and community infrastructure. However, in 2016 the total value of Commonwealth grants equated to just 7 per cent of the amount spent by local government nationally. In its 2019 national election proposals, ALGA called for further funding for these programs in addition to health and wellbeing, digital, and Indigenous community funding.

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15.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Australia: An Introduction

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From 1992 to 2020, local governments were represented at Australia's chief intergovernmental forum, the Council of Australian Governments (COAG), through the Australian Local Government Association (ALGA).

COAG was established to improve and promote intergovernmental arrangements. It sought to ensure co-operation between all levels of government and increase structural efficiency. It also aimed to find ways to enhance accountability, as service delivery in Australia is often poorly delineated between different levels of government. COAG focused on key policy reforms of national significance, such as the National Competition Policy.

ALGA is the peak body of state local government associations. It advocates on behalf of its members and has historically represented local government at a range of national government committees and forums. ALGA's board is made up of 2 representatives of each state association plus an independent chair. ALGA was a member of COAG, together with the Australian Government, the governments of the six states and two mainland territories.

When created, COAG replaced Premiers' Conferences and, progressively, a large number of Ministerial Councils including the Council on Local Government. Through ALGA, local government had observer status at some of these meetings, but formal membership was normally restricted to state and federal government representatives.

On 29 May 2020, in response to the crisis brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic, the Australian Prime Minister announced the establishment a National Cabinet to replace COAG. The National Cabinet is now the country's chief inter-governmental decision-making body. It comprises the Premiers and Chief Ministers of the eight states and territories and the Prime Minister. ALGA, and by extension local government, is not a member of this Cabinet. Within this new institutional landscape, the Commonwealth may be more inclined to leave local government issues to the states, and state governments might become more centralist, increasing their control over local governments. This is a particular risk during and post-Covid where state and local government revenue bases have been much reduced and many local governments will likely not be financially viable without increased state support.

In this context, and during a time of major change, ALGA found itself potentially marginalised and expressed concern that the voice of local government would not be heard. While there have been calls for a decision about appropriate governance arrangements remain, the current question is how local government should position itself within this evolving institutional context.

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15.3 Changes in the Structure of Intergovernmental Relations and their Implications for Local Government

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Relevance of the Practice

It is not clear how changes in the structure of intergovernmental relations within the Australian Federation will affect the status of local governments. The ability of the sector through its peak body, the Australian Local Government Association (ALGA), to have its voice heard in policy debates and negotiations at a federal level has been severely curtailed. The implications of this exclusion not only in policy making but delivery of essential services and partnership in political leadership, may be examined as we evaluate the efficacy of our responses to Covid-19 pandemic.

Description of the Practice

The shift from the Council of Australian Governments (COAG) to a National Cabinet structure has excluded local government from the primary intergovernmental mechanism within Australia. More work needs to be done to understand the repercussions and implications of this shift. A review of the relative strengths and failings of the COAG model, the opportunities and limitation of the National Cabinet structure, capabilities and limits of current local governments' engagement and influence in the national arena and exploration of comparative practice and models in other countries.

Assessment of the Practice

While some lobbying has taken place by ALGA and some of the state level peak bodies for the inclusion of local government within National Cabinet, debate on this issue continues to be relatively muted. It is unclear whether the presence of local government within this intergovernmental mechanism would indeed make a significant difference to the sector or to the federation as a whole.

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16. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Malaysia

16.1 The System of Local Government in Malaysia

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Types of Local Governments

Under the Federal Constitution of Malaysia 1957, there are three levels of government: federal, state and local. Local government is designated under Schedule 9 as a state matter. Nonetheless, local government is governed by uniform legislation in the form of the Local Government Act 1976 (LGA) and other statutes such as the Street, Drainage and Building Act 1974, and the Town and Country Planning Act 1976 (TCPA). It should be noted that this uniformity only applies to the 11 states of West (otherwise known as ‘Peninsular’) Malaysia, and not to the East Malaysian states of Sabah and Sarawak on the Island of Borneo, which have different legal systems from that of West Malaysia, as well as different legal and administrative history, statute laws generally, and extent of state autonomy compared to the states of West Malaysia.³⁷⁴ Accordingly in this report, to avoid laborious double coverage and potentially confusing, varied responses on each issue, this report is confined to West Malaysia, although federal statistics necessarily apply to Malaysia as a whole, and cannot usually be broken down.

The historical development and the present structure of local government are set out in detail in report section 4. Malaysia has three types of local governments, namely, city councils (18), municipal councils (38), and district councils (94). Apart from these three types of local council, there are six special-purpose local governments designed as ‘development authorities’.³⁷⁵ There is only one level of local government, and local councils are accordingly not placed under higher-level authorities other than the state and federal governments, and there are no intermediate organisations of any kind.

These types of council are somewhat differently structured but perform the same functions. District councils, which cover rural areas, are the most recently created, and it is only since the 1976 reforms that all rural areas in West Malaysia have become areas governed by local authorities.³⁷⁶ District councils will be seen in this report to be under-privileged compared to the two kinds of urban council, being relatively poorly endowed and empowered in practice compared to the other two types of local government. This is in spite of the fact that their

³⁷⁴ Local government in Sabah is governed by the Local Government Ordinance 1961, and the equivalent legislation in Sarawak is the Local Authority Ordinance 1948, the Kuching Municipal Ordinances 1988, and the City of Kuching North Ordinance 1988.

³⁷⁵ See below, Section 3 on the (A)Symmetry of the Local Government System.

³⁷⁶ For more detail on the 1976 reforms, see the introduction to the Structure of Local Government in Malaysia, report section 4.1.

functions are exactly the same, albeit applied to smaller populations. Accordingly, it is difficult to differentiate between rural and urban local government in the absence of any clear markers and a lack of literature encountered in this project that is devoted to district councils as opposed to all councils. To take just one example, the issue of practice regarding public-private partnerships is distinguished³⁷⁷ between states that are part of the federal government's consortia arrangements and states that are not; there is no distinction between urban and rural councils. The urban-rural divide in terms of treatment is a deep and historic one in Malaysian local government, and is of course a very symptomatic of countries like Malaysia that have been in the throes of rapid development and the intense urbanization that goes with it. Despite the fact that, as we shall see, local governments exercise a wide range of powers, a number of factors inhibit the autonomy of local governments. These factors will be examined further in this report, especially in report section 5 on inter-governmental relations (IGR).

First, local government elections are not required by the Constitution, and have been suspended since 1965, so that there is no local *self-government*, and no *right* as such to local self-government.

Secondly, as a consequence of this, local councillors are appointed by the state governments, and appointments are usually, although not always, made on the basis of party allegiance to the party in power at the state level; this does not seem to depend on whether that party is in government or in opposition at the federal level. Accordingly, local government is stitched into the patronage-based, clientelist system that characterizes Malaysian politics, rendering it especially unlikely that local councillors will decide against the desires of the state government.³⁷⁸ This factor is critical.

Thirdly, state governments have powers under the LGA, Section 103, to give directions of a general character to local governments; this power is expanded even further on occasion in practice to directions of a specific character.

Fourthly, policy on local government is coordinated amongst the various states by the National Local Government Council, a federal body set up under Article 95A of the Constitution, which gives much power to the federal government to control the operation of local government despite it being a state matter.

Fifthly, as is that case in most countries, it is universally acknowledged that local government finance faces considerable challenges, except in some wealthier areas such as Penang and Selangor. Local government finance is discussed further in report section 4 on local government structure.

Taken together, these five factors restrict considerably the freedom of operation of local governments. Under report section 5 on IGR the report introduced as an example the 'SPICE' episode, set out in detail in a recent book by a former Penang councillor, Lim Mah Hui. In this episode the state government went beyond its powers, in making decisions regarding a

³⁷⁷ See report section 3.2. on Urban Cleansing and Privatisation.

³⁷⁸ Lim Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied? A Personal Journey into Local Government in Malaysia* (SIRDC 2020).

contract to build a new conference centre, that were properly within the jurisdiction of the local government.³⁷⁹

Legal Status of Local Governments

List II of the Federal Constitution's Ninth Schedule recognises local government as function of the state governments, but, acting under a provision in the Constitution (Article 76) for effecting uniformity amongst the states, Parliament passed the LGA in 1976, and this statute governs local government in West Malaysia. Accordingly, the local government system is legally and constitutionally entrenched, even though there are no elections.

Local government authorities are legal persons in the form of bodies corporate and may sue or be sued in their own rights as well as being subject to judicial review under administrative law with respect to their acts and decisions. In a recent example, a district council was held to have exceeded its powers by amending a valuation list and charging rates to a company not included in the original list.³⁸⁰ Powers not specifically allocated to the federal power under the Constitution lie with the states; however, local government powers have to be specifically granted by statute and they are subject to the overriding principle that local authorities cannot act *ultra vires*, that is, beyond the powers they are given by statute. Local government powers nonetheless include any powers that are *reasonably incidental* to the statutory powers they enjoy. This is specified in the LGA, but is also a well-known principle in common law systems.³⁸¹

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Local government is the lowest level of Malaysia's multi-layered system of government, employing only 7 per cent of all public employees. Nonetheless, local government functions such as development control, public housing, roads and transport, parks and public places, and public nuisances are extremely important aspects of both urban and rural living and the environment.³⁸² The three types of local authority represent a basically symmetrical system, all local authorities performing the same functions. They are all under state control, except for the Federal Territory of Kuala Lumpur, which is under federal jurisdiction. There are six special-purpose development authorities focused on development in specific areas at the local level, which are under federal, not state, control. These are the Federal Territories of Putrajaya and Labuan, Pengeran and Johor Tenggara Local Authorities in Johor, the Tioman Development

³⁷⁹ *ibid.*

³⁸⁰ *Majlis Daerah Hulu Selangor v United Plantations Bhd* [2021] MLJU 1205, Federal Court. For a striking recent example of judicial review, see *Perbadanan Pengurusan Trellises & others v Datuk Bandar Kuala Lumpur & others* [2021] 2 CLJ 808, Court of Appeal. This case is discussed in detail in report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making. And for the juristic nature of local authorities, see LGA, Sec 13.

³⁸¹ LGA, Sec 101(hh); see Andrew Harding, 'Planning, Environment and Development: A Comparison of Planning Law in Malaysia and England' (2003) 5 *Environmental Law Review* 231.

³⁸² Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (2nd edn, Hart/Bloomsbury, forthcoming 2022) Chapter 5.

Authority in Pahang, and the Kulim Hi-Tech Industrial Park Local Authority in Kedah. The Iskandar Regional Development Authority is also discussed under report section 4 on local government structure, but this authority acts only in a facilitative way and does not exercise statutory powers over specific local government functions in its area.

Political and Social Context in Malaysia

Currently more than two thirds of Malaysians live in urban areas, and these (municipal and city councils) correspond to most of Malaysia's 'local government areas', that is, those areas (now encompassing all of Malaysia's territory) that have local authorities as defined by the LGA, Section 3. Over the last four decades Malaysia's developmental state under the 'Vision 2020' policy has instrumentally recreated the country as an industrialised one, transforming it from a largely agricultural society into an urban and suburban one.³⁸³

Rural areas are under the authority of district councils, which are still administered with respect to local functions by something resembling the colonial system of district officers.³⁸⁴ District officers are appointed by, and are responsible to, either the state government or the federal government, depending on the state in which the authority lies. The district officers are chairs of the district councils, which are advised by various committees of specialists. The districts, that is, rural areas, have never at any point had representative local government. Nonetheless, the district councils perform equivalent functions to those of municipal and city councils. They are also under-funded compared to urban authorities. This is typical facet of uneven development in many countries. As Singaravelloo reports,

'Financial strength is proportional to the size of the local authority. Larger local authorities have a larger population and economic base that provides the revenue needed to finance their activities. Smaller local authorities, however, especially district councils, have smaller populations and economic activities that can only contribute a small amount to their revenue. Examples of local authorities with a critical population size in 2010 were Majlis Daerah Lenggong (13,378), Majlis Daerah Pakan (Sarawak) (15,139), Majlis Daerah Pengkalan Hulu (15,878), Majlis Daerah Kuala Penyu (Sabah) (18,958), Majlis Daerah Jelebu (26,608), Majlis Daerah Labis (32,540), Majlis Daerah Cameron Highlands (34,510). The smaller revenue base is not even sufficient to provide the basic services that local authorities are assigned to deliver.'³⁸⁵

The National Physical Plan and the National Urbanisation Plan³⁸⁶ emphasize urbanization, which is seen as Malaysia's major priority and problem. This indicates that rural areas are of

³⁸³ Andrew Harding, 'Law and Development in Malaysia: A Vision Beyond 2020?' in Salim Ali Farrar and Paul Subramaniam (eds), *Law and Justice in Malaysia: 2020 and Beyond* (Thomson Reuters 2021).

³⁸⁴ Jagdish Sidhu, *Administration in the Federated Malay States* (Oxford University Press 1980).

³⁸⁵ Kuppaswamy Singaravelloo, 'Local Government and Intergovernmental Relations' in Noore Alam Siddiquee (ed), *Public Management and Governance in Malaysia: Trends and Transformations* (Routledge 2013) 211.

³⁸⁶ *ibid.* 214.

low political concern. It is suggested that any reintroduction of local government elections and any revisiting of state and local government powers should embrace district as well as urban councils, and address squarely the needs of rural communities.³⁸⁷

Local councils consist of between eight and 24 persons who are appointed by the state governments from amongst prominent citizens resident in the locality for terms of three years.³⁸⁸ Councillors have therefore tended to reflect the interests of the political party or parties in power at the state level; in West Malaysia at least, political parties operate at the national level and there are no purely local parties, although obviously some parties are perceived as being stronger in some specific areas or originated therefrom (e.g. Parti Gerakan is associated with Penang). With regard to Kuala Lumpur, since it is a federal territory, the *Datuk Bandar* (mayor) is appointed by the federal government for a period of five years, and the *Dewan Bandaraya Kuala Lumpur* (Kuala Lumpur City Council) is placed under the Prime Minister's Department.³⁸⁹

Reforms to the local government system, especially regarding elections in some urban areas, were promised by the Pakatan Harapan (PH) government, which left office on 1 March 2020. The present Perikatan Nasional (PN) government has not stated any intention in this regard, but meanwhile the country has been under emergency rule (from 12 January to 1 August 2021) due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Under the Emergency (Essential Powers) Act 2021, all elections were suspended; this ordinance has now been revoked.³⁹⁰

Despite the stability enforced by the Malaysian Government's largely successful efforts to improve the economic standing and opportunities of the majority Malay/Muslim population (around 60 per cent of the population of 32 million), there still exists a strong ethnic social division which in recent years has tended increasingly to be expressed via religious affiliation (Muslim and non-Muslim).³⁹¹ Under the Constitution, Article 160, a Malay is defined in terms of adhering to Islam as well as using the Malay language and Malay customs. This ethnic factor has had a considerable impact on local government, as successive governments have declined to reintroduce local elections in spite of strong demands, especially in mixed urban areas, for local democracy.³⁹² The often-stated reason is that local democracy is likely to inflame inter-ethnic tensions.³⁹³ Nonetheless, the 14th general election in May 2018 was conducted entirely without violent incident anywhere in Malaysia, indicating a level of political maturity that belies the fear of ethnic violence, most evident in the tragic events of 13 May 1969 (see below), reemerging.

³⁸⁷ The most recent proposals in this regard, by the PH government in July 2018, mentioned only reintroducing local elections in some densely-populated urban areas; in any event these were not acted upon. See, further, Danesh Prakash Chacko, *Reintroduction of Local Government Elections in Malaysia* (Bersih & Adil Network Sdn Bhd. 2021).

³⁸⁸ LGA, Secs 3 and 13.

³⁸⁹ Federal Capital Act 1960, Secs 4 and 7.

³⁹⁰ Emergency (Essential Powers) Ordinance 2021, Secs 12-13.

³⁹¹ Dian AH Shah, *Constitutions, Politics and Religion in Asia: Indonesia, Malaysia and Sri Lanka* (Cambridge University Press 2017) 10.

³⁹² Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied?*, above.

³⁹³ This issue is discussed in detail in report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

Since significant changes in the law and socio-economic policy in 1971, spurred by the 13 May incident, the majority community (styled *bumiputera*) community, comprising Malays and natives of Sabah and Sarawak, have benefited from special quotas in certain areas such as education and employment opportunities.³⁹⁴ This system has impacted local government in various ways discussed later in this report.

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Phang Siew Noi, *Local Government System in Malaysia* (Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka 1996)

³⁹⁴ There is vast literature on this issue but see, e.g., Lee Hwok-Aun, *Affirmative Action in Malaysia and South Africa: Preference for Parity* (Routledge 2021); Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (2nd edn, Hart/ Bloomsbury, forthcoming 2022) Chapter 3.

16.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Careful perusal of the text of the Federal Constitution would indicate that the intention was to provide only a measure of real autonomy for state governments from the federal government, and that local authorities also enjoy autonomy from state and federal governments, albeit less than that enjoyed by state governments. However, such reading would obscure the fact that very little such autonomy exists in practice. The centralised nature of the federation is well established in analyses in the literature (Malaysia is often referred to as a ‘quasi-federation’ rather than a real federation, or as truly federal only with regard to Sabah and Sarawak, not the states of Peninsular Malaysia).³⁹⁵ As a result the government system is in practice far more centralised than Southeast Asia’s unitary states, such as Thailand, Indonesia and the Philippines. Much the same may be said of local government, which has even less say than state governments in inter-governmental relations (IGR). This situation is due to a number of factors, mentioned earlier, which are now examined in turn in more detail.

Dominant-party System and Patronage-based Politics

IGR involving local government in Malaysia are rendered more complex than a mere statement of constitutional and administrative law might indicate, due to the operation (historically speaking) of the dominant-party system under the Barisan Nasional (formerly Alliance) (BN) government (1957-2018). For almost all of this period and in almost all states, at least up until 2008, when the federal opposition coalition won several state governments, appointees at federal, state and local government levels were appointed from within the BN power structure. This meant that state *Menteri Besar* (chief ministers) were in effect appointed by the Prime Minister; state executive councils (equivalent of the cabinet at federal level) were appointed by *Menteri Besar*; and local councillors were appointed by the state government almost exclusively from the ranks of party members. In this system IGR were therefore in large part a matter of intra-party (not even inter-party, except for BN component parties) relations. A good example of the effects of the political process on local government is provided in the case study of the SPICE controversy³⁹⁶ in Penang. This shows that what is described here is not at all confined to the BN and its component parties, but is taken as a norm even by parties that have been in opposition to the BN and are now in power in some states.

The National Council for Local Government

The National Council for Local Government (NCLG) is a body established under Article 95A of the Constitution in 1960 that makes national policies for the promotion, development and control of local governments, and in effect controls the kinds of laws and policies that the

³⁹⁵ Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (2nd edn, Hart/Bloomsbury, forthcoming 2022) Chapter 6.

³⁹⁶ See report section 5.2. on the SPICE Controversy in the section on intergovernmental relations of local governments in Malaysia.

states can make on local government.³⁹⁷ The state governments must follow the policies made by the NCLG. For example, when the state governments of Selangor and Penang (then held by federal opposition parties) requested the Election Commission (EC) to conduct local government elections, the EC held (it is suggested, incorrectly) that NCLG's agreement was necessary.³⁹⁸

The NCLG consists of a federal minister as chairman (normally the Prime Minister), and one representative from each of the states (normally the Chief Minister) appointed by the Ruler (or Governor, on government advice); and generally no more than 10 representatives of the federal government. Given this composition, the NCLG is without doubt highly influential, and the Prime Minister, normally chairing the meetings, determines its agenda and direction.³⁹⁹ Ultimately, the NCLG's agenda and interests reflect those of the federal government.⁴⁰⁰ For this reason, the NCLG is considered by some to be quite improper in a federal system, as it can be said to trespass on states' rights, which include powers in respect of local government. Since the NCLG is legitimised by a constitutional amendment introducing Article 95A, it can only be argued that it is an unconstitutional body by relying on the 'basic structure' doctrine, which has a hold, but a tenuous hold, in Malaysian case law.⁴⁰¹

The setting up of the NCLG is considered to be part of the extensive local government reforms that took place between its establishment in 1960 and 1988. It was established under Article 95A to coordinate policies and laws between the federal, state and local spheres of government, such that uniformity of local government laws and policies in Malaysia could be achieved. Article 95A provides that after consultation with state governments the NCLG can 'formulate policies for the promotion, development, control of local government throughout the federation and for the administration of any laws relating thereto'.⁴⁰²

A Penang state assemblyman, Gooi Hsiao Leung, reflecting widely-held opinion, stated that the state governments could become more effective if there were a decentralisation of power from the federal government: 'It will be better for Penang as we are in the best position to know what is needed for our state instead of bureaucrats stationed far away in Putrajaya'. An example he provided was that 'even when the state government wants to reinstate the Penang Voluntary Patrol Team (PPS), it cannot be done without federal approval'. In fact the PPS was held by the Court of Appeal to be constitutionally within state powers.⁴⁰³ Gooi also pointed out that federal funds were being distributed unfavourably to the states: 'Penang received only 3 per cent of the tax revenue collected from the state between 2001 and 2008'. He reported

³⁹⁷ See Art 95A, and also Art 76 of the Federal Constitution, which provides for the federal legislature to make laws for the purpose of uniformity between states.

³⁹⁸ Danesh Prakash Chacko, *Reintroduction of Local Government Elections in Malaysia* (Bersih & Adil Network Sdn Bhd. 2021).

³⁹⁹ Tricia Yeoh, *Federal-State Relations under the Pakatan Harapan Government* (ISEAS Publishing 2020).

⁴⁰⁰ Kai Ostwald, 'Federalism without Decentralization: Power Consolidation in Malaysia' (2017) 43 *Journal of Southeast Asian Economies* 488.

⁴⁰¹ Wilson Tay, 'Basic Structure Revisited: The Case of *Seminyeh Jaya* and the Defence of Fundamental Constitutional Principles in Malaysia' (2019) 14 *Asian Journal of Comparative Law* 113.

⁴⁰² Phang Siew Noi, *Decentralisation or Recentralisation? Trends in Local Government in Malaysia* (University of Malaya 2008).

⁴⁰³ *Government of the State of Penang v Minister for Home Affairs & others* [2017] 4 MLJ 770.

that the budgets of all 13 states in Malaysia combined were equivalent to only 6 per cent of the federal budget in 2013 and the was figure reduced by 0.2 per cent in 2018.⁴⁰⁴

Although local government policy is formulated by the NCLG in consultation with federal and state governments, the political system as outlined above means that the federal government gets its way, and local authorities are – astonishingly – not represented at all in a process designed to serve their needs. There is a Malaysian Association of Local Authorities⁴⁰⁵ which could easily represent them in such policy deliberations.

The Public Service

The public service (equivalent to the ‘civil service’ in some systems) is organized via the Public Service Commission (PSC) at the federal level, serving both federal and state governments, but not local government, which employs its own staff. This system works to the disadvantage of local government and to IGR in two respects.

First, the PSC provides consistent standards and rules for recruitment, pay, promotion, and transfer between governments. Local government staff do not have these advantages, and tend to get stuck in terms of advancement due to lack of opportunity. This decreases morale and commitment.

Secondly, local government does not, as a result, benefit from integration of public service that would render smooth and highly professional the system of IGR across federal, state and local governments.

The argument is often heard that deficiencies in staffing, and especially in technical expertise, make decentralisation at the local government level a risky enterprise. This of course is an outcome of the system of public employment, not a necessary consequence of having local government or subsidiarity per se. Subject to democratic controls, adequately funded, and linked to the PSC, there is no reason to suppose that local authorities would not perform very well, as they did during the first ten years after independence.

Powers of State Governments

As was stated earlier, state governments are also empowered under the LGA to give general directions to local governments. In addition, local council budgets must be submitted to the state government for approval not later than 20 November in each year;⁴⁰⁶ and the raising of loans by local governments is subject to the consent of the state government.⁴⁰⁷ Furthermore, all local government by-laws, rules, and regulations are subject to state government approval;⁴⁰⁸ as are annual assessments, drainage rates and valuation lists.⁴⁰⁹

⁴⁰⁴ ‘Backbencher Wants more Autonomy for Penang’ (*Malay Mail*, 11 December 2018) <<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2018/11/12/backbencher-wants-more-autonomy-for-penang/1692628>>.

⁴⁰⁵ See the association’s website, <www.mala.com.my>.

⁴⁰⁶ Local Government Act 1976 (LGA), Sec 55.

⁴⁰⁷ Sec 40.

⁴⁰⁸ Sec 103.

⁴⁰⁹ Secs 127, 128, 143.

State governments also exert some control over local governments' exercise of planning powers. States are governed planning-wise by a system of structure plans under the Town and Country Planning Act 1976 (TCPA), while local plans are drawn up by local governments.⁴¹⁰ The latter are still nonetheless subject to approval by the state government. Oddly enough, though, the TCPA allows local governments to make rules regarding regulation of land development, classes of use, and regulation of height, design, appearance of buildings and density of developments; and these rules *prevail* over state government rules if they conflict. This is one of few areas where local governments can go against the wishes of the state government.

It is therefore not too much of an exaggeration to say that IGR in Malaysia present a highly centralised system of government in which local governments exercise comparatively little discretion as to policy and even sometimes with regard to particular decisions, as seen in the SPICE case study below.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Harding A, 'Local Democracy in a Multi-Layered Constitutional System: Malaysian Local Government Reconsidered' in Andrew Harding and Mark Sidel (eds), *Central-Local Relations in Asian Constitutional Systems* (Hart Publishing 2015)

Phang Siew Noi, *Decentralisation or Recentralisation? Trends in Local Government in Malaysia* (University of Malaya 2008)

Yeoh T, *Federal-State Relations under the Pakatan Harapan Government* (ISEAS Publishing 2020)

⁴¹⁰ For more information on this, see report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

16.3 The SPICE Controversy

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Relevance of the Practice

This section consists of a case study rather than a local government practice as such. Nonetheless the case study is by no means untypical, and although 'practice' is possibly too strong a word for the phenomenon described here, it does represent a realistic and common scenario. Other similar examples, those of Johor Bahru's 'floating city' project and the Penang Hill controversy, are referred to in the report section on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

Not surprisingly, it is with regard to development that conflict between local and state government is most likely. The general laws set out in the last section appear to indicate a clear if not entirely satisfactory demarcation between general rules and policies, on the one hand, which can be controlled by state governments, and particular decisions, on the other hand, which are entirely within the remit of local governments. Nonetheless, in the case study, as in many other cases, the state government has used its leverage to make decisions that oust local government powers.

Description of the Practice

In the instant case, there was a joint venture project between MBPP (Penang Island City Council) and a private company, SP Setia, to develop via co-financing the Subterranean Penang International Convention and Exhibition Centre (SPICE), an initiative designed to attract tourism and business to the State of Penang as well as provide indoor sports activities. The project was a state government plan but was entrusted to MBPP, on whose land the SPICE was supposed to be built. In 2010 MBPP asked for proposals from the private sector. The project was awarded to a subsidiary of SP Setia. Negotiations were undertaken by state and local government officials without the knowledge of councillors, even those on the finance committee; they learned of it only when the RM 300 million contract had been signed and was referred to in the press. Councillors complained that the contract was lop-sided in favour of the private partner, and had been negotiated in an untransparent fashion, contrary to the state government's stated 'CAT' policy of 'competence, accountability and transparency'. MBPP was therefore asked to approve a decision that had already been taken and a budget of RM 50 million for a BOT (build-own-transfer) arrangement involving MBPP's property contained some troubling features that included a lease of 30 years, twice renewable by the company for 15 years, with concessions regarding both assessments and density of retail outlets. In terms of cost-benefit, MBPP contributed the land and part of the finance but got little in return – the right to use the facilities for 42 days a year, and return of the land after 60 years. Despite these concerns, voiced by two councillors and civil society representatives, the majority of

councillors, appointed by the state government, went along with the decision. SPICE opened on the agreed terms in 2015.

Assessment of the Practice

In a developmental state such as Malaysia it has been common for developmental concerns to trump governance concerns. There is no better example of this than the SPICE episode, but examples of this phenomenon appear to proliferate in urban areas all over the country.⁴¹¹

At the level of states such as Penang, where federal opposition parties are usually in control of the government, there is a strong political push to achieve development, and in this case to attempt to replicate Singapore's vaulting development ambitions as a centre for trade and investment. As we have seen, the resources of state and local governments are not extensive, and the state government will use every resource and leverage it can to gain votes by demonstrating strong development. Accordingly, governance norms are often overridden by arrangements and negotiations done directly with developers, in which the state government will no doubt have made promises and taken positions that are strictly, as in this case, for the local authority to decide on. While the temptation is strong to ride roughshod over correct processes in the interests of securing an important deal, the lack of process may well result in mistakes, such as lop-sided contracts, where the interests of private corporations are placed above those of the public. There is also of course a distinct danger of corruption in such decision-making.

The SPICE episode compels the conclusion that legal and democratic norms have to be adhered to, rather than traduced by inappropriate decisions taken without proper consultation. The spineless response of most Penang councillors in this matter reveals the political realities that lie behind development at the local level.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Mah Hui L, *Local Democracy Denied? A Personal Journey into Local Government in Malaysia* (SIRDC 2020)

Tang Seng Hai, 'CAT Needed in Penang's SPICE Project' (Malaysiakini, 4 October 2011) <https://www.malaysiakini.com/letters/177679>

⁴¹¹ While there are examples of development projects in rural areas, e.g. converting rural land into housing estates, the system operates in a political manner, with politics in a real sense as described in the SPICE episode only happening in urban settings. Moreover, the literature rarely deals with rural local government issues, except to suggest that they are somewhat deprived of resources and compared to, e.g. Penang, Ipoh, or Kuala Lumpur, they have no power in the system.

17. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Canada

17.1 The System of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction

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Types of Local Governments

Canadian federalism divides governing responsibilities among three levels of government: federal, provincial, and local. However, the Canadian Constitution gives the provinces sole jurisdiction over municipalities, which results in significant inter-provincial variation among local government systems. While the federal government in recent years began to provide money through joint federal-provincial programs for services that are ultimately delivered by municipalities (primarily hard infrastructure), there is typically no direct federal policy or regulatory involvement with the municipal level of government.⁴¹³ One side effect of this lack of federal involvement is that it is difficult to determine how many local governments there actually are in Canada. A comprehensive survey of available data from numerous sources, conducted in June 2021 by researchers at Western University,⁴¹⁴ indicates that there were 3,533 local governments in Canada as of 2020. This is a significant decrease from the total of 4,432 in 1995, which reflects the results of a large-scale wave of provincial imposed consolidations in several provinces around the turn of the millennium. Despite this consolidation, most municipalities in Canada are small and rural. A report based on the 2016 census finds that only 723 had a population of 5,000 or greater. By contrast, 24 municipalities had over 200,000 residents, while three municipalities (Toronto, Montreal and Calgary) had over 1 million inhabitants. Toronto is Canada's largest municipality, with a population of 2.9

⁴¹² Acknowledgements: Data regarding number of municipalities in Canada, as well as the analysis of rural-urban demographic and economic differences in Ontario, were compiled and produced by Amanda Gutzke at Western University. Our sincere thanks for her excellent work.

⁴¹³ Erin Tolley and William R Young, 'Municipalities, the Constitution, and the Canadian Federal System' (Government of Canada 2001) <<http://publications.gc.ca/Collection-R/LoPBdP/BP/bp276-e.htm#Municipalities>> accessed 25 July 2019.

⁴¹⁴ These data were collected and analyzed as part of another research project, led by Zack Taylor and Martin Horak.

million as of July 2018.⁴¹⁵ Just as the country's 10 provinces and three territories⁴¹⁶ vary in population size, so too do their municipal populations. Ontario tends to have larger municipalities as a result of its history of amalgamations imposed by the province, many of which took place in the 1990s.⁴¹⁷ Ontario currently has 444 municipalities.

In some cases, urban municipalities have distinct status under provincial law. For example, Vancouver, Winnipeg, Montreal, and Saint John are Charter Cities, which means that they are governed by their own piece of legislation – or 'Charter' – rather than being subject to the broad, province-wide legislation that governs the activity of other municipalities.⁴¹⁸ The City of Toronto is likewise governed by stand-alone provincial legislation. However, in general the degree to which these charters grant powers and resources over and above those of other municipalities is limited.

Table 3: Types of municipalities in Canada's four most populous provinces.⁴¹⁹

Province	Types of Municipality
Ontario	Village
	Township
	Town
	Municipality
	City
	County
	Regional Municipality
Quebec	Village
	Township
	United Township
	Town

⁴¹⁵ 'Municipalities in Canada with the Largest and Fastest Growing Populations between 2011 and 2016' (*Statistics Canada*, 8 February 2017) <<https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/as-sa/98-200-x/2016001/98-200-x2016001-eng.cfm>> accessed 1 August 2019; 'Municipalities in Canada with Population Decreases between 2011 and 2016' (*Statistics Canada*, 8 February 2017) <<https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/as-sa/98-200-x/2016002/98-200-x2016002-eng.cfm>> accessed 1 August 2019; 'Toronto at a Glance' (*City of Toronto*, undated) <<https://www.toronto.ca/city-government/data-research-maps/toronto-at-a-glance/>> accessed 1 August 2019.

⁴¹⁶ Canada's three territories (Nunavut, the Northwest Territories, and Yukon) are located in the far north. Despite their large geographical size, they have very small populations, totaling only about 110,000 in all three territories, which is less than the population of the smallest province (Prince Edward Island, 150,000 inhabitants).

⁴¹⁷ Andrew Sancton, *Canadian Local Government: An Urban Perspective* (2nd edn, OUP 2015) 150, 152.

⁴¹⁸ 'Power of Canadian Cities- The Legal Framework' (*City of Toronto*) <https://www.toronto.ca/ext/digital_comm/inquiry/inquiry_site/cd/gg/add_pdf/77/Governance/Electronic_Documents/Other_CDN_Jurisdictions/Powers_of_Canadian_Cities.pdf> accessed 25 July 2019; John Stefaniuk, 'Municipal Powers and their Limits' (TDS Law) <<https://www.tdslaw.com/site-content/uploads/municipal-powers-and-their-limits-2.pdf>> accessed 25 July 2019.

⁴¹⁹ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 7-8; 'Types of Municipalities in Alberta' (*Government of Alberta*, undated) <<https://www.alberta.ca/types-of-municipalities-in-alberta.aspx>> accessed 25 July 2019.

	Municipality City Parish Regional Government Metropolitan Community Regional County Municipality
British Columbia	Village Town District Municipality City
Alberta	Summer Village Village Town City Specialized Municipality Municipal District Improvement District Metis Settlement Special Areas

Generally, Canadian municipalities are responsible for providing physical services including water supply, waste management, local infrastructure management, sewage treatment, planning and development services, libraries, parks and recreation, local police, and parking.⁴²⁰ These local government tasks are administered through general purpose municipalities (variously called cities, towns, villages, etc., depending on size), sometimes in conjunction with special purpose bodies. The table above compares the largest four provinces by population to illustrate variation in the legal types of municipalities. In addition to these, there are numerous local government bodies that do not have municipal status – such as British Columbia’s regional districts, which are multi-purpose service federations of municipal governments.

In some provinces, including Ontario, Quebec and Alberta, there is a single tier of local government in some areas, and two tiers of local government in other areas. Upper-tier governments in Ontario, for example, are either called counties or regional municipalities, with the latter typically found in large urban areas. Upper-tier municipalities are comprised of the lower-tier governments within their boundaries. They provide region-wide services like arterial

⁴²⁰ ‘The Three Levels of Government’ (*Parliament of Canada*, undated)
 <https://lop.parl.ca/about/parliament/education/ourcountryourparliament/html_booklet/three-levels-government-e.html> accessed 25 July 2019.

roads; transit; policing; sewer and water systems; waste disposal; region-wide land use planning and development; and health and social services.⁴²¹

Legal Status of Local Governments

Canada's Constitution specifies the terms of Canadian federalism. It assigns responsibility for local governments to the provinces. This means that the provincial governments have full jurisdiction over the local governments in their territory. Section 92 of the Constitution Act of 1867 specifies the powers of the provinces and Section 92(8) gives each provincial legislature the power to make laws for the municipal institutions under its jurisdiction. Municipalities are often referred to as 'creatures of the province' because they rely on the provinces for their legal existence.⁴²²

There is significant variation among the provinces in terms of the structure of municipal legislation. Historically, provincial legislation has tended to lay out every power granted to its municipalities; if a specific power is not listed, municipalities do not possess that power. However, in recent years this has shifted, and most provinces now have legislation, such as that implemented in Alberta in 1995 and Ontario in 2001, which grants municipalities the same powers as a 'natural person' unless specifically excluded by the legislation. This gives municipalities the same rights as businesses to enter into contracts, own property, and make investments. Moreover, British Columbia's provincial government sets only broad legislation within which municipalities have the authority and flexibility to respond to each community's unique and changing needs. The Government of British Columbia views municipalities as autonomous and accountable to their democratically elected municipal councils.⁴²³

Both urban and rural municipalities in all Canadian provinces have some legal authority to act in the following functions: fire protection; animal control; roads; traffic control; solid waste collection and disposal (except in Prince Edward Island); land use planning and regulation; building regulation; economic development; tourism promotion; public libraries parks and recreation; cultural facilities; licensing of businesses; emergency planning and preparedness; rural fences and drainage; regulation and/or provision of cemeteries; airports (excluding major airports formerly operated by the federal government); and weed control and regulation of cosmetic pesticides.

Additionally, the following functions are typically delivered by urban municipalities: public transit; regulation of taxis; water purification and distribution; sewage collection and treatment; downtown revitalization; and regulation of noise. Generally, urban municipalities

⁴²¹ 'Ontario Municipalities' (AMO, undated) <<https://www.amo.on.ca/AMO-Content/Municipal-101/Ontario-Municipalities.aspx>> accessed 25 July 2019.

⁴²² Tolley and Young, 'Municipalities and the Constitution', above; Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 27.

⁴²³ For a comprehensive overview of Canadian municipal legislation, see Zack Taylor and Alec Dobson, 'Power and Purpose: Canadian Municipal Law in Transition' (2020) 47 IMFG Papers on Municipal Finance and Governance; 'Municipalities in British Columbia' (*British Columbia*, 2019) <<https://www2.gov.bc.ca/gov/content/governments/local-governments/facts-framework/systems/municipalities>> accessed 25 July 2019.

are also responsible for policing, although in some provinces special purpose bodies take care of this function. The exception is Newfoundland and Labrador, where policing is taken care of by the Royal Newfoundland Constabulary. Moreover, the Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP) (or a provincial police force, as in the case in Quebec and Ontario) enters into contracts with some urban municipalities to provide policing, and it is typical for the RCMP or provincial police to provide policing in rural areas.

Ontario is unique in that the province mandates that its municipalities deliver certain social services. This includes income and employment assistance through the Ontario Works program and subsidized childcare with provincial oversight and financial assistance. Additionally, Ontario municipalities are required to provide subsidized social housing, with limited financial assistance from the province. Municipalities in other parts of the country do not have the same statutory responsibility to provide these social services.⁴²⁴

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The fact that the provinces have under the Canadian Constitution sole jurisdiction over municipalities gives rise to considerable inter-provincial variation. Although municipal powers and responsibilities thus vary by province, common core functions include planning, regulating, protecting, and providing infrastructure services for the built environment.⁴²⁵

In some cases, there is also asymmetry within provinces in terms of how local government is structured, as different laws may exist for urban and rural municipalities. As noted above, several of Canada's largest urban municipalities are governed by charters that outline specific institutional arrangements for that municipality, and/or grant it additional powers and revenue sources. Toronto, for example, was granted charter status in 2007, giving it additional revenue raising tools beyond the property taxes and provincial transfers that most municipalities rely on. However, it should be noted that Charter Cities do not have additional constitutional protections. A municipal charter can be changed by the province at any time. Indeed, there is much disagreement surrounding the utility of granting cities such additional powers, as such powers have typically been limited and are often not fully used.⁴²⁶

General municipal statutes and special charters are not the only laws that apply to municipalities. Indeed, since provincial governments set parameters for municipal action in a multitude of policy fields, ranging from planning and environmental services to policing and housing, the cope of municipal action is shaped by dozens, if not hundreds of different statutes in each province.⁴²⁷ In addition, in some provinces, provincial governments may enact laws that apply only to particular municipalities or groups of municipalities – that is, single

⁴²⁴ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 22-23.

⁴²⁵ Taylor and Dobson, 'Power and Purpose: Canadian Municipal Law in Transition', above.

⁴²⁶ Harry Kitchen, 'Is Charter City Status a Solution for Financing City Services in Canada – Or is that a Myth?' (University of Calgary School of Public Policy SPP Research Paper 9-2, 2016) <https://www.policyschool.ca/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/charter-city-status-kitchen_0.pdf> accessed 26 July 2019.

⁴²⁷ *ibid* 8.

municipalities can apply to their provincial government to request private statutes as a remedy for a particular local problem for there is no other legal recourse.⁴²⁸

Political and Social Context in Canada

All Canadian municipalities are governed by a democratically elected council.⁴²⁹ Ward systems are commonly used, especially in large municipalities; Vancouver is Canada's only large city where councillors are elected at-large. With the exception of the City of Vancouver and larger municipalities in the Province of Quebec, local government is non-partisan. The provinces of British Columbia and Quebec are the only two provinces that have legislation that allows for the existence of political parties at the local level.⁴³⁰ The fact that local government tends to be non-partisan, and that provincial party systems also tend to be quite distinct from the federal party system, means that the broader political context within which municipalities operate is marked by only weak political links among levels of government. This lack of vertical political integration, together with the weak legal status of local governments, made them the target of politically expedient decentralization in the fiscally lean 1990s. At that time, structural fiscal pressure on the welfare state produced a cascading decentralization of policy and fiscal responsibility through the Canadian federation, and municipalities had to cope with the imposition of unfunded or partly funded policy mandates from the provincial level. The result was intergovernmentally induced fiscal stress at the local level, which has only in recent years begun to be mitigated by increasing fiscal transfers.

Many scholars suggest that local governments, with their weak legal status, are primarily 'policy takers', rather than 'policy-makers', in the Canadian context.⁴³¹ There are certainly cases where Canadian municipalities do make policy independently of the provinces. To a significant extent, their ability to do so depends on their population size and their local property tax base. Since rural municipalities have both a small population and a weak property tax base, their autonomous policy-making capacity tends to be very limited. For both reasons, there is thus a policy capacity divide among Canadian municipalities that closely mirrors the rural/urban divide.

Like many post-industrial countries, Canada is highly urbanized. Almost 72 per cent of the population lives in urban areas with over 100,000 people, and more than a third of all Canadians live in the three largest urban areas (Toronto, Montreal and Vancouver).⁴³² The Canadian population is thus concentrated primarily in a handful of large urban areas, whose

⁴²⁸ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 31.

⁴²⁹ However, upper-tier governments in two-tier systems (e.g., Greater Vancouver and Ontario's regional municipalities) sometimes have indirectly elected councils composed of representatives of lower-tier municipalities.

⁴³⁰ Sancton, *Canadian Local Government*, above, 173, 180, 186, 188.

⁴³¹ *ibid* 251.

⁴³² Calculated from Statistics Canada Census 2016 data reports.

population is growing quickly. By contrast, the population of rural Canada is (in most regions) growing much more slowly,⁴³³ and rural areas are on average older, whiter and poorer.

Table 4: Selected Demographic and Economic Indicators in Ontario, by Type of Census Division.⁴³⁴

	Metropolitan	Mixed	Non-Metropolitan
Population change (2011-2016)	+ 5.57%	+ 4.54%	+ 0.92%
Visible minority population (2016)	43.5%	13.5%	2.6%
Average household income (2016)	\$78,477	\$73,258	\$65,748

An analysis of 2016 census data conducted for this report paints a picture of the demographic and economic contrasts between rural and urban areas in Ontario, Canada’s largest province by population (table above). The data are divided into three kinds of census divisions (CDs) – metropolitan CDs, which are located in urban areas with more than 100,000 people; non-metropolitan CDs, which are fully outside settlements with more than 100,000 people; and mixed CDs, which include a combination metro and non-metro areas. As is clear from the table, non-metropolitan – that is, rural and smaller-town – CDs grew much more slowly in population than others between 2011 and 2016; they were also much whiter, with only 2.6 per cent of the population identifying as visible minority, as opposed to 43.5 per cent in metropolitan CDs; and they were poorer, with an average household income that was only 83.7 per cent of the metropolitan average. These demographic differences, which reflect an economic base that has increasingly transitioned towards post-industrial urban productive sectors, set the context for the distinct governance challenges faced by rural and urban local governments in Canada in recent years.

For some time now, rural areas in the urban periphery of large cities in Canada have experienced some out-migration of urban residents facing high housing prices in the city. It appears that the Covid-19 pandemic has rapidly intensified this trend, to the extent that may fundamentally change the rural-urban dynamic in the longer run. Of course, it is too early to tell if the trend will be sustained. There is not even reliable data on the scale of the out-migration over the course of the pandemic yet. However, it was notable that *all* the experts and practitioners interviewed for this research noted this out-migration as a major development and a source of significant challenge, as well as potential opportunity, for rural areas. Interviewees all agreed that the structural driver of the out-migration is the very high cost of housing in large urban centers, most notably Toronto and Vancouver. With the Covid-19 pandemic entrenching work-at-home possibilities for white collar professionals, and

⁴³³ Between 2001 and 2016, the rural Canadian population grew by 5.5%, while the overall national population grew by 16.9%. Even this modest rural growth, however, is largely concentrated near urban areas. See Federation of Canadian Municipalities, ‘Rural Challenges, National Opportunity: Shaping the Future of Rural Canada’ (2019).

⁴³⁴ All data are calculated from Statistics Canada 2016 census of the population data tables.

simultaneously enhancing the appeal of low-density rural living, this structural trend has rapidly acquired more force.

Speaking about dynamics in the Toronto area, one policy analyst said: ‘Especially with the last year, housing has just moved out of the [Toronto area] and it's encroaching on a lot of these different communities. People who would have loved to have lived in downtown Toronto, but simply can't afford to are buying homes in Oxford County’ – about 150km from Toronto.⁴³⁵ While the experts interviewed for this project all focused on the Ontario context, media reports suggest similar dynamics surrounding other large urban centres.

This influx of new residents and money brings some benefits to rural areas, such as more budget money for municipalities that rely heavily on property taxes and development fees. As one interviewee noted, ‘from a property tax perspective, from a development perspective, it's pretty significant, (...) you go to some of these places, there's a lot of nice new playgrounds and parks and stuff like that. If you go to Innisfil [a rural community one hour north of Toronto], they built one of the nicest libraries I've ever seen. It's like a monument, incredible. And they're like, “yeah, that's development dollars”’.⁴³⁶

The other side of that same coin, of course, is that housing affordability is quickly becoming a major problem in rural communities that are relatively near to urban centres. ‘This notion that affordability is only an urban issue, it really needs to dissipate’, said one respondent. Those households that cash out of hot urban property markets have been driving up housing prices in rural areas at an unprecedented rate, especially since the beginning the Covid-19 pandemic. One interviewee noted that median house prices went up 40 per cent or more during 2020 in many rural communities that are within a two-hour drive of the Toronto area.⁴³⁷ Another challenge that comes with the influx of what one interviewee called ‘rural gentrifiers’⁴³⁸ is that they tend to want more municipal services in communities that have long provided just the basics, putting upward pressure on property taxes.⁴³⁹

Most respondents also noted that the new urban out-migration is leading to cultural and lifestyle tensions in rural areas that are experiencing high rates of influx. ‘It's gonna be a little bit like it was after the Second World War, when a lot of European immigrants showed up in these communities,’ said one interviewee. ‘They haven't seen that kind of change in a generation in two generations really, and they may have a lot of people coming to town that don't look like them, don't engage in the same economic activities that they're used to, that have different expectations. And they may want to set up cricket pitches, not baseball diamonds’.⁴⁴⁰ Another respondent noted of the new arrivals from urban areas: ‘You know, they need to have a big box store, they want some things from you know from the supermarket and

⁴³⁵ Interview with local government expert, Rural Ontario Institute (20 July 2021)..

⁴³⁶ Interview with local government expert, York University (10 July 2021)..

⁴³⁷ Interview with local government expert, Guelph University (28 July 2021).

⁴³⁸ *ibid.*

⁴³⁹ Interview with local government expert and consultant, Toronto (13 June 2021).

⁴⁴⁰ *ibid.*

stuff, and [long-time residents] are complaining that all these weird products are showing up in the supermarket right like avocados and (...) gluten-free food'.⁴⁴¹

It is far too early to tell how extensive this out-migration to rural areas will ultimately be, and whether it will continue after the Covid-19 pandemic. However, it appears that a significant shift in rural-urban dynamics is underway in the parts of rural Canada that are relatively close to major metropolitan centres, with possibly far-reaching knock-on effects on rural governance issues.

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⁴⁴¹ Interview with local government expert, York University (10 July 2021).

17.2 Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Canada: An Introduction

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Since provincial governments have constitutional responsibility over local government in Canada, the primary nexus of intergovernmental relations is the provincial-municipal one. Federal government involvement in local affairs has been episodic, and has been largely limited to the development of various infrastructure funding transfers, which usually require matching funding across all three levels of government. The Federation of Canadian Municipalities (FCM) represents and lobbies for municipal interests at the federal level; however, given the lack of institutionalized federal-local relations, place-specific and project-specific advocacy by local political representatives and/or local members of federal Parliament also play a role in shaping flows of federal funding for local infrastructure. Over the last 20 years, the growth of federal cost-shared infrastructure funding, as well as the rise of some project-specific efforts at federal-provincial-municipal coordination, have deepened and broadened multilevel governance mechanisms spanning all three levels of government; yet tri-level coordination is still partial, unstable, and highly vulnerable to short-term political pressures.⁴⁴²

Systems of provincial-municipal intergovernmental relations vary significantly from province to province. However, in most provinces they are shaped by a combination of factors that is arguably unique to Canada: 1. Comprehensive provincial legal authority over local governments; 2. High reliance of local governments on locally raised revenues;⁴⁴³ 3. Low intergovernmental political integration; 4. Low intergovernmental administrative integration. The latter two points deserve some elaboration. With respect to political integration, in most of Canada, local government is non-partisan; and in the places where it is partisan (Vancouver, and many Quebec municipalities), local parties are often different than provincial parties. As a result, in the political sphere intergovernmental relations tend to lack the glue of integrated party systems that exist in many other countries. With respect to administrative integration, Canada has no unified civil service that operates across levels of government. Each province has its own civil service system; and there is no comprehensive civil service system for local governments. This makes intergovernmental communication on the administrative front more difficult and less systematic than it otherwise might be.

Provincial-municipal relations have evolved differently in different provinces in response to these realities. In British Columbia, for example, the provincial government in the 1970s instituted a system of 'regional districts' – large-scale service-sharing structures that also serve as intermediary institutions between the province and municipalities, supporting a relatively consensual model of provincial-municipal relations. In Ontario, by contrast, the norm is much more one of provincial legislative and regulatory dominance of local governments, with limited

⁴⁴² For a detailed discussion, see Martin Horak, 'Conclusion: Understanding Multilevel Governance in Canada's Cities' in Martin Horak and Robert Young (eds), *Sites of Governance: Multilevel Governance and Policy Making in Canada's Big Cities* (University of Toronto Press 2012).

⁴⁴³ See report section 3 on local finances for further discussion.

openness to local concerns. In this context, provincial-level associations of municipalities have become important intermediaries in the provincial-municipal relationship.⁴⁴⁴

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⁴⁴⁴ We explore their behaviour – especially insofar as it relates to the different interests of rural and urban municipalities – in report section 5.1. on Representing Toronto's District Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government.

17.3 Representing Toronto's Distinct Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government

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Relevance of the Practice

As we saw in the Introduction to Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments, report section 5.1., Canada lacks party systems and civil service systems that are integrated across levels of government. Absent these mechanisms of intergovernmental communication, many provincial governments adopt a very top-down approach to their relationships with municipalities. This is certainly the case in Ontario, where the provincial government has a history of dealing with local governments without much regard for local preferences or inter-local differences. Historically, this tendency has manifested itself in a number of ways:

- through periodic provincially-imposed structural reorganization;⁴⁴⁵
- through periodic top-down reorganization of functional and funding responsibilities;⁴⁴⁶
- through the tendency of the provincial government to develop homogeneous standards and policies for all local governments, rural and urban.

Insofar as municipal governments in Ontario have had a say in provincial policy and action towards the municipal sector, it has mostly been through collective action by the Association of Municipalities of Ontario (AMO), the province's main municipal association. For a long time, AMO represented all of Ontario's 444 municipalities – a remarkably diverse group, ranging in population from 97 people (Brethour) to 2.9 million, and from ethno-racially diverse urban centres to sparsely populated tracts of wilderness in the far north. Because of this diversity, Ontario has over the decades evolved a range of smaller municipal associations that represent more specific groups of municipalities. These include the Rural Ontario Municipal Association (ROMA), the Northwestern Ontario Municipal Association (NOMA), the Federation of Northern Ontario Municipalities (FONOM), and others. AMO itself has also developed a system of internal caucuses that group municipalities regionally and by population. Nonetheless, the City of Toronto, which is three times as large as the next largest municipality (Ottawa), has chafed at being part of a large collective, and in 2005 it left AMO, and has since 'gone it alone' in dealing with the province. The successes and limitations of this strategy give LoGov researchers insight into the capacity of Ontario's largest urban municipality to articulate its own interests in a centralized provincial-municipal system.

⁴⁴⁵ As discussed in report section 4.1. Beyond Municipal Amalgamations in Ontario, above.

⁴⁴⁶ The most recent major reorganization of this kind occurred in the late 1990s, at the same time as the wave of amalgamations discussed above. At this time, the provincial government took on costs for public education, while downloading costs and responsibilities for numerous social services and public transit to local governments.

Description of the Practice

After the municipal amalgamations and imposed reorganization of provincial-municipal responsibilities and funding arrangements in the late 1990s, the municipal sector in Ontario sought to identify ways to increase local input into provincial policies regarding municipal matters. In 2001, AMO convinced provincial officials to engage in a periodic process of negotiating an AMO-Provincial Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) that would identify mutually agreed policy directions and priorities. While many Ontario municipalities saw this as a step forward in provincial-municipal relations, the City of Toronto did not. The new post-amalgamation city had distinct needs and policy priorities from many other Ontario municipalities, including higher than average social service costs and a backlog of large transit infrastructure funding needs. Furthermore, with about 20 per cent of the province's population, Toronto was not content to be one of 444 municipal voices in AMO. As a result, in 2004 Toronto left AMO, and began dealing with the provincial government independently. Toronto has remained outside of the AMO framework since that time.

Assessment of the Practice

Toronto's strategy of going it alone in its relationship with the provincial government has been quite successful in some ways. Taking advantage of the weight of its large population and economic base, Toronto has at times been able to successfully articulate its distinct needs and priorities to the provincial government, as well as to the federal government. An early example of this came in 2007, when the city successfully concluded negotiations with the provincial government for a stand-alone piece of governing legislation, the City of Toronto Act. This act, which came into force in 2008, removed Toronto from the jurisdiction of the Municipal Act (which continues to apply to all other municipalities in Ontario), and gave the city some modestly expanded powers and resources, including some new taxing powers.⁴⁴⁷ Beyond this, withdrawing from AMO has given Toronto the opportunity to negotiate independently with both other levels of government about a variety of issues and initiatives. For example, allocations of the federal gas tax, which are the subject of an agreement between the federal government, the provincial government and AMO for most of the province, are the subject of a separate federal-provincial-Toronto agreement.

Of course, Toronto's successes in 'going it alone' in its relationship with other levels of government is only made possible because of its extraordinarily large population. This is not an option that would be viable for other Ontario municipalities, which must continue to struggle with the priority trade-offs inherent in being part of a collective municipal association. According to one expert interviewed for this project, Toronto leaving AMO precipitated a crisis in the organization, which led to internal reforms that have ultimately made AMO a more effective representative of municipal interests at the provincial level.⁴⁴⁸

⁴⁴⁷ See report section 3.1. on Property Tax Reliance and the Re-Emergence of Provincial Funding Transfers to Local Government in Ontario.

⁴⁴⁸ Interview with local government expert and consultant, Toronto (13 June 2021).

Toronto's strategy has also faced some limitations. First, since the City of Toronto contains less than half of the population of the Toronto urban area, its independent intergovernmental status has not helped it in having a voice on issues that are regional in scope – such as planning and regional transportation. On the contrary, divisions on regional policy priorities between Toronto and the surrounding suburbs have tended to deepen in recent years, and there is a truly remarkable lack of coordination between Toronto and the 24 suburban municipalities that surround it (which together house about 3.5 million people). The lack of intra-regional coordination is all the more striking given that Toronto and AMO maintain a regular dialogue, and on many general issues of law and policy that affect all municipalities they present a common front to the province. Second, going it alone on intergovernmental relations has meant that these relations have been destabilized by Toronto's notoriously unstable political leadership, which tends to swing among political priorities from one electoral term to the next. As a result, important provincially supported projects such as major transportation infrastructure initiatives have become bogged down by local political instability.

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